

Creating waves: culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing in Paisley

By

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Abstract

This thesis argues that, in order to fully mobilise culture and the arts in support of health and wellbeing, a paradigm shift is needed in how we think about health and wellbeing. This shift is needed to counter persistent orthodoxy of reductionist thinking and individualism that manifest in processes such as evaluation and evidence-building, for instance in the use of culture and the arts for social purposes. There is policy emphasis on this use in Paisley, a post-industrial town in the West of Scotland. My research practice involves observing constellations of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing activity in Paisley, in their dynamic and holistic form. The Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme, is both a constituent of these constellations and is co-constituted from these constellations.

My thesis is built from two intertwining abductive processes: the proposal for a paradigm change and my research puzzle, the health and wellbeing dimension of the Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme. The puzzle provides a case for place-based policies designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing.

I am informed by a bricolage and facet methodology approach, to holistically view the puzzle and draw on diverse ways of knowing. My thesis grows, layers and juxtaposes knowledge of my critical observations of the growth of Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension, and undertakes the essential work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing. From the insights gained, I develop my proposal of four propositions for paradigm change.

My abductive approach analyses the conditions and processes that develop the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley. I argue that place-based policies at a local authority level by being between the cultural sector and the healthcare sector, could create possibilities for using culture for paradigm change if an explicit radical approach to health and wellbeing is articulated.

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Abbreviations

APPGAHW	All-Party Parliamentary Group on Arts, Health and Wellbeing
CAHSC	Culture Arts and Social Care Network
CCSE	Centre for Culture, Sports and Events
FPPB	Future Paisley Partnership Board
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
NHS GGC	NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde
RMHAF	Renfrewshire Mental Health Arts Festival
RHSCP	Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Partnership
SHARP	Sustainable Health Action Research Programme
SPG	Strategic Planning Group
SMAF	Scottish Mental Health Arts Festival
TSI	Third Sector Interface
UKCoC21	UK City of Culture 2021

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis is entirely my own work, and that no part of it has been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification.

Lan Pham

1. Introduction

1.1. An introduction and an account

This research is a critical account of how I follow my constantly evolving research puzzle, the health and wellbeing dimension of the Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme, in a unique phase of its growth. My research puzzle serves as a case for place-based policies designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing. The thesis also follows the development of a proposal to shift how we think about health and wellbeing. This proposal contains the need for this shift, an argument for a change in how we think about health and wellbeing, and language that can help us change our thinking. I develop this proposal by undertaking the work of counter conceptualising health and wellbeing which draws on critical accounts of health and wellbeing.

These two dynamic research concerns form my research aim to investigate how place-based policies designed to utilise culture and the arts for social ends might shift thinking on health and wellbeing by observing developments in policy and activity in Paisley.

This chapter starts with the insights offered my research puzzle and proposal for paradigm change. I then proceed to orientate the reader by providing key facts about Paisley and the UK City of Culture 2021 (UKCoC21) bid, from which this research emerges. What I offer in this critical account is not what I originally intended to offer when I responded to a PhD studentship advertisement in November 2018. The research brief was from the newly formed Centre for Culture, Sports and Events (CCSE), a partnership between the University of the West of Scotland and Renfrewshire Council. The process of change from my original research focus is important to my research account and as this process shows the need for my research. Therefore, this chapter is kept brief by moving onto how my research offering changed. As throughout the thesis, I trace how the research aim evolved with emergent knowledge and my development as a researcher. The methodology and methods were also emergent, developing in parallel to the constantly evolving research puzzle; and to develop an abductive process to simultaneously infuse the development of my proposal with both theoretical and empirical insights.

In this chapter I illustrate how my research offering changed by providing the original brief and my interest in the brief. I provide some of the factors for the change in research direction that led to my new focus on the research puzzle and the proposal. The emergent nature of this new focus is shown by an account of how the research questions and research aim evolved.

This thesis serves as an account of my research puzzle and research proposal. As such, it paints a picture of complex concepts co-constituting one other within changing conceptual and empirical contexts and therefore the research puzzle is not viewable as a whole. My methodological choice to view my research puzzle and proposal is through the layering and juxtaposition of insights by drawing on bricolage and facet methodology. Knowledge is grown and developed into insights by following lines of inquiry that I term 'research trails' to convey their active and exploratory nature. These trails form the chapters that structure this research account and conclude this chapter.

1.2. A puzzle and a proposal

There are many research contributions which can be made by investigating the case of 'place-based policies designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing'. This phrase is laden with complex concepts that are academic fields in themselves. Contributions can be made by selecting component concepts, critically interrogating its relationship to the phrase, or selecting more than one concept and examining conceptual relationships. For example a contribution could be made by using cultural policy to examine 'place-based policies designed to use culture and the arts' (Belfiore and Gibson, 2019). Or a focus could be on 'place-based policies for health and wellbeing' through fields such as health geography and sociology (Bambra, 2019).

This thesis argues for a focus on two arrangements to analyse the case, 'health and wellbeing' and 'culture and the arts for health and wellbeing'. These arrangements are the main lines of inquiry through which I will; investigate my research puzzle, the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme, and develop my proposal for a change in how we think about health and wellbeing. I argue we need a focus on relational health. With this proposal I consider what type of culture and the arts activity may help create a focus on relational health. Through these two arrangements, my interest in the research case is to examine the potential of these policies to contribute to relational health.

However, this research puzzle and proposal is not where my research started. I initially investigated my puzzle and proposal as a means to understand the context to the initial brief I was given.

1.3. Paisley: the town and the bid

Before I discuss the original brief set for this research. I need to locate the research in the town which serves as its case, Paisley, as well as outlining the key event underpinning the original research brief: the UK City of Culture 2021 (UK CoC2021) bid put forward by the town.

Paisley: the town

Paisley has a heritage over 1,000 years old. In the 18th century, Paisley became known for textiles and weaving. The production of thread and the Paisley pattern are key to Paisley's erstwhile wealth and fame. The company, Coats, was one of the first multi-national companies and in 1912 was the world's third largest company¹. The closure of thread mills starting in the 1950s was part of a wider process of deindustrialisation in the west of Scotland.

Paisley is the fifth largest locality in Scotland after four of Scotland's six cities, Glasgow, Edinburgh, Aberdeen, and Dundee making Paisley the largest town in Scotland. The population is 77,270 (National Records of Scotland, 2022). Paisley is located in the west of Scotland, in the local authority area of Renfrewshire, and borders the city of Glasgow, the largest city in Scotland, which is 10 miles to the east of the town.

Paisley: the bid and cultural regeneration programme

Renfrewshire Council made a commitment to be the UKCoC2021 in *Paisley the Untold Story* (The Untold Story) published in 2014 (Renfrewshire Council, 2014). The Untold Story report lays out how Paisley will leverage its heritage and cultural assets to transform Paisley through economic regeneration. The report provides details on what is considered Paisley's heritage and cultural assets which includes several buildings such as Paisley Abbey, Paisley Town Hall and Paisley Museum's collections. The report describes some of these collections as internationally recognised, such as textiles and natural history. In preparation for this bid, the Paisley Partnership Board was established in 2015 with 15 members².

In 2017, Paisley placed its UKCoC21 bid (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018a). Following the award of the title to Coventry, the preparatory legacy work from the UKCoC21 bid in Paisley (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b) was continued in a cultural regeneration programme. Paisley Partnership Board has now expanded to 18 local, regional, and national organisations across the public, business and third sectors³. The cultural programme had five Step Changes: (1) grow a significant new

¹ <https://coats.com/en/About/Our-heritage>

² https://consult.gov.scot/culture-tourism-and-major-events/culture-strategy/consultation/view_respondent?sort=excerpt&order=ascending&_b_index=60&uuld=902341124

³ Renfrewshire Council, Renfrewshire Leisure, University of the West of Scotland, West College Scotland, Renfrewshire Chamber of Commerce, Paisley First, Glasgow Airport, Young Scot, STAR Project, Engage Renfrewshire, Creative Scotland, Visit/Event Scotland, The Glasgow School of Art, Scottish Enterprise, Skills Development Scotland, Arts and Business Scotland, NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde and Police Scotland

dimension to Paisley's economy, (2) lift communities out of poverty, (3) radically change Paisley's image and reputation in Scotland, the UK and internationally, (4) Paisley will be recognised for its cultural excellence, (5) transform Paisley into a vibrant cultural town centre.

CCSE has been tasked to undertake an evaluation of this cultural regeneration programme and its five proposed Step Changes (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b). As part of this programme of evaluation, three PhDs are commissioned. Each one is attached to a Step Change. One research project is related to Paisley's economy, a second is concerned with Paisley's image and reputation and the third, my research, is attached to 'lifting communities out of poverty'. The preparatory legacy work from the UKCoC21 bid in Paisley suggested an Arts, Health, and Social Care subgroup be set up, with membership drawn from the Paisley Partnership Board.

When I started the PhD programme in February 2019, the cultural regeneration programme is named as Future Paisley. The Paisley Partnership Board is now the Future Paisley Partnership Board (FPPB) and the Step Change I am attached to, is now called commonly referred to as Step Change 2. The Arts, Health, and Social Care subgroup is now named the Culture Arts and Social Care Network (CAHSC). My PhD brief was to be embedded in CAHSC.

1.4. The brief and the researcher

The title of the PhD brief was 'Poverty, Health and Action Research in Culture-Led Regeneration'. Paisley was offered as a case for the research. The brief reflected the concerns of the Step Change it was attached to, Step Change 2, 'lifting communities out of poverty'. I was interested as the opportunity offered scope to be involved in the intersection between the use of culture in the design of a place-based policy, the field of arts and health and the contribution of non-healthcare sectors to health and wellbeing. These are all topics that I had previously been involved in through my professional, volunteering, and leisure activities.

In my prior role to this research, I was working as a research assistant for an advice service organisation. I observed how important advice services were to people's health and wellbeing, directly through reducing anxiety or signposting to food banks, or tackling the determinants of health such as housing assistance and increasing people's incomes, to more indirect means, such as treating people as human and hearing about their whole life due to the holistic nature of the service. I heard from clients, volunteer and staff advisors and service managers how the trusting relationships that develops from treating people as human and with empathy are key to achieving individual benefits from health and wellbeing to resolving consumer issues. However, when it came to illustrating the value of the service, the orthodox methods of showing value such as social return

on investment or health and wellbeing surveys, did not make visible or central the work of creating trust and being empathetic. These were taken as a given or as an input in evaluations, where narratives were often linear. Furthermore, these methods of showing value did not give room for people's experiences.

I was attracted to answering the PhD brief as there was a focus on developing innovative evaluation methods to evidence how cultural participation could lead to health and wellbeing. By taking up this opportunity, I anticipated I would be able to investigate my interest in how to evaluate health and wellbeing improvement by services outside the healthcare sector. I intended to immerse myself in projects to get to know people and their experience of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing.

The opportunity to investigate how culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing entangled in people's lives is personally exciting to me. For the past five years, every October I spend many days at an Edinburgh art venue volunteering as a planner, curator, and invigilator for an exhibition open to anybody with lived experience of mental health issues to submit. I hear hundreds of people with their own experiences of mental health issues communicate what matters to them as exhibitors and audience members. People communicate through their exhibit; through conversations they have with me when I invigilate and through the exhibition's invitation for them to share what the exhibition mean to them.

1.5. A change in the research direction

My initial aim was to contribute to knowledge of how culture and the arts influence health and wellbeing. I anticipated my contribution would emerge from theoretically and empirically researching mechanisms and pathways from culture and the arts to health and wellbeing. I investigated conceptualisations of health and wellbeing that would be amenable to the influence of culture and the arts. My conceptual investigation was both theoretically and empirically grounded as I wanted to help people with their questions about what they could do in their role to address health and wellbeing. I considered my contribution in terms of adding to the evidence base of how culture and the arts leads to changes in health and wellbeing. I was investigating culture in a way Belfiore (2021, p. 8) evaluates as a methodological problem, a 'case for the arts'.

However, I became frustrated with my theoretical explorations and realised my line of inquiry about mechanisms and pathways were not fruitful. I was drawn to critical accounts of health and wellbeing, from human geography and within public health. I started to investigate loneliness as a public health issue. This topic served as a site to understand ontological and epistemological tensions. There is friction between orthodox approaches to researching and intervening in public

health issues and people's experience of the issues. I started becoming aware that my research approach was determined by orthodox approaches to health and wellbeing, and I began to critically assess my research and evaluation practice of creating evidence by showing change in projects and programmes. My awareness drew me to the idea of waves of public health by Hanlon et al. (2011), who identify four waves and invited proposals for a fifth wave of public health. The idea of waves of public health is relevant to the context of public health in Scotland as it informs the Scottish Government's review of public health (Scottish Government, 2016). Each wave is related to a shift in thinking about health and society. New waves do not displace previous waves. The waves of public health work alongside each other. Out of my theoretical frustrations emerges an argument that in order to investigate 'place-based policies designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing' I need to engage with a new paradigm. This argument contributes to public health in Scotland as I suggest the current wave of public health has reached its limits as progress on issues such as health inequalities and obesity has stalled in Scotland. I also argue that the current description of the fifth wave of public health developed by Davies et al. (2014) does not sufficiently address these issues or make enough room for ways of knowing from non-healthcare sectors. Therefore, my thesis needs to develop a proposal for a fifth wave of public health. I developed my research puzzle and proposal together with both processes co-constituting each other. This intertwining process creates opportunities to develop insights into how non-healthcare sectors can contribute not just to health and wellbeing but also the work of changing how we think about health and society. My conceptual exploration of culture and the arts through my proposal for the fifth wave of public health investigates culture as an ontological and epistemological problem.

My contribution to research and policy has evolved to align with Belfiore's (2021) questioning of the nature of evidence and the consideration of evidence in terms of an argument and an act of persuasion. My research account is an argument that the mobilisation of culture and the arts for health and wellbeing needs to consider how a new wave of public health can be created. At the same time without a new wave of public health, the contribution of non-healthcare sectors, such as culture and the arts cannot be fully mobilised. I argue that place-based policies using culture and the arts for health and wellbeing purposes has a useful role in creating the fifth wave of public health by being outside the cultural sector and outside the healthcare sector.

1.6. The questions and the aim

I develop my arguments and contributions through a research approach that is responsive and adaptative to change. Sources of change include; developments in academic research in the fields I engage with, my development as a researcher as my conceptual awareness and knowledge grows,

the evolution of Future Paisley Step Change 2, national policy developments, and change in the activities in Paisley that create interactions between culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing. The evolution of my research from the original brief is one example of my responsive and adaptive approach. One significant change is the COVID-19 pandemic at the start of my second year of the research. I had spent a year building relationships with members of CAHSC and we were ready to scope out potential projects I could immerse myself in. The lockdown and travel restrictions of COVID-19 put projects on pause. In this period, I continued my conceptual interrogation of health and wellbeing and with my emerging interest in developing a fifth wave of public health my first research question emerged:

- What might the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health be?

The theories and concepts I used to interact with my growing empirical knowledge were complex and contained ideas people were less familiar with. I realised my research needed to develop a language that would resonate with the health and wellbeing work of those outside the healthcare sector. This language would make visible the work they undertook which they may not have considered as the work of health and wellbeing. I needed to develop concepts that could move people away from the orthodox ways of thinking about health and wellbeing and towards my proposal. My work aligns with what Atkinson (2020) terms a 'counter-conceptualisation' to how health and wellbeing is currently viewed. An endeavour Atkinson suggests is paradoxically likely to fail yet also ethically necessary to undertake. From this realisation emerged my second research question:

- What concepts could help articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health?

The layering of knowledge from these two research questions provides a conceptual viewpoint to define culture and the arts. The use of this definition of culture and the arts, if incorporated into policies that have health and wellbeing aims, may help create a shift in thinking about health and society. I develop a third research question to develop these possibilities:

- How might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and wellbeing?

Overtime, as my intended immersion in projects are stalled, my increasing knowledge about Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension starts to become the focus of my research. I realise that I have been observing the growth of this dimension and my observations offer insights into what constitutes Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension. These insights grow knowledge about

the possibility of whether this dimension can create a fifth wave of public health. As I focus more on Future Paisley, I realise there is an interesting case for the study of the use of culture and the arts for social purposes, particularly in the context of policy design. Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension brings together two fields of study relating to the use of culture and the arts for social purposes, arts and health and cultural regeneration. In addition, the third research question has led to an investigation of community arts, bringing a third field of study relating to the use of culture and the arts for social purposes into my research process.

My research aim now moves to focus on the development of a health and wellbeing dimension of a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social purposes. My research puzzle is the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme which serves as a case for place-based policies designed to use culture for health and wellbeing. The emergence of this puzzle is brought together with my growing knowledge and insights from the previous three questions to develop a new research aim:

'Investigate how might place-based policies designed to utilise culture and the arts for social purposes shift thinking on health and wellbeing by observing developments in policy and activity in Paisley.'

To develop knowledge to investigate this research aim I develop a fourth research question. This research question formally includes into my research my investigation of the possibilities for Future Paisley to create a fifth wave of public health. To assess these possibilities, I analyse what elements constitutes Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension and what informs these ongoing processes of constitution. This analysis informs the fourth research question:

- how might a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends grow a health and wellbeing dimension?

1.7. Thesis structure and methodology

My process of changing the original brief results in an emergent research process informed by a fluid methodological approach. Developing a proposal for the fifth wave of public health means developing ontological and epistemological commitments. I constantly return to my methodology to evolve my approach in order to keep up with my deepening commitments. I also return to my methodology as keeping up with my research puzzle in live time means taking every opportunity to create research encounters. In a sense, the subsequent chapters of this thesis including the methodology and methods chapter provide an overview of my methodological approach. Therefore, this section provides the structure of the thesis and includes an overview of the knowledge that is

introduced and grown in each chapter, in order to provide a guide of how knowledge is grown, layered and juxtaposed in order to build my argument.

Chapter 2 will start with my research approach to health and wellbeing. This chapter introduces Hanlon et al.'s (2011) framework of waves of public health and discusses the proposal for a fifth wave of public health. The key legislative and policy background to public health in Scotland since 2010 including the incorporation of the fifth wave of public health into Scotland's public health reform process. I start to develop my argument that originates with Hanlon et al.'s (2011) suggestion that the fourth wave of public health has reached its limits and a fifth wave of public health is needed. As part of this argument, I suggest the description of the fifth wave of public health that is used in Scottish policy is too narrow and does not provide enough of a shift in thinking about health and society that a new wave of public health requires. In particular I suggest that the current wave of public health does not provide adequate language to articulate the contribution of non-healthcare sectors to public health therefore the work of proposing a fifth wave of public health needs to attend to the work of counter-conceptualisation of health and wellbeing and a diversity of ways of knowing. This work needs to be done before I can investigate the research puzzle.

Chapter 3 provides my methodology and methods. I start with a description of who I was as a researcher when I started my thesis. I go on to provide my definition of a research case. I outline my research puzzle, which is the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley. I go on to develop my methodology by describing research approaches that inform my research orientation. My research sensibilities are then provided. These sensibilities are a way of being in the world that can assist me to attune to people's experiences and knowledge. The lines of research inquiry I follow are laid out in this chapter. I list the research encounters that provide the opportunities to gather and grow knowledge. The chapter ends with my research process for how I grow the knowledge into insights and arguments that address the research questions.

I present my proposal for the focus and the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health in Chapter 4. This chapter outlines my suggestion for the ontological and epistemological perspectives required to underpin the shift in ideas of health and wellbeing that the fifth wave of public health requires. I introduce my use of loneliness as a public health challenge as a site to investigate health and wellbeing with my suggested ontological and epistemological perspectives. I discuss the work required to facilitate health and wellbeing in the fifth wave of public health. I introduce my development of gateway concepts to bring people into the idea of relational health and sensitizing concepts to help people attune to the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health.

To understand the rationale of using culture and the arts for social purposes I need to conceptually investigate the terms culture and the arts. Chapter 5 will outline key academic discussions relating to concepts of culture and the arts and the use of culture and the arts for social purposes. I focus on two uses, the field of arts and health and cultural regeneration. I will bring this investigation together with my argument for the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health by exploring what critical approaches towards health and wellbeing are used when examining the social purposes of culture and the arts. I lay out what ideas of culture and the arts have dominated policy making and how these ideas have been challenged. I set out how I view culture and the arts in my thesis.

I need to grow knowledge relating to how culture and the arts activity is interacting with health and wellbeing in Paisley. This knowledge is needed to understand what activity Future Paisley is influenced by and could have an influence on in the context of health and wellbeing. Chapter 6 contains the knowledge I have grown regarding how cultural activity emerges in Paisley and the current and possible future interactions with Future Paisley. This knowledge is brought together with knowledge grown in the previous chapter relating to the conceptual knowledge of culture and the arts and the social purposes of culture and the arts. This layering of knowledge enables my research to assess how the interaction of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing in activities and policies could grow the fifth wave of public health.

In Chapter 7 I build on my argument for the importance of including experiential knowledge in research and policy by investigating loneliness as a public health issue. I analyse understandings of loneliness in programmes that seek to use culture and the arts to address loneliness. I examine the tension between the different understandings of loneliness: experiential, policy and conceptual and therefore how might my proposal for the fifth wave of public health help navigate these tensions.

Chapter 8 explores the resonance of my suggestion for gateway concepts to bring people into the idea of relational health and sensitizing concepts to help people attune to the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health. I use these concepts to consider how health and wellbeing might be facilitated by organisations and programmes in Paisley and whether this facilitation can contribute to my proposal for a fifth wave of public health.

The layering of the knowledge and research perspectives developed in the preceding chapters enable my research to go onto examine the development of a health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley. Chapter 9 brings together the knowledge grown in the preceding chapters, with ideas drawn from applying assemblage thinking to policy, particularly policy transfer and academic arguments about a case for using culture for social ends in the design of place-based policies. I examine the case for culture in Paisley, the conditions for a health and wellbeing dimension of place-

based policy to develop in Paisley and the possible future entanglements between health and wellbeing and Future Paisley. I assess whether these entanglements can contribute to my proposal for a fifth wave of public health.

Chapter 10 concludes the thesis with the aims that have been achieved in the research and the contributions the thesis has made. The strength and limitations of my research is provided, and I suggest avenues for future research.

2. Creating waves of public health

2.1. Introduction

I respond to the invitation to research Paisley's place-based policy that is designed to use culture and the arts to improve health and wellbeing. This invitation emerges from two fields that are concerned with the social impact of culture and the arts. The first field brings together existing practices that combine culture, the arts, health and wellbeing into an arts and health field. The most visible and influential articulation of this field in the UK is the Inquiry Report published in 2017 by the All-Party Parliamentary Group on Arts, Health, and Wellbeing (APPGAHW) which was set up in 2014. This report calls for recognising the significant and powerful contribution the arts make to health and wellbeing. These activities cover many spheres of our lives from the built and natural environment, to crafting at home and attending cultural events (APPGAHW, 2017). Arts and health activities are starting to interact with other uses of culture. Such place-based policies (University of Warwick and Coventry University, 2022) that are designed to use culture and the arts for social ends such as urban regeneration policies. This field has been referred to as cultural regeneration and is the second field that is concerned with the social impact of culture and the arts that Future Paisley emerges from.

I need to examine what is meant by improving health and wellbeing before I investigate the health and wellbeing dimension of these two fields, arts and health field and cultural regeneration field. In this chapter I lay out the operational definition of public health used in Scotland where this research is located. I then present the idea of waves of public health proposed by Hanlon et al. (2011). I evaluate the proposal's argument that public health needs a shift in thinking about health and society. I start this evaluation by presenting key conceptual and policy approaches to health and wellbeing. I then move on to consider the usefulness of these approaches for tackling public health challenges. I situate the proposal in the Scottish public health policy context. The conclusion of my evaluation of whether public health needs a shift in thinking about health and society leads to the proposal presented in Chapter 4. With this proposal I then investigate the concept of health and wellbeing in the arts and health field and the cultural regeneration field in Chapter 5.

2.2. Why do we care about public health if we're interested in culture and the arts?

Advocates, such as the APPGAHW, for the greater integration of culture and the arts with health and wellbeing strategies and services make the case that 'the arts are a vital part of the public health landscape' (APPGAHW, 2017, p. 5), arguing for its transformative effect on people's health and wellbeing and should be utilised to address health and wellbeing policy issues. Examining this claim requires a critical assessment of how health and wellbeing are defined.

I situate my research in the Scottish policy context by using an operational definition of public health is given by the Scottish Government (2016, p. 9)

‘Public health is the science and art of promoting and protecting health and wellbeing, preventing ill-health and prolonging life through the organised efforts of society... we can describe public health as

- a. Being population based – concerned with the factors that make populations (e.g., communities, cities, regions, countries) healthier or unhealthier;
- b. Emphasising collective responsibility for health, its protection and disease prevention – through the organised efforts of society;
- c. Recognising the role of the state, and of the underlying socio-economic and wider determinants of health and disease, including the distribution of power, resources and opportunities within and across populations; and
- d. Involving partnership with those who contribute to the health of current and future populations.’

2.3. Waves of public health

I examine how we think about health and wellbeing influences public health through the idea of waves of public health (Lyon, 2003; Hanlon *et al.*, 2011). This idea is relevant to the context of public health in Scotland as it informs the Scottish Government’s review of public health (Scottish Government, 2016). Waves of public health is part of the argument for why there needs to be a public health review.

Therefore while there are other proposals for typologies of public health centred around ideas and traditions that propose a new idea for public health (Lang and Rayner, 2012), the waves of public health is the most relevant for my research as it engages my research in language and concepts already used by public health in Scotland. The focus of my critical engagement with the waves of public health is developing a proposal to respond to Hanlon *et al.*’s (2011) invitation to think about the fifth wave of public health. The remainder of this chapter is spent on why I have decided to respond to the invitation.

Hanlon *et al.* (2011) suggests public health improvement since the Industrial Revolution as overlapping phases of public health improvement and each one has related to a shift in thinking of the concept of society and health (Table 2.1). New health challenges are always arising, and a new

wave is needed when the current wave’s power to respond is limited. A new wave does not replace current and previous waves and works alongside the waves that have gone before.

Table 2.1: Summary of the four waves of public health including dates of peak of effectiveness (Hanlon et al., 2011, p. 32)

The first wave	The second wave	The third wave	The fourth wave
Approximately 1830-1900:	Approximately 1890-1950:	Approximately 1940-1980:	Approximately 1960-2000:
Classical public health interventions, such as water and sanitation etc; concerns with civil and social order.	Scientific rationalism provides breakthroughs in many fields – manufacturing, medicine, engineering, transport, and communications etc.	Emergence of the welfare state and the post-war consensus: the National Health Service, social security, social housing and universal education etc.	Effective health care interventions help to prolong life. Risk factors and lifestyle become of central concerns to public health. Emergence of nascent concerns with social inequalities in health

2.4. Fourth wave of public health

Hanlon et al. (2011) suggests the fourth wave of public health as arising from the limits of medical interventions to deal with issues such as the impact of de-industrialisation and complex social issues such the rise in drugs and violence. In the fourth wave of public health, there is a greater focus on social, psychological, and environmental factors, particularly there is a focus on health inequalities and the social determinants of health that emerged in the 1980s in the UK (Acheson, 1998; Marmot, 2001; Dahlgren and Whitehead, 2006). The concept of health inequalities is often described as differences in health between groups in the population. Blaxter (2010, p. 109) argues the differences have to be ‘socially determined’, ‘felt to be unjust, inequitable or immoral’ and ‘held not to be inevitable.’ The main concepts used to categorise groups are social class, gender, ethnicity and geographical location (Krieger, Williams and Moss, 1997; Nettleton, 2013; Bartley, 2016). Social determinants of health, the conditions in which people are born, live and work, through their unequal distribution is a key factor in occurrence of health inequalities (World Health Organization, no date).

2.5. Contribution of the fourth wave of public health

In the fourth wave of public health, there is a new focus on how social contexts affect health at an individual and population level, embracing the connections between health and society. This focus has helped professionals and policymakers outside the health service conceptually understand how their roles contribute to public health and has facilitated different sectors to work together on public health issues (Dahlgren and Whitehead, 2021). The factors affecting health inequality have been well described through the majority of the focus of research regarding health inequalities looking at the causal link between absolute material deprivation and health inequalities (Porter, Roberts and Clements, 2007). Policy makers, professionals and the general public understand that social factors contribute to health (Carlisle *et al.*, 2007; Smith and Anderson, 2018). However there is a gap between this understanding and policy recommendations which focus on individual responsibility and changing people's behaviours (Kriznik *et al.*, 2018; Smith and Anderson, 2018).

2.6. Limits of a fourth wave of public health

Hanlon *et al.* (2011) contend that the fourth wave of public health's research and policy focus on risk factors, and behaviours have limited ability to deal with issues such as obesity, social inequality in health and loss of wellbeing, particularly depression and anxiety. However Hanlon and Carlisle (2015) argue that current public health approaches tend to be reductionist and limits the ability to tackle the complexity of many public health issues.

It has been over ten years since Hanlon *et al.* (2011) made the case that a fifth wave of public health was needed to address the challenges of obesity, inequality and loss of wellbeing. These challenges remain (Williams and Fullagar, 2019; Marmot *et al.*, 2020) as have the broader issues Hanlon *et al.* (2011) identify of finite resources, climate change, and the cultural values of capitalism. New public health challenges have emerged such as loneliness (Lim, Eres and Vasan, 2020). Research into these public health challenges such as obesity (Rutter, Marshall and Coutts, 2020), loneliness (Mansfield *et al.*, 2019) and health inequalities (Walsh *et al.*, 2016) take the approach that understandings of these challenges emerge from complex interactions between individuals and their environment, from the intertwining of the social, cultural, and historical context of people's life histories. However, the fourth wave of public health focuses on risk factors and causal approaches which requires the experience of life to be carved up into factors that are linked up again through pathways and mechanisms, often linear, creating a flattened copy of life that misses the richness of everyday life. People are left as discrete individual units, the 'sovereign self' (McLeod, 2017, p. 5). Causal narratives link people to their contexts which are ossified as 'causal factors' rather than thinking of peoples' everyday experiences as being made up of histories, culture, and social structures which

dynamically shape everyday life (Williams, 2003). There is a tension in the fourth wave of public health between the aspirations of a public health grounded in everyday life as described in the Ottawa Charter (World Health Organisation, 1986) and the dominance of reductionist and mechanistic approaches in health related research, policy and practices (Rutter, Marshall and Coutts, 2020; Blue, Shove and Kelly, 2021). Kelly and Russo (2018, p. 83) analyse the mechanics of creating causal narratives from risks and behaviour change, and its prevalence in policy documents from the UK to global organisations: such as the WHO and across the past four decades.

‘The simple causal narrative is that non-communicable diseases (NCDs) arise from a set of well-known risks which have been identified in epidemiological studies (McMichael 1999), particularly: smoking, overeating or not eating the right kinds of food, not taking enough exercise and drinking too much alcohol. These risks are attributed to the consequences of people’s behaviours and lifestyles or their inability to make healthy choices on account of the social conditions in which they live (see Department of Health 1992, 1999, 2003, 2004, 2010; see also Kriznik 2015). Therefore, in order to reduce exposure to these risks, interventions to change behaviours and lifestyles are required. In other words, once a plausible account of the aetiology of the disease is established (the risky behaviour), it is assumed that acting on the same mechanisms (the behaviour) will reduce the burden of disease (Department of Health 1992, 1999, 2004, 2010).’

Kickbush’s (1996) tribute to Aaron Antonovsky and his idea of salutogenesis shows that causal narratives also impact concepts of health. Antonovsky (1996) proposed a sense of coherence as an answer to his question of ‘what creates health?’ A sense of coherence (SoC) is a multidimensional concept encompassing the concepts of meaningfulness, comprehensibility, and manageability. SoC has been operationalised as a scale through questions that ask individuals about how they perceive the world. SoC becomes part of the deficit model, as SoC is identified something people are lacking and is considered as a risk factor for health and wellbeing. Kickbush (1996) terms this as the ‘risk factor’ trap that health promotion was in constant danger of falling into. What was conceived as a new way of thinking about health and wellbeing has been subsumed into the dominant paradigm. A concept that was conceived to be at the nexus of society and the individual falls to the framing of individualism. The ‘risk factor’ trap has consequences for how health and wellbeing is addressed. Academic research has shown that a strong SoC is linked to improvements in health and wellbeing outcomes, and this has led to suggestions that health promotion should consider targeting SoC (Super *et al.*, 2016). However, studies into programmes seeking to enhance SoC do not investigate the mechanisms that create these changes, or how the activities may have contributed to increased levels of SoC (Super *et al.*, 2016). The dominant paradigm, by reducing a complex concept to

something measurable, gives an illusion that SoC can be targeted. I suggest that a question that is more in keeping with Antonovsky's vision for salutogenesis is 'who does the work of facilitating health and wellbeing and what does this entail'? My suggestion aligns with Kickbush's (1996) suggestion for policy responses that are in keeping with the vision of salutogenesis, to undertake preventative work by strengthening sense of place and sense of self, that will create the conditions for SoC to improve. Kickbush suggests that this work has more resonance with those involved in the practice and policy of health and wellbeing outside the health professions because they are more attuned to everyday life. This illustration of what a dominant paradigm can do to ideas of health and wellbeing suggests that part of the proposal for a fifth wave of public health needs to be anchored in an ontology and epistemology of anti-reductionism and anti-individualism. There needs to be active resistance to the dominant paradigm, otherwise any proposal will be subsumed into the fourth wave of public health and a shift in thinking about health and wellbeing is less likely to occur.

2.7. Defining wellbeing

Wellbeing has been proposed by Hanlon et al. (2011) as an emergent quality of the fifth wave of public health. However, wellbeing is a highly contested and elusive term (Dooris, Farrier and Froggett, 2018; Stansfield and Bell, 2019). The view that health is more than the absence of disease results in a conflation with the concept of wellbeing (Barry, 2009; Atkinson, 2013; Dooris, Farrier and Froggett, 2018). Conceptualising wellbeing has two traditions, hedonic and eudaimonic which come from discussions of how to live life and what a good life is (Oman, 2021). The hedonic approach considers how to feel good, how to be happy, the maximisation of pleasure and the minimisation of pain. The eudaimonic approach considers how to be good and live the good life, both individually such as being the best version of oneself, to socially as in how to live virtuously (Lindert *et al.*, 2015; Dooris, Farrier and Froggett, 2018; Fisher, 2019). The conflation of health and wellbeing has particularly entangled the terms mental health and subjective wellbeing (Atkinson, 2011, 2013). Mental health is also a concept without consensus (Manwell *et al.*, 2015). Subjective wellbeing follows the hedonic tradition of wellbeing and defines wellbeing as people's subjective satisfaction with life (Fisher, 2019; Das *et al.*, 2020). The entanglement of the terms mental health and subjective wellbeing tends to pull the term mental health towards a focus on the individual, and health and wellbeing as being located within the individual (McLeod, 2017) and therefore the responsibility of the individual self (Atkinson, 2013), and thus amplifies a tendency to downplay structural or contextual factors in the composition of 'good mental health'. Atkinson and Joyce (2011) demonstrate the discursive linking of health and wellbeing by local government authorities in policy in the United Kingdom. A focus on health and wellbeing as individual attributes means they can be measured and standardised and fed into the evaluation practices of policy (Scottish Government, no

date). This conceptual convergence is magnified by a rising policy focus on wellbeing in policy, exemplified by the wellbeing economy agenda that is a priority for the Scottish Government (Scottish Government, no date) This agenda measures how a country is performing through wellbeing measures rather than Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Anand, 2020).

Wellbeing, through its conceptual overlap with health brings its individualistic viewpoint from psychology (Fisher, 2019) to conceptions of health and may potentially harm wellbeing outcomes (Atkinson, 2020). Focusing on individuals alongside a deficit way of thinking, leads to a focus away from structural determinants of health to focusing on individual behaviours (Porter, Roberts and Clements, 2007), which has been termed the 'lifestyle drift' (Smith *et al.*, 2015). This drift has been cited as one of the reasons into why progress on health inequalities has stalled (Mackenbach, 2012). The fourth wave of public health's atomisation of the collective into discrete human beings, leaves people shorn of the context that makes them up, combined with the biomedical approach to health, can result in the medicalising of everyday life and a culture of blaming (and shaming) individuals if they diverge from normative definitions of good health and wellbeing. Diverging from societal norms shuts people out of being fully human, leaving people burdened with objective evaluations of the world being not 'for' them (Webb, 2022). Proposing that there is a norm, repeats the biomedical viewpoint of illness as being a deviation from the norm and enhances the risk of stigmatising those who deviate. For example, it dichotomises the complexity of food choices into 'healthy' and 'unhealthy'.

2.8. Lay perspectives of health

Lay perspectives of health show there are a multitude of dynamic processes in food choices, of which nutritional health is only one aspect amongst broader processes of health and wellbeing (Kitching, Fernández and Horgan, 2021; Burningham and Venn, 2022). These perspectives align with Williams's (2007) view that everyday life is intertwined with structures and context in complex ways beyond behaviour. Williams (2007) argues that addressing the complex and dynamic nature of everyday health requires more radical thinking about public health and more integration between individuals and their environment.

One example of the harm of reductionist thinking and individualism and the culture of blame is how obesity has shifted from being a risk factor to disease to a disease itself, sweeping the nations in the so-called 'obesity epidemic', creating stigma and enhancing people's evaluation of the world as unwelcoming. A discursive trajectory that loneliness, already an evaluation of the world, is following. These trajectories evoke Illich's (2003, p. 919) notion of 'medical nemesis' where the transformation of 'pain, illness, and death from a personal challenge into a technical problem, medical practice

expropriates the potential of people to deal with their human condition in an autonomous way and becomes the source of a new kind of un-health.' Illich articulates the culture of health as the weapons, rules, and styles which are given to humans in their struggle with the fragility of life, a struggle which is the heart of being human. In medically dominated countries, this culture of health is one that denies the acceptance of pain, sickness, and death, which he termed cultural iatrogenesis, differing it from clinical iatrogenesis which was the harm to health of clinical interventions, most vividly brought to life by the opioid crisis in America and social iatrogenesis which is the reliance on healthcare to provide answers and solutions to life and undermine individual capabilities.

2.9. Everyday life

The focus of the fourth wave of public health on risk factors and behaviours does not give a picture of everyday life. The Ottawa Charter (World Health Organisation, 1986) describes health as created and lived by people in their everyday lives. Attuning to everyday life provides an insight into how preventative health and wellbeing processes emerge. A five year action research programme in Wales, Sustainable Health Action Research Programme (SHARP) was designed to come up with an alternative to the focus on health behaviour to address health inequalities (Cropper, Porter, *et al.*, 2007). The programme found transformation of individuals occurred through the accumulations of small moments. These moments were noted due to the length of the project and the embedding of the researchers in everyday life, thus giving the ability to 'observe processes that are not trapped by surveys or hit-and-run focus group studies' (Moore, 2007, p. 186). Moore goes on to analyse how the programme showed how progress emerged through small steps, such as regaining the confidence to make a telephone call. Over time these built up to using the internet, having a driving license or gaining qualifications. These increases in individual capacity enabled people to join in with community activities. Health and wellbeing improved through feeling positive towards life, through increasing capability. Collective capacity also increased, through individuals providing examples of positive change to their communities. Researchers saw this growth through daily encounters and through the accruing of resources, gathered from their own attributes or human capital and resources gained from their networks or social capital. The programme concluded that these were intimately linked:

'Because it is in their relations with others in the locality that individuals' self-esteem, self-confidence and therefore human capital grows. What they see in the eyes of others is an enhanced image of themselves as someone who has a contribution to make. The resulting gain in confidence enables them to extend their capabilities. ...people who have made the

progression are able to help others make the same progress... There is no boundary between human and social capital – they are reciprocal and complementary.’

(Moore, 2007, p. 189).

This approach shows evaluations of the world, being seen, and how people are seen, are important to facilitating health and wellbeing processes and are driven by human interrelations. Individuals and their social contexts are viewed as co-constituting each other. Wellbeing work is undertaken by the locality and its constitutive social and material relationships and affordances. These views find resonance with Hanlon et al.’s (2011) suggestions for the emergent qualities of a fifth wave of public health. These qualities include acknowledgement that health is complex, and involves greater working with others, growth of human life and spirit and integrating the objective with the subjective and intersubjective.

2.10. Are we in the fifth wave, or not?

There have been responses to Hanlon’s invitations to discuss the potential qualities for a fifth wave of public health (Hemingway, 2011; Davies *et al.*, 2014). In 2014, Professor Dame Sally Davies, Chief Medical Officer (CMO) for England and Chief Medical Adviser to the UK government and colleagues published a vision for the fifth wave of public health (Davies *et al.*, 2014).

Davies et al. (2014) response to Hanlon et. al.’s (2011) invitation was to propose a fifth wave of public health characterised by healthy behaviour as the standard mindset and is supported by society and the environment. Davies et al. (2014) conceptualise Hanlon’s first four waves of public health based on its focus. These waves are structural, biomedical, clinical, and social (Figure 2.1). A fifth wave is proposed where the focus is a culture for health.

‘We start from the premise that population health improvement is conditional on a health-promoting societal context. This context is characterised by a culture in which healthy behaviours are the norm, and in which the institutional, social, and physical environment support this mindset. Achievement of this ambition will require a positive, holistic, eclectic, and collaborative effort, involving a broad range of stakeholders. We emphasise three mechanisms: maximisation of the value of health and incentives for healthy behaviour; promotion of healthy choices as default; and minimisation of factors that create a culture and environment which promote unhealthy behaviour.’

(Davies *et al.*, 2014, p. 1891).

Figure 2.1: Waves of public health including vision for the fifth wave (Davies *et al.*, 2014, p. 1891).

Davies *et al.* (2014) argue that a fifth wave of public health is needed due to the damage of the rise of individualism in modern society on individual and societal health and wellbeing. Therefore, the fifth wave of public health needs to focus on society working together to improve health, and value health, as a common good. This vision has been incorporated into the Scottish public health policy landscape through Scotland's public health reform work (Scottish Government and COSLA, 2019a) and used in academic literature to frame the contribution of arts and culture to public health (Sonke, Rodríguez and Valerio-Shewmaker, 2021). Scotland's public health reform work has produced a timeline framed by the waves of public health and declares that since 2010 Scotland is in the fifth wave of public health (Scottish Government and COSLA, 2019b).

Davies *et al.*'s vision for a fifth wave of public health acknowledge that behaviour change requires more than changing individual behaviour and structural and environmental changes are needed. However the vision's focus on behavioural change, which is present in the fourth wave of public health does not represent the radical break in thinking about health and society that Hanlon *et al.* (2011) argue is required. This vision could entrench the existing issues of a 'lifestyle drift' in health policy if the implementation of the vision focuses on the individual behaviour change parts of the argument. In addition, this chapter has already shown that an emphasis on behaviour, perpetuates the issues of individualism, leaving the focus of the fifth wave of public health at odds with its aims of tackling individualism. I argue that this vision for the fifth wave of public health, by proposing a norm, compounds the issues of stigma and shame already identified in this chapter. And therefore, there is a lack of attention of how individuals and their social contexts co-constitute each other. The vision does not make conceptual room for the complexities of health and wellbeing issues, such as the example of obesity and the everyday processes of health and wellbeing given earlier in this

chapter. The examples I have shown, demonstrate a need for valuing a range of different ontologies and epistemologies.

Davies et al. (2014, p. 1893) suggests how working across sectors 'will require alignment of motivations, attitudes, and trust to respond in innovative ways'. However, I argue that this alignment is not enough if there is no challenge to reductionism and individualism. In addition, health and wellbeing is not conceptually challenged by this proposal, leaving the concept defined by the healthcare sector. This limits the opportunity for other sectors to bring their ways of knowing and understanding health and wellbeing. Having a dominant way of viewing and knowing the world, means that other sectors have to fit their viewpoint and knowledge into this reductionist view of the world. This enforced reshaping entrenches the problems of the fourth wave of public health dulling the value of the ways of knowing and doing other sectors bring.

Broader definitions of health and wellbeing are needed to provide a description of public health that other sectors can more fruitfully contribute to, to build the cross-society sector partnerships needed to tackle public health (Atkinson, 2013).

I have thus established that a need for a shift in policy thinking and public perceptions about how health and society has been identified. The fourth wave of public health shifted thinking about health and society by introducing a social model that challenged a largely medical model. However, in many instances, the social model has not moved away from reductionist and individualistic approaches, which inform the tendency of policies to reduce health inequalities to focus on the individual rather than thinking about health and society. Any proposed characteristics of a fifth wave of public health need to counter the dominance of reductionist and individualistic approaches by valuing the connections between us (Kriznik *et al.*, 2018). This proposal needs to also value complexity, a challenge that is faced not just by health policy, but policy making overall (Cairney and Geyer, 2015). The proposal also needs to address a conceptual challenge resulting in what Atkinson (2020) terms as 'toxic wellbeing'. Atkinson suggests that without paying attention to the nuances of relationships, which help us understand how we become well together, collective wellbeing defaults to the sum of individual wellbeing, entrenching individualism.

The fifth wave of public health needs qualities that counter individualism and the interiority of health and wellbeing to avoid medicalising everyday life and causing harm. Characteristics of a fifth wave should include a direct engagement with what it means to be human and be well together, and view practices and experiences of everyday life as generating the foundational processes of health and wellbeing.

2.11. Fifth wave of public health in Scotland

This section starts with the key legislation that shapes the Scottish health policy context and has created key organisations that deliver health in Scotland. The health policy context starts from 2010. This is the year that the public health reform programme in Scotland declares as the start of the fifth wave of public health (Scottish Government and COSLA, 2019b)

The reform of public health in Scotland views the fifth wave of public health as partnership working and cites Christie Commission as the first milestone in the move towards a fifth wave of public health⁴. The influential Christie Commission on the future of public services (Davidson, 2021; Glasgow, 2021; McKinlay, 2021) was set up by the Scottish Government and chaired by Dr. Campbell Christie. In 2011, the findings of the Christie Commission were published (Scottish Government, 2011). The report found that public services are riddled with systemic defects from short term planning, a top-down approach that is unresponsive to communities, and fragmented services. The report identified four principles to guide reform: empowering individuals and communities to involve them in the design and delivery of the services they use, greater partnership working, prioritising prevention, and avoiding duplication and sharing services across the whole system, including the public, third, and private sector. The report identifies positive approaches to public services reform as those that centre people's lives and the lives of communities of place and interest.

Health and social care were brought together by the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014 which was passed by the Scottish Government in February 2014 and came into force on April 1, 2016. The Act brought health and social care together by creating 31 Integration Authorities. The intention was shift services towards preventative and community-based services. In Renfrewshire this authority is the Renfrewshire Integration Joint Board⁵. Health and Social Care Partnerships are tasked with delivering the services set by the Integration Authorities (IA). Health and Social Care Partnerships services were previously managed separately by NHS Boards and local authorities. In Renfrewshire the NHS Board is NHS GGC and the local authority is Renfrewshire Council. The HSCP in Renfrewshire is the Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Partnership (RHSCP)⁶. RHSCP's third Strategic Plan places at its core equalities, lived and living experiences (Renfrewshire Health and

⁴ <https://publichealthreform.scot/media/1630/phs-timeline.pdf> (Accessed 22/03/2022)

⁵ <https://www.renfrewshire.hscp.scot/article/5230/Integration-Joint-Board> (Accessed 22/03/2022)

⁶ <https://www.renfrewshire.hscp.scot/article/5231/Renfrewshire-Health--Social-Care-Partnership> (Accessed 22/03/2022)

Social Care Partnership, 2022) The strategic context in this plan shows growing inequalities in mortality since 2008, across Scotland.

Scotland's public health systems and functions were examined in 2015 by the Scottish Government's Public Health Review group (Scottish Government, 2016). The Review group summarised the policy context in Scotland as providing a language for public services to describe key features such as new ways of working, community empowerment, a focus on inequality and a shift towards prevention. (Scottish Government, 2016). The review designates a core public health workforce as those engaged in public health activities and identify their role as being primarily public health and a wider public workforce consisting of staff and volunteers of any group and organisation that play an essential role in improving the public health and wellbeing. The long list of examples ranges from leisure services to greenspace organisations. Following the review, the Scottish Government and the Convention of Scottish Local Authorities (COSLA) partnered a public health reform programme. The national public health agency, Public Health Scotland was set up by this programme in April 2020.

The third sector is recognised by the Scottish Government as key to delivering the preventative agenda in the Christie Commission and is a key partner in the delivery of public health in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2016) . The Scottish Government set up the Third Sector Interface (TSI) network in 2011. The goal was to create, in each local authority area, one access point for support and advice to the third sector, and to provide leadership and advocacy of the sector to engage in the planning and delivery of local services (Social Research, 2016). TSIs can be single organisations or partnerships. Engage Renfrewshire is the TSI for Renfrewshire local authority and is a single organisation. Evaluations of TSIs find variation in how effective TSI are in delivering their core functions and third sector satisfaction with the local TSI (Social Research, 2016; TSI Scotland Network, 2021).

The radical shift towards preventative public spending recommended by the Christie Commission has not emerged (Boyle, 2021). There has been legislative action to empower communities, such as the Community Empowerment (Scotland) Act 2015⁷, which gives new rights to community bodies and new duties to public sector authorities. The Planning (Scotland) Act 2019⁸ introduced Local Place Plans to empower communities, these give new rights for communities to propose plans for development and use of land as part of the Scottish Planning System. These Acts impact on

⁷ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/community-empowerment-scotland-act-summary/> (Accessed 22/03/2022)

⁸ <https://www.gov.scot/policies/planning-architecture/reforming-planning-system/> (Accessed 22/03/2022)

community development and cultural production as well as health. For example, one of the first Local Place Plans in Scotland is led by WHALE Arts in Wester Hailes in Edinburgh. The organisation describes itself as a community-led arts charity and social enterprise, and as a cultural anchor organisation for Wester Hailes. The organisation is also undertaking a Community Asset Transfer, a right for community bodies to request local authorities and public bodies for land and buildings they could make use of that are part of the Community Empowerment Act⁹.

The Scottish Government's Culture Strategy for Scotland was published in February 2020 (Scottish Government, 2020a). The Policy continues the language of the Scottish policy context of working across sectors and empowering the community. The policy's guiding principle include place and culture as essential to wellbeing. The policy does not have a definition of culture, instead the policy lists how people engage with culture and that for many people it is something they determine and part of their everyday life. The policy has three ambitions, the first is 'strengthening culture' which is concerned with the cultural workforce and sector. Wellbeing is central to the other two ambitions: 'transforming through culture' focuses on culture being embedded across all policy areas and central to Scotland's wellbeing and 'empowering through culture' which is concerned with culture at a community and individual level, and views wellbeing as essential to our lives and wellbeing. There is a section titled Culture and Health. This section is scarce on details and merely states that it will work with Public Health Scotland and the support of the Arts Culture Health and Wellbeing Scotland network. The Cultural Policy has led to three programmes. One of these programmes Creative Communities, has mental wellbeing and reducing loneliness as one of its three areas of focus. Creative Communities aims to support and empower communities to develop cultural activities. Culture Collective aims to respond to the pandemic and encourage people to be involved in shaping their local culture life through supporting creative practitioners and communities to work together.

2.12. Conclusion

I set out in this chapter a definition of public health and a way of thinking about the different focuses of public health through Hanlon et. al.'s (2011) idea of waves of public health. I explore Hanlon et. al.'s (2011) argument that the fourth wave of public health has reached the peak and a fifth wave of public health is needed. I reach an agreement with Hanlon et al.'s argument and I suggest that the work to conceptualise health and wellbeing for my research needs to take place within this framework of waves of public health. The key legislative and policy background to public health in

⁹ <https://www.gov.scot/policies/community-empowerment/asset-transfer/> (Accessed 22/03/2022)

Scotland since 2010 incorporates the idea of the fifth wave of public health as set out by Davies et al. (2014). I suggest that the definition of the fifth wave of public health that is in use in Scotland is narrow. What emerges in this chapter is the pervasiveness of the orthodoxy of reductionism and individualism. The work of creating a fifth wave of public health, and therefore the work of my thesis requires developing ways to resist this orthodoxy and develop and make space for alternative ways of thinking.

I argue the work to resist orthodoxy and create space is required to mobilise culture and the arts for health and wellbeing, and therefore recognise public health activity beyond the formal health care sector. As without an expansion of ontological and epistemological approaches, there will not be the conceptual and epistemological space for non-healthcare sectors to bring in their own knowledge. The work of counter-conceptualisation is needed as the fourth wave of public health does not provide adequate language to articulate the contribution of non-healthcare sectors to public health. Without this work, knowledge is warped as people pretzel their knowledge to fit into the hegemonic language.

The orthodox approach to thinking about health and wellbeing may be useful when seeking to understand the factors of health and wellbeing. However, when the task is to understand how to facilitate health and wellbeing, particularly the everyday processes of health and wellbeing, and subjective experiences, the thinking of the fourth wave of public health reaches its limit. A fifth wave of public health is needed to bring in multiplicities of knowledge, to ensure a diversity of thinking and knowledge is valued by designers of policies and services that seek to improve health and wellbeing. This knowledge could include the knowledge of those who facilitate health and wellbeing through place-based policy, facilitators who work in non-public health settings and individuals facilitating their everyday health and wellbeing.

In this chapter I have identified a range of characteristics needed for a fifth wave of public health. These characteristics are embracing multitudes of knowledge and complexity, a concern with connections, and a focus on the everyday. I also identify the need for my research to make ontological and epistemological commitments. My research needs to develop ways to resist reductionism and individualism and give room to multiplicities of knowledge of ways. Therefore, I need to develop a methodological approach that makes these commitments and is suited to examining my proposal for the characteristics of a fifth wave of public health.

3. Methodological approaches and methods

3.1. Introduction

The development in my research focus and in myself as a researcher means my methodological approach evolved throughout my thesis. My fluid and flexible methodological approach meant I adapted to the many changes that arose throughout this research. My approach also responded to the deepening ontological and epistemological commitments my thesis was making. Therefore, this chapter provides my methodological approach and methods and also provides an overview of the process of evolving a suitable methodological approach.

I start this chapter with my relationship to methodology and methods in order to introduce where my thesis and my researcher self evolves from. I expand on my introduction in Chapter 1 of the policy interest in Paisley by the FPPB of the use of culture and the arts for health and wellbeing ends, as a case for this research. I add more detail to the overview given in Chapter 1 of how I critically engaged with my original research brief and developed a new research focus. My methodology is built from by my research orientation which guides my ontology, the focus on the relational and the everyday, and how I approach the research process. The description of methodology is continued in a section that lays out my research sensibilities, a way of being in the world that can assist me to attune to the nuance of people's experiences and knowledge. This section examines my position on epistemology, the commitment to diversity of knowing, and how my position informs the self in the field. I present the lines of inquiry that provide research trails for my research to follow. These trails lead to research encounters that contribute to growing knowledge.

The methods that inform how I grow knowledge are then provided, along with my research ethics. Processes of how I make meaning and how these processes move away from qualitative research is discussed. The process of making sense of knowledge provides insights that are framed by the research questions. Collectively these insights give a sketch of the research puzzle that informs how I meet the research aim.

3.2. Methodological baggage

My methodological baggage influences the emergence of my research aims and questions. The baggage comes from a professional career as an economic development consultant between 2003 and 2014. My undergraduate and post graduate economics courses completed two decades ago did not make explicit that I was thinking within a positivist paradigm of an objective reality that can be known to research. Neither was it deemed necessary to explain that I was undertaking a reductionist

approach to understanding complexity by breaking phenomena into smaller parts. There was no need to talk about paradigms because my economic courses considers that there is only one paradigm, that of positivism and reductionism. This paradigm was compounded by economic impact and evaluation orthodoxy set out by the UK Government. I modelled impact and scenarios of projects, programmes, and organisations. I enjoyed taking complex narratives and reducing them to a diagram or an infographic. I was good at reductionism and clients found these narratives helpful in communicating their work. However, there were limits to what I could explore in my work. I was not required to explore mechanisms in my professional practice of creating logic chains for programme evaluation. The standard steps in logic chains are input, activity, output, and outcomes. I was frustrated at the lack of attention on how activity results in output and outcomes, such as the time and emotionally intensive work of building trust and relationships. This gap has been termed a 'black box' (Dalkin *et al.*, 2015). I was also frustrated by the value placed on quantitative data over people's experiences, the belief in the objectivity of data, and building evidence around returns to £1 of funding rather than trust. I started developing discomfort that the quantitative 'evidence' I was producing was perpetuating the values, beliefs, and systems I was frustrated with.

I was attracted to the brief for this PhD opportunity as the suggestion to undertake action research and develop evaluation methods would provide an opportunity to explore my discomfort and create action to address them. I was excited to delve into the 'black box' by exploring mechanisms and pathways between the experience of culture and the arts and an improvement in health and wellbeing. I had intentions of placing mechanisms in a theoretical framework. In doing so, I would address an underexplored area in the arts and health field (Stickley *et al.*, 2017). However, I found a further black box. When phenomena such as self-esteem, meaningfulness or sense of belonging are designated as a mechanism (What Works Wellbeing, 2019), there is no further investigation of how these phenomena are formed. There was a limit to my reductionist approach, and I started to search for ways of thinking to help understand how these phenomena emerge.

I discovered that shedding the methodological baggage of positivism and reductionism required more than learning different methodological approaches. I understood that there were ontological and epistemological tensions both between and within the fields I was investigating, such as health inequalities and the use of culture and the arts for social purposes such as health and wellbeing. However, for me to fully discern these tensions and to situate my work within them requires experiential knowledge as well as an abstract understanding. I had to bring to the theoretical analysis and empirical knowledge I was growing, my own experiences of living the concepts I was proposing, as a health and wellbeing practitioner and a facilitator of the intertwining processes of culture, the arts, health and wellbeing. I had to inhabit a range of epistemological perspectives in

order to feel the tension. I found undertaking researching in an epistemological fluid manner uncomfortable. As it left me without a named methodological approach that I could get to know, that would give me an initial roadmap for research design, one that would give me something concrete to position myself with, a place to be in conversations with others such as critical realism (Pawson, 2013) or constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2014). I had to adapt to what the research needed, not what I needed.

I have undertaken a wide range of methodological training to develop my methodological knowledge. I have also gained knowledge about what evaluation and evidence means to people from listening: in person, in webinars, in volunteering conversations, and in conversations in Paisley. I hear many conversations about the gap between their perception of what people felt they had to provide as evidence and what they thought was important about the work they undertook. I listened to conversations about the performative nature of providing evidence and the ethics of asking people to fill in surveys about how they were feeling. These conversations helped my reflexive interrogation of my own practice and ontological and epistemological unease about contributing more evidence. These conversations grounded the increasingly theoretical nature of my work. The development of my conceptual thinking is rooted in my observations of what people do in terms of facilitating health and wellbeing and people's accounts of how they experience culture, the arts, health and wellbeing. I found that this facilitation was not always seen as work or as a skill that had been developed, as for facilitators, this work was just part of what they needed to do to make a space welcoming or to make people feel validated. I started to recognise that I was also in this position, that I have unknowingly had a practice of facilitating health and wellbeing. Without the language to articulate what I had been doing, I and the people I have been speaking to, have not recognised our role as wider public health workers. This realisation led me away from searching for mechanisms and towards seeking concepts that would help articulate my observations of the work undertaken to create health and wellbeing. The ontological and epistemological directions of this search took me away from the positivist paradigm that was deeply ingrained in me to the point I did not realise how my thinking was constrained by the dominant paradigm. I did not realise my search for mechanisms was a manifestation of the constraint in thinking resulting from this paradigm. Therefore, I came to the realisation that the starting research question of 'how might culture and the arts contribute to health and wellbeing' was also constrained by the dominant paradigm, as the question presupposes that if there is a contribution it is a linear relationship between two separate groups of concepts. My initial research question is a manifestation of reductionist thinking. Finding a different research question required developing a different paradigm of health and wellbeing. As my

research became more focused on developing a paradigm for health and wellbeing, I became aware that I was responding to Hanlon et al.'s (2011) invitation to propose a fifth wave of public health.

3.3. A shift in research focus

The shift in research focus also occurred through the shift in my engagement with activities in Paisley. The interest in Paisley, of which Future Paisley is one example, to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing improvement could be categorised as a case. A case can be a process, an object, a concept, something at the micro or macro level and something operated to bind things (Stake, 1995; Merriam, 1998; Yin, 2009; Creswell, 2012; Schwandt and Gates, 2017). The binding in my research is geographical, the town of Paisley. The binding is also an interest, the policy interest in Paisley to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing ends. As I develop my ontological and epistemological perspective my definition of policy evolves. Descriptions of my approach to describing the term policy is provided in subsequent chapters. I start with Bell and Oakley's (2015) broad view of policy as ideas that have some kind of form and are assumed to have some kind of effects. The geographical binding is porous as key organisations in Paisley such as the local council, the health and social care partnership, the leisure trust and the third sector interface operate at a local authority level, Renfrewshire. The interest to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing ends, evolved in the research to focus on the development of policy and organizations in Paisley.

Different cases emerge in the research for different research intents. I develop a research focus to explore the ontological and epistemological tensions of how health and wellbeing is defined. My conceptual exploration leads me to focus on one public health issue, loneliness, which could be considered a case. Future Paisley could be viewed as a case for place-based policies designed to use culture for health and wellbeing. Organisations emerge in my research as cases for conceptual approaches to health and wellbeing. To make my research process clearer, 'case' in this research refers to the bounded situation I enter to undertake the research: Paisley as a place where there is a policy interest in using culture and the arts for social ends. I use the term research object and research puzzle to describe what Mason's terms (2018) my intellectual puzzle, which is what I want to know more about. This section outlines how the research focus and research puzzle evolved from my engagement with the policy interest in Paisley to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing.

I am an outsider to Paisley. It takes two trains and two hours to travel from my home in Edinburgh to Paisley. I have no relationship to the town except for the management of one consultancy project that required me to visit the town twice to carry out meetings and interviews. My immersion in Paisley started from the beginning of the PhD, in February 2019. The research focus at this time was

to build relationships that would develop into an action research project. Building these relationships would help me understand the nature of the interest to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing. This involved one to one meetings with people in Paisley as suggested by my supervision team, attending CAHSC meetings, meetings with organisations and conversations with people I meet through CAHSC and events in Paisley. An action research project was emerging in January 2020 with the intention of using the newly set up CAHSC Research and Evaluation group as a community of inquiry. It was anticipated that projects exploring evaluation with individual organisations would be developed.

On 2⁴th of March 2020, lockdown was announced to deal with COVID-19. This led to measures to restrict going out and meeting people and an introduction of social distancing. In Paisley, organisations pivoted to frontline work to individuals connected to the community and each other and address local needs. People were adjusting to altered roles and new ways of working. Ethically, it was not an appropriate for me to request time of people. A research project is to some degree an intrusion into the working lives of potential participants, and the researcher has to balance whether this intrusion is appropriate (Maxwell, 2013). I judged that it was not appropriate to ask people who are taking on more work to adjust to COVID-19, to make space for my research. In addition, I believe the needs of the community are more of a priority than my research.

It was not feasible for me to embed myself in activities in other ways, such as volunteering for organisations I had formed relationships with and observing the adjustment to lockdown. As I do not live in Renfrewshire and as well as distance rules, there were restrictions regarding leaving my local authority area to go to Renfrewshire, and restrictions on the use of public transport. My relationship building and the planned programme of research activity paused. I had not yet developed relationships with specific projects and therefore there was not the option of joining online groups. In the absence of generating knowledge by immersing in activities in Paisley, knowledge was generated by applying my emerging conceptual lens to my own current activities. Two of the three strands of action research, action and participation frayed, leaving just research.

Loneliness as a public health issue became my site of investigation for exploring health and wellbeing. My interest in loneliness emerged from my conceptual explorations of the fifth wave of public health and my observations of what was going on in Paisley. My interest in understanding how projects and organisations in Paisley were tackling loneliness led to research encounters with organisations, networks, events and conversations with individual people with roles related to mitigating loneliness and social isolation.

The evolution of Future Paisley Step Change 2 continued and as a member of CAHSC, I was invited to a series of workshops to develop this Step Change. My research shifted from a project level focus and from project evaluations to a focus on the interaction between organisations, projects, evaluations and the development of policy.

This shift from a research interest in designing evaluations to questioning the purpose of evaluations intertwined with a shift in conceptual orientation. My conceptual exploration of culture, the arts, health and wellbeing led me towards ideas that emphasised openness and complexity. This exploration along with the shedding of my methodological baggage led to an emergence of a new research focus, to develop a response to Hanlon et al.'s (2011) invitation to envisage the characteristics of a fifth wave of public health. From this research intent emerged an iterative process of drawing together empirical and theoretical knowledge. The research veers closest to the abductive approach to knowledge growing which Mason (2018, p. 228) suggests as where 'theory, data generation and data analysis are developed simultaneously in a dialectical and iterative process.' The simultaneous growth in my conceptual and empirical knowledge, leads to the emergence of Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension as my research puzzle and my research focus evolves to analyse this dimension through the lens of my proposal for the characteristics of a fifth wave of public health.

Mason (2018) provides a typology of different types of intellectual puzzles which influence the research orientation. The development of my ontological and epistemological views means I start to view my concepts as dynamic shifting processes, and I become interested in how things change and influence each other. Therefore, I start evolving a view of the research object that aligns with Mason's description of a processual puzzle. My ontological interest in the relationship between individuals, the world they inhabit, the feelings that influence this relationship and how this relationship emerges from the way entities co-constitute each other also leads to my view of the research puzzle aligning with Mason's description of an ecological puzzle. In addition, the length of the immersion in the case allows me to approach the research object as a processual puzzle and an ecological puzzle. As I am able to have a dynamic view of the movements that shape the research puzzle as some activities emerge, some disappear. Since the start of the research there has been a rapid growth in the academic field of arts and health, and new national policies and ideas have emerged and interacted with activities in Paisley. My conceptual exploration of definitions of health and wellbeing led to an ontological focus on the interactions and connectiveness of things and elements. This research direction was reinforced by the pandemic which brought into focus how we can be collectively well together, what we connect to and how we co-constitute each other.

3.4. Research aims and questions

I have expanded on the change in my research questions and in set out in Chapter 1. My research aim now is to investigate how place-based policies designed to utilise culture and the arts for social ends might shift thinking on health and wellbeing by observing developments in policy and activity in Paisley.

I start to explore the research aim with the following research questions:

- What might the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health be?
- What concepts could help articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health?
- How might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and wellbeing?
- How might a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends grow a health and wellbeing dimension?

3.5. Research orientation

Research designs are differentiated by what they seek to accomplish (Creswell, 2012). My research orientation is an active process. It is more than an ontological and epistemological lens. It is a resistance to a paradigm, it is a way of being in the world, an evolving direction into a new paradigm and it is also an ethos. The previous chapter argues that these are the characteristics I need to seek a new wave of public health. I suggest in the previous chapter that health should be viewed through an ontology of complexity, relations, processes, openness, and constant changes. That there should be an epistemological approach to invite and value a diversity of ways of knowing. This approach is a research technique to keep up with the dynamism of my research puzzle and research context. It is also an ethos regarding what types of knowledge I value. My research orientation needs to have the ontological and epistemological qualities that Chapter 2 concluded the fifth wave of public health requires. Kincheloe's (2005, p. 327) quote illustrates that bricolage has these qualities as 'bricoleurs plan their escape from the limitations of monological knowledge, they envision forms of research that transcend reductionism.' This quote encapsulates my research position at the start of the research process of escaping my methodological baggage. My emerging envisioning of forms of research is given in the section on the shift in research focus. The resonance of this quote leads to me to turn to bricolage to form my active research orientation. Going further into Kincheloe's (2005) article I find that bricoleurs undertake epistemological analysis that investigate questions about how

different paradigms shape what we know and we value. This analysis is what I need to address my research aim and questions.

Bricolage is a fluid approach of using whatever is available to undertake the research (Kincheloe, 2001; Maxwell, 2013; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Bricolage can be oriented at paradigm and methodological levels (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). To maximise the openness of my research orientation, I situate myself inbetween multiple ways of knowing, disciplines, and discourses. Bricolage views the 'nodes, the nexuses, the linkages, the interconnections, the fragile bonds between disciplines, between bodies of knowledge, between knowing and understanding themselves.' (Lincoln, 2001, p. 694) and has an 'epistemology of complexity' (Kincheloe, 2005, p. 324). The viewpoint of bricolage resists reductionism and connects 'the research act to the emotion and heart of lived human experience' (Kincheloe, 2005, p. 348). In the previous chapter, I argued that this connection to emotion and experience is a necessary characteristic of the fifth wave of public health.

The viewpoint of articulating a research paradigm can be considered restrictive, and it may be more useful to think of a research framework as being built from perspectives (Maxwell, 2013). Facet methodology is helpful for me to think through this idea of perspectives. Facet methodology's connective and anti-reductionist ontology (Mason, 2011) extends the bricolage viewpoint that the whole is greater than the sum of the parts (Kincheloe, 2005). Facet methodology commits to not just the work of bricolage in bringing pieces together in a collage and juxtaposing them but also investigates the connectivity and entwinement between the collage pieces (Mason, 2011). Facet methodology is helpful for my research orientation due to the focus on both the whole and the parts. My whole is the research case of place-based policies designed to use culture for health and wellbeing ends, my parts or facets are the indicative research questions. Facets are what I want to bring into view about research case and research puzzle. Facet methodology acknowledges that the whole is never fully known and instead seeks to engage with the research case through flashes of insight rather than discerning the overall shape. Therefore my research moves away from a case study approach (Creswell, 2012). Acknowledging that the whole is never fully known is an important start for my research, as the research puzzle constantly evolves, and I am interested in the process of this evolution. Following my research focus requires an abductive process between understanding the research puzzle and developing a proposal for the fifth wave of public health. A case study approach would put more focus on understanding the research puzzle. I use facet methodology to juxtapose pieces that give knowledge of both the research puzzle and my proposal for a fifth wave of public health. Facet methodology is a useful guide to help me think about how to approach an

abductive process. The focus on connectivity and entwinement is more ontologically aligned with the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health that start emerging from the previous chapter.

3.6. Research sensibilities

3.6.1. Introduction

I argue in the previous chapter that the invitation to envisage the fifth wave of public health is a call to action by widening who and what activities are part of public health. Therefore, meaning making is an important part of my methodology. Ideas to shift thinking on health and wellbeing need to be meaningful to people. Meaning is constructed by resonating with people's experience of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing and with practitioners' knowledge of facilitating these experiences. I need to have an epistemological approach of being where people are in terms of how they think about health and society in order to make my epistemological commitment to a diversity of ways of knowing. This knowledge grounds my conceptual exploration in what matters to people. Research sensibilities are a way of being in the world that can assist me in attuning to people's experiences and knowledge. This section examines the research sensibilities that inform my methodology to explore my research questions.

3.6.2. Action research sensibilities

My original research focus was to work collaboratively with organisations and individuals on issues where there is mutual need and interest. Action research is a term for a group of research approaches from a broad range of different traditions that emphasise collaboration, the study of ongoing action and pursue both action and theory development (Cropper, Snooks, *et al.*, 2007; Dick, 2007; Herr and Anderson, 2015). The research aim and the use of action research as a research approach are aligned as the purpose of both is to produce useful knowledge that contributes to wellbeing (Reason and Bradbury, 2008a).

Action research seeks to accomplish change. Changes occur within the setting or within the participants and researchers (Herr and Anderson, 2015) through improving practice, developing projects and programmes and addressing needs (Stringer, 2013). Knowledge is generated and tested through action (Greenwood and Levin, 2006). Action, research, and participation are the three interwoven strands of action research (Greenwood and Levin, 2006).

Action research has the characteristics of pragmatism and flexibility, as it is a research approach that designs research, while learning about the context (Herr and Anderson, 2015). As an emergent design, action research allows for a fluid research process that adapts to a growing understanding of

a situation and changes in context and circumstances (Herr and Anderson, 2015). One task of action research is to create the conditions where action might happen and there is time and space to adjust the nature of the action (Cropper, Snooks, *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, action research suits my constantly evolving research puzzle and the dynamic theoretical and empirical context where I am always in the midst of understanding.

In action research, a major goal is to produce local knowledge for the local setting (Herr and Anderson, 2015). My initial intention is to undertake an action research programme with partners. I would begin with a relationship-building period to build trust and understanding and to scope out partners who may be interested in collaborating with an action research project. The intent was for communities of inquiry to be set up with interested parties to follow Reason and Bradbury's (2008b, p. 5) description of good action research emerging iteratively 'as individuals develop skills of inquiry and as communities of inquiry develop within communities of practice'. I anticipated communities of practice in keeping with Wenger's description (1998) would grow around a shared interest in culture and the arts projects that sought to improve health and wellbeing. And the knowledge we would share and grow together would centre around how to evaluate these types of projects. I envisioned my action research role was to 'become a facilitator who acts as catalyst to assist stakeholders to define their problems clearly, and to monitor and support their activity as they work towards effective resolution of the issues that provide the focus of their investigations.' (Stringer, 2013, p. 20). These problems would relate to how to evaluate projects and show progress towards Step Change 2.

Action research projects never materialised due to lockdown measures related to COVID-19. However, I had built relationships and the principles of seeking social change were carried on in my research, therefore an action-informed imprint was left on my research sensibility. As my research left the intent of undertaking action research behind, the emphasis on emergent design and the goal to produce local knowledge was still carried forward. I still seek to create useful knowledge and to contribute to change even though the scope is more modest and informal than an action research project. I still retain the action research double goal of testing the conceptual lens in the local context and affecting change in the local context (Herr and Anderson, 2015). I seek to contribute to change by contributing to a shift in ideas about health and society, and introducing concepts to practitioners in Paisley that can articulate the work required for the fifth wave of public health. This research carries with it the action research belief that theory needs to be accompanied by action, which is mutually constituted in praxis (Carr and Kemmis, 1986). My research sensibility is informed by systemic action research (Burns, 2007). This approach to systemic action research seeks sustainable change by engaging with the whole system such as looking at how different actors may sit in different parts of the system. Looking at one piece of the system, such as one project or

organisation, is not enough to understand the systemic nature of change. This sensibility leads me to develop a research approach of aiming to accept all invitations to grow knowledge, both for my research and for local stakeholders. As the research progresses and takes on more of a policy focus, this sensibility is helpful in considering Future Paisley's ambitions for system change in the delivery of public services.

My research practice is informed by Wicks, Reason and Bradbury's (2008, p. 15) description of action researchers' practice as underpinned by 'the web of relationships, events, influences, role models, and experiences'. They go on to suggest action research as a practice intimately intertwined with the researcher's life, principles, stance, and interest, which emerge from who they are and what they do in the world. This description guides me to bring in experiences and knowledge I have gained outside this research project and develop a reflexive research practice. The action research web of relationships fits with the ontology of my research orientation of bricolage and facet methodology. An action informed research practice fits with the epistemology of bricolage and facet methodology which takes a stance of not viewing boundaries between different ways of knowing such as the theoretical and empirical, and instead sees them as embedded in each other (Kincheloe, 2005).

3.6.3. Ethnographic sensibilities

The nature of the research object alignment with Mason's (2018) typology of intellectual puzzles as a processual and ecological puzzle suggests that I need a research sensibility that is helpful to discerning dynamics and nuances. Ethnography is one approach that provides this sensibility. Ethnography is described by Atkinson et al. (2007, p. 2) as having 'deep and diverse roots, its wide-ranging methods, and its many applications'. Ethnography therefore cannot be equated to one disciplinary tradition despite anthropology and sociology's claims to this research approach. A commitment to experience and the exploration of a social and cultural situation, usually through participant observation, bonds the diversity of ethnographic approaches to each other (Atkinson *et al.*, 2007; Van Maanen, 2011). I take this commitment to experience as part of my research sensibility. I require this commitment as the literature review identifies a lack of consideration of the experience of culture and health and wellbeing in policy-making and academic research. This commitment aligns with the commitment to epistemological diversity of my research orientation.

I argue in the previous chapter that the everyday is the site for individual transformation.

Ethnography by its definition is about exploring and understanding the everyday. An ethnographic sensibility 'is attention to the conditions and experiences of life as actually lived' (McGranahan, 2018, p. 7). I argue in the literature review that knowledge gained from this attention is undervalued in the reductionist approach of seeking mechanisms, pathways and factors in the evaluations and

causal narratives that dominate orthodox approaches to gathering evidence. To attend to everyday life, some reflexive moments in my research have an autoethnographic flavour in order to build knowledge from my experience of concepts.

Reductionist approaches abstract the human experience. When everyday life is abstracted, humans become objectified and datafied. Humanness disappears from the research view and some humans, such as those who do not fit into survey categories disappear altogether. My research sensibility has an ethnographic alignment as it asks the ethnographic question of how meaning is brought into people's lives and is grounded in the messiness of life (McGranahan, 2018). Knowledge about universal concepts such as health and wellbeing is grown from the jumble of these everyday moments. Starting from this heap of moments is my approach to resisting reductionism. I draw from Ingold's (2014) approach to resisting reductionism as thinking of knowledge as grown through relationships rather than through a process of collection. My ethnographically informed research sensibility fits with the ontological focus on questions of being human required by my research orientation of bricolage and facet methodology.

3.6.4. Living with concepts

The research sensibilities inform how I use concepts to create knowledge to fulfil the research aim. During this research, I have found that to put theory to work and start the process of generating insights, for theory be useful as a lens to see the world, to explain my world view to others, I must live the concepts. Concepts must be present in my everyday life, made personal and become practice. This animation of theory through experience is how I seek to obtain the affective register to make theory resonate with people. To sink theory into their skin as well as mine, to paraphrase Ahmed (2017).

Three types of knowing are guiding me on how to live concepts: 'know in', 'know with', and 'know about' concepts. These ways of knowing are where observations and theory are drawn together (Sumartojo and Pink, 2018). I find these ways of knowing helpful to guide the research through the process of researching in emergent and uncertain environments and seeks to bring a closer dialogue between theory and empirical research.

Knowing in locates me and my research in the concept. Knowing happens in the concept, and I must be purposefully immersed in them. This type of knowing helps me to understand how the concept is constituted and experience the concepts. Through 'knowing in', I will develop my conceptual approach to culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing. I take the concepts into my own life to identify tensions and resonance. I will identify other people's knowing of these concepts through academic

literature grounded in everyday life, such as ethnographic accounts of health and wellbeing, community arts, and socially engaged arts practice. 'Knowing in' will guide me to experience the unsatisfactory nature of current understandings and definitions of health and wellbeing. Through this experience I will grow my conceptual sensitivity to how people express health, wellbeing, culture, and the arts in their terms. I will increase my capacity to engage people in discussions about health, wellbeing, culture, and the arts in an experiential way rather than an abstract way. In turn, the potential will increase for conceptual discussions to resonate with people's experiences and practice. The approach of knowing in will grow knowledge that will help with the research questions of 'what might the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health be?' And 'what concepts could help articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health?'

Knowing about suggests ways to analyse the concept after it has emerged, the conditions for emergence, understanding its configurations, effects, and impacts. My process of 'knowing about' will draw on a range of sources to understand the context for the emergence of Future Paisley. The process of 'knowing about' will help grow knowledge to answer the indicative research questions of 'how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society?' And 'how might a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends grow a health and wellbeing dimension?'

Knowing through is about using concepts to understand something else. I will identify gateway concepts through which people can engage with the ontological and epistemological thinking required for the fifth wave of public health. I will identify sensitizing concepts through which people can attune to everyday health-facilitating moments. I will use the phenomenon of loneliness to understand non-medical public health challenges and explore health and wellbeing as the dynamic accumulation of everyday encounters. As loneliness is a concern for Future Paisley, 'knowing through' loneliness will help me engage with people in Paisley to examine what they are doing in terms of loneliness and therefore for public health. The process of 'knowing through' concepts and loneliness will help grow knowledge to answer the indicative research questions of 'how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society?' And 'how might a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends grow a health and wellbeing dimension?'

3.6.5. The self in research

My research sensibility is informed by action research and ethnography. Both these research approaches require identity work and critical engagement with the self that appears in the field (Mason, 2018). Wicks, Reason and Bradbury (2008, p. 16) asked the editorial board of the Handbook

of Action Research what grounded their action research practice. They received replies recounting life journeys. These revealed the:

‘web of influence that has sustained and contributed to their work overtime. These webs encompass a wide range of influences, including personal and collegial relationships; encounters with role models; political and other significant events; spiritual disciplines; literature (fiction and nonfiction); activism and engagement with practitioners.’

Action research and ethnography approaches are both concerned with the importance of being transparent about the complexity of roles a researcher brings to their research and who they are in the research process. My research sensibility requires asking how who I am as a professional, and as a person, affects my research role in order to contribute to an interrogation of self (Herr and Anderson, 2015; Mason, 2018). Reinharz (1997) responds to the idea that the self is the key fieldwork tool. She suggests the self determines how I relate to people and how others relate to me. How I perceive myself affects my understanding of self and how the study proceeds. Reinharz (1997) categorised the selves she had in her research which were specific to the research context, and those which can be generalised to other research. The selves that I bring to my research are grouped in Reinharz’s three categories as:

- Research-based selves – PhD student affiliated to CCSE, academic researcher, being on a three-month placement as a social researcher with the Scottish Government.
- Brought selves – volunteer in various health and wellbeing related roles over multiple decades, consumer of arts and culture, non-human collective view of self, volunteer organiser of fitness and art activities that seek to create a sense of belonging and community, impact assessment and evaluation professional.
- Situationally created selves – evaluation knowledge, disseminator of theoretical knowledge from my research, particularly relating to health and wellbeing concepts.

These selves guided my reflective practice, which I use as a professional approach to support and develop practice (McIntosh, 2010). The need to draw on my own life to live my research concepts leads me to a reflexive engagement with my volunteering practice. As a volunteer, the idea of having a practice relating to the production of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing did not occur to me. In addition to my methodological baggage, I was also hindered by thinking that practice was something professionals did in their roles, such as those who are paid for such work or have been trained. I was unaware that I have a practice of reflexivity. My collective advocacy volunteering questions the political and social structures that shape our lives, such as cultural hierarchies, and creates a space to bring these structures into critical view. The need to develop the credibility of my

situationally created self, led to undertaking further training. For example, I undertook a course in evaluation training in arts and health and attended webinars to learn from other evaluators of arts and health projects and programmes. This inquiry into my multiple strands of practice meets with Reason and Bradbury's (2008a) guidance on compelling and enduring research. Research should be undertaken at three levels of inquiry, your own practice, your practice with others and a wider community of inquiry.

These selves interact with each other. Bringing the situationally created selves with the research-based selves could be useful when discussing evaluation processes. Evaluations with an explicit theoretical basis can provide a more constructive process (Daykin and Joss, 2016). To bring different ways of knowing together, from the experience of culture, health, and wellbeing to the practice of policy and evaluation, requires me to draw on these multiple selves, sometimes simultaneously. Mason and Dale (2011, p. 20) helpfully illustrate this process as 'the idea of reflexive engagement of an agentic researcher, blurring the boundary between data generation, analysis and theorising.'

3.7. Being in the research and finding sites to grow knowledge

3.7.1. Introduction

This section examines the research trails I followed. These trails build knowledge to answer the indicative research questions. I outline how I sought to immerse myself in the field and how the immersion was shaped by COVID-19, the strategic context in Paisley, and my growing conceptual awareness. The research trails are also informed by my position in the field, which is shaped by my research sensibilities and the self that is in the field. I communicate how the selves examined previously develop and interact with each other, how they find a way into the research and grow knowledge.

3.7.2. Research trails

My research case, place-based policies that are designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing purposes, has many dimensions. The process of following research trails can be illustrated by Mason's (2011, p. 83) descriptions of facets which 'are directed towards puzzles about the entwinement, contingencies, and multi-dimensionality of the world'. Following facet methodology, I have chosen facets of my research case and research puzzle to serve as lines of inquiry. These facets intersect to build a cumulative argument regarding how these policies might contribute to a shift in thinking about health and society to grow a fifth wave of public health. These facets are my indicative research questions and my initial sites for bringing together my developing and empirical insights and grow knowledge.

I used seven lines of inquiry to guide the development of my knowledge of the research case and research puzzle. I thought of them as research trails as I am a trail runner, and the term resonates with the explorative and flexible way I make my way through the terrain. I then undertake the work of a bricoleur to make decisions on juxtaposing, ordering and layering knowledge (Wibberley, 2012). These lines of inquiry and the reasons for ordering are:

- In Chapter 4 I conceptually explore health and wellbeing. This exploration needs to be my starting point to understand what is meant when policies aim to improve health and wellbeing. This exploration is required to build a proposal to respond to the suggestion in Chapter 2 of a need for a shift in thinking about health and society in order to create a fifth wave of public health. This work needs to be undertaken first as this exploration provides the theoretical framework for the research as a whole and initiates the work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing that I engage with throughout the thesis.
- In Chapter 5 I conceptually explore culture and the arts so I can understand the rationale of using culture and the arts for social purposes. I take the knowledge grown in Chapter 4 to assess the literature of culture and the arts for social purposes for the potential contribution to the fifth wave of public health. This assessment starts to grow knowledge of the use of culture and the arts in the design of place-based policies that seek health and wellbeing goals.
- With the conceptual knowledge grown, I have the ontological and epistemological foundations to layer on empirical knowledge. In Chapter 6, I follow how cultural activity emerges in Paisley and the current and future interaction with Future Paisley in order to grow knowledge of how culture and arts activity is interacting with health and wellbeing. This knowledge will inform insights into the health and wellbeing activities that influences Future Paisley, and what health and wellbeing activities Future Paisley could have an influence on.
- I have developed my research viewpoint theoretically and empirically. I can now grow more knowledge in Chapter 7 by focusing on loneliness as a public health issue, as a site of theoretical and empirical investigation. At this site I juxtapose experiential knowledge of loneliness in academic research, grey literature, policy, research encounters in Paisley and further afield and from the knowledge of my brought selves. Knowledge is grown from this juxtaposition that adds another layer to the intertwining of theoretical and empirical knowledge formed in the previous chapters.
- In Chapter 8, now that familiarity has been established with activities and organisations in Paisley through Chapters 6 and 7, I can bring to the knowledge grown from research

encounters in Paisley, the gateway and sensitizing concepts I introduce in Chapter 4 to explore their resonance.

- The development of the research puzzle is followed in Chapter 9. The previous chapters have given the research an attunement to theoretical, empirical, and experiential knowledge relating to health and wellbeing, and of culture and the arts for social purposes. The establishment of this attunement and the knowledge I have grown from it, means I am able to layer observations about the research puzzle. This layering means the knowledge I grow from my observations will be nuanced and theoretically, empirically and experientially informed. The knowledge I grow provides insights into the conditions for the research puzzle to emerge and the possibilities for the research puzzle to contribute to a shift in thinking about health and wellbeing.

In keeping with my research orientation of bricolage, the order of layers is important to how research insights are developed. The layering of the chapters provides the reader with an attunement to specific ways of knowing and of particular characteristics of the research case and research puzzle that are then carried into and inform the subsequent chapters.

I am informed by Kincheloe's (2005) bricolage approach of searching for ways to be with, and make visible, the pain and joy of human experience. This visibility he suggests is the mark of the quality of the research. Making visible experiential ways of knowing provides a contrast with the abstractness of policy knowledge explored across the chapters, to provide insight into the tension between different approaches to knowing. My research by immersing the reader in how loneliness feels and forms the experience of being in the world, gives my research an experiential grounding that can be carried into the subsequent chapters. The anchoring of my research in feelings aims to counter the suppression of affect and emotion that leads to the leaching of the liveliness of life in reductionist approaches to data (Ravetz and Gregory, 2018). This methodological approach shows the process of bricolage in action.

3.7.3. Positioning

The multiplicity of selves needed to follow the research trails in turn creates a multiplicity of positionings as I seek to find the in-between positions articulated in the research orientation. An action research sensibility would suggest these positions as occupying multiple points on the continuum of positionality between insider and outsider (Herr and Anderson, 2015). These multiple points give a range of vantage points and a multi-dimensional view that are part of the active research orientation of facet methodology to resist the ontology and epistemology of reductionism. The intersections between positions place me in the tension of the fields and viewpoints being

researched. I examine these tensions to gain insights to help me view the complexity of my concepts and research puzzle.

I am an outsider in terms of my academic and practitioner knowledge. I am not from the field of health or culture, either as an academic researcher or as a practitioner. I would not consider myself an artist despite Matarasso's (2019) suggestion that my involvement in the occasional creative act of sketching defines me as an artist. Reflexivity regarding my brought and situated selves was immediately required on the commencement of the PhD to examine what knowledge I have that I can bring into dialogue with the knowledge I ask others to share. This dialogue forms dialogic processes of growing knowing and intersubjective meaning making.

I have outsider vantage points from being outside the design and delivery of policy and projects. My insider vantage points come from my brought self living the concepts and being invited into the development of Future Paisley's Step Change 2. I am neither a covert observer nor a fully overt observer. People are aware I am a PhD researcher. People let me in their spaces such as meetings as researcher or as my situated self as an evaluation expert. People know I am researching how culture and the arts contribute to health and wellbeing, that I have a particular interest in loneliness and what health and wellbeing means and also an expertise in evaluation. Openness is a characteristic of my positioning, in emails, in meetings, in casual conversations. I respond to invitations and requests, as my action research sensibility seeks to help people make change. My openness aligns with the characteristics of a bricoleur.

3.8. Methods and research encounters

3.8.1. Introduction

My research orientation and sensibilities value an emergent process to growing knowledge that is dependent on the situation I find myself in. Knowledge that is grown in this thesis are facilitated through methods driven by a greed in the search for knowledge and insight (Mason, 2011) and are grouped into the categories in this section. In keeping with bricolage's process of theory and empirical knowledge being embedded in each other, this section also gives details of the empirical sites in Paisley where theoretical developments have taken place.

3.8.2. Participant Observation

Participant observation is used in this research to see data emerge during meetings, as it is a method where the researcher is in everyday settings (Glesne, 1998). This method has been most associated

with ethnography (Bryman, 2012). Ingold's (2014, p. 389) description of participant observation as a practice of attending resonates with my research sensibilities of attunement:

'To attend to what others are doing or saying and to what is going on around and about; to follow along where others go and to do their bidding, whatever this might entail and wherever it might take you. This can be unnerving and entail considerable existential risk. It is like pushing the boat out into an as yet unformed world—a world in which things are not ready made but always incipient, on the cusp of continual emergence.'

Ingold (2014) suggests participant observation as an ontological commitment against objectification. Participant observation, like my conceptual stance on culture, health, and wellbeing, is a process of the accretion of small everyday moments into something that has enough form to be considered knowledge and used in this research.

Groups where I have been invited to meetings include:

- CAHSC – my involvement commenced at the start of the PhD. CAHSC was freshly formed, and I have participated in its subsequent iterations. This provides an insight into the nexus between policy and practice and between culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing.
- Paisley Museum – the organisation's management intended to develop a definition of health and wellbeing to assist the process of embedding health and wellbeing into all the organisation's activity. This process is informed by a community listening exercise, the vision of the overall Paisley Museum Reimagined project, the goals of OneRen and Future Paisley. The definition of health and wellbeing will inform project development and evaluation. I was invited in September 2020 onto two workstreams that will contribute to the process of embedding health and wellbeing into the Museum's way of working and thinking, The Volunteering and Skills workstream and the Public Programming Workstream. It was intended that participation in the meetings would give me an insight into the organisation. This insight would lead into conversations to assist in the development of a description of health and wellbeing for the organisation. This description would help prioritise activities to inform the monitoring and evaluation plan of the workstreams. However, a change in senior management meant this activity did not progress. Engaging in the museum provides an insight into the perspective and actions of a cultural organisation that seeks to embed health and wellbeing across the organisation.
- Recovery Hub – managed by Renfrewshire Drug and Alcohol Service, which is part of the RHSCP. The Hub aims to provide meaningful activities for people recovering from addiction and mental health issues. I was initially connected to the Recovery Hub through a series of

meetings in September 2020, due to my interest in finding a project concerned with addressing loneliness. The connection came from staff at the Hub looking for somebody to lead a jogging group. A relationship was subsequently developed due to management interest in how the Hub could demonstrate the impact they were having. The Hub has an approach to ensure that lived experience and peer work is core to the development of the Hub. The Hub set up a focus group to determine what the Hub means to the people who will interact with it, including discussing what health and wellbeing means to them. I was invited to participate in the focus group meetings where people discussed what health, wellbeing, and meaningful activity meant to them. I accepted as this would grow knowledge into how people talked about health and wellbeing and how processes of co-creation developed.

- RHSCP SPG Connectedness Network – the first meeting was in September 2020 with a pause due to a change in personnel of the third sector organisation leading the Network and the moving on of the first project officer. Attendance at these meetings grew knowledge of community-centred approaches to health and the local context for addressing loneliness and social isolation.

I also participated in workshops to develop Future Paisley and its monitoring and evaluation plan. I made ad hoc contributions to the Open Mind Summit, a Future Paisley project led by Create Paisley. This is an annual one-day event exploring how creativity and culture improve young people's wellbeing. It was first held in 2019 and mainly attracts practitioners such as educators, third sector workers to youth workers. My contributions included input into its evaluation process and hosting a panel discussion in 2020. That year's event had a focus on exploring how creativity can help children and young people overcome isolation and loneliness. My discussion was about what do we mean when we talk about isolation and loneliness in young people.

Through my membership of CCSE I attended steering group meetings where I heard about projects and activities in Paisley and from people in key strategic organisations. My participation in the CCSE annual symposium in 2021 involved liaising with local practitioners and projects to present their activity and to host a discussion with presenters. My participation grew my knowledge of what was happening locally in terms of activities that entwined culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing.

One of these local practitioners was a member of Renfrewshire Arts Team and this example is one of the many interactions I have with the Team, dating back to the start of the research due to their membership of CAHSC. Interactions include one to one conversations, being at the same events, workshops/discussions, and presenting to the same FPPB meetings. Measuring impact and evaluation is a theme running through our interactions. During the first lockdown I co-designed a

survey for their RenTV project, OneRen's online platform showing events, films and gigs. I hoped the survey could be used for my own research purposes. Due to technical issues, the survey was never launched.

3.8.3. Observation, learning and training

My research also grew knowledge through undocumented observation. A separation from the field due to lockdown, led to me to follow on Twitter, organisations and people that I had met in Paisley. I grew knowledge of how organisations and people were adapting to COVID-19, what activities and projects being undertaken by organisations. I also gained a sense of key partnerships from who was tagged and referred to in posts and through retweets and linking. I observed encounters between the activities of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing and interactions between organisations beyond culture, arts, health, and wellbeing. The weekly blogs published on the CCSE website also contributed to the process of learning about activity in Paisley and Renfrewshire related to culture, the arts, health and wellbeing.

I grew knowledge by undertaking professional training. The development of my situated self required new skills and keeping up to date with new research and activities. I attended a multi-day NHS training course on being an effective public health practitioner and a multi-day training course on evaluating arts projects for health and wellbeing (Daykin *et al.*, 2017). This training included webinars with topics such as evaluating the impact of arts projects on loneliness, research on social prescribing, and peer research. I also learnt about projects by organisations that are part of my field work, such as Paisley Museum's project with care experienced young people. I also learnt about culture, health, and wellbeing work from elsewhere such as the Great Place Greater Manchester Project¹⁰ which commissioned a report, 'A Social Glue' on culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing in Greater Manchester (Parkinson, 2021). I listened to practitioners in the cultural sector and the third sector talk about evaluation and culture and grew knowledge of practitioner perspectives and feelings regarding evaluation. I disseminated my learning back to CAHSC, in meetings, through presentations and via emails. The growth in my situational self grew capacity to generate knowledge for my research self.

3.8.4. Conversations – interviews, discussions, and introductions

I undertook 6 semi-structured discussions and interviews. These included one-to-one interviews to understand the contexts and processes that inform the use of culture and the arts in health and

¹⁰ <https://greatplacegm.co.uk/>

wellbeing policy and practice within the town of Paisley. In particular I wanted to understand the history of the development of Future Paisley and understand what culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing means to key organisations in Paisley. Interviews are semi-structured around these broad themes. These interviews are transcribed.

I undertook a discussion with the Renfrewshire Arts Team to share ideas of what we thought health and wellbeing meant in relation to culture and the arts and their practice. I learnt about what projects they were undertaking and how these projects came about.

My research self meant that new hires to roles related to culture, arts, health, and wellbeing as part of their task of getting to know people in Paisley, were directed to me. In our conversations they could hear more about my knowledge of the concepts that informed their role such as social prescribing or loneliness. These conversations sometimes involved my situational self as we shared ideas of evaluation and example projects from elsewhere. These conversations provided opportunities for mutual learning.

Crafting a research self involves giving my knowledge when requested. My conceptual ideas such as assemblages of health, or affective infrastructure, seep into the conversation. For example, when a research participant talked about how they wanted people to feel something when they walked into a place, that the place had its own character, that although the place had meeting rooms and a café, they didn't want it to feel that way and wanted to cultivate a different feeling. This was an appropriate point to talk about atmospheres. I talk about how these feelings contributes to the emergence of atmospheres, which enable people to enter other worlds (Duff, 2016). My research created self aims to help people come to a meaning that has resonance and salience for them, that works for them and enables them to articulate the things they do. My theoretical knowledge of health and wellbeing enables me to notice when people talk about health and wellbeing in terms of my framework. However, people are not always aware that they are talking about health and wellbeing as they consider health and wellbeing in more orthodox ways. This theoretical knowledge is what an action researcher can bring (Burns, 2007). This intersubjectivity contributes to making explicit the tacit knowledge of practitioners that then contributes to growing knowledge for my thesis.

3.8.5. Documents

I used documents to understand the development of Paisley's cultural regeneration approach. These were sourced from Renfrewshire Council Leadership Board meeting documents¹¹. These documents also provided an understanding of what other strategies are in operation in Renfrewshire. Strategic documents for other key organisations such as RHSCP were sourced online. Historical context was found through online documents such as the development of HSCPs, TSIs, consultation of the draft Culture Strategy for Scotland and the development of Public Health Scotland. Following organisations and projects on Twitter provided leads to further documents such as reports for activities undertaken. The groups I am in and the organisations I meet sometimes sent me links to documents including reports of activities they have undertaken.

3.8.6. Growing knowledge through research encounters

In my following of research trails, I have recorded one hundred and five research encounters. These encounters are categorised by type in Table 3.1 and given in full in Appendix 1. These moments are formal in the sense that they have calendar entries, as opposed to informal discussions which do not have a calendar entry. These research encounters are sites for growing knowledge and have shaped my research situated selves. Research encounters cover any activity with a calendar entry where I have gained knowledge that has been brought into the research such as knowledge to develop my evaluation practice or knowledge to understand activities in the Arts and Health sector. Several of these encounters, such as those categorised as interviews, maybe considered as formal data collection sites, in that there is written consent for the encounter to occur and formal research participants. Section 3.9.2 describes further how I my approach of growing knowledge is wider than data collection, due to my ontological and epistemological commitments. Eighty-seven of these encounters are directly connected to Paisley, such as representing Paisley at national meetings or activities in Paisley. The other encounters relate to opportunities to learning from outside the town. Meetings are distinguished from discussions by a greater degree of formality and purpose, discussions usually involve sharing knowledge and getting to know each other. Courses are for developing my research skills in relation to this research, hence the use of the term Continued Professional Development (CPD) to describe the training for the situational self. These research encounters last a minimum of an hour and up to several days for a course. The research encounters

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https://renfrewshire.cmis.uk.com/renfrewshire/CouncilandBoards/tabid/62/ctl/ViewCMIS_CommitteeDetails/mid/381/id/26/Default.aspx

categorised as Discussion/Interview indicates a discussion, that was recorded and transcribed. As interviews were also recorded and transcribed, I have categorised these two types of discussions together. In 2019, twenty-seven encounters were recorded, 2020 had thirty, 2021 had forty-five, and 2022 had three research encounters.

Table 3.1: Formal encounters of growing knowledge by type

Type	Number
Discussion	9
Discussion/Interview	6
Conference/Summit/Symposium	6
Course	6
CPD	2
Delivering training	1
Event	3
Field trip	1
Group discussion	1
Group interview	1
Meeting	56
Meeting/Presentation	3
Webinar	5
Workshop	4
Workshop/Presentation	1
Total research encounters	105

These encounters are presented discretely in the table. However, in keeping with my methodology (Section 3.9.2), I do not view these encounters as discrete events that are brought together in

analysis. These encounters accumulate, knowledge is rolled forward into the next encounter, shifting as the theoretical knowledge embedded within these encounters grows.

In Appendix 2, I have provided the approximate number of attendees for the research encounters where I am an invited member of a group or network. I also provide the approximate number of invited members in the group and their organisation and role.

3.9. Processes for making meaning and actions with data and knowledge

3.9.1. Introduction

Qualitative research is usually defined as understanding the meanings people have constructed and their ways of making sense of the world (Merriam, 2009; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). The development of my ontological and epistemological commitments and my active research orientation (Section 3.5) means that like other researchers with this stance, my research does not easily fit with how qualitative research is usually described (St. Pierre, 2021). The development of my research proposal (Section 3.3) and my research sensibilities (Section 3.6) leads me to seek change as well as knowledge. My research principles of doing and dynamism does not ontologically fit with the research stages of data collection feeding into stages of data analysis (Creswell, 2012; Braun and Clarke, 2013). In particular, my principle to resist reductionism does not fit well with classic qualitative approaches of data condensation (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014). My process for making meaning involves asking what work can concepts such as loneliness and evaluation be put to in order to shift paradigms and create a health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley. I am interested in the future health and wellbeing possibilities of my research puzzle. My research takes on a non-representational hue as I grow closer to Vannini's (2015, p. 12) description of a non-representational orientation style as a change of interest from representing what happened, to 'what is happening now and what can happen next' by being concerned with 'reverberations with people' and inspiring social change.

This section brings together the topics in this chapter to describe my meaning-making processes. These processes transform knowledge into insights into the research questions, which in turn inform the proposal and puzzle. These processes resist reductionism through being open and ongoing. These processes are not linear discreet stages, they are ongoing and constitute each other.

3.9.2. Growing knowledge

Data analysis can be considered as a transformation of data which are thought of as observations that range from the purely descriptive to incorporating theory (Wolcott, 1994). My proposal of

action and resistance means my observations are infused with theory. I use the term knowledge rather than observations to indicate this move away from descriptive notes. In addition, the term knowledge fits more closely with my action research sensibilities of learning from experts by practice and experience. I use the term growing knowledge to describe the dynamic nature of this knowledge. Growing knowledge (Section 3.8.6) is my term to move from the implied discreteness of the term data and the machine-like implications of applying methods for data collection and analysis. Growing knowledge follows the use of the data and keeps me grounded in what matters to people. Therefore, transformation of knowledge is a continuous and intrinsic process in my research. This process is inherently reflective and reflexive due to the nature of my research proposal and my focus on counter-conceptualisation.

Following the growth of knowledge from one research encounter can show its dynamic nature. I attend a webinar (Appendix 1: 18th February 2021) and learn about conceptual ideas of being together that I believe are relevant to CAHSC. I reflect on these new ideas and co-read through my notes of the webinar with academic literature about conviviality and social infrastructure (Bredewold et al., 2020; Layton and Latham, 2021; Blokland and Jackson, 2022). The knowledge from the webinar has shifted in shape due to the addition of theoretical ideas from co-reading. I bring this knowledge to another research encounter, the next CAHSC meeting (Appendix 1: 24th February 2021). I make notes in the moment that captures the new shape of the knowledge as people respond to the knowledge. Further shaping occurs through writing, as I email CAHSC my reflections. The knowledge is then put to work, helping me attune to everyday moments of connection in my daily life (Section 7.5), assisting me in living the concept of atmospheres (Section 4.4.4), and think through loneliness as an everyday experience (Section 7.5). The knowledge is put into the thesis, grows through being entangled with other knowledge in writing. Growth in knowledge happens through editing as the knowledge moves around the thesis and is brought into conversation with other knowledges and perspectives for example weaving together atmospheres and affective infrastructure (Section 8.3.3)

Appendix 3 provides a further example of growing knowledge that shows my process of reflection. My emerging conceptual thoughts are put to work during my volunteering as an exhibition planner. I write my reflections about this experience in a CCSE website article that I send to the exhibition planning group. This is an ethical practice of transparency, to let them know that my research self publicly draws on my exhibition experiences. I write a reflective note on the feedback that my article resonates with socially engaged art practitioners, that I have articulated their practice in a way they have tried to but not found the words for and I have made concepts that are new to them meaningful and relevant to their art practice. This feedback prompts reflection and encourages me

to explore these concepts further. The knowledge grows outside my research, as these practitioners send my article to others including a public health practitioner they are working with.

Mason (2018) has a helpful language to illustrate my process of growing knowledge. She termed researchers who are 'living with' data as having an affinity. It is more than being familiar with data, it is the cultivation of a close everyday interpretative relationship with data. Mason's language of a 'continuous intimate iteration' of knowledge to build flashes of insight has helped articulate my relationship to knowledge growing. As described by Mason (2018, p. 246) I think with, feel with, and have ideas with my knowledge and therefore create knowledge that has potency. To cut growing knowledge into discrete data, i.e., webinar notes, meeting notes, emails, blunts the dynamic nature of knowledge transformation in my research. This process of transformation is not through the application of tools, instead transformation has occurred through knowledge being put to work, its interactions with other knowledge and its open-ended nature. I find alignment with other researchers with similar ontological and epistemological commitments:

'Data typically are considered to be inert, lifeless, and disorganized. They wait to be "collected," "processed," and vivified—awakened to meaning through the ministrations of researchers and their specialist, methodic procedures.'

(Koro-Ljungberg, MacLure and Ulmer, 2018, p. 806)

These researchers consider data as active and lively as 'data promote change, advocate, and increase awareness' (ibid, p. 813). This character of data doing and being on the move has kinship with other sense making approaches to data (Jackson and Mazzei, 2018). A process of growing knowledge with these characteristics assists me to keep my ontological commitments of not draining my research of life and dynamism (Section 4.2.1). This process is an ethical process as knowledge grows through processes of validity and meaningfulness (Section 3.11.3). My approach of growing knowledge aligns with pragmatic views of action-orientated research where knowledge is constantly adapting to where its located (Hammond, 2013)

3.9.3. Resonance

I use resonance to describe the characteristic of knowledge that evoke responses such as tension or affinities. These responses have to be present across the following dimensions:

- Theory – making an argument for the proposal requires a critical approach to concepts in order to think through what we are doing when we seek to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing purposes.

- Empirical – the research needs to be in discussion with what is happening elsewhere and what has happened before in regards to the interaction between culture, health and wellbeing. This includes lessons from previous projects, situating the research in current practice and the current state of the fields of arts and health and cultural regeneration.
- Paisley context – the research needs to matter to people, projects, practitioners and policy related to culture, health and wellbeing in Paisley.
- Brought selves - I need to live the concepts in order to think with and work with theory (Section 3.6.5). I need to give life to concepts in order to increase the likelihood of resonance with people I share the concepts with. I give life by drawing on my experiences and having an affinity with knowledge (Section 3.8.6) which leads to insight that have greater resonance (Mason, 2018).
- Situationally created self – knowledge grown needs to resonate with my situationally created self, so I can bring knowledge into Paisley and put it to work. This is part of my ethical practice (Section 3.1.3). I create reciprocal relationships with those I meet by giving to the spaces I am invited to. I therefore need to be useful and bring knowledge, expertise and skills to help practitioners develop their projects and activities.
- Policy - The research puzzle is concerned with policy therefore the research needs to be in discussion with the interests of Future Paisley and the wider Scottish policy landscape.

In Chapters 4 to 9, a table is provided that shows how the Chapter resonates with these dimensions (Table 4.1, Table 5.1, Table 6.1, Table 7.1, Table 8.1, Table 9.1). Resonance is a pragmatic approach as the proposal is grounded in what interest, knowledge and practices exist in Paisley and what matters to practitioners of culture, health and wellbeing. For example, sense of belonging is drawn into my research through how I conceptually approach loneliness (Section 4.5.2) through my sensitising concept of atmospheres (Section 4.4.4). Belonging is also a topic that matters to practitioners and people in Paisley through the practice of creating places that people feel they belong. However, belonging did not emerge as a research trail as unlike loneliness, belonging does not have the same prominence as a public health issue (Section 4.5) and as a policy interest at local and national level (Section 6.6 and 7.4). Loneliness through social prescribing (Section 5.9.1) has received more focus from the field of arts and health than belonging. Loneliness resonated throughout all the dimensions (Table 7.1) which led to my choice to use loneliness as a site of investigation for health and wellbeing and as a line of inquiry.

3.9.4. Research trail and line of inquiry

A line of inquiry is formed out of resonance and creates a research trail to guide growth of knowledge. My use of the phrase line of inquiry aligns with Denzin and Lincoln's (2018) suggestion that inquiry implies resistance, open-endedness and uncertainty which are characteristics in keeping with my ontological commitments. These lines of inquiry form Chapters 4 to 9 of the report as described in Section 3.7.2. Some of the key sites for growing knowledge are given in tables in Chapters 6 to 9 of the report and due to their nature, overlap with the emergence of research trails through resonance (Table 6.2, Table 7.2, Table 8.2, Table 9.2).

Lines of inquiry guide research encounters. For example, to follow the research trail of loneliness (Chapter 7), I asked in a CAHSC meeting for suggestions of who could be interested to explore the experience of loneliness and its relationship to health with me. Research trails can be formed after research encounters occur and serve as a guide for seeking insight in knowledge grown. For example, Chapter 9 arose as my intention to immerse into projects did not emerge and I found myself involved in the development of Future Paisley's Step Change 2. I realised I had been growing knowledge about policy rather than projects. This changed my research puzzle and changed the direction of how knowledge is grown.

Appendix 1 presents the research encounters in chronological order in order to show how the research adapts and shifts as it follows Future Paisley in live time. These do not cover all the research encounters that grow knowledge for the lines of inquiry. Living the theory and concepts means everyday encounters such as volunteering, conversations with friends, reading the news, walking the dog became informal research encounters as I brought theory into everyday life.

3.9.5. Check-ins

Check-ins assist in assessing the validity of my developing insights. There are four common forms of validity (construct, internal, external, ecological) highlighted by Braun and Clarke (2013). They argue ecological validity is most relevant to qualitative research. Ecological validity is described as how closely the data is to the real world and the applicability of the results to the real world. All the processes described so far in this section keep the research both embedded and applicable to the real world and check-ins are a further process to ensure the knowledge grown is meaningful in the real world. Check-ins occur in some research encounters (Appendix 1) and in reading academic and grey literature. Check-ins provide opportunities to test meaningfulness. They are sites of reflectiveness and reflexivity where I can seek answers to questions such as does my knowledge

matter? Are my concepts useful? Do they have kin with experiential knowledge? Topics of check-ins include:

- Check-in with new developments in relevant fields such as loneliness, arts and health, community-centred health. These check-ins provide an opportunity to consider if there is work being undertaken that is addressing the issues I am identifying. These spaces grow my knowledge regarding what is considered good practice in the sector and where the focus of activities resides. This knowledge situates my work with what is going on in the real world. Reflecting on moments of alignment and moments of tension between my research and what is going on assists my reflexive practice.
- Check-in with practice of evaluation. These check-ins assist my situated self to be up-to date with current practice and provide useful and relevant information to practitioners in Paisley. I create spaces to critically consider the practice of evaluation by exploring topics such as what practitioners are asked to demonstrate in evaluations, what they would like to ideally demonstrate, how evaluation can be a way of communicating their ideas relating to what should be valued to policy. Check-ins are pragmatic as in this space I find out practitioner's resources and capacity for evaluation, therefore my insights are rooted in what is achievable for practitioners in their everyday practice.
- Check-in with empirical accounts of lived experience. These check-ins are a way to ensure that the growth of my knowledge draws in the multiplicity and nuance of how people are experiencing my research interests such as sense of loneliness, connection and culture and arts.
- Check-in with what is going on elsewhere regarding using culture and the arts for health and wellbeing ends. Keeping up with the latest activities enables me to situate Future Paisley and Paisley within current and future developments in policies that use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing ends. Check-ins grow knowledge through asking questions such as are there unique features of Paisley's cultural regeneration approach in addressing health and wellbeing and is Paisley meeting its aim to be a leader in town regeneration (Future Paisley, no date). These check-ins enable learning of what characteristics of Paisley's approach is similar and what is different from other areas. This learning helps the growth of useful knowledge as passing on this knowledge to practitioners and policy makers in Paisley helps them to situate and develop their work.

Knowledge is also grown from multiple check-ins that I cannot weave into the text. People in my everyday life, who infuse into my brought self such as personal acquaintances who work in my areas of research outside Paisley. People who I ask questions that are outside the scope of culture, arts,

health and wellbeing, whose answers frame culture and arts in the wider setting of non-clinical health and wellbeing interventions. Section 3.11.3 further describes how check-ins are a practice of ethics.

3.9.6. Insights

Establishing the meaningfulness of my explorations on the research trails through check-ins, prompts me to grow knowledge into insights that illuminate my research questions and dimensions of my research proposal and puzzle. Therefore my insights are in line with Mason's (2018, p. 104) ethical process of honouring commitments to participants, yourself and to qualitative research by framing insights 'in such a way that they feed into or are resonant with wider sets of issues of question, or help initiate debates about issues and questions which are worthwhile.' These insights maybe about future possibilities. This process is described in Section 3.11 as an ethical process. Insights are gathered in the conclusion of Chapters 4 to 9 and in Chapter 10.

3.9.7. Layering

The ordering of Chapters 4 to 9 is a process of layering knowledge and described in Section 3.7.2. Section 3.9.4 show the dynamic nature of the chapters as they include knowledge grown from a line of inquiry and also shape the knowledge to be taken into other Chapters, for example Chapters 4 and 5 could be considered the theoretical rucksack to be carried on the research trails of Chapters 6 to 9. The process of layering uses the research orientation of bricolage (Section 3.5) to consider how to develop the most useful and illustrative argument for the proposal and puzzle from the insights grown. Layering is a process that aligns with facet methodology (Section 3.5) and is pragmatic as it considers how can obtain the most illumination into the research proposal and puzzle with the knowledge I have as it is not possible to obtain a complete picture.

3.9.8. Propositions

My research finds kinship with Mason's (2018) view that qualitative researchers should focus on the making of argument. A view that has particular resonance in the field of culture and the arts for social purposes (Belfiore, 2021). Mason (2018) describes different ways of arguing, two of which align with my approach, arguing as an engagement with theory and arguing reflexively or with multiple voices. The insights provide the knowledge to develop actions to address the research proposal. These actions are framed as propositions (Chapter 10) and generate further insights to the research questions. Propositions are actions of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing (Section 1.6) which is work that is central to my making meaning process.

3.9.9. Limitations

My research is built around a the puzzle, of the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme, and a proposal for a change in how we think about health and wellbeing.

My use of facet methodology acknowledges the limitations of my research, that I cannot view all of my research puzzle. My insights are focused on viewing the research puzzle and may not apply to cultural regeneration programmes outside Paisley. For example, the insight regarding the role of HSCP and TSI may not apply outside Scotland as these organisations are Scotland specific and there may not be similar organisations outside of Scotland. Within Scotland, HSCPs and TSIs vary between local authorities such as in their organisational and strategic capacity. Some insights of a conceptual nature may have application to other cultural generation programmes such as the insight that a more expansive definition of loneliness should be used in policy. Other conceptual insights depend on local context. In Section 8.8 I describe the limits of my counter-conceptualisation work, by describing my gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts as an offering based on what I have observed in Paisley. This offering may not be appropriate to other areas as they may not resonate or there are other concepts in use which resonate more. My propositions are based on not creating or amending a model, therefore there are not limitations on the applicability of the model. My research is an argument about adding to any model that seeks to understand the interaction of culture, the arts, health and wellbeing. These additions are the work of counter-conceptualisation. As my research is an argument and an action, rather than findings, the limiting consideration relates to the desire and capacity to undertake the work of counter-conceptualisation, a work that I have acknowledged as needed but difficult to make happen (Section 1.5).

The limits of my work are operational. I have developed a proposal (Section 1.5), contributed propositions (Section 10.2) and provided gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts to do the work of counter-conceptualisation (Section 4.3.6, 4.4.3 and 4.4.4) to attune to and articulate the work of relational health. However, these contributions have not been developed into a process of evaluation for culture, the arts, health and wellbeing. Therefore there are limitations to the usefulness of my work. These limitations and the research that could address them are discussed in Sections 10.9 and 10.10.

3.10. Weaving knowledge into insights to answer research questions

My process of weaving the knowledge grown into insights is given below and structured by my research questions.

What should the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health be?

What concepts could help articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health?

These two questions are intimately linked. I start to grow knowledge of what the characteristics should be from my argument in the previous chapter. I explore academic literature looking for concepts that can act as a gateway to thinking about health and society in a way that contributes to a shift in thinking. These gateway concepts serve as starting points to construct my proposal for the fifth wave of public health. These concepts are broad and open to be helpful to a wide range of academic fields and sectors across society. Gateway concepts are chosen, as thinking with them can lead to other concepts that are more context specific. Therefore, these concepts need to resonate with people's experiences and practice of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing. I grow knowledge through seeking sensitizing concepts. I argue in the previous chapter that attention to everyday moments is needed to understand how lives are transformed. I aim to create a toolkit of sensitizing concepts that I can use to articulate the textures of everyday life. I grow knowledge by paying attention to people's experiences through assessing academic literature and observing people. In Chapter 4, I grow knowledge by evaluating academic literature that considers critical approaches to conceptualise health and wellbeing. This chapter develops my proposal for the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health and sets out my gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts. Chapters 6, 7, 8, and 9 build knowledge through synthesising concepts with observations relating to how people think about health and wellbeing. Chapter 7 brings to the thesis experiential knowledge of health and wellbeing. Chapter 8 uses the conceptual toolkit built in Chapter 4, to articulate the experience of health and wellbeing and the work undertaken to facilitate health and wellbeing. This experience is brought into conversation with policy and projects that aim to improve health and wellbeing. This discussion will contribute to the evaluation process of policy and projects' contribution to the fifth wave of public health.

How might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to shift thinking on health and wellbeing?

My initial site for growing knowledge to answer this question is analysing literature related to the social impact of culture and arts-related activity. This analysis is presented in Chapter 5. The knowledge from Chapter 5 will help me explore in Chapter 6 what kind of culture emerges from my research journey of finding out where and how culture, arts, health, and wellbeing interact in Paisley. I follow how organisations and programs facilitate these interactions. This exploration will build knowledge of what is meant by culture in the context of health and wellbeing in Paisley. This knowledge about culture in Paisley is taken into Chapter 7 where the context of health and

wellbeing is examined through investigating loneliness as a public health issue. This investigation considers loneliness through the knowledge grown about culture in Paisley and interacts with knowledge from other investigations of loneliness. These investigations consider loneliness from the perspective of policy, lived experience and the idea of relational health. Together, the knowledge grown leads to an exploration of what kind of culture and arts-related activity may be mobilised by these perspectives and whether these activities contribute to a shift in thinking about health and wellbeing.

In Chapter 8, I examine how culture and arts-related activity is mobilised to improve health and wellbeing and whether this mobilisation contributes to a shift in how we think about health and society. Chapters 8 and 9 grows knowledge of how culture, health, and wellbeing emerge and is facilitated by practice and organisations through the place-related concepts examined in Chapter 5.

In Chapter 9, I assess this research question through a policy lens by assessing the case for using culture in the design and delivery of policy to achieve social goals. The chapter explores the case for using culture for health and wellbeing goals by developing the analysis in Chapter 5 and drawing on insights I have made about Future Paisley. This chapter builds on the previous chapters by examining the findings through a policy lens. I will explore the role envisaged by Future Paisley of culture and the arts in contributing to social change. I examine how this case for culture takes shape and the possibilities for health and wellbeing that this case creates.

How does a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends grow a health and wellbeing dimension?

I draw on the findings and discussions from the research questions discussed so far to investigate how components of Future Paisley come together to form a health and wellbeing dimension. This investigation is presented in Chapter 9 where I follow the research trail of how and why policy emerges and form. I examine the processes of how culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing align in Future Paisley, the work to create and hold alignment and the conditions for alignment. The chapter considers the future movements for alignment and what this means for the potential for Future Paisley to shift ideas of health and society.

3.11. Ethics

3.11.1. Introduction

My research practice aligns with Mason's (2018, p. 85) argument that 'ethical decision-making is an ongoing and relational activity that takes place in the context of the situated practice of the

research.’ My ethics approach views ethics as a continuous process, deeply embedded in my everyday thinking and doing of research. My ethical practice encompasses my ontological and epistemological commitments, research aims, questions, orientation and sensibilities.

This section outlines my ethics process by firstly stating how I adhere to professional ethical standards. Then I go on to illustrate how my research practice is an ongoing and relational activity that demonstrates situated ethical judgment.

3.11.2. Standards and professional expertise

I have professional expertise from my brought self as a consultant and my situational self as an expert in evaluation processes. I continue to develop my situational self through training during my research. To meet professional standards as a social science researcher I have followed the following principles set up by the Economic and Social Research Council¹² which provides a framework for research ethics and sets out good practice for social science research.

Research should aim to maximise benefit for individuals and society and minimise risk and harm

Bryman (2012, p. 135) describes several facets of harm: physical harm; harm to participants’ development’ loss of self-esteem; stress; and ‘inducing subjects to perform reprehensible acts’. My research approach and design do not have the scope to cause this harm. Information of a personal and sensitive nature is not shared in my research encounters. The information shared is not of the type that will cause distress or trauma. Deception is not part of my research. Harm would only come from my unprofessional behaviour in research encounters which has not occurred in this research. This is demonstrated by my continuous engagement with practitioners, groups and organisations in Paisley in Appendix 1. My approach to maximising benefit for individuals and society is outlined in Section 3.11.3 regarding the validity of my action-informed research.

The rights and dignity of individuals and groups should be respected

I adhere to this principle through my ongoing situational and relational practice of research which is described in Section 3.11.3. The conversations I have with people are not of a sensitive or personal nature. Those who I meet in my research encounters in Appendix 1 and in informal research

¹² <https://www.ukri.org/councils/esrc/guidance-for-applicants/research-ethics-guidance/framework-for-research-ethics/our-core-principles/>

encounters in my everyday life are kept anonymous and confidential in my conversations and written thesis.

Wherever possible, participation should be voluntary and appropriately informed

Ethical approval was sought and gained from the University of the West of Scotland Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee for interviews and two action-informed projects to create a space for the projects to gain new knowledge about how health and wellbeing is conceptualised and evidenced. The two projects did not occur. For the interviews, I asked research participants to read a participant information sheet, ask questions about the research, then sign a participant consent form where they agree the interviews will be recorded and transcribed. I provided them with a topic guide before the meeting. I appropriately informed people I meet in my research encounters by always presenting my research self including my interest in Future Paisley and if relevant my situational self such as in introductions to meetings, training and webinar. In spaces where I have been invited to, in my introduction I always state my purpose for being in the meeting, what I hope to learn by being in their space and if relevant what I seek to contribute to the space.

Research should be conducted with integrity and transparency

In research encounters related to Paisley as a case, I am invited into events, groups and meetings through my external supervisors, my membership of various groups, and through my relationship building activities. The aim of my research to understand how culture and the arts impact health and wellbeing is always communicated to those I meet in Paisley. In addition, through my process of check-ins (Section 3.9.5) and my dissemination of my relevant parts of research either directly or through CCSE, people I encounter are aware of my research aims and are able to check the honesty of how I present myself and my research and the progress of my research.

Lines of responsibility and accountability should be clearly defined

My participant information form provides a Data Protection Privacy Notice and states that the data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland. My transparency in communicating that I am a member of CCSE and the University and that my research is affiliated to Future Paisley makes clear who I am accountable and responsible to.

Independence of research should be maintained and where conflicts of interest cannot be avoided they should be made explicit

My research self is a member of CCSE undertaking research for Future Paisley. My independence to pursue my research is demonstrated by the critical perspectives I bring to my research through

seeking to resist the dominant paradigms of individualism, human exceptionalism and reductionism which was not stated in the scope of the research brief. My independence means there is no conflict of interest between my research interests, my researcher funder interests, the interests of individuals and organisations that I meet in my research encounters. I have frequent research encounters and check-ins with CCSE and Renfrewshire Council through which they are aware of the emerging direction of my research. I am under no pressure to be an advocate for the art and produce positive benefits and impacts for Future Paisley. Advocacy for arts and culture is a critique of research undertaken in the area of culture, arts, health and wellbeing (Belfiore, 2021; Jancovich and Stevenson, 2021). In my research encounters in Paisley, I position myself as a critical friend to Future Paisley stakeholders and to practitioners (Section.3.11.3). In doing so I offer a space to be reflexive about health and wellbeing and evaluation.

3.11.3. Situational and relational ethics

In this section I detail key ethical processes that are part of my research practice. I frame this section using Mason's (2018, p. 86) argument that researchers have an 'ethical responsibility to produce good research which is valid and meaningful, following sound epistemological principles.'

Process of validity

My research has the research sensibility (Section 3.6.2) of being action research informed. I follow McTaggart's (1998) extension of research validity in action research as beyond knowledge claims and should also be concerned with social change. McTaggart (1998, p. 233) suggests that research should have 'comprehensive attention to changing practice and the conditions and understandings which frame it'. My research is concerned about social change through presenting a proposal as the purpose of my research. My propositions in Chapter 10 are about the conditions and understandings which frame health and wellbeing. I also use the findings of my research to make policy recommendations to Future Paisley that seek to change evaluation practice.¹³

Action informed research means a commitment to action, change and usefulness. My processes for making meaning (Section 3.9) describes how I bring conceptual ideas, knowledge of good practice and other projects to individuals and organisations I meet in my research encounters. My credibility in Paisley and the trust that results from my relational practice is demonstrated by new hires in Paisley being introduced to me and encouraged to schedule a conversation with me as part of their

¹³ To be published on CCSE website <http://ccse.uws.ac.uk/>

induction. These ways of working are described by McTaggart (1998, p. 223) as ways to establish research validity.

‘Establishing credibility among participants and informants: This refers to the ways in which participants are useful and helpful to each other. The ways in which this is accomplished are diverse, and may include the professional researcher in providing information - theoretical perspectives, conceptual resources or knowledge of other relevant cases.’

The action informed nature of my research is inherently pragmatic as it seeks to usefully change what exists and is therefore rooted in policy and practice and what is achievable. It recognises the difficulty of paradigm change and seeks pragmatic change by seeking out where points of resistance are possible. These points are built on what is already happening or taking place. The framing of my research around gatherings and happenings (Section 6.3, 9.3 and 9.5) means I focus on what gets drawn into policy from what already exists and what is already threaded through FP. My process of growing knowledge (Section 3.9.2) continuously contributes actionable recommendations.

The development of my research as an argument (Section 1.5) rather than as an advocate for the arts, creates this reflexive space. In doing so I address the issues highlighted by Jancovich and Stevenson (2021) in the cultural sector of a lack of honesty and critical reflection, and so my research facilitates a process of validity rather than performative evaluation.

Process of meaningfulness

Meaning-making is an important part of my methodology (Section 3.6). My research process of growing knowledge is a process that is inherently meaningful (Section 3.9). I draw together various aspects of my meaning-making process to highlight the ethical nature of the process in the following paragraphs.

Research self (Section 3.6.5): Meaningful research is inbuilt into my thesis which was set up to contribute to the evaluation of Future Paisley and therefore to be of use and relevance. The work of being useful and relevant is built in by check-ins with CCSE steering group, attendance at specific Future Paisley meetings and writing articles for the CCSE website that provide updates of my research.

Situational self (Section 3.6.5): Ethics is ingrained in my development of a situational self. This self means that I required to provide meaningful and useful and honour my commitment to action. I create a situational self as someone who brings conceptual knowledge of health and wellbeing and loneliness and practice knowledge of evaluation and participatory practices of research and evaluation. I develop my situational self through research encounters to improve my knowledge and

skills in these areas such as through webinars by professional organisations and training courses. These serve to ensure I am up to date with current practice and knowledge. They also serve as check-ins to my development of a critical approach to evaluation and policy approaches to loneliness. These check-ins give the opportunity to ask myself does my critical viewpoint matter to people doing this work.

Resonance (Section 3.9.3): my process of ensuring resonance across different perspectives means that it is grounded in practice, policy, activities and knowledge that exists in Paisley. Resonance ensures that the knowledge I grow makes a contribution across all these perspectives from the theoretical and conceptual to policy and practice of culture, arts, health and wellbeing.

Research trails (3.9.4): the knowledge I grow is made useful and meaningful as I follow lines of inquiry through disseminating knowledge and creating reflexive spaces for practitioners to consider the concepts and practices which are part of their roles such as health, loneliness and evaluation. My check-ins to test my approach to conceptualising health and wellbeing align with McTaggart's (1998) processes of validity 'testing the coherence of arguments'. As these check-ins could be described as creating McTaggart's (1998) 'critical community' or a community of 'critical friends'. The check-ins provide opportunities to test is there still a need for my research, given the constant developments in projects and policy in Paisley, Scotland and in the field of arts and health. The check-ins provide a space to test if my research concerns matter. The mattering of my research concerns is shown by the follow up invitations I receive, for example my presentation to Paisley Museum (Appendix 1 July 17th 2020) leads to further conversations (Appendix 1 September 23rd 2020) and invitations to join workstreams (Section 3.8.2). My discussion with Renfrewshire Arts Team (Appendix 1 November 17th 2021) leads to a research encounter where I am asked about evaluation (Appendix 1 March 24th 2022).

Epistemological principles (Section 3.6): I have a commitment to multivocality. An example is Chapter 4 identifies the need for drawing on lived experience for policy and practice. When it was not possible to work in a participatory way with those who are experiencing of culture, arts, health and wellbeing my bricolage sensibilities sought lived experience perspectives from a range of sources. I drew on academic literature, grey literature, my situated and brought self, and through autobiographical moments. I argue that these ways of knowing are required to achieve my research proposal. This commitment requires a practice of listening in order to valuing a multiplicity of voices, knowledge, experiences. Listening requires me to consider whose space am I in? What is this space is for? How do I not disrupt the purpose of this space? For example, using some of the invitations described in Section 3.8.2:

- The Paisley Museum workstreams are an invite for me to know what is going on in the museum. I am there to observe how health and wellbeing arise in discussions. The space is for museum staff to develop projects. I am not a museum professional, therefore I mainly listen and consider discussions through my conceptual lenses in order to grow knowledge to situate myself in future as a critical friend to the Museum regarding health and wellbeing concepts.
- RHSCP SPG Connectedness Network invite me to share my conceptual knowledge of loneliness and social isolation and my knowledge of activities from elsewhere. The space is for third sector organisations to develop activity to address loneliness, therefore my knowledge is helpful for the group to think through what they are addressing when they are addressing loneliness and I situate myself as a critical friend to the Network.
- Recovery Hub – this space is a co-production space for users of the future Hub to design aspects of the Hub together with peer worker and staff members. I am invited to develop an understanding of how the Hub operates in order for a research activity to be designed. This space is therefore not for me to participate. It would be inappropriate for me to make suggestions regarding which logo I preferred or what the Hub’s name should be. I situate myself quietly and unobtrusively.

3.12. Conclusions

In this chapter I describe my processes for making meaning and actions and how these are also ethical processes. I have provided the ontology and epistemological processes that form my methodology and methods. I situate the methodological process of growing knowledge in terms of what I bring to the research, the identity work I undergo, and the research orientation and sensibilities which I use to encounter and grow knowledge. I detail in this chapter the methods I use to grow knowledge from my research encounters and the ethics that shape these encounters.

My view of the research object using Mason’s (2018) typology of intellectual puzzle as a processual and ecological puzzle determines the nature of the argument I make in this research. I demonstrate in this chapter how processual and ecological arguments are built from an approach that is characterised by abductive reasoning, living with the knowledge grown, ‘continuous intimate iteration’ of knowledge and bringing life to concepts.

Together these research trails will lead to my research aim to investigate how place-based policies designed to utilise culture and the arts for social ends might shift thinking on health and wellbeing by observing developments in policy and activity in Paisley.

4. A proposal for the fifth wave of public health

4.1. Introduction

In this chapter I develop my proposal for the fifth wave of public health and continue the work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing.

I present the theories that I draw from to develop my rationale for the use of relational thinking to shift ideas of health and society. I then further develop my focus on everyday health and wellbeing by conceptually examining place as a site where everyday health and wellbeing processes are formed.

I use the lens of place to develop my focus on the interaction between the everyday, health, wellbeing, and relationships. I draw on place-based concepts to use as gateway concepts to bring people into, and think with, the idea of relational health. Place-based concepts are also used as sensitizing concepts to help people attune to the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health. Gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts are part of my proposal for the fifth wave of public health. I suggest that these concepts could contribute to the development of language to articulate the contribution of non-healthcare sectors to public health, in particular to relational health.

I evolve the term 'existential feelings' as a conceptual tool to examine how health and wellbeing emerges from the relationship between individuals and the environment. I use loneliness as a public health issue as a site to continue the counter-conceptualisation work required for developing my proposal of the fifth wave of public health. The work involves examining tensions in ways of knowing by exploring the relationship between policy approaches to loneliness and the experience of loneliness.

Finally in this chapter I explore who does the work of relational health.

4.2. Resonance and research trails

Section 3.9.3 describes the process of resonance which forms the research trail I explore in this chapter. Table 4.1 provides the key sources of resonance in each dimension. The academic literature in this table are texts that are continuously read and serve as check-ins for the development of my ontological and epistemological perspectives. My conceptual exploration of health and wellbeing grew increasingly critical and cohered into the emergence of a research focus on developing an argument. This coherence was catalysed by the change in focus from specific

projects to a focus on paradigm change and the growth in the academic field of arts and health in Summer 2021.

Table 4.1: Resonance dimensions for a proposal for a fifth wave of public health

Theory	Duff (2012, 2016), Kearns (2014), Elton (2021) Hanlon et al. (2011), Ratcliff (2005), Atkinson (2020)
Empirical	Antiss et. al (2018), Kelly and Russo (2018), Cropper et al. (2007), Garven et. al. (2016), Jackson (2020)
Paisley context	Future Paisley, CAHSC, Paisley Museum
Brought selves	Health and wellbeing volunteer, impact and evaluation professional
Situationally created self	Critical friend regarding concepts of health and wellbeing
Policy	Christie Commission (2011), A Connected Scotland (2018a)
Emergence of research trail	Summer 2021

4.3. Shifting ideas of health and society

4.3.1. Relational thinking

My path to relational thinking, one that emerges through the search to understand complex multi-faceted phenomena and resist linear approaches is a well-worn path (Strom, 2018). Interest in researching phenomena constituted from complex relationships has led to a rise in the popularity of theoretical orientations that focus on relationality, such as assemblages (Rose and Wilson, 2019). Relational thinking is concerned with connections between things. Relational thinking can be thought of as focusing on the between (Atkinson, 2013). Humans are one of the many things that can form relationships. Humans are therefore not exceptional, countering individualistic notions of human primacy. As human exceptionalism has been cited at the root of many of societal issues (Vallee, 2022), I find relational thinking important as a counter to this, as it offers a way of thinking about collectives.

I need a theoretical guide to think relationally. I find there are many relational ontologies (Zielke, 2022) which have a long history of countering orthodox thinking, for example by shifting from

human exceptionalism to collectives (McLeod, 2014). Examples of relational ontologies include non-representational theory (Andrews, Chen and Myers, 2014), new materialism (Fox, 2011) and actor network theory (Müller, 2015). I find resonance in Dewsbury et al.'s (2002, p. 437) proposal for non-representational theory with the term 'curious vampirism' to highlight how the search for the measurable through over-simplistic causal narrative models and mechanisms produce an account of the world that is drained of dynamism and character, that they suggest is ontologically frozen. The idea of assemblages appears in many of these approaches and emerges from people's differing encounters with the term (McFarlane and Anderson, 2011).

4.3.2. Assemblage thinking

Assemblage thinking is a type of relational thinking that is concerned with both wholes and parts (McFarlane and Anderson, 2011). Wholes are more than the sum of parts (Briassoulis, 2019) due to relationships between entities. Assemblage thinking is concerned with compositions of the whole and what holds the whole together (Anderson *et al.*, 2012). Thinking with assemblages gives me a framework for viewing wellbeing as a process and a relational community endeavour (Atkinson *et al.*, 2019). Assemblage thinking takes a less linear approach to cause and effect. It is interested in the 'active processes of formation' (McFarlane and Anderson, 2011, p. 173), through which phenomena such as health and wellbeing may become constituted.

Assemblages are groups of things, ranging from people, objects to events that enter in relationship to each other. The concept derives from Deleuze and Guattari (1987) and can be used as a critique, an orientation, a concept, ethos and methodology (McFarlane and Anderson, 2011). Its popularity has led to criticisms that its users have not fully engaged with the work of Deleuze and Guattari (Buchanan, 2017) or detaching, and not using assemblages to their full conceptual potential (Buchanan, 2020). I use this assemblage literature as a guide for viewing everyday health and wellbeing generation in a processual and relational way. Furthermore, Atkinson's (2020) provocation of the toxic effects of the concept of wellbeing, such as the concept making us less satisfied with our life. The overall effect of these toxic effects Atkinson (2020, p. 3) suggests is an 'impoverished understanding of what it is to be human.' Assemblage thinking appears in Atkinson's provocation as a possible tonic to this impoverishment. I decide to take this tonic, to guide me in developing my focus for the fifth wave of public health on becoming human.

I seek to find the language to translate these theoretically dense ideas (Strom, 2018; Lorne *et al.*, 2019) to a general audience, therefore I draw on different traditions of assemblage thinking to find out what ideas resonate. I use the term assemblage thinking to indicate my choice to be informed by a multiplicity of the relational approaches. My research is embedded in a local context and searches

for the potential of a fifth wave of public health to emerge through the interaction of diverse terrains. This search involves probing for the presence of the fifth wave of public health approaches in the case of Paisley through a fluid approach to using assemblage thinking language that allows me to conceptually shift in the moment to find possible resonance. The research seeks a gateway approach to thinking relationally that can introduce people to sensitizing concepts to bridge the familiar to the less familiar and attune to everyday life. For these concepts to be useable, they must find kin with people's practices and understanding. This research uses assemblages as an ethos (McFarlane and Anderson, 2011), to provide the shift in thinking of the nature of health and the social that the fifth wave of public health requires.

4.3.3. Gateway to the everyday

I need concepts to help me attune to everyday moments. I have found assemblage thinking helpful as this approach gives room for considering affects, a concept that is by its nature hard to conceptualise. Affects can be vague, can precede conscious thought, can be intensities, energies, flashes, sensations (Stewart, 2007; Andrews, Chen and Myers, 2014). Affects flow, between things, sweeping things up in a collective intensity (Wetherell, 2012). Affects are a way of seeing how wellbeing arises out of everyday moments (Andrews, Chen and Myers, 2014), the 'fleeting moments of wellbeing-in-the-making that punctuate our lives' (Kearns, 2014, p. 147). Assemblage thinking provides the gateway to foreground feelings and gives conceptual room for emotions and affects to matter. Human geography has explored emotions and affects in order to think through how the world is made and lived in (Anderson and Smith, 2001; Thien, 2005). The conceptual terrain of emotions and of affects lacks consensus due to the conceptual broadness, complexity and elusiveness and the different fields the entanglements emerge in (Pile, 2010; Wetherell, 2012). Unpicking all of these conceptual entanglements and associated implications is beyond the scope of my research, but the method does focus on the stance that feelings matter and draws on associated concepts relating to feelings. For example Mason (2017) finds assemblages a lifeless term, and argues that research needs to attend to sensations and a sensory-kinaesthetic register in order to understand the potency of connections, which when they rise up from encounters and matter, she terms as 'affinities'. They are lived, make us feel kin, illuminate conviviality and so are an important part of everyday life and being well together. I do not fully take up Mason's invitation to think with affinities. However, through the conceptual possibilities provided by assemblage thinking, I leave myself open to ideas such as affinities, to understand the textures and experiences of everyday life. Attuning to everyday life finds the process of being human is often composed with non-human connections. There are a range of theoretical approaches that emphasise the agency of non-humans

both biological and non-biological entities (Andrews and Duff, 2020). Thinking with assemblages requires paying attention to relational and the material (Müller, 2015). This attention requires me to have a posthuman perspective of the world by giving weight to the contribution of non-human entities, both animate and non-animate to the world (Cohn and Lynch, 2017). A posthuman perspective challenges human exceptionalism as our lives are intimately intertwined with non-human entities (Vallee, 2022). Assemblages thus provide a broader approach to what entities people connect to and how individuals feel connected (Ulmer, 2017). This approach shifts the focus of health and wellbeing away from the individual human managing a condition, to health as a process of encounters encompassing human and non-human, creating a web of relationships (Elton, 2021). For example, the COVID-19 pandemic intensified people's connection to indoor plants, relating to them as another living, breathing entity and easing the sense of being alone (Doughty, Hu and Smit, 2022). While humans are not the centre of the world in assemblage thinking, human experience can be. An attunement to the everyday of human experience can help reveal the character of posthuman relations that constitute individuals and the liveliness of life (Ravetz and Gregory, 2018).

In this thesis I use non-human to indicate that I am including biological and non-biological entities. I often use the term 'thing' as this has more informal connotations than entities. The term 'thing' can range from technological objects to meaningful snippets of text. I use the term 'more-than-human' to refer to biological entities.

I suggest the term 'becoming human' to talk about human experience as being human is too static a phrase as it indicates a settled state. The idea of 'becoming human' has resonance with the ideas that Kelly (2017, p. 237) suggests drove the community arts movement, that we 'become people through social interaction'. My non-human viewpoint extends interactions beyond the social to all entities. Using the term 'becoming human' rather than 'being human' signals my view that there is no fixed state of humanness, whether biologically (Gilbert, Sapp and Tauber, 2012) or in all the possible combinations of eco-bio-psycho-social. I use this phrase to be inclusive of all the political and personal processes of humaning. Assemblage thinking embraces this open, dynamic shifting state. I suggest the term 'becoming human' as a focus of the fifth wave of public health. That this wave should bring into focus the everyday practices of becoming human, a becoming constituted from relationships. As one interviewee replied when asked about what we mean when we talk about health and wellbeing, it is a life experience.

4.3.4. The everyday and health

Assemblage thinking offers me a view of how health and wellbeing is experienced in the everyday. Health and wellbeing dynamically emerges from assemblages (Andrews and Duff, 2019). A health and wellbeing assemblage can be thought of as assemblages that make health and wellbeing possible which depends on relational capacity. An assemblage with diminished relational capacity can be thought of as ill health (McLeod, 2017). The everyday opens up health to the diversity of experiences and the diversity of things that can affect health from the fleeting to the historical (Duff, 2016) and more readily leaves in a messy intertwined state that is the nature complex phenomena such as health, wellbeing and life itself. Health assemblages expand on the fourth wave of public health thinking and the social determinants of health by expanding the range of encounters that give rise to a person with a health status (Andrews and Duff, 2019) for example an obese individual arises from encounters such as stigma, media representations and the sizing of material objects. Assemblage thinking asks how, and why affective, social, and material resources generate wellbeing? (Duff, 2011, 2016; Kearns, 2014). This provides a viewpoint to see more of the work of making, maintaining and generating health and wellbeing and the relationships and things involved in this work.

Duff (2014) folds capability theory into assemblages of health. Capability theory emerged from Amartya Sen's pursuit of an answer to why health outcomes diverges amongst questions is a question (Sen, 1999a, 1999b). Sen considered wealth and GDP as an inadequate perspective for development as there should be more concerned with people's lives and income does not explain all of the differences of people's wellbeing. Sen notes that there are many questions that are asked to judge whether a person is doing well. Sen's approach is to take a freedom perspective to identify 'a general approach that concentrates on the capabilities of people to do things – and the freedom to lead lives-that they have reason to value.' (Sen, 1999b, p. 85). Sen finds that this approach could fold in ideas of human wellbeing and by leaving the valuing of doing well to people, does not seek to provide definition of what these capabilities might be, and focuses on processes of choice and the freedom to act, the individual liberty and the resources needed for substantive freedoms. Capability theory's concern with the individual is mitigated by the collective orientation of assemblage thinking. The folding of capability theory into assemblages of health results in a definition of health as the sum effect of the social, affective and material encounters that promote a body to become 'strong', 'reasonable' and 'free'. This approach results in thinking about health and wellbeing issues beyond ideas of individual improvement to build a richness of capacities (Kitching, Fernández and Horgan, 2021). I find a synergy between Duff's definition of health and the SHARP project introduced

in Chapter 2 which I used to argue for the importance of the everyday, as it is through the accumulation of the small moments illustrated that individual and community capacity is expanded.

4.3.5. Relational health

I view health as a process emerging from relationships with non-human things and use the term relational health to term this view (Elton, 2021). I argue this should be the focus of the fifth wave of public health. The focus on relationships and therefore connections and interrelatedness, addresses the core issues that lead Hanlon et al. (2011) to declare a need for a fifth wave of public health. Hanlon et al. (2012) identify four separations which are the result of western society's worldview and which materialise in public health issues, that current ways of thinking are not equipped to deal with. These separations are separation from nature, resulting in ecological crisis; separation from other humans, resulting in damaging forms of individualism; separation from ourselves, resulting in a lack of purpose; and separation from spirit, due to an objectivist conception of our world. Wendell Berry (1994) brings together Illich's argument of iatrogenesis with this idea of separation being the cause of ill health to argue that health is a form of membership and asks: can an individual be healthy in a toxic environment whether at home or in ecosystems? Relational health offers me conceptual room to consider the nature of connections that might counter these separations that impair health.

4.3.6. Gateway concept to relational health – existential feelings

One way to consider the nature of connections is through the following senses which are all linked to health, sense of belonging (Lambert *et al.*, 2013), a sense of coherence (Mittelmark and Bauer, 2017), a sense of purpose (Alimujiang *et al.*, 2019) and a sense of loneliness (Holt-Lunstad *et al.*, 2015; Prohaska *et al.*, 2020). These senses intertwine an individual's internal and external worlds, through the entangling of your view of yourself with how you perceive others and how society views you. These are subjective and intersubjective evaluations of an individual's relationship to the world, that is continuously emerging from the interaction of entities (Yanguas, Pinazo-Henandis and Tarazona-Santabalbina, 2018). They are intimately bound up with each other (Ma *et al.*, 2019). These evaluations shape an individual's orientation to life. When loneliness is experienced, individuals think and act differently and their perception of the social environment changes (Masi *et al.*, 2011). These feelings affect others and one's self through the production of atmospheres and space (Duff, 2016; Jackson, 2020).

I use Ratcliffe's theory of existential feelings to talk about these senses collectively. Existential feelings are feelings of being that forms the sense and practice of becoming human, these feelings inform our togetherness with the world:

'The world can sometimes appear unfamiliar, unreal, distant or close. It can be something that one feels apart from or at one with. One can feel in control of one's situation as a whole or overwhelmed by it. One can feel like a participant in the world or like a detached, estranged observer, staring at objects that do not feel quite 'there'.

(Ratcliffe, 2005, p. 45)

Ratcliffe coined this term arguing that feelings of being are distinct from emotion, although the two terms may overlap. The term is sometimes closer to affect in its unnameable quality (Ratcliffe, 2013) and Ratcliffe's interest in the bodily dimension of existential feelings (Saarinen, 2018) also relates it to the sensory-kinaesthetic register in Mason's (2017) description of affinities. Existential feelings are important to understanding our experience as they 'constitute the affective background of all our experience' (Kreuch, 2019, p. 74). It is beyond the scope of my research to engage fully with Ratcliffe's theory of existential feelings, such as their biological, bodily, and philosophical dimensions and the conceptual relationship with affect and affinities. At the core of the existential feeling definition, is the blurring of emotions and affect into something distinctly relational that dissolves the boundary of an individual's inner state and the outside world and that is about the feeling of becoming human. Existential feelings, conceptually encompasses these 'senses of' feelings that are important to health and wellbeing and my argument for the characterisation of relational health. I suggest the use of existential feelings to collectively talk about this cluster of senses is appropriate and also necessary as these feelings don't emerge in isolation from each other. 'Senses of' can be considered as facets of one's existential feelings.

It is beyond the scope of my research to engage with all the fifth wave of public health issues, however, a fifth wave of public health must have characteristics to enable it to engage with all the public health challenges that the current and previous public health is not equipped to deal with. These challenges can arise from disconnection. Existential feelings are a gateway concept to help with thinking relationally. Existential feelings are an affective and emotional current through the separations that Hanlon et al. (2012) examine. The fifth wave of public health engages with all challenges, including those yet to emerge, by bringing into focus connection and relationships, to the work of making kin with and beyond humans, through love and care. The work of the fifth wave of public health is to dissolve boundaries through connections, to create better conditions for empathy to be where humans and non-humans are in order to close the distance between us and alter the

texture of existential feelings into a collective of feelings more amenable to health and wellbeing. By drawing on non-human perspectives, the fifth wave of public health provides a different way of thinking about health and society. Instead of the discrete social determinants of the fourth wave of public health, states of health and wellbeing, such as depression or addiction emerge from a multitude of human and non-human encounters (McLeod, 2017; Andrews and Duff, 2019).

4.4. Place, relations and the everyday

4.4.1. Place and relations

I use the concept of place to focus on the processes and relationships which generate health and wellbeing. A focus on place provides a lens to ground health in everyday processes, since place is key to the experience of everyday life (Duff, 2011) as there is always a spatial dimension to everyday life, from where we live to the different spaces an individual moves through (Mossabir, Milligan and Froggatt, 2021).

Place has been thought of as a product of relations (Massey, 1999), constituted from practices, trajectories and interrelations made through interactions and is an ongoing production (Massey, 2004). Human geography has an array of approaches to thinking of place as a relational space (Degnen, 2016; Preece, 2020), to the point that a 'relational turn' in human geography is considered to have happened (Jones, 2009; Anderson *et al.*, 2012). Relational thinking draws upon sociology and anthropology to view social practices and processes that construct relational spaces such as practices of belonging (Degnen, 2016; Jackson, 2020).

4.4.2. Place and health

Medical geography moves beyond the fourth wave of public health's description of disease. Relational approaches to place is used by medical geography with approaches to critique the dominance of the medical model (Atkinson *et al.*, 2015). This critical approach moves beyond the fourth wave of public health's focus on describing disease as this does not 'further an understanding of the cultural specificity of embodiment, well-being, or the politics of health' (Atkinson *et al.*, 2015, p. 74).

The development of the concept of therapeutic places explores the interaction between health and geography. This concept was first introduced by Gesler in 1990 (Kearns and Milligan, 2019) which seeks to account for the physical, social and symbolic things that contribute to the healing process in a place (Gesler, 1992; Kearns and Milligan, 2019). Therapeutic places intersect with assemblage

thinking by attending to sensations, more-than-human dimensions and everyday geographies (Cattell *et al.*, 2008; Doughty, Hu and Smit, 2022).

4.4.3. Gateway concept to place and health – enabling places

My search for gateway concepts to bring people into the idea of relational health takes me to Duff's (2011) work, which takes the concept of therapeutic places in a relational direction in order to understand how these places develop (Kearns and Milligan, 2019). Duff's focus on relational processes in his research into the recovery process, which he terms as the process of becoming well as it is always unfinished, has created a range of theoretical developments in thinking about how places create health (Kearns and Milligan, 2019). Duff's (2016) conception of health as a function of social, material and affective encounters leads to thinking about 'health generating places' as providing social, material and affective resources for these encounters to occur. Duff (2011) terms these sites as enabling places. Places are relational: a sense of place is generated by drawing together and creating interactions of social, material, and affective resources (Table 4.2). 'Enabling places' has been used to view activities in spaces that illustrate the everyday work of recovery and how local communities may support this work.

Table 4.2: Resources on enabling places: (Duff, 2011, 2012).

Social: Processes and interactions including the relational and cognitive skills and assets, such as trust and reciprocity which support the creation and maintenance of social networks and social capital.
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Material: Diverse objects, assets and benefits that circulate in and through local economic and social networks, as well as the material affordances that local community settings make possible.

Affective: Physical, material, social and relational experiences of place can give rise to feelings of a place. Affective resources shapes moods and feelings and transform an individual's capacity to act in relation to one's health now and in the future. Examples include hope, belonging and optimism.

Enabling places is a useful gateway concept, as it gives room for thinking about affect. Social infrastructure is a concept on the rise (Middleton and Samanani, 2022) and growing in familiarity to policy makers (Kelsey and Kenny, 2021). The concept is concerned with spaces where people make connections and to be with others (Latham and Layton, 2019). The term has a spectrum of meanings ranging from all the qualities of facilities in a place from social relationships to services to spaces where people make connections and to be with others (Latham and Layton, 2019; Kelsey and Kenny,

2021). As argued earlier without allowing space to concepts related to feelings, social infrastructure alone provides too narrow a view of the world we live in which limits the conceptual space to explore how places become meaningful (Layton and Latham, 2021). Even when feelings are included in the definition of social infrastructure such as trust or pride of place, how these feelings are nurtured and meaningful relationships emerge is less focused on (Kelsey and Kenny, 2021). In addition social infrastructure without a non-human infused orientation leaves the world we live in composed only of other humans (Latham and Layton, 2019). I require concepts that articulate feelings to understand the whole experience of how people feel in places, and how these feelings arise. This understanding can lead to an understanding of how social inclusion arises in everyday encounters such as the concept of convivial encounters. These moments are transient interactions that have atmospheric and affective qualities that may lead to loose and casual sense of connection (Barker *et al.*, 2019; Bredewold *et al.*, 2020). Conviviality is a useful sensitizing concept to attune to the everyday. My use of the conceptual lens of enabling place would view convivial encounters as part of affective resources as well as part of social resources. It is beyond the scope of this research to separate out emotion and affect, my use of the word feelings contains both concepts.

4.4.4. Sensitizing concept - atmospheres

My search for sensitizing concepts to help people attune to the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health takes me to the concept of atmospheres. I utilise atmospheres as a sensitizing concept to attend to everyday moments. Atmospheres help conceptualise how meaning is made in our environment (Duff, 2016). Atmospheres are about what places and events mean, as well as how they are felt. Atmospheres are dynamic and changing configurations that constantly emerge from our everyday world. Understanding atmospheres requires understanding how we constantly encounter and make sense of our surroundings, what we do in them and with whom, and how we ascribe value and meaning to this (Sumartojo and Pink, 2018). Atmospheres are an integral part of how everyday activity is created (Hicks, 2020) and integral to health as 'atmospheres are the shared ground from which subjective states and their attendant feelings and emotions emerge' (Anderson, 2009, p. 78). The concept of atmospheres has been used to hone into how a sense of being well can be facilitated, (Fletcher and Barroso, 2020). Kreuch (2019, p. 81) which draws on the concept of atmospheres to illustrate existential feelings when it takes on a situation-specific quality as an 'atmospheric feeling.' Existential feelings by surfacing in atmospheres that constitute the feelings of others show how we constitute each other's feelings of being in the world and our health. Duff's (2016) research explores how atmospheres are encountered and facilitated in the recovery process to create assemblages of health. Three atmospheres are identified that are conducive to processes of becoming well: atmospheres of sociality, atmospheres of safety, belonging and becoming well,

and atmosphere of hope and belief. Focusing on everyday experiences can provide an attunement into how these atmospheres create spaces of wellbeing through a break in the everyday. An example is provided by Atkinson and Robson's (2012) use of the concept of liminality to examine changes in everyday routines. 'Liminality thus entails an effective separation from the everyday routines and entry into an alternative social encounter in which different rules, different values and different relations apply' (Atkinson and Robson, 2012, p. 1350). Liminality is used in this instance to examine how arts and health practitioners remove schoolchildren from the everyday life of the classroom by creating relational and transitional spaces where transformation can occur, and emotional and social wellbeing gained.

Everyday moments may be mundane, but they can accumulate into atmospheres that facilitate health and wellbeing as the quote below demonstrates through the use of the phrase 'sensorial constellations'.

'What sensorial constellations— such as of the smell of freshly baked muffins, the pleasure of a hot shower, the sounds of breath in a group meditation session, the friendly exchanges between peer staff and guests—make up experiences of mental wellbeing at a peer respite?'

(Fletcher and Barroso, 2020, p. 5).

4.5. Loneliness as fifth wave of public health issue

4.5.1. Loneliness and the fifth wave of public health

Loneliness brings pain through subjective and intersubjective evaluations of the world rather than through direct biological means. Therefore, loneliness situates my research in the tension between the ongoing dominance of biomedical thought and the nature of the phenomenon. Loneliness is suited to exploring the idea of waves of public health and as a site to investigate my proposal for a fifth wave of public health. Loneliness is a challenge that is conceptually suited to relational thinking as loneliness could be considered a relational condition. Weiss (1973, p. 277) suggests loneliness is 'a response to the absence of specific relational provisions.'

Loneliness is also suited for further conceptual exploration as tackling loneliness is a policy concern in the UK. Loneliness is considered a critical public health issue (Frost and Cowie, 2019, Lim, Eres and Vasan, 2020), with national strategies in the UK to tackle the issue (Scottish Government, 2018a). The measures in 2020 to tackle coronavirus, such as physical distancing, have increased focus on the impact of loneliness on health, particularly mental health (Holmes *et al.*, 2020). Loneliness is cited by

advocates of culture and the arts as a challenge facing health and social care that the arts can make a contribution to tackling (APPGAHW, 2017).

4.5.2. Conceptualising loneliness

Loneliness research usually takes the Perlman and Peplau (1981) definition of loneliness as a starting point, referencing a discrepancy between an individual's desired and achieved levels of social relations, a subjective experience and as an unpleasant experience (Dahlberg and McKee, 2014; Cacioppo et al., 2015). Loneliness is usually defined as having two distinct forms identified by Weiss (1973), social loneliness and emotional loneliness (Dahlberg and McKee, 2014; Yanguas, Pinazo-Henandis and Tarazona-Santabalbina, 2018). An additional category is existential loneliness (Mansfield *et al.*, 2019). Social loneliness refers to the 'absence of social connection, the perception of social isolation and dissatisfaction with the quality of relationships' (Mansfield *et al.*, 2019). Emotional loneliness refers to the 'absence or loss of meaningful relationships that meet a deeply felt need to be recognised and 'belong' to someone or to a group such as at work, or in a family' (Mansfield *et al.*, 2019). Existential loneliness is 'less related to the specifics of relationships but is focused upon a more global evaluation of disconnection from others and the wider world.' (Mansfield *et al.*, 2019). These dimensions of loneliness relate to the type of social relationships people have: intimate relationships, relational such as quality friendships and social support and collective relationships from belonging to a group with shared purpose and interests (Hawkey, Browne and Cacioppo, 2005; Cacioppo and Cacioppo, 2012). Emotional loneliness is associated with greater psychological distress and greater prevalence in the population compared to social loneliness. Social loneliness by itself has similar levels of psychological distress as those with low loneliness, and when paired with emotional loneliness exacerbates psychological distress, suggesting quality of connections more important than quantity (Hyland *et al.*, 2019). The different types of loneliness show that loneliness is a complex phenomenon.

The experience is characterised by a lack of meaning in the components of life, work, relationships, connections, place, identity. Loneliness is an evaluation of the world that is intertwined with other evaluations, such as sense of belonging (Parsons, 2020) and sense of purpose (Kang *et al.*, 2021) that are also factors for health and wellbeing.

4.5.3. Medicalisation and socialisation of the concept of loneliness

The usage of the term loneliness influences the focus on social loneliness. Loneliness is often used together with social isolation. Social isolation is an individual's evaluation of the quantity and quality of their social relationships such as the frequency of social contact and whether there was anybody

an individual could turn to for support (Teuton, 2018). The Scottish Government social isolation and loneliness strategy states that it addresses both types of loneliness. However, there is a much stronger focus on social isolation, leading to a focus on making social connections. The strategy states in its strategic vision that 'everyone has the opportunity to develop meaningful relationships regardless of age, stage, circumstances or identity' (Scottish Government, 2018a, p. 8). The focus of this strategy reflects a general finding that there is more of a focus on social loneliness than emotional or existential loneliness (Mansfield *et al.*, 2019). A focus on social loneliness centres the attention of interventions to mitigate loneliness on human relationships. A reductionist linear approach to thinking about how to tackle loneliness views loneliness as a deficit of human relationships. These interventions may not sustainably decrease loneliness (Foster *et al.*, 2020) and are at risk of becoming Illich's unhealth in action. Mobilising the wider public health activities of other sectors, with a medical approach, could spread cultural iatrogenesis beyond healthcare.

The medicalisation of loneliness is also driven by the dominance in loneliness research of disciplines that tend to view the world through a medical model (Courtin and Knapp, 2017), particularly psychology which through surveys and scales results in descriptions of loneliness shaped by measuring and mapping (Phillips *et al.*, 2022). I argue that these fields reinforce the fourth wave of public health approach as these fields focus on individuals and take a deficit-based approach, where interventions are tailored for the root causes of an individual's loneliness (Prohaska *et al.*, 2020). I find that interventions suggested by a medical model viewpoint to health contrasts with research that asks how people felt about loneliness. Discussions about services, community groups or activities that targeted loneliness and social isolation stated they found that people did not want services that were about them (Zubairi, 2018). When asked what support people would like for loneliness, group activities with a shared interest are the most popular type of support, regardless of age group (Kharicha *et al.*, 2017; Co-op Foundation, no date). Health and wellbeing from people's viewpoint reveal a different perspectives on practices of health for example fast food shops are considered unhealthy due to the food, however as places they contribute to young people's practices of being well together (Burningham and Venn, 2022). Viewing health and wellbeing through experiential knowledge suggests non-healthcare organisations and groups and informal places that are part of everyday life play a role in improving health and well-being.

4.5.4. Diversity of knowledge

Hanlon *et al.* (2011) calls for the fifth wave of public health to be more diverse in ways of thinking, in order to explain reality and understand the health issues we face. This chapter supports this by

showing the different understandings of loneliness. A diversity in thinking about health issues has two interrelated parts, the nature of the health issues and how to address the issue.

I have found research about Men's Sheds a useful way of contrasting different approaches to place-based approaches to loneliness. Men's Sheds, due to the global scale of activity, have been the subject of academic research. Men's Sheds are an example of place-based group activities with a shared interest, a source of meaningful activity that contributes to health, however health creation is not the core rationale (Kelly *et al.*, 2019). Men's Sheds are a community-based movement that are 'practical communal spaces, typically workshop areas that provide opportunities for men to take part in meaningful social and recreational activities that encourage skill-sharing and informal learning' (Kelly *et al.*, 2019). Formalising Men's Sheds by incorporating them into the healthcare system would reduce their effectiveness (Kelly *et al.*, 2021) as Men's Sheds emerge from the needs of the local men who create the Sheds (Anstiss, Hodgetts and Stolte, 2018). This suggests the importance of community groups and activities outside healthcare. Therefore, I suggest that academic research into Men's Sheds is a useful site to examine further the contribution of different ways of knowing to developing approaches to tackle loneliness.

How Men's Sheds might contribute to health and wellbeing is often analysed by frameworks and models that seek to show cause and effect. There are various types of frameworks and models that seek to show how an entity may cause an impact on society, such as improved health and wellbeing. Logic modelling is a model used in both evaluation (Daykin and Joss, 2016) and research (Kelly *et al.*, 2019). These models use logic chains to show the steps between an entity's resources and the impact on society (Daykin and Joss, 2016). A logic model showing how Men's Sheds contribute to health and wellbeing illustrates many possible pathways leading to a multitude of long-term outcomes that improve health and wellbeing (Kelly *et al.*, 2019). These long-term outcomes are what I suggest could be considered existential feelings. Cause and effect models are more focused on pathways and mechanisms. There are different definitions of 'mechanisms'. However, they can broadly be defined as entities that generate 'outcome' (Dalkin *et al.*, 2015). Cause and effect models are less focused on illuminating how an individual brings together these aspects of an entity to create health and wellbeing. Meaning-making is often not explored as meaning is a component in these models either as a mechanism (What Works Wellbeing, 2019) or a component of a logic model (Kelly *et al.*, 2019). When entities are placed into a category, they become irreducible. Whether it is part of a logic chain or defined as a mechanism, their purpose of explaining the generation of health and well-being outcomes is served and do not need unpacking. This boxed up approach also does not convey the dynamism and interrelatedness of subjective evaluations of external evaluations. Therefore, cause and effect frameworks are a reductionist and static approach to explaining

phenomena such as health creation. These frameworks, by their nature, are not ontologically or epistemically designed for exploring meaning-making activities and processes of how these subjective evaluations come into being. This example shows Dewsbury et al.'s vampirism in action and the draining of life (2002).

Life is brought back through observing small moments as demonstrated by a study of Men's Shed (Anstiss, Hodgetts and Stolte, 2018) that uses ethnography and lens of social practice, material practice and place. The research views evaluations of the world as a sense of belonging as relational resources cultivated from repeated routines and social practices to become continuous and familiar and create a place. All these elements combine to become a home. The research reveals the small moments that accumulate into the feelings of social inclusion. 'Through opportunities to relax, reflect, reminisce, tell stories, and share jokes with other men, in a space where they feel that they can expect to be treated as equals' (Anstiss, Hodgetts and Stolte, 2018, p. 221). This approach provides an alternative to cause-and-effect models by highlighting things too small and fleeting to appear in a framework or model. These small moments of everyday life are the everyday experiences from which health and place emerge.

4.5.5. Tensions

Lay knowledge and expertise, such as that from the community partners, tend to be less visible as evidence. (Carlisle *et al.*, 2007). Community partners may not see themselves as health creators.

'We're talking about trust and connecting with people, and transforming their options and self esteem. People like {name}, she runs theatre, she doesn't do an asset-based approach... but yet it's demonstrably about discovering assets and abilities unfold. So we should try and find a language that allows people to understand that that's what they're doing'

(Garven, McLean and Pattoni, 2016, p. 27).

It is suggested that health inequalities research should focus on proposals for their reduction, rather than analytically describing the problem.

'The focus of future health inequalities research should shift away from merely analysing the problem (where the risk of reinforcing people's sense of stigma, shame and powerlessness seems greatest), to better understanding potential proposals for their amelioration. One way of achieving this might be to experiment with deliberative democratic forms of

engagement (Blacksher 2013) and/or with participatory practises specifically intended to overcome alienation (Blencowe et al. 2015).'

(Smith and Anderson, 2018, p. 167).

Relational health provides a focus on lived experiences of loneliness. I find Ahmed's (2014) approach to thinking about emotions helpful. Ahmed suggests that as emotions are hard to define yet shape our world, a useful approach is to ask what emotions can do. This can provide a useful template to thinking about existential feelings like loneliness. Again following Ahmed's approach to emotions and taking the spatiality of these evaluations, that these are not psychological states but social and cultural practices (Ahmed, 2014) and asks why these feelings stick to some things and glide over others, which can serve as a line of inquiry about how a sense of belonging to groups and projects attach and grow. Raising these questions are important to thinking about what place does as processes of meaning-making are less studied in areas such as environmental psychology (Lomas, Ayodeji and Brown, 2021). In these areas, I find again the dominance of the discrete individual in ideas such as place attachment, and I suggest links to health geography should be made to move beyond the orthodox ways of thinking (Lewicka, 2011). The use of health geography in assemblage thinking therefore provides a useful conceptual tool. Assemblage thinking through providing the gateway to thinking loneliness as a social and culture practice can lead us to think about what habits transform our evaluations of the world. Jackson's (2020) analysis of a bowling alley views belonging and becoming as practices to understand convivial participation.

Relational health provides the basis for thinking about the public health work force beyond the formal. Through assemblage thinking and the conceptual toolkit, the work of facilitating health and wellbeing requires those facilitating informal places of health and wellbeing, places that give rise to affective encounters, those who have the skills to facilitate atmospheres and can encourage relational capacities. It goes beyond an emphasis on the social, whether its relationships or infrastructure, and provides a gateway to thinking about the feeling and experience of relationships. However, there is a tension between the richness of knowledge gained from non-reductionist approaches to research and lived experience, and the abstractness of policy as demonstrated by the example of the Scottish Government's social isolation and loneliness strategy and the focus on social loneliness. This tension reflects the limited presence of relational thinking in public health and policy approaches to health and wellbeing (Atkinson, 2020; Elton, 2021).

Using loneliness as site of investigation for my proposal for the fifth wave of public health shows the importance of concepts related to feeling, and shows the process of becoming human, how

individual's humanness fluctuates and shifts, and that life is in the living. Becoming human is expressed by Ingold (2014, p. 389) as 'wherever you find them, humans are humaning'.

4.6. The work of relational health

Relational health puts a focus on the practice of those who facilitate and mediate health and wellbeing. The shift from interiority and exteriority that assemblage thinking provides, also shifts responsibility for health and wellbeing being the main responsibility of the individual, to asking what can the collective do? This leads to focusing on those bringing together assemblages that have the capacity for health and wellbeing and those that tend to relational capacities of assemblages.

An example of this focus is shown by the view assemblage thinking offers me, of how wellbeing is experienced in the everyday, as constantly shifting through the diversity of experiences and the diversity of things encountered, such as people, spaces, events and objects as demonstrated by this quote from Duff (2016). Through this quote Duff illustrates more of the work recovery, and the varied resources, relationships, spaces and objects involved in this work has potential to be extended to health and wellbeing overall:

'Practices and experiences as diverse as travelling without any particular destination on a city train; getting one's hair cut in the company of sympathetic strangers; browsing for a film or a novel in a local store; launching into a handstand on a quiet street corner; enjoying the repose of the botanical gardens; or simply brewing a cup of tea in one's kitchen can avail social, affective and material resources for the ongoing formation of an assemblage of health.'

(Duff, 2014, p. 190)

The sensitizing concepts I have introduced in this chapter can be deployed to view the health and wellbeing dimensions of the practices and experiences in this quote. We can view the haircut as a 'convivial encounter', green space as 'affective infrastructure', the handstand providing a 'sensory-kinaesthesia' moment. All small moments, but if accumulated into a day, positive health and wellbeing would emerge. The quote suggests that those who do the work of relational health can range from those who extend a warm welcome and help facilitate atmospheres to hairdressers, to those that maintain green space.

4.7. Conclusion

I present in this chapter a proposition for the fifth wave of public health as one with a focus on relational health. I use assemblage thinking to develop my suggestion in Chapter 2 of the

characteristics of the fifth wave of public health: embracing multitudes of knowledge and complexity, a concern with connections, and a focus on the everyday. I grow insights that the characteristics of a fifth wave should include a direct engagement with what it means to be human and be well together, and view practices and experiences of everyday life as generating the foundational processes of health and wellbeing.

What emerges in this chapter from assemblage thinking is that my aim is not to make models, whether it is to extend, critique or develop a new model for public health. For example Hanlon et al. (2012) have developed a set of frameworks and models to answer their invitation to envisage a fifth wave of public health. Instead, I create a space for people to bring their models and concepts of relational health. This space needs to be rooted ontologically and epistemologically, so that shifts in thinking about health and wellbeing do not drift back into the current paradigm.

My emerging focus on developing ontological and epistemological roots for my proposal for a fifth wave of public health leads to my insight that I need to translate these roots into concepts we can think with and lenses for viewing and making visible the health and wellbeing work we do and the health and wellbeing processes we encounter. I address this need by my work of counter-conceptualisation and my thesis offers the idea of gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts.

I draw on assemblage thinking for my counter-conceptualisation work to resist orthodox thinking. I align with Atkinson's (2020) suggestion that assemblage thinking offers possibilities for this work. Out of this thinking emerges a concern with thinking about the parts of a model holistically and collectively. An explorative interest in thinking about components together emerges and offers me a way to pursue Atkinson's (2020, p. 3) 'elusive relationality that makes collective wellbeing about more than an aggregate of the constituent individuals.' I take this interest to develop the insight of utilising the concept of 'existential feelings' to view loneliness as intertwined with other feelings relating to our togetherness with the world. My insight of 'existential feelings' as a cluster of interdependent feelings shapes my investigation of loneliness as a public health issue. I start to view loneliness as a cluster of feelings. I consider these feelings as dimensions of a multi-faceted complex phenomena. An approach that has precedence in the field of emotional history (Bound Alberti, 2018). Through this approach I demonstrate how my counter-conceptualisation work brings a richness to how health and wellbeing is viewed and centres the process of becoming human, contrasting with the lifelessness of the orthodox approach.

My concern with how to translate the roots and relationships into ideas we can think, draws on human geography to explore place through a relational lens and arrives at the concept of 'enabling places' as a gateway concept, and 'atmospheres' as a sensitizing concept. My conceptual offering

creates room for thinking about the affective dimension of everyday processes of health. I explore the experience of loneliness to examine the tension between the experience of loneliness and policy approaches to loneliness and suggest that non-healthcare policies could contribute to navigating this tension and make an important contribution to public health by shifting ideas of health and society.

The work undertaken in this chapter of developing a proposal for the fifth wave of public health and developing ways to undertake the work of counter-conceptualisation equips me to follow my next research trail, exploring the use of culture and the arts for social purposes.

5. Culture (What is it good for?)

5.1. Introduction

Culture is good for you, as its suggested it makes a 'powerful contribution' to health and wellbeing (APPGAHW, 2017, p. 4). Culture is bad for you, is the possibility proposed by Brook, O'Brien and Taylor (2020), arguing culture is closely linked with social inequality. Culture is a social glue as it is concerned with connecting us (Parkinson, 2021). Culture for social ends has a history going back to the times of ancient Greece (Belfiore and Bennett, 2008). These claims for culture suggest it has a transformative effect on individuals and society. The transformation of individual lives, health, and wellbeing as well as social improvements are given in evaluation of cultural participation projects as evidence of what culture and the arts can do for people. Improving health and wellbeing is one of the claims for the use of culture and the arts for social purposes (Matarasso, 1997).

In this chapter I develop my proposal for the fifth wave of public health by using the proposal to examine the claims for the social purpose of culture and the arts. This examination provides insight into whether culture and the arts can be mobilised to help shift ideas of health and wellbeing. In particular, can ideas be shifted through the use of culture and the arts in the design of place-based policies that have health and wellbeing goals?

This chapter provides the next step in my analysis of my research puzzle by conceptually exploring the terms culture and the arts. I start with what is meant by culture, one of the most complex terms in the English language (Williams, 1988a). This starting point analyses the conceptual traditions of culture and the entanglement with the concept of art, and how these conceptual tangles influence the claims for the social purpose of culture and the arts. These claims lead into an investigation of how ideas of culture and the arts inform and challenge policy and practices that use culture and the arts for social purposes. I extend my counter-conceptualisation work into the realm of culture and the arts by examining the approaches used to conceptualise, research, and practice the use of culture and the arts for social aims. Next, loneliness as a public health issue is used as a site of investigation for examining how culture and the arts is used by research and policy to address health and wellbeing. Using the lens of the waves of public health I go on to assess two ideas, arts and health and cultural regeneration, that inform place-based policies that are designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing benefits. I conclude by presenting my suggestion of how these policies could create a fifth wave of public health through using my proposal for gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts.

5.2. Resonance and research trails

Section 3.9.3 describes the process of resonance which forms the research trail I explore in this chapter. Table 5.1 provides the key sources of resonance in each dimension. The academic literature in this table are texts that are continuously read and serve as check-ins for the development of my ontological and epistemological perspectives. The thesis was set up to understand the impact of culture and the arts on health and wellbeing so the research trail for the use of culture and the arts for health and wellbeing was present from the start of the research in Spring 2019.

Table 5.1: Resonance dimensions for the use of culture and the arts for health and wellbeing

Theory	Williams (1961)
Empirical	White (2009), Crossick and Kaszynska (2016), Crummy (1992)
Paisley context	Future Paisley
Brought selves	Economic development consultant, volunteer for exhibition relating to culture, arts, health and wellbeing
Situationally created self	Advisor on processes of evaluation
Policy	Scottish cultural strategy, APPHAW
Emergence of research trail	Spring 2019

5.3. Entangled definitions of culture and the arts

Concepts of culture and the arts are deeply entangled. I start working through the threads of defining culture and the arts by starting with the commonly used discussion of the traditions of defining culture. This discussion highlights a tussle between two traditions, the ‘Arnoldian’ tradition of excellence and an anthropological tradition of understanding everyday life (Hawkes, 2001; Bell and Oakley, 2015; Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016; Highmore, 2016). This tussle between ‘elite’ and ‘democratic’ models of cultural production is tied up with the concept of ‘the arts’. A linking of meaning of culture to the conceptualisation of the arts occurs in the 19th century particularly with the ideas of Matthew Arnold (Highmore, 2001; White, 2009; Bell and Oakley, 2015; Crossick and

Kaszynska, 2016). Writing in the 19th century as part of a group of 'post-enlightenment' thinkers, Arnold argued for the value of culture to society by making a case that culture offers a way to tackle society's issues through self-improvement (Arnold, 1869). In Arnold's description, culture is the best of thoughts and knowledge diffused across society, so all can be the best they can be, and these thoughts can be found in literature, arts, and science. Culture, in this tradition, is a noun describing the works and practices of intellectual activity, particularly artistic (Williams, 1988a).

The Arts Council England (2020, p. 9) for their 2020-2030 strategy talked to over 5,000 people and found 'across the country, there are significant differences in how 'arts' and 'culture' are defined, understood and valued. Many people are uncomfortable with the label 'the arts' and associate it only with either the visual arts or 'high art', such as ballet or opera.' Fine art refers to art as defined by art markets, galleries and their curators, and major funders, particularly arts councils and art schools (Crehan, 2011). These organisations can be seen as an institutional framework for the governance and resourcing of culture, which is structured by dominant social forces. Art is defined as an activity within this framework and a reproduction of the dominant social forces (Dickson, 1995). This notion of arts sits at the top of the hierarchy of arts. The nature of the hierarchy can take place along many dimensions, within art forms (Fisher, 2013) and created by a wide range of cultural forces, from government surveys (Taylor, 2016) to lists canonising particular cultural works. The exact nature and terminology of the hierarchy is debated due to the variety of terms such as high art, low art, popular art, and mass art (Fisher, 2013). There is consensus that culture is linked with artistic activity at the top end of the hierarchy (Tiller, 2017). This linkage creates an association between culture, the arts, and elitism (Arts Council England, 2020). Individuals and communities perceive that culture and the arts are not for them either as participants or producers (Dickson, 1995; Symons and Hurley, 2018). People are reluctant to describe themselves as artists (Secker *et al.*, 2018). The Arts Council England's finding that people are uncomfortable with the term 'the arts' creates a separation between people and culture and the arts, rather than culture and the arts as something meaningful to individuals and therefore constitutes their life and who they are. Culture and the arts in this model, disconnect with meaning-making activities, and this limits its potential role in health and wellbeing.

The second tradition is culture as everyday life and everyday communication. In this tradition, culture is determined by what people do. This tradition places culture in the realm of everyday life. The everyday is an ambiguous and evasive concept supported by a wide range of theories (Highmore, 2001; Ebrey, 2016). The discussion of this tradition often uses Williams' (1988b) phrase, 'culture is ordinary' (Oakley, Ball and Cunningham, 2018). Williams embeds this phrase in his description of the everyday and biographical details of his growing up, his father and grandfather. He

uses culture to mean the ordinary processes of meaning-making that constitute human individuals and human society. In the previous chapters I argue that focusing on the everyday provides an attunement to what is meaningful to people, in their everyday encounters. Focusing on what people do moves the focus away from a deficit model of participation (e.g. focusing on 'cold spots' (Gilmore, 2013). Symons and Hurley (2018) argue that the most significant barrier to engagement with culture is peoples' perceptions of the term. To overcome it, they emphasised culture as a process of making meaning. Paying attention to everyday life matters (Back, 2015, p. 834) suggests 'because it offers the opportunity to link the smallest story to the largest social transformation.' These small stories can be articulated through the concept of affects introduced in the previous chapter and expressed vividly by Stewart (2007, p. 63) 'the ordinary can happen before the mind can think. Little experiences of shock, recognition, confusion, and déjà vu pepper the most ordinary practices and moves.' At this level we can then explore how the shifts and moods of everyday life surface into meaning-making activities, and then into wider conceptions of culture, arts, health, and wellbeing. The concern with meaning and everyday life, means this tradition culture as everyday life and everyday communication has more affinity for my proposal of the fifth wave of public health.

5.4. Social purpose of culture and the arts

Different concepts of culture inform different orientations towards the facilitation and purpose of culture in research, policy, and practice. Culture in the Arnoldian tradition, conceptually entangled with the arts, sets up a defined group of activities rooted in particular traditions of practice and specialist knowledge and skills, such as opera or visual arts. A definition of culture, which roots in a set of formal activities informed by tradition, invites questions of participation and barriers (Gilmore, 2013). This approach to culture leads to a deficit approach of framing non-involvement in these activities. In contrast, taking an asset-based approach starts from where people are, rather than bringing 'culture' to people and is more in keeping with the theory of culture as everyday activity. Therefore an asset-based approach invites questions of what exists, what resonates with people and what can be nourished (Gilmore, 2013; Jancovich and Stevenson, 2021). The gulf between cultural practitioners and individuals regarding what is meaningful activity and what is defined as culture, has been identified as one of the ways in which cultural policy and cultural projects consistently fail (Jancovich and Stevenson, 2021). My argument that the fifth wave of public health needs to be characterised by an attunement to everyday life and seek a diversity of ways of knowing could contribute to reducing this gulf.

Since the 'counterculture' of the 1950s and 1960s, deficit concepts of culture have been challenged by a range of art practices. Fine arts and the role of arts in society has been challenged by artists

who grouped under the term community arts, which in many settings defined itself in opposition to fine arts. This resistance to hierarchies of cultural value is termed cultural democracy. Community arts emerged at a time of increasing global radical activity (Kelly, 1984) and an interest in an alternative way to organise society (Dickson, 1995). As community arts question the role of arts in society, the focus of community art became a way of working based around notions of ‘access’ and ‘participation’ (Dickson, 1995). In Scotland the community art tradition had particular interest in locality and place-making and ‘a pattern emerged of artists committing themselves to long-term involvement with specific local communities’ (Dickson, 1995, p. 31). The approach of community artists is community-led as the community articulates the needs. The relational aspect of culture and the arts is highlighted in this quote by Matarasso (2019, p. 39):

‘Art becomes a territory of meetings between people, a forum for encounter, friendship, exchange, conflict, alliance, misunderstanding, love, negotiation, mistrust, dislike, discovery, rejection—in fact, for the whole spectrum of human relations. As such, it matters enormously how those relations are regulated and who is allowed to take part.’

The alienating effect of the conceptualisation of culture as linked to the top end of a hierarchy of artistic activity has been challenged by community artists with a long-term commitment to local communities. Braden (1978) details many examples of how artists worked with communities to make culture relevant to them in her report of her commission from the Gulbenkian Foundation to make a study of its artists in residence programme. One of many examples in this commission of the process of making culture that is meaningful to people, starts with where people are, is given by John Phillips, a sculptor trained by the art establishment (Sheffield College of Arts) who was running a community printshop in Paddington:

‘If you are attempting to explore society creatively, then whoever you hold a dialogue with you have to understand and accept their language. There is no kind of pure aesthetics that can only be understood by an elite. Culture is everything, everyone has a culture. Yet our word for Culture is only for the cultured if you see what I mean.’

(Braden, 1978, p. 163)

5.5. Everyday life

Relational thinking can provide the conceptual room to understand and examine how culture and the arts interact with health and wellbeing. The fourth wave of public health is hindered in its thinking about how culture and the arts interact with people and how activities develop (White, 2009) due to a focus on outcomes rather than processes and experiences. In the previous chapter, I

argue that the fourth wave of public health thinking is not suited to questions regarding how to facilitate meaning or health and wellbeing generating spaces. The search for outcomes means that culture and the arts often use the language of healthcare and medical science to frame the case for benefits. Culture and the arts have been framed through the 'biopsychosocial model' (Fancourt, 2017), the social determinants of health (Gordon-Nesbitt and Howarth, 2019), salutogenesis (APPGAHW, 2017) and the fifth wave of public health through cultural health (Sonke, Rodríguez and Valerio-Shewmaker, 2021). As discussed in Chapter 2, health and wellbeing approaches share a focus on an individualised view of a person's health and wellbeing, which reduces the analytical space to analyse how and why participatory activities are beneficial to health and wellbeing (Atkinson *et al.*, 2015). A fifth wave of public health is needed to counter the dominance of 'what works' with 'what matters' (Williams *et al.*, 2007). The conceptual approach of culture as everyday life is concerned with 'what matters' and therefore aligns with my proposal for the fifth wave of public health.

Relational and meaning-making work and a focus on 'what matters' is a knowledge that artists have. A knowledge that is less centred in discussions of health and wellbeing due to the search for outcomes and a focus on individual benefits. Through focusing on creative and generative processes, community arts literature provides an insight into how culture, arts, health, and wellbeing can be facilitated together. The cultivation of health and wellbeing through an approach rooted in place and people's everyday life has been part of the practice of community artists. The UK has a tradition of community arts that aims to stimulate wellbeing and community engagement (Symons and Hurley, 2018). Community arts is very diverse, encompassing a wide variety of media, forms, techniques and situations (Bennett, 2017). Some forms are place based, some are artist led, some are neither. Crehan (2011) in a longitudinal study of the work of Free Form Arts Trust, based initially on Tyneside from the early 1970s onwards and subsequently in London, provides insights into this tradition through an anthropological perspective. This study examines how community art making provides processes in which the community could explore their experiences and their specific problems. This exploration provides the terrain for the community to work with community artists to find solutions. The experience of everyday life was key to the practice of community artists as they worked to share their knowledge of aesthetic language to 'show people how they could use aesthetic forms to tell their stories, to provide representations of their world rooted in their own day-to-day experiences.' (Crehan, 2011, p. 119). Community arts is a practice that focuses on working with the grain of everyday life. Therefore, through my view of health and wellbeing as processes, emerging from everyday life, community arts is a practice that by its nature facilitates health and wellbeing.

5.6. Working and mattering

Accounts of community art practice show how current health and wellbeing challenges have long been the concern of community projects. Crummy (1992) gives an account of the Craigmillar Festival Society, a voluntary organisation working in an area of the City of Edinburgh that was considered disadvantaged. The first festival, the Craigmillar Festival of Music, Arts and Drama was held in 1964. I find in her reflections an observation on the limitations of the social determinants of health when this approach was still new. Dahlgren and Whitehead's (2021) model of health determinants had been published the previous year. Crummy's account closes with the improvement to housing in the area and reflects why this has not tackled social decay. Crummy (1992, p. 238) terms people's creative energies as the 'nation's greatest source of wealth' that is fraying from social decay and the effect of government policies. This leads to a range of issues from the elderly dying in social isolation to deteriorating mental health. At the time of this account these issues are not yet a key policy concern, for example the UK's first loneliness strategy is still 16 years away (Prime Minister's Office, 10 Downing Street, Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport, Office for Civil Society, and The Rt Hon Theresa May MP, 2018). Crummy's account of the Society resonates with William's (2007) recommendations from the SHARP project in Wales for addressing health inequalities. These recommendations stated that national redistributive policies and participative social movements that build on the considerable knowledge of local communities and organisations were required to tackle health inequalities. Crummy suggests that the organic government and community partnership that evolved in Craigmillar, could provide a policy solution to health and wellbeing challenges. In her postscript, she articulates a relational approach of working with people through supporting and recognising people, in a society that shares and cares. Her discussion of partnerships comes almost a decade before the Christie Commission. The Craigmillar story talks about the health and welfare centres developed. Similar centres are now part of policy for example through the 'Deep End' community Link Worker Project (Chng *et al.*, 2021) which embeds link workers into general practices serving some of the most deprived areas in Scotland.

Going through Crummy's account illustrates that 'what works?' is known in both community and academic knowledge. More widely this knowledge exists in ethnographic accounts of community and socially engaged arts practice, particularly in nuanced and non-reductive ethnographies and reflections (Artlink, 2005; Crehan, 2011). Through Crummy's account of the Craigmillar Festival Society I find further examples of 'what works' such as asset-based approaches and affective, physical, and social resources. The Craigmillar story opens with a community relocation in 1929 that did not take an asset-based approach and draw on existing affective, physical, and social resources such as a sense of belonging and green space. Instead, the relocation dented these resources. The

consequences of such an approach to urban development and its generational impact on health and health inequality have been explored through the term 'Glasgow Effect', a term to describe the unexplained higher levels of poor health and mortality in Glasgow compared to other areas with a similar socio-economic profile. The Glasgow Effect has been dismantled by Walsh et al. (2016) as excess mortality in Glasgow is explained by making visible the complex historical and political effects on health and health inequality such as housing policy and local government responses to urban change, particularly from the 1950s. Craigmillar's story illustrates Ledwith's (2011) description of community development as beginning in the lives of local people, as this is the initial context for sustainable change, where the process of empowerment and participation begins, where community development can grow through a diversity of local projects that address issues faced by local community.

The fifth wave of public health's concern with 'what matters' counters the dominance of the language of interventions, the concern with 'what works' (Tyמושuk *et al.*, 2019) and the production of causal stories (Oman and Taylor, 2018). My proposal for the fifth wave of public health to be characterised by a concern with the challenges of 'becoming human' offers a focus on 'what matters' to people. Cropper et al. (2007) argue this focus is essential, as their learnings from SHARP find approaches that focus on 'what works' without focusing on 'what matters' to people are doomed to fail, 'what works' needs to be in context of 'what matters'. This point is amplified by Oakley's (2015) suggestion that the everyday cultural experiences people choose to pursue, from blogging to allotments, potentially offer better outcomes for area-based regeneration than one-off spectacles. Therefore, these place-based policies that utilise culture and the arts for social purposes should start from what people value. Cultural democracy is required as a principle.

5.7. Everything works

A further issue with the question 'what works' in terms of which activity to participate in is that everything works. Focusing on the benefits rather than the processes of health and wellbeing means much shown about culture and the arts contribution to health and wellbeing is the benefits of engaging in a meaningful activity. This focus present in the links between leisure and health, whereas with arts and health, the two are shown to be linked, but the 'how' of the linkages is unclear (Peel, Maxwell and McGrath, 2019; Mansfield, Daykin and Kay, 2020). Greater muddling between the terms 'arts' and 'leisure' ensues from the conceptual overlap where the tradition of culture as everyday life with that of leisure, particularly the concept of casual leisure (Stebbins, 1997). Casual leisure, such as pottering, is important for health and wellbeing (Scott-Arthur, Brown and Saukko, 2021). The approach 'what works' represents the flip side of the exhaustion of the

determinants and epidemiological approach to health research and policy, where every possible experience could carry at least some risk of harm (Duff, 2014). It is sometimes hard to know what isn't 'healthy anymore', with research finding a wide variety of activities that contribute to health and wellbeing such as hyperthermic baths (Naumann *et al.*, 2017). Activities that people seek to do, because people find them meaningful and worthwhile, intrinsically contribute to health and wellbeing. This proliferation of factors that could contribute to health and wellbeing, leads to complex descriptions of the social determinants of health and less focus on health and wellbeing as an experience of living (Duff, 2014). This point is picked up by Clift *et al.* (2021) in their critique of research on social and health impacts of the arts where they suggest there is no surprise that people will gain benefits from doing activities they enjoy and value, especially over a period of time.

The positive health outcomes from cultural and art activities have been well researched, but how these activities create health outcomes has been less examined (Raw, 2014). What arts and culture itself contributes is unclear (Secker *et al.*, 2018). How something such as a project or programme works is usually framed as a mechanism or pathway. However, the benefits of engaging with culture and the arts will vary for individuals and the benefits may not be related to the size itself but as Sagan (2017) argues in the accumulation of benefit, as this is how transformation of the self occurs. Duff (2016, p. 71) illustrates the process of accumulation, starting with unassuming moments such as practices and relations and argues that 'what counts is the extent to which these practices and relations begin to ramify, to accumulate, to resonate together in the formation of an assemblage of health.' A focus on these processes of accumulation and health and wellbeing as an experience, suggests that health and wellbeing should be thought of as emergent, that the form of the experience of health and wellbeing that results from engaging with culture and the arts cannot be predicted or fully known.

5.8. Policy and social purpose of culture and the arts

Policy makers' usage of culture and the arts also influences practitioners and public perceptions of the social purpose of culture and the arts. There is a policy history of a belief that culture and the arts can have 'place-based' benefits (Brook, O'Brien and Taylor, 2020). This approach aims to meet a range of policy goals in a variety of ways, including inward investment, tourism, branding, skills, community cohesion, and creative/cultural sector growth (Bell and Oakley, 2015; Campbell *et al.*, 2016; Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016; Local Government Association, 2019). These policy goals came together in the use of culture for urban regeneration in order to re-vision the city (Hewitt, 2011). Regeneration is a term used to collectively describe policy responses that deal with the issues of economic, social, and physical decline (Evans, 2011). This term bundles together a variety of policy

agendas from economic growth to social inclusion (Hewitt, 2011). Initially, regeneration was associated with de-industrialisation, a term describing how the manufacturing sector's decline in the 1960s and 1970s led to the loss of major employers in an urban area (Tallon, 2013). Urban regeneration is one of the main uses of culture and the arts in policy (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016) and is an example of a place-based policy that leverages culture and the arts. Health and wellbeing have often been considered part of social outcomes (Matarasso, 1997; Evans and Shaw, 2004).

An emphasis on 'what matters' and starting from what people already value would create a focus on smaller-scale cultural activities and engaging with communities (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016). Cultural regeneration approaches are often larger-scale activities such as infrastructural, building based projects, such as cultural quarters and flagship projects (Bell and Oakley, 2015). An emphasis on 'what matters' leads to a focus on informal and everyday cultural activities, small scale and organic assets, such as knitting circles and allotments (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016). These activities create an overlap between culture and leisure research and the research literature on green space and community gardens. These literatures have examined the health and wellbeing effects of these spaces, including the perspective of seeing these spaces as 'more than therapeutic', seeing them as 'enabling places' where norms of society may be challenged (Wiles *et al.*, 2020). Valuing 'what matters' would emphasise valuing the experience of culture, a form of knowledge that policy research in the field of culture often takes little account of, (Bennett, 2004) leaving casual leisure less valued and sometimes demonised in policy (Oman, 2021). One reason for the low valuation of casual leisure Oman (2020) argues, is due to the culture of the selective tradition, which is culture that is recorded. Selective culture is considered valuable by policymakers therefore what can be measured becomes valuable.

Interest in arts and culture's contribution to health has been increasing in the last two decades in research, policy, and practice (Daykin, 2019a; Fancourt and Finn, 2019). The APPGAHW Inquiry Report into the existing engagement of the arts in health and social care describes itself as making the case 'that the arts have a vital part to play in mitigating the effects of the social determinants of health.' (APPGAHW, 2017, p. 31). Through invoking the social determinants of health, the report makes a case that the arts are core to the fourth wave of public health. The usage of the report leads Brook, O'Brien, and Taylor (2020) to suggest that health and wellbeing may be the primary approach to discussing the benefits of culture and the arts.

I use the term arts and health to refer to a growing field that draws in culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing. The intersection between these areas is unclear, as illustrated by the lack of consensus on what activities are placed in this intersection (Dose, 2006; APPGAHW, 2017; Fancourt, 2017; Arts

Council of Wales, 2018). Some definitions consider art and music therapy as separate to arts and health, due to arts and music therapy's formal acceptance in healthcare through being a registered profession in the UK. Daykin (2019a) defines the field as a cluster of activities and resources that have different linages. There is a long history to the field of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing (Yoeli *et al.*, 2020) that overlaps with the intellectual history of the social purpose of culture and the arts (Belfiore and Bennett, 2008). I refer to the field of arts and health using Clift *et al.*'s (2021, p. 442) identification of a 'growth of interest in the UK in the social and health impacts of the arts from the late 1990s onwards.' An overview of the state of the field of arts and health research is provided by an article reflecting on a national seminar series and building a UK research network for arts, health, and wellbeing. This article starts with 'research on arts, health, and wellbeing is an established and dynamic field of interest in the UK. This is reflected in the emergence of several university centres of inquiry which are represented through the authorship of this paper' (Stickley *et al.*, 2017, p. 14). As I am interested in the claims for arts and health, I consider the field more by authors and the field's self-definition than activities, such as authors contributing to Stickley *et al.*'s (2017), reflections on a national seminar series on Arts, Health and Wellbeing and those in edited books such as *Oxford Textbook of Creative Arts, Health, and Wellbeing: International perspectives on practice, policy and research* (Clift and Camic, 2015) and *Arts, health and wellbeing : a theoretical inquiry for practice* (Stickley and Clift, 2017). Arts and health includes journals cited in Stickley *et al.*'s reflections (2017) and the *Nordic Journal of Arts, Culture and Health*. I include in this field activities that are included in mapping reports and overviews (APPGAHW, 2017; Arts Council of Wales, 2018; Rocket Science, 2021), membership organisations such as Arts & Health South West and Culture, Health and Wellbeing Alliance and events related to these organisations. It also includes evidence reviews such as Fancourt and Finn's (2019) review for the WHO. Arts and health is sometimes described as creative health such as the work in Greater Manchester Combined Authority (Parkinson, 2021). My categorisation of arts and health is by nature imprecise despite efforts to create a shared language (Davies and Clift, 2022). In particular the advocacy tendency of the field (Stickley *et al.*, 2017) leads it to claim the benefits and engagement from a wide range of activities particularly leisure. An example of what I include as arts and health research, based on the authors that also encompasses leisure research is the *report Community COVID: How can community assets address health inequities?* (Mughal *et al.*, 2021). My use of the term arts and health does not include some types of culture and arts activity that have an impact on health and wellbeing as such as community arts even though it may blur with arts and health, for example Greater Manchester defines itself as drawing on a century of practice (Parkinson, 2021). Community arts has a tradition and history, which although lacks consensus on a definition, is discernible through core texts

(Braden, 1978; Dickson, 1995; Fox, 2002; Crehan, 2011). Arts and health as a field of research and practice is diffuse, constantly shifting, and ambiguous, and I will critically engage with the term arts and health throughout this thesis.

The fifth wave of public health has been evoked as a rationale for culture and the arts in health and wellbeing (Sonke *et al.*, 2019). In Sonke's article it is used in terms of collaboration to bring culture and the arts together and working across sectors. While mobilisation of the wider public health role of non-healthcare sectors is needed to tackle health and wellbeing issues, this approach leaves intact the envisaging of a world with boundaries between sectors. This issue of boundaries is shared with other interdisciplinary approaches to health share. For example, One Health takes an integrative approach to health by drawing together the environment, animal, and human worlds. Boundaries remain as these worlds remain conceptually separate. I find in Davis and Sharp's (2020) account of critically engaging with One Health through assemblage thinking, helpful for my proposal for the fifth wave of public health. This article shows that when the sectors of One Health are seen as enmeshed, a more expansive view of health is enabled. There are multiple ways for health to form, therefore, multiple ways of knowing are needed to understand these processes. Davis and Sharp's (2020) article draws on the knowledge of a spiritual leader and healer that provides advice to people in Maasailand. This knowledge makes visible the impact of hegemonic thinking, the transmission of this thinking through (post) colonialism and neoliberalism and how this thinking shapes people's lives and health.

The issues identified in the previous chapter about the fourth wave of public health need to be explicitly acknowledged and addressed as these issues are also present in other sectors. Bringing other sectors into the realm of public health without acknowledging these issues could compound the current challenges of the fourth wave of public health and entrench the problems with current thinking about health and society. I argue in Chapter 4, that the fifth wave of public health needs to bring into focus these ontological and epistemological challenges in order to create the space for other sectors to bring in ways of knowing and doing, that currently fit less comfortably with the existing waves of public health.

I have found that the academic and grey literature of arts and health causal narratives, dominate approaches to research into how culture and the arts contribute to health and wellbeing, a trait shared with loneliness research. Logic models and mechanisms are used to evaluate and conceptualise how activities lead to health and wellbeing outcomes through providing a causal narrative from inputs and factors to outputs and outcomes (Daykin and Joss, 2016; Fancourt and Finn, 2019; Mansfield, Daykin and Kay, 2020). The nature of this empirical research in the arts and

health mainly focuses on establishing the evidence base for the field (Stickley and Clift, 2017) (Stickley and Clift, 2017). This focus results in greater attention on achieving health outcomes than how these outcomes have come about (Raw *et al.*, 2012). The health benefits of arts, health and wellbeing projects and programmes are well illustrated (Fancourt and Finn, 2019) though robustness of some research has been challenged (Clift, Phillips and Pritchard, 2021).

Reductionist methodological techniques also dominate. These frameworks claim to demonstrate 'how change happens' and answer questions about 'what works', particularly to create evidence to influence commissioners of services, policymakers, and funders (Daykin and Joss, 2016). In academic literature, a theory of leisure activities has been built out of mechanisms that address issues of non-linearity and which take a complex adaptive systems approach where leisure is seen as a complex societal intervention (Fancourt *et al.*, 2021). Although this approach acknowledges complexity, it still atomises everyday experience into cause and effect. These models are concerned with reducing the value of culture and the arts to an outcome, in this case, health rather than considering the experience of culture and the arts. These techniques assess benefit at points in time, often at one point after a project has concluded. This pointillist approach does not resonate with the conception of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing as part of everyday life, constantly in flux, where projects and experiences reverberate temporality as affective and qualitative moments accumulate and interact. The acknowledgement of this everyday perspective, the lack of easy answers on how people respond to culture and the arts, and admitting the absence of tidy pathways to social impact is needed to counter the 'bullshit' Belfiore (2009) identifies in academic cultural policy research.

The issues of the dominance of reductionist techniques are compounded by the evidence base agenda. The emphasis on outcomes and impacts in 'evidence base' approaches can obscure theories, ideologies, values, and principles (Carlisle *et al.*, 2007), institutional capacity and constraints for delivering interventions (Porter, Roberts and Clements, 2007) and generally places less value on lay knowledge and expertise (Carlisle *et al.*, 2007; White, 2009). This tendency is compounded by the frequent conflation of arts and health research with advocacy and obscures critical theories and perspectives (Stickley *et al.*, 2017). The drive for evidence can also be found in the drive to developing and demonstrating evidence-based practice (Stickley *et al.*, 2017). The difficulties of evidencing practice in the arts and health field can lead to a perception that the field has a weak evidence base, leading to initiatives to create common evaluation frameworks, templates or toolkits, that can be used across the sector and develop evaluation skills in the sector to improve engagement with policy and funding agendas (Daykin *et al.*, 2017). The conversation around evaluation usually involves barriers to evaluation and how to improve the process using toolkits and frameworks. The conversation is often also focused on artists and communicating the

value of arts-based activities within the delivery of healthcare services, narrowing the potential scope of arts and health. There is less questioning of what this search for evidence and wellbeing data does to how we think about culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing. A question Oman (2021) engages with in their book that unpicks the relationship between wellbeing, data, social and cultural policy and research, particularly through raising the question of how much can data help us understand people and how does data affect wellbeing. These questions are important as they shape how fully the fifth wave of public's health focus on 'becoming human' can be engaged with by place-based policies that use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing ends.

The issue of how the arts interact with health has been raised by Hanlon and Carlisle (2015) as giving them a sense of unease due to studies using reductionist approaches to show biomedical benefits. These approaches they suggest are valuable but could divert attention from focusing on larger challenges which they argue are fundamentally about being human. Their proposal for the fifth wave of public health puts aesthetics integral to the fifth wave of public health. I take a different direction for my research as I choose to situate myself between fields and draw together knowledge across fields. The fields that I encounter is an emergent process, informed by where the trails take me, as I follow in real time, the development of Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension. Therefore, it cannot be foreseen what my research encounters are, and the fields that the encounters need to be engaged with, in order to iteratively grow knowledge from an intertwining of theoretical and empirical analysis. My research orientation is an open approach that seeks resistance to orthodox thinking in whatever fields I may draw upon to grow knowledge regarding the ontological and epistemological dimensions of my proposal for fifth wave of public health.

5.9. Ask the lonely

5.9.1. Social prescribing

I have suggested that loneliness as a public health issue is a useful site of investigation for my proposal for a fifth wave of public health. This site will be used to assess the role of culture and the arts in health and wellbeing services. The increased interest in interventions to alleviate loneliness and the involvement of arts-based and cultural activities in achieving health outcomes, have come together in social prescribing (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2018). There are many models of social prescribing; broadly, this term is applied to non-medical interventions to improve health (Drinkwater, Wildman and Moffatt, 2019). People are generally supported to access community activities, often by specialist workers. Social prescribing provides a route for the greater involvement of the voluntary and third sector into the delivery of formal health and social care services. When culture and the arts are a core part of the prescription, social prescribing is sometimes referred to as arts on prescription,

with the first UK programme set up in 1994 (Bungay and Clift, 2010). Social prescribing has become a key activity in the arts and health landscape (APPGAHW, 2017; Parkinson, 2021) and an activity within the cultural landscape (Coventry UK City of Culture 2021, no date). More recently, the role of museums in public health has become a dynamic area of research and organisational activity (Camic and Chatterjee, 2013; Desmarais, Bedford and Chatterjee, 2018; O'Neill and Hooper, 2019) and has a history of involvement with social prescribing (Froggett, Farrier and Poursanidou, 2011) including specifically targeting social isolation (Thomson *et al.*, 2017). The tensions of what counts as knowledge is highlighted by Parkinson's (2021) assessment of the social prescribing of arts activities. They evaluate the assessment of the mixed state of the evidence base for social prescribing of the arts which ranges from strong, for some outcomes such as improving cognition in healthy older adults, to non-existent for others as social inequalities (Fancourt, Warran and Aughterson, 2020). Parkinson suggests this may be due to the issues argued in this thesis as being characteristics of the fourth wave of public health, the use of reductionist approaches and trying to fit the complexities of lived experiences into the dominant frameworks of health. Tensions between the unsuitability of dominant research methods, an approach driven by identifying benefits, and the complexity of experience are also found in the overall social prescribing literature (Calderón-Larrañaga *et al.*, 2022).

5.9.2. Over prescribing?

The discourses of social prescribing that influence implementation and evaluation found by Calderón- Larrañaga *et al.* (2022) resonate with the arguments for the waves of public health I have put forward. Calderón- Larrañaga *et al.* (2022) suggests there are three discourses of social prescribing. Two of the three discourses map onto my arguments regarding the dominant characteristics of the fourth wave of public health: the trend for individual responsibility, overmedicalisation and research designs producing descriptions of loneliness. There is a danger that social prescribing could result in a new manifestation of the 'lifestyle drift' away from structural determinants of health to focusing on individual behaviours. The third discourse values 'human dimensions, relationships, experiences, reciprocities' and highlights the lack of relational work in the healthcare system (Calderón-Larrañaga *et al.*, 2022, p. 8). Relational work can be the main value of social prescribing to individuals, and the loss of the relationship with the link worker when the programme ends can impact the health and wellbeing of the individual (Foster *et al.*, 2020).

The danger of arts and health reinforcing the 'lifestyle drift' is highlighted by research into the quantification of the right dosage of engagement with culture and the arts to improve health (McCrary, Redding and Altenmüller, 2021). This approach suggests that a population approach to

improving wellbeing would be to encourage the population to engage in culture, the arts, and other wellbeing promoting activities (Davies, Knuijan and Rosenberg, 2016). An instrumental value of culture derives from how well culture achieves societal ends, for whom, and whose cultural value is utilised (Belfiore, 2012, 2018). A dosage approach to engaging with culture and the arts would result in an instrumentalisation of culture and arts, where the types of culture and the arts being prescribed, and modes of engagement are valued for their apparent impact on health and wellbeing. Research would be concerned with size of effects and clinical meaningful impact of interventions (Fancourt and Finn, 2019), creating a focus on activities that have a proximal benefit, a tendency that led to the 'lifestyle drift'. New hierarchies of cultural value would be created. Hierarchies would be exacerbated by the evidence base being more developed in some areas than others (Fancourt and Finn, 2019).

The search for dosage has also occurred in research into the health and wellbeing benefits of nature (White *et al.*, 2019; Meredith *et al.*, 2020). There are similar tensions between the lack of focus on experience (Couper, 2018), the multiplicity of experiences and the policy driven reductionist agenda to value and quantify (Bell *et al.*, 2019). The combination of this dosage approach and the social prescribing agenda leaves policy solutions to loneliness seen through the lens of the fourth wave of public health. Approaches using this lens can be beneficial to health and wellbeing, however the lack of ontological and epistemological diversity means they are not equipped to fully understand the relationship between nature, culture, the arts, and other activities. Bell (2019, p. 10) suggests:

'If we are to fully understand and enable the links between nature (charismatic or otherwise) and human well-being in a meaningful way, we need to appreciate the plurality of embodied human experience, and therefore the plurality of ways to 'be well' in the world.'

I suggest this argument also applies to culture, leisure and other activities that are meaningful. Bell's suggestion highlights the importance of existential feelings, which are a crucial part of 'being well' in the world and are integral to the process of becoming human.

5.10. It's the same old song but with a different context

The arts and health field extends the literature regarding the social benefits of culture and the arts further into health and wellbeing (Brook, O'Brien and Taylor, 2020). The discussions over whether culture and the arts involve passive consumption or are a vehicle for activism and change (APPGAHW, 2017; Daykin, 2019a) and whether inequality will reinforce and reproduce hierarchies of value echo discussions in other fields that use culture to meet other policy agendas such as through

urban regeneration. The questions raised by Belfiore and Bennett (2010) over a decade ago regarding methods to assess the social impact of the arts are still pertinent such as the lack of clarity about how individuals are affected by the arts, the claims for the transformative powers of the arts and the need for a better understanding of how individuals interact with the arts. Engagement with these questions is required before issues such as impact are discussed. I suggest that engaging with these questions requires a shift in the way we think about health and society.

Place-based transformations through the use of culture have a long critical academic tradition (Brook, O'Brien and Taylor, 2020). In the UK, the term culture-led regeneration started emerging in the late 1980s (Vickery, 2007), gathering interest across Europe in the 1990s (García, 2004), spurred on by well-documented examples of cities using culture in urban regeneration practice that became models for other cities. Examples include Glasgow's year as European City of Culture in 1990 (Mooney, 2004; Vickery, 2007) and the 'Bilbao Effect' from the opening of the Guggenheim Museum in Bilbao in 1997 (Bell and Oakley, 2015), resulting in one of the many tangled strands between cultural policy and urban regeneration policies (Bianchini and Parkinson, 1993). The main entanglements are through what culture can bring to the economic sphere (García, 2004; Campbell *et al.*, 2016).

Cultural regeneration is plagued by reductionism through the demand for an evidence base. Policy is shaped by the desire for evidence formed through evidence-based policy (EBP) a popular and much debated term. EBP claims to add rationality to policy-making process through more scientific methods and less ideology and which draws on discourses of evidence-based medicine. I am not focused on exploring EBP as a concept, but instead I focus on the effects of EBP on policymaking and on the practice of leveraging culture and arts for health and wellbeing. Two key effects of EBP are identified by Belfiore and Bennet (2010), a focus on 'what works' and the key role of 'policy evaluation' in the policy process to assess the effectiveness of projects and programmes initiated by policy as well as policy itself. The scientific, positivist framework provides a driver for the search for causal narratives based on empirical evidence of 'effect' and 'outcome'.

5.10.1. Policy entanglements

Entanglements between cultural policy and culture-led regeneration have occurred in the area of health and wellbeing. Museums are part of a typology of culture-led regeneration as they are often an area's flagship cultural facility (Vickery, 2007). Museums also form part of arts and health through some museums developing a role as a space for wellbeing (Desmarais, Bedford and Chatterjee, 2018). Entanglements have also happened with culture-led regeneration and arts and health, through asking what culture can bring to health and wellbeing. The question of what culture and the

arts can bring to health, risks situating culture and the arts in a supplicant position to powerful medical and socio-economic narratives of wellbeing. Through the entanglements with urban regeneration and now arts and health, the field of culture and the arts is forever having to justify its funding and public service role. This justification usually takes the form of reductionist approaches to evidence gathering and articulating value, even though EBP is riven with contradictions, a lack of consensus regarding the term, (Cairney, 2022) and programme roll-out can come before the evidence base, such as in the delivery of social prescribing (Husk *et al.*, 2016).

Powerful discursive drivers of EBP such as public choice economics, neoliberalism and new public management (O'Brien, 2012) are beyond the scope of this research. Through reductionism, the themes of scientific rationalisation, accountability and control unites all these drivers. Although EBP, in practice, is often a myth as policy makers often use a wide range of types of knowledge from their own to public opinion (Cairney, 2022). However, EBP shapes the doings and makings of policy such as what cultural and art activities are valued, what health and wellbeing ends are sought, and inform conversations about the purpose and benefit of culture, art, health, and wellbeing. Practitioners of arts and health express anxieties about evaluation (Tanner, 2020; Rocket Science, 2021). Cultural regeneration shows the quantities of evidence produced to meet this agenda (Campbell, Cox and O'Brien, 2017), such as festivals (Evans, 2011). Despite critiques of the evidence produced, evidence keeps being generated (Campbell, 2019). Arts and health is following the trajectory suggested by Campbell, Cox and O'Brien (2017) regarding the achievements of culture in regeneration strategies, where the evidence takes an advocacy tone which sweeps up any positive information and muffles or masks critical voices or perspectives. In Scotland, arts and health activity is potentially caught in a self-reinforcing loop of evaluation where artists consulted on their concerns, reply that they are concerned about evaluation. These concerns are channelled into recommendations for 'better evaluation' (Rocket Science, 2021). Whether the concerns are taken on leads to more evaluation, and the cycle is never stopped or critiqued.

The lack of causal narratives such as mechanisms and pathways from participating in culture to improved health and wellbeing are considered a shortcoming of research (Stickley *et al.*, 2017). I consider this lack as an ontological and epistemological tension between the nature of the perceived problem, the knowledge of how to address the problem and the tools provided by the fourth wave of public health. The reductionist thinking of mechanisms and pathways dominates thinking of other academic literature regarding the health benefits of non-medical health assets. I have argued, how crowding out other forms of knowledge such as experiential knowledge leads to an incomplete understanding of the links between activities such as participating in leisure and in culture and health and wellbeing.

Culture as an everyday meaningful activity is found not in measurements or survey categories but in free text boxes. Oman (2020) finds in their analysis of Office for National Statistics data from the Measuring National Well-being of thousands of free text fields responding to the question 'What things in life matter to you?' that the most frequent theme, contained in forty percent of responses mentions leisure and free time. Respondents mentioned leisure and 'ordinary' cultural practices, arts and culture were less mentioned.

The field of arts and health doesn't fully engage with these epistemological issues, a situation that will increase as more longitudinal studies are undertaken (Tyמושuk *et al.*, 2019). In addition there are wider issues with data that conflict with a cultural democracy approach (D'Ignazio and Klein, 2020) as survey tick boxes do not just exclude what people do, people are also excluded (Keyes, 2019). Techniques to generate an evidence base can reduce what it means to be human, creating tension with claims by culture and the arts about being human.

5.10.2. Arnoldian ideas linger

Arnoldian ideas of the benefits of culture linger in arts and health. For example, the ways people have expressed the fundamental nature of arts, which are claimed to be central to not just health but becoming human and to do with human flourishing, livelihood and 'quality of life'. Clift and Camic (2015) argue that what arts offers is fundamentally creativity and problem solving, and most importantly creating both meaning and a sense of beauty. APPGHAW quotes the former Secretary of State for Health, Alan Johnson, 'access and participation in the arts are an essential part of our everyday wellbeing and quality of life' (APPGAHW, 2017, p. 21). I find implicit undertones of deficit thinking in claims for culture and the arts, that without the experience of the arts, individuals are missing part of the human experience and are less likely to be empowered (Matarasso, 2019). The cultural democracy language that is intended to free us from the hierarchy of culture and the arts and value what individuals find meaningful, risk instead reducing individual's agency. By declaring that we are all artists, and that we all have creativity (64 million artists, 2016; Matarasso, 2019; Arts Council England, 2020) those that do not choose this identity are assumed to be in wellbeing deficit and not living life well. Activities deemed to not have a creative process, such as aerobics, are therefore considered to have fewer ways of impacting wellbeing and, so less valuable to society (Boyles, 2017). Do these transformative claims of the arts mean that people are less human, experiencing less of life if they choose to wild swim (Foley, 2017) or bowl (Jackson, 2020)? The transformative nature of arts for health activities echoes the transformative claims for regeneration, a refrain of the Arnoldian ideas of improvement. In this context of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing I find that the Arnoldian ideas of the betterment of individuals and society segue into the

issue of the placing of responsibility for improvement onto the individual. Hewitt (2011, p. 33) describes this placing of responsibility as making ‘socio-economic problems appear like psychological disorders in need of some therapy.’ Arnold’s ideas of the social purpose of culture and its deficit approach still linger even though the language to define culture encompasses the everyday and the grassroots (Scottish Government, 2020a). My argument for the idea of relational health means becoming human is not an exclusive property of culture and the arts. If as Brook, O’Brien and Taylor (2020) suggests health and wellbeing is the primary way we discuss the benefits of culture, then the fifth wave of public health has the potential to shape what we mean by culture and the arts in the design of policy, both for cultural and for health and wellbeing ends.

5.10.3. Using the toolkit to shift thinking about health and society

I introduced the term atmospheres in Chapter 4. This term can be used to focus on the practice of facilitating spaces of health and wellbeing. One of White’s principles for arts in community health is about creating congenial space and the importance of process to create ‘a climate for meaningful engagement where conversation comes naturally’ (White, 2009, p. 105). These social climates and encounters offer the atmospheres of sociality, safety and belonging, and hope and belief that Duff (2016) evaluates as allowing people to be themselves. Managing atmospheres, tone and affects is a key part of art in the community practice (Atkinson and Robson, 2012; Raw and Mantecón, 2013). Duff (2016, p. 69) illustrates how atmospheres intertwine with creativity and lead to health:

‘An atmosphere of safety and security is to the work of actually discovering and cultivating practices, such as cooking or creativity, by which safety may be articulated as a social, affective and corporeal property of a body in recovery. Something as seemingly mundane as attempting to cook a new dish, even making a cup of tea, may in these respects take on greater significance as moments whereby safety settles into the body as a distinctive structure of feeling. Gathering together forces (will, desire), bodies (ingredients, cook books, utensils) and spaces (a clean kitchen), April’s kitchen manifests an atmosphere of safety, a space of recovery.’

The practice of artists creating these spaces of health and wellbeing is a relational practice through creating a relational framework (Raw and Mantecón, 2013). As this framework is fluid and dynamic, it requires constant attuning to and affecting interactions. Relational practices help participants achieve or regain a sense of their social abilities. Cultivating possibilities of change through interactions and relationships motivate art practitioners in the community in the UK (Raw and Mantecón, 2013) as they are motivated by discovering what people are capable of. White’s description of art as a relational practice and the expansion of individual capabilities echo and

elaborate on the notions intertwining social capital and human capital that Moore (2007) finds in the SHARP programme in Section 2.9:

‘Making art together can be a relational practice that helps participants to achieve or regain a sense of their social abilities. This has implications for social inclusion in areas of high health inequalities that are characterised by a paucity of social capital, low expectations and disenfranchisement through apathy. In addressing these problems, issues of identity and place become paramount, and the picture is more subtle and complex than epidemiology statistics alone can convey.’

(White, 2009, p. 106).

Focusing simply on how art and culture is reported to affect individuals narrows the scope of understanding how culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing emerge, develop, and relate to each other. While there is evidence which shows that individuals are changed through encounters with the culture and the arts, focusing on the individual risks diverting attention from the relational (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016). The relational is also important for positive health approaches that seek to build community relationships. Art in this context of community is a relationship. White (2009, p. 104) captures this relational aspect through his description of art as a ‘gift rather than a commodity; recognising that it is something created for an occasion to exchange information, feelings or experiential wisdom.’ White outlines seven essential principles for effective practice of arts in community health draws Lewis Hyde’s account of how art is shared in the public realm and the idea of reciprocity in the art of giving, a gift that builds as it moves between people. This leads White (2009, p. 104) to provide a definition of health close to Duff’s capabilities ‘health comes from individuals realising their potential and gaining access to other opportunities for personal and social advancement.’ and leads White to reflect that the gift giving nature of arts in community that I find have the similar characteristics of transformation as the SHARP five-year action research project that I introduced in Section 2.9. The gift is:

‘Character building for the individual and it can also increase morale in the social group: the look at what we did’ factor. When cultural activities in arts, sports and community action can clearly show that the people involved in them are valued, they stimulate a reciprocity that other kinds of public-sector intervention struggle to achieve, and so they are central to a regeneration strategy, not just window dressing.’

(White, 2009, p. 104)

Considering culture and arts as an everyday activity, means that individuals constitute health and wellbeing out of their own practices. Leisure activities can create dynamic processes of belonging and community, where an individual's contribution to these processes also constitutes who they are (Jackson, 2020). This illuminates the processes that create subjective evaluations of external views of self such as sense of belonging or sense of loneliness and how the psychological and the social processes are intimately and inextricably linked. Jackson's (2020) study of participating in a bowling league shows how small moments, experienced individually, link to broader processes that support health and wellbeing, such as belonging or spatial and social practices such as the creation of atmospheres, in this case convivial spaces. Leisure research through attunement to the cumulation of resonant encounters and fleeting moments can bring together the idea of affect and emotion as a continuum, with practice, affect and health generating places (Foley, 2017).

5.11. Conclusion

What culture is good for, whether it is transformative or entrenches social inequalities depends on how it is defined and valued, which I suggest in the context of improving health and wellbeing is determined by ideas of health and society. Definitions of culture have been a site of shifting ideas of health and society and resisting orthodox thinking. Resistance has come through relational work and attention to making meaning with others, ideas that align with my proposal for the fifth wave of public health. My proposal for the fifth wave of public health to be characterised by diverse ways of knowing, would give more visibility and value to the knowledge of practitioners who undertake this relational and meaning-making work. Tending to the ontological and epistemological roots of my proposal for the fifth wave of public health, the focus on the relational and the everyday and a commitment to diversity in ways of knowing, develops the insight that conceptually the ideas of cultural democracy and emergent cultural and arts processes are fruitful for growing knowledge about the relationship between culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing.

In this chapter I develop the insight that the growth of the arts and health field and its increasing entanglement with urban regeneration policies creates possibilities for how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society. One possibility is that the move towards the fourth wave of public health could be facilitated by place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing ends. This move is necessary due to the stalling of health inequalities and the prevalence of the medical model that emerged in the third wave of public health. However, the dominance of fourth wave of public health approaches such as individualism, reductionism and causal narratives could be entrenched: as I have argued, the use of culture and the arts in policy for social purposes brings considerable ontological

and epistemological baggage. I suggest that this move towards the fourth wave of public health should not happen without there also being a move to the fifth wave of public health. So, another possibility is that a fifth wave of public health could emerge as culture and the arts could shift ideas of health and wellbeing through relational practice and through conceptualising culture and the arts as a core part of everyday meaningful activities. This could bring a focus on 'what matters' to accompany the 'what works' approach of the fourth wave of public health. Therefore, I grow the insight that it is of interest to understand what understanding and conceptualisations of culture gets drawn into place-based policy and to what health and wellbeing ends.

The need for my counter-conceptualisation work is shown by my examination of the claims for culture and the arts by advocates for the social benefits of participating in these activities. Advocates argue for a status of uniqueness for culture and the arts while at the same time claiming a swathe of activities as being cultural and arts-related activities. Therefore, culture and the arts occupy a position that is both elevated above other leisure pursuits and also presented as an activity everyone can do. This tussle with conceptions of culture and art in current arts and health research repeat tensions and discussions that have been enacted before such as in the use of culture in regeneration policy. My counter-conceptualisation work views culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing as everyday practices and an experience of living. Therefore, the fifth wave of public health needs to give conceptual room to value things as they are experienced and to attune to interactions that accumulate into health and wellbeing creating moments. An approach that leaves undimmed the wonder brought by culture and art, as well as the other meaningful activities that shape our lives and the health and wellbeing we experience. Through this approach, the process of becoming human can be centred in the fifth wave of public health and culture and arts-related activity could be more fully mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society.

I gain insights in this chapter into how might culture and the arts be mobilised to help shift ideas of health and wellbeing. I also gain insights from my counter-conceptualisation work that help me to view culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing as everyday practices and an experience of living. These insights equip me to undertake another research trail to gain insights into my research puzzle. I can now go on to grow knowledge relating to how culture and the arts activity is interacting with health and wellbeing in Paisley. This knowledge will grow insights to understand what activity Future Paisley is influenced by and could have an influence on in the context of health and wellbeing.

6. Following the thread of culture

6.1. Introduction

This chapter follows the research trail of exploring how cultural activity emerges in Paisley, how this activity encounters health and wellbeing and the current and possible future interaction of this activity with Future Paisley. This exploration grows knowledge about the research object, the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley.

I start this chapter with the view from Chapter 5, that culture is everyday and formed out of processes and practices that have meaning. I move on to consider how to conceptually develop this view in order to gain a perspective on how culture is formed at a collective level. Using this perspective, I linger on one encounter with cultural activity in Paisley that does not fit neatly into the categories of activities in the arts and health field. This encounter has resonance with my growing awareness that I have a practice of facilitating culture and the arts with mental health. This encounter starts my attunement into the relationship between community-centred health and cultural democracy. I provide more detail regarding community-centred health and the strategic context for community-centred health in Renfrewshire. Next, analysis is provided of how being attentive to community-centred health in Paisley also informs my observations about how cultural democracy emerges. These two topics are brought together through exploring everyday culture and health. I evaluate this process of community-centred health and cultural democracy in the context of the literature regarding cultural participation and cultural inclusion. I analyse how this process embeds culture in other sectors and services, examining how encounters of culture, arts, health, and wellbeing happen across sectors.

The research uses the empirical and theoretical insights grown to consider the possibilities for the strategic influence of these twin processes of community-centred health and cultural democracy. These possibilities are assessed to consider how cultural policy might achieve health and wellbeing goals and whether these goals can help a move towards the fifth wave of public health.

The chapter concludes by considering these possibilities in the context of the field of arts and health, to evaluate how the wider strategic context regarding arts and health shapes future activities in Paisley.

6.2. Resonance and research trails

Section 3.9.3 describes the process of resonance out of which research trails are formed. At the start of the research in 2019, I did not intend to seek out where culture emerge, as I had intended to

immerse myself in projects that used culture for health and wellbeing purposes. When this immersion did not happen and in summer 2021 reflecting on the knowledge I had grown, particularly the key sources of resonance in the table below, I found I had observed culture emerging from health and wellbeing activities. This observation resonated with empirical literature related to community arts. Situating this insight in theoretical and empirical texts, I found a contrast with the dominant approaches of artist-led activity in the literature. This insight turned into a line of inquiry and a research trail emerged in summer 2021 (Table 6.1).

Table 6.1: Resonance dimensions for the how cultural activity emerges in Paisley, encounters health and wellbeing and interacts with Future Paisley

Theory	Categories of arts and health
Empirical	Community arts, everyday understandings of culture and well-being
Paisley context	CAHSC, HSCP, TSI entanglements, UK Coc21 bid talked about as a community based bid
Brought selves	Evaluation and impact, volunteer grassroots mental health arts exhibition
Situationally created self	Critical friend regarding concepts of health and wellbeing
Policy	Future Paisley Step Change 2
Emergence of research trail	Summer 2021

Selected key sites of knowledge growing on the path of the research trail is given in Table 6.2. As described in Section 3.9.4 these sites show the key directional markers in Paisley that indicated that continuing the path that emerged from resonance would provide valid and meaningful insights through the relevance to policy, how this research trail is part of my everyday life and the perspectives I use to grow knowledge. The emerging nature of resonance and lines of inquiry means there is overlap between the two processes of growing knowledge. These sites are presented by type and in chronological order of when I became aware of them.

Table 6.2: Growing knowledge for the how cultural activity emerges in Paisley, encounters health and wellbeing and interacts with Future Paisley

<p>Key knowledge growing sites in Paisley</p>	<p>Renfrewshire Scottish Mental Health Arts Festival (Spring 2019)</p> <p>Interactions with HSCP (Spring 2019 to Spring 2022- including research encounters through CAHSC, SPG Connectedness Network and other meetings, emails and documents)</p> <p>Internal document provided through CAHSC Membership in August 2019 Case Study: Renfrewshire Model: a community and cultural response to Covid 19</p> <p>SPG Connectedness Network – attendance at group meetings and discussions with project officers (Autumn 2020 to Spring 2022)</p> <p>Scottish Government Community Mental Health and Wellbeing fund (Autumn 2021 – Autumn 2022: Scottish Government website, Engage Renfrewshire website, SPG Connectedness Network meetings in 2021-2022)</p> <p>CAHSC co-ordinator role (Internal document provided in October 2021 through CAHSC membership Proposal for Future Paisley Activity Plan Funding 2022-24, job advert, informal conversations and emails from Autumn 2021 to Autumn 2022)</p>
<p>Context in Scotland and elsewhere</p>	<p>Creative Scotland’s mapping of arts-related activity (Rocket Science, 2021)</p>
<p>Everyday sites</p>	<p>Living the concepts - asking friends and volunteering colleagues about their relationship with their local TSI and HSCP</p> <p>Volunteering as an evaluation professional and bringing my concepts into conversations such as affects and material (see Appendix 2)</p> <p>My practice of cultural democracy</p>
<p>Perspectives</p>	<p>Gatherings and happenings (Tsing, 2017)</p>

	<p>Typologies of culture, health and wellbeing (APPGAHW, 2017; Fancourt, 2017; Yoeli et al., 2020)</p> <p>Using culture to shift ideas of health and society (Section 5.10.3)</p>
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6.3. Thinking about culture

The Future Paisley policy document does not define culture and avoids conceptual entanglements. A lack of definition provides resistance to the selective tradition of culture (Williams, 1961; Oman, 2020), a tradition where what can be measured and surveyed shapes what culture is perceived to have value. This resistance is bolstered by the wide range of activities listed and the inclusion of everyday participation.

A conceptual guide is required to explore the everyday processes from which culture emerges, and where it encounters health and wellbeing at a collective level. This view then considers how culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing may be facilitated. Holden's (2015) cultural ecology approach defines culture as a happening, emerging from a gathering of possible things from people to opportunities, histories, resources, and policies. The lack of conceptual consensus about culture flows into the lack of consensus on a definition of cultural ecology (de Bernard, Comunian and Gross, 2021). Holden argues for the usefulness of the term cultural ecology by drawing on the move in the field of ecology from classification to environmental ecology, which focuses on wholeness and interdependencies. Culture is a social process (Holden, 2015). I go beyond the concept of cultural ecology as I consider 'we' through a nonhuman lens. Using ecological metaphors helps to move from a machinic and reductionist view of culture into organisms and wholes. My perspective of culture continues the tradition of drawing on ecological ideas through the concept of assemblage. Ecologists find assemblage thinking helpful in moving beyond the idea of the whole, which has connotations of a boundary (Tsing, 2017).

Culture is a mutual-making process, a view which corresponds with Kelly's (2017, p. 237) description of the ideas that have powered the Community Arts Movement, which take a 'more active view of human beings and society.' This view suggests that we make each other up, as we are more than interdependent on each other, as we are inexorably intertwined with each other. As I have argued through the consideration of the concept of One Health in Chapter 5, thinking without boundaries and therefore thinking about the enmeshment of entities opens up a more expansive view of complex processes. So again, I turn to relational thinking as a conceptual guide. Tsing provides me with helpful guidance in thinking with assemblages to move beyond cultural ecology. Tsing (2017, p.

23) defines assemblages as ‘open ended gatherings. They allow us to ask about communal effects without assuming them.’ Assemblage thinking allows Tsing to ask (2017, p. 23) ‘how do gatherings sometimes become “happenings” that is, greater than the sum of their parts?’ Tsing’s use of assemblages focuses on encounters and what emerges from them. Assemblages go beyond the idea of the whole in cultural ecology, as assemblages are an open-ended entanglement of ways of being, which in turn are emergent effects of encounters. Using the concept of enabling places, these encounters are not just social but also material and affective. The research trail I follow in this chapter orientates me to look out for the encounters that facilitate the emergence of culture. This search enables me to follow where the emergence of culture and health intertwine to find out what forms of culture facilitate the qualities, enabling conditions for the fifth wave of public health.

6.4. Looking for culture

Future Paisley’s strategic interest in health and wellbeing has been evolving. The interest was not yet articulated when this research started in 2019. As part of my first CCSE meeting, I was shown a document with Future Paisley’s Step Changes and associated outcomes. The strategic interest in health and wellbeing is not stated in the Step Changes described in Chapter 1, which have a range of social goals. Health and wellbeing related strategic outcomes come under the remit of Future Paisley’s Step Change 2, along with education, digital and deprivation-related outcomes. The health and wellbeing strategic outcomes are concerned with reducing alcohol and drug-related hospital admissions.

An interest in health and wellbeing can be inferred by the strategic structure, which designates CAHSC as the delivery group for Step Change 2. The remit and name of CAHSC and the lead of CAHSC by a healthcare partner, NHS Greater Glasgow, and Clyde (NHS GGC), place health and wellbeing at the centre of the delivery of this Step Change. The health and wellbeing strategic outcomes are of limited help in guiding the delivery of Step Change 2, as the outcomes are expressed as indicators and in Renfrewshire, there is already dedicated activity to tackling alcohol and drug-related issues¹⁴. To avoid duplication of roles, these issues are not the focus CAHSC. The lack of strategic guidance on the nature of health and wellbeing leads to culture and health encounters being defined through projects gathered into the remit of CAHSC. These projects show a mix of common typologies of culture and health encounters, such as social prescribing of culture, museum wellbeing, focus on

¹⁴ <https://publichealthreform.scot/latest-reform-news-and-blogs/renfrewshire-taskforce-takes-a-fresh-approach-to-tackle-alcohol-and-drug-use>

young people, and arts in healthcare settings (APPGAHW, 2017; Fancourt, 2017; Arts Council of Wales, 2018).

The development and delivery of these common typologies have taken time to emerge in Paisley. Future Paisley has consistently had an explicit interest in social isolation, providing a natural entry point for the social prescribing of culture to be part of cultural regeneration policy.

Renfrewshire Council in the aftermath of the UKCoC21 bid stated its continued commitment to the cultural regeneration of Paisley by committing to a variety of actions, including social prescribing (Crearie, 2018). In the action plan (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b) that evolved into the Future Paisley Document there is the outcome 'Have enhanced mental health and reduced social isolation in our communities and reduced addiction to alcohol and drugs.' Social prescribing already exists in Paisley, and I observe in CAHSC meetings a concern about duplicate existing activities. A Social and Cultural Prescribing Co-ordinator was appointed in autumn 2021, two and a half years after the start of my immersion in Paisley. The co-ordinator has a remit to develop a model for the cultural social prescribing service. The desire to not replicate existing activities in Paisley is also shown in the slow development of engagement with local artists, who may have an interest in health and wellbeing due to the existence of a network for local artists. In conversations with Paisley Museum, I observe that embedding wellbeing as a goal across the organisation is a discussion but not yet defined goal or activity. A personnel change disrupted the work of articulating and embedding health and wellbeing across the organisation. The change also disrupted my contribution to this work.

6.5. Beyond categories of culture

Renfrewshire Mental Health Arts Festival (RMHAF) does not fall into the typologies of culture and health encounters that are usually found in documents describing the field (APPGAHW, 2017; Yoeli *et al.*, 2020). RMHAF is the regional programme of the Scottish Mental Health Arts Festival (SMHAF), which started in 2007. SMHAF is held annually in May across Scotland. The festival describes itself as combining high-quality artistic events with community-led programming and a social justice agenda to support art and challenge perceptions of mental health¹⁵. The lead partner is a mental health charity, and key partners are mainly healthcare organisations, including NHS and HSCP organisations. RMHAF is led by RHSCP. RMHAF provides an example of cultural activity supported by healthcare funding and delivered by a third-sector organisation outside the cultural sector.

¹⁵ <https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/scotland/arts/scottish-mental-health-arts-and-film-festival-smhaff>

RMHAF has been part of Future Paisley's cultural programme since I first started my research. One of the first meetings I took to immerse myself in Paisley at the start of the research in 2019 was a planning meeting for that year's festival. Around the table were various local groups; some were creative activity-centred, and others were community-centred. SMHAF has personal meaning for me as the exhibition I volunteer with in my home city of Edinburgh used to be part of SMHAF and retains strong links with the festival. The Edinburgh exhibition I volunteer with exemplifies SMHAF's ethos as it grew out of a community-led project whose participants wanted to put on an exhibition to be heard, visible, and seen on their terms. An exhibition for people with lived in experience of mental health issues by people with lived in experience of mental health issues. In conversations with potential exhibitors, I find that the perception that a cultural or artistic output needs to be produced is, in some sense, a barrier to participation. The absence of criteria on what can be submitted removes the expectation or weight of having to 'produce' and 'create.' The exhibition offers a space for any medium of expression. Submissions are usually visual. There are also aural and text submissions. Cultural democracy is an intrinsic quality of this exhibition as there is no cultural authority or organisation involved or curatorial hierarchy. There are no demands deriving from the need to demonstrate health and wellbeing aims, themes or outcomes. The exhibition as a whole is an activist for the arts and mental health, being an activist, or taking an activist stance is not asked of exhibitors. The only requirement is that exhibitors describe themselves as having lived experience of mental health issues. To have explicit demands or requirements would be replicating the oppressive social structures that some participants take a stance against. Some of the artworks that have left a significant impression on me are critical of systems such as navigating the NHS, filling in surveys to assess wellbeing, and using brown envelopes. The absence of cultural, artistic, health, and wellbeing direction, parameters, and expectations does not hinder the opinion of some visitors that great art is produced, individually and as a collective. Participants are asked what the exhibition means to them. Accounts are given, some brief, others detailed, some poetic, others personal.

I avoid asking for impact due to the reductionist connotations of the term as used in evaluation practice. The term does not convey the nuance of how the exhibition can seep into people's everyday life and identity, becoming an integral part of everyday experience. Impact implies a starting point that culture and the arts are separate from health and wellbeing. It suggests thinking of these experiences as discrete bounded entities, with one entity acting on the other. This thinking is reinforced by visual representations of impact chains with boxes and arrows in the reductive schemata of 'patient pathways' and 'logic models.' Listening to exhibitors, I grew attentive to the plurality of ways of being in the world and how this is informed by participating in the exhibition.

This knowledge grounds and add life to my development of a conceptual view of health and wellbeing.

On reflection, this planning meeting for RMHAF 2019 was my first research step into community-centred health and the start of ‘knowing in’ the concept of cultural democracy. As I draw together my growing theoretical and empirical knowledge from both the field and my brought self, including a history of encounters with ‘arts and health’ practices such as those illustrated in the paragraph above, I start to become aware that I have a principle and practice of cultural democracy. In hindsight, this is where the erosion of my initial research focus started. My starting intention of taking apart people’s experiences to identify mechanisms for theoretical purposes sat in tension with accounts of how health and wellbeing emerge and interact with culture and the arts. I start thinking about the processes where culture, art, health, and wellbeing may emerge as well as how these processes can be purposely facilitated, designed or mapped out in advance.

6.6. Community-centred health

Community-centred health, by its nature, is a field that creates gatherings for health to happen. The meetings I attend in Paisley can be thought of as gatherings, therefore RHSCP is a creator of these gatherings. I observe the potential for culture, health, and wellbeing to emerge. The gatherings create conditions for emergence as people get to know each other. Links are formed and maybe followed up, the potential for an activity or an event is created as people weave into these potentials, different forms of culture or their creative practice or experience.

Paisley has many activities intertwining culture, arts, health, and wellbeing that represent many of the APPGHAW (2017) categories, from museums and wellbeing, art in hospitals, to social prescribing of culture. Community-centred health as a site of gatherings grew in my research through theoretical, practice, and observational encounters. I attended a multiple-day NHS Scotland training course on becoming an effective Health Improvement Practitioner in 2019. The course included training on community development and community-centred health. Public Health England’s (2015) report outlining community-centred approaches and common UK models provided the following diagram. In Paisley I observe many projects that fit into this diagram, from peer support to participatory budgeting.

Figure 6.1: Community-centred approaches for health and wellbeing and examples of common UK models (Public Health England, 2015)

My interest in loneliness and social isolation resulted in an invitation to be part of the Loneliness and Social Isolation RHSCP strategic priority subgroup in September 2020. ROAR: Connections For Life, a Paisley-based charity supporting older people's wellbeing through a range of health and wellbeing clubs and programmes, leads the subgroup. The subgroup is an example of a community-centred approach in partnership with community organisations. RHSCP SPG govern the subgroups. The RHSCP SPG is co-chaired by Engage Renfrewshire, the TSI for Renfrewshire responsible for developing relationships with third-sector partners. Members of the RHSCP felt the quality of the relationships within the RHSCP SPG to be central to the positive response to the challenges of the pandemic (Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Partnership, 2022). One method of developing relationships with community organisations is through health and wellbeing priorities being driven forward by the RHSCP SPG and a community partner (Figure 6.2). Loneliness and social isolation are one priority. Other priorities are inequalities, mental health and wellbeing, housing as a health issue, early years and vulnerable families, healthy and active living, and collaborating for greater impact.

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Figure 6.2: RHSCP priorities (Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Partnership, 2022)

My participation in the Loneliness and Social Isolation meetings revealed to me the presence of cultural and creative activities in organisations. Cultural and creative activities are one amongst various health and wellbeing approaches, from gardening to community fridges. I observe connections to Future Paisley are provided by some subgroup members who are also part of other groups, particularly CAHSC. The development of the subgroup paused due to a change of personnel with both the chair changing and the subgroup project officer moving on. The project officer role was filled at the end of 2021 through a role share between two people.

6.7. Everyday culture and health

In 2020, my interest in loneliness became known to organisations involved in CAHSC. I expressed an interest in being involved with or delivering a project to improve health and wellbeing. I wanted to apply assemblage thinking to loneliness. This involvement would provide an opportunity for 'knowing in' and 'knowing about' assemblages of loneliness. I would be immersed in the experience of how loneliness emerges in everyday encounters and influences people's feelings of being. I was put in touch with Renfrewshire Alcohol and Drug Recovery Service, which was delivering a new Recovery Hub in Paisley, as they were possibly looking for somebody to organise running groups. The Hub aims to be open every day from morning to evening. I was invited to attend a series of focus groups facilitated by peer staff and those involved in delivering recovery services. The purpose of the focus groups was to understand what those in recovery wanted from the Recovery Hub and plan the Hub's development, such as its name and logo. There were frequent conversations about what they would like to do, so that activities could be planned to meet their interests. I observed the type of

activity was less important than having something to do and a purpose. Creative activities such as photography came up in the conversations along with a variety of other activities. The Hub's opening was delayed. When I first joined meetings, it was anticipated that the Hub would open in early 2021. The Hub finally opened in November 2021. I observed in Paisley the network of partnerships, collaboration and close working practices in action as many organisations offered to work with the Hub, including Paisley Museum, Renfrewshire Arts Team and OneRen's leisure facilities. Conditions for the emergence of culture and the arts were forming.

The national government has recognised the role of grassroots community groups to a preventative health agenda. The Scottish Government allocated £0.5m to Paisley as part of its two-year Communities Mental Health and Wellbeing fund to support community-based ideas for adults to address the aftereffects of COVID-19, particularly social isolation, loneliness, and mental health inequalities. The fund targets grassroots charities, social enterprises, and community groups. It focuses on relationships by stating a focus on providing opportunities for people to connect, build trusted relationships and revitalise communities (Engage Renfrewshire, no date). In February 2022, the successful applicants to the Scottish Government Community Mental Health and Wellbeing fund were announced. Engage Renfrewshire received applications that totalled £1.2m (Engage Renfrewshire, no date). I observe a range of cultural and creativities emerge from this fund. Organisations that more explicitly deliver cultural and creative activities such as radio stations, community circus and art and music groups receive funding. Activities more traditionally considered creative also emerge from the funding of organisations with other social goals, such as the creation of a poetry book by Renfrewshire Anti-Stigma Alliance, a community craft programme delivered by Mossvale Community Church and art, music, and cookery sessions from Kickin' On, a grassroots, mental health, addiction, and suicide prevention peer support. The range of cultural and leisure activities span from gardening activity to walking groups and leisure classes is in alignment with Oman's (2020) analysis of free text boxes to the question of what in life matters to people. This fund is an example of culture emerging from preventative community-centred health funding. The range of projects and organisations funded shows the everydayness of health and wellbeing and the diversity of ways to mitigate mental health and develop relational health. The fund is delivered through TSIs. In Renfrewshire, a dedicated TSI staff member has been allocated to this fund. They are tasked with planning the next phase of the fund, evaluating activities, and developing the sector. They have also been at CAHSC meetings providing a link for this activity to interact with Future Paisley. One of the funded projects is ROAR, providing a link to RHSCP and the strategic activity to address loneliness and social isolation that is discussed in Chapter 7. This fund illustrates culture emerging from community-centred health initiatives connecting with cultural regeneration policy

through existing networks in Paisley. There is no focus on culture in this fund, so there is no hierarchy of culture or cultural authority. A focus on emergent culture challenges the selective tradition of culture and wellbeing policy, which values certain cultural activities as having a greater benefit to wellbeing and therefore is of greater value to policy makers (Oman, 2020). The provision of conditions for emergent culture enables cultural democracy to emerge. This fund illustrates how a wellbeing policy may encourage cultural activity that a policy focused on cultural production may be less likely to facilitate. My observation of the emergence of culture through this funding is a natural effect of what happens when people gather, if culture is seen through Braden's (1978, p. 174) description of culture:

'The truth is that *people make culture*. They make it in towns and cities, in villages and hamlets, in Hampstead and Hull. It is to do with self-expression and social needs. It is active, not passive. It is neither a sub-culture or an alternative. It is active and to be lived in rather than be passive and be appreciated.'

Paisley has a range of ways where cultural processes emerge from the community. I observe processes such as cultural emergence (emerging from the non-cultural activities of community groups), community-led (cultural activities of community organisations), community co-production (cultural organisations producing with communities), community and socially engaged artists, and community informed and engaged (cultural activities produced with community involvement or in response to community ideas). These processes cover a spectrum of cultural production from informal and unfunded cultural activity to funding related for the specific creation of cultural outputs such as the work of Renfrewshire Arts Team and Arts in Hospitals. These processes are fluid, potentially shifting from one type to another and merging into other types. Communities are involved at different levels of participation (Arnstein, 1969; Hart, 2008). A focus on partnership provides the opportunity for these processes of meeting and merging to occur, resulting in a fluid, dynamic, and active support for culture and the arts.

6.8. Culture, community and what matters

A focus on community-centred health means that rather than cold spots of culture, the focus is on cold spots of community. Cold spots are defined locally; I observed in conversations that characteristics of cold spots can include a lack of community gathering spaces or a place-based charity, places where barriers to accessing services is high or there are low levels of volunteering reported. COVID-19 showed organisational responsiveness to cold spots, with Neighbourhood Hubs (Coutts *et al.*, 2020) setting up a partnership between the Council, the HSCP and the third sector. The hubs were set up to respond to people's needs as a whole rather than using a hierarchal

approach to needs. People's requirements were identified, they ranged from grass cutting, to toys and dog walking. I find resonance between what people require and Oman's (2020) analysis of the free text box responses to the question of 'What things in life matter to you?' in the Measuring National Well-being Survey discussed in Chapter 5 in terms of the importance to people of casual leisure activities. The Hubs were set up with sixty volunteers, recruited and trained by the end of April 2020.

In a SPG Connectedness Network meeting, I hear the founder of a charity, set up during the COVID pandemic, recount how and why they started. They found the rural nature of their area created barriers to accessing services which are mainly located in urban areas, such as food banks or a well-established community charity such as the STAR Project, a community organisation project that is part of the Future Paisley Partnership Board. I hear familiar names as I listen to the founder tell their story of how they grew. Engage Renfrewshire provided support such as mentoring and connections to volunteering. They talked about how they aspired to be a baby STAR Project. They were effusive regarding the support they received and delighted to have a relationship with STAR Project.

My observations find that in community-centred health, culture and arts are not viewed as produced by a sector, organisation or particular individuals (Mackay et al., 2021). Production is too deliberate a term, a conscious making and staging of cultural output, rather than emergence from a collective expression. The value of culture is often viewed through economic or quality indicators (Mackay et al., 2021). This view does not give room for local understandings, valuing of culture, how people feel, and how they empower people (Mackay et al., 2021). I observe a theme in conversations in workshops to develop Future Paisley's Step Change 2, that activities are not primarily intended to make people consume culture or increase participation. Consumption and participation have been a feature of cultural policy in the UK and reinforced through indicators such as those used in the Scottish National Framework (Scottish Government, 2018b). These indicators measure attendance at cultural events or places of culture and participation in cultural activity. Answers to a national government survey provide data for the measures. There is no prescriptive idea of what culture is in Future Paisley, both in statement and in delivery. For example, I observe in a report on the community and culture response to COVID in Renfrewshire covers grass cutting, litter picking, dog walking, and prescription pick-ups. These are activities not included as a cultural activity in the Scottish Government indicator for culture, highlighting the tension on whether everyday, mundane activities have cultural worth (Oakley and Ward, 2018; Oman, 2020). As cultural democracy does not presupposes what culture is, thinking with cultural democracy results in a constant exploration of what culture is valued. Amongst the Renfrewshire Arts Team, I do not hear dialogue about forms of

culture. The conversation is about what the community wants, what the community needs, how do they know that something useful and meaningful is being done?

I asked interviewees about the UKCoC21 bid about what culture meant to people. They found that the bid enabled dialogue with young people about what culture means to them and helped create a sense that culture was not something remote. During workshops related to the development of Step Change 2 people talked about cultural activity targeted at young people. I observed again the theme of making culture feel like something they could belong to. This feeling could contribute to removing conceptual barriers to culture.

Understanding how to facilitate the sense that culture belongs to people, even if they do not participate, puts a focus on practice. This focus contributes to attuning to everyday life. For example community can be viewed as a practice by individuals in their everyday life (Jackson, 2020). Observing the emergence of culture in the landscape of community-centred health, where empowering people is usually part of practice and an aim, counteracts the idea of culture being produced and consumed.

6.9. Culture and weaving assets

I find these incidences of grassroots approach to embedding culture in health and wellbeing resonates with the idea of art as a catalyst found in community arts (Crummy, 2017). Community art is a term that encompasses a range of approaches (Bennett, 2017). The approach driven by community development rather than the involvement of artists has resonance with the grassroots approach to culture encountered in this research stream. A belief that people create their own culture, individually and collectively. I suggest the creation of encounters between processes of culture, arts, health, and wellbeing through community-centred health, which increases the likelihood that a cultural democracy approach to culture can emerge. The focus increases the likelihood that practices that attend to relational health will emerge. COVID-19 has highlighted the importance of a network of community-health activity and that the health and care system is wider than the HSCP, therefore collaborative, cross-sector working is required (Head of Strategic Planning and Health Improvement for Renfrewshire, 2021). This collaborative work provides the foundation for Scottish Government's Communities Mental Health and Wellbeing Fund, which builds on the community response to the pandemic which kept people connected.

The relationships between community organisations weave threads for an asset-based approach. The more threads that exist, the more health and wellbeing processes can be woven. The greater the diversity of threads, the greater the quality, and the richer and more robust the cloth will be. An

asset-based approach picks the most useful thread. In Paisley this thread is culture. In other places the thread could be nature, food, or a historical narrative. Paisley's radical history is drawn into its culture. The Sma' Shot festival is held annually in Paisley. This event celebrates the 1856 victory of local shawl weavers dispute with manufacturers. One of the inspirations for Paisley Book festival are the Paisley Radicals who in 1820, the series of meetings and strikes created an uprising demanding better wages and conditions (Paisley Book Festival, no date). An openness to describing assets leads to organic connectivity from cultural activity to other social challenges. I hear about the Ethnic Communities Cultural Steering Group, an alliance which co-produces, programmes, and curates work relevant to the region's ethnic minority communities. The group have a strong interest in health and wellbeing and would like to work on this topic. Other encounters with ethnic minorities groups occur, for example the previous SPG Connectedness Network project officer volunteered with and now is employed with Pachedu, a charity established in 2016, working with ethnic minority groups to promote diversity, tolerance and dignity for humanity. In a meeting with Paisley Museum, I hear of a museum project with Jambo! Radio, Scotland's only African-Caribbean Radio Station, based in Renfrewshire. The project seeks to support four heritage trainees over 18 months to produce a series of heritage-themed radio programmes for their communities and listeners. Through these examples and others, I see culture threading into other Renfrewshire assets and other societal issues.

The following of community-centred health provides the research with an insight into the greater involvement of RHSCP in the health and wellbeing activities of Future Paisley and bringing culture, arts, health, and wellbeing together more widely. The Partnership Board in 2018 has NHSC GCC as the only public sector health-focused organisation and as the chair of CAHSC. RHSCP was appointed as the lead of CAHSC in January 2020 when the network was reorganised with the intent to be more strategically focused. The change in leadership was made to provide a stronger focus on local activity. A senior strategic staff member of RHSCP now chairs the network.

6.10. Pop up possibilities

The assemblage approach sees 'multiple futures pop in and out of possibility' (Tsing, 2017, p. viii). Paisley is in the midst of its cultural regeneration strategy. In hindsight, my research follows an interim phase of this strategy. Between the initial setting down of the text and the delivery body of the strategy, and when the text and delivery bodies take on a more settled form and are more aligned with each other. Added to this interim phase is the disruption of responding to COVID-19. My research ended at a time when new activities were starting. I hear in strategic conversations about the desire to think differently about public services, which can be thought of as potential

futures and enactments. Potentials allow room for experimentation and failure. Potential gives people agency instead of shepherding them towards an outcome. Temporality is acknowledged that this is one moment amongst many. Potential fits well with the capability approach that informs assemblages of health (Duff, 2014). I observe much of the work with young people is about increasing the imagining of potential futures. The admission of potential is the admission of a future and an admission of hope, which is an important affective resource for health generating places, particularly for those in the recovery process (Brijnath, 2015). Assemblage thinking gives conceptual room for possibilities. The changing form of possibilities is the essence of prevention, as one possible life path becomes less probable and different ones grow in possibility. Possibilities offer the potential for transformation. Staff involved in an art project with young people ask in a workshop how we can know what effect this project may have in 20 years? A participatory evaluation with young people for Creative Scotland (Media Education, Nugent and Deacon, 2020) answers by focusing on what can we know, letting participants tell their stories in ways which felt meaningful to them so the experience of evaluation is beneficial to their lives and participants are happy to keep returning with updates.

I suggest community-centred health as the focus for encounters for culture and health makes it an amenable setting for the culture suggested by Kelly (1985), which arise from communities, through common meanings and common purposes. Creative acts help shape this description of culture, and these can range from jokes, informal sports, and dance music. Research has also shown how these creative acts such as jokes and common purpose also create atmospheres and resources that facilitate enabling places that generate health (Anstiss, Hodgetts and Stolte, 2018). As community-centred health focuses on these everyday creative acts, on communities and individuals representing themselves through culture, community-centred health provides an approach to the question of how might cultural democracy be facilitated through policy? The delivery of Future Paisley's health and wellbeing agenda through community-centred health, brings into focus the currents of community-led and community-engaged activities occurring in Paisley in different areas, and driven by different agendas.

6.11. Arts and health landscape

I find that the description of a fluid community-centred health landscape with multiple processes of emergence of culture is wider than the arts and health field, which focuses on artist-led activities. Yoeli et al. (2020, p. 91) define this field as an arts and health movement with artists operating as arts and health practitioners and arts and health is a 'relational and process driven tool for individual empowerment, collective health activism and social change.' This movement has not emerged in

Paisley due to the slow development of engaging artists in this area. Developing a network of artists has been suggested, however care is being taken to consider how this fits with existing artists' networks.

Creative Scotland's mapping of arts-related activity, that is designed to enhance health and wellbeing, focus on professional artists (Rocket Science, 2021) and those with a health-related condition or illness, the wider public, and the healthcare workforce. The field of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing are narrower than the activities this research has found in Paisley. This narrowness creates tension with cultural democracy. I observe how activities in Paisley demonstrates how partnership, and a community-centred approach provides room for a multitude of activity.

The questions asked in the mapping survey related to three areas: how Creative Scotland could support survey participants, what their ambitions were for a health and wellbeing agenda, and challenges and barriers to delivering an arts and health and wellbeing agenda. Concerns relating to evaluation processes were found to be a theme across the three areas. The report recommends responding to the evaluation-related needs and concerns expressed. I suggest that an uncritical response could perpetuate the dominance of measurement and standardised evaluation approaches. A full understanding of work in arts and health that reflects the depth and richness of practice would not be found in this potential future.

The Creative Scotland report notes that organisations need a strong TSI to help build partnerships with HSCPs as art organisations have limited engagement with HSCPs. Creative Scotland provide no details on what is meant by a strong TSI. Paisley offers learning on what 'strong' could mean and how this informs the landscape for culture, arts, health, and wellbeing. The role of a 'strong' TSI in building partnerships that contribute to the development of arts and health activity in Scotland is beyond what is suggested in Creative Report as TSIs, as defined in Chapter 1, were created to do more than share services and enhance participation. This chapter has demonstrated what this role could be and its contribution to culture, arts, health, and wellbeing in Paisley through my encounters with Engage Renfrewshire both directly and indirectly.

6.12. Conclusion

In this chapter I grow insights into how culture and the arts-related activity might be mobilised to contribute to a shift in thinking about health and society. Paisley shows how investment in community-centred health leads to the emergence of everyday cultural experiences that Oakley (2015) argues should be the starting point for area-based regeneration. Health, seen through the

lens of community-centred health, can conceptually be seen as practices of everyday being such as practices of community and belonging rather than health as something identified and to be achieved.

I develop the insight of viewing community-centred health as a nurturer of everyday culture, arts, and wellbeing encounters creates conditions for cultural democracy which can be viewed as a relational approach to working, a way of closing distance between people by being where they are. Creating connections by starting where people are naturally infuses connections with meaning which in turn makes the conditions for relational health. Community-centred health and cultural democracy can be mutually benefiting processes emerging together from a focus on 'what matters,' which I have argued contributes to a shift in thinking about health and society. My observations in Paisley gains insights into how further mobilisation of culture and the arts can be achieved. In Paisley there is a multiplicity in how culture emerges, that accumulate through an interlinking of processes of emergence through relationships between people and organisations. In this multiplicity there is an emphasis on community-centred approaches to culture, both in explicit cultural production and in emergence from community activities.

My insights contribute to how culture and arts-related activity might be mobilised to contribute to a shift in thinking about health and society as the consideration of emergent processes of culture has been less of a feature of arts and health in the UK. This field has tended to focus on artist-led activity.

I gain insights into how place-based policies in Scotland might be designed to use culture and the arts for social ends and grow a health and wellbeing dimension. These insights grow from knowledge of how these processes of community-centred health and cultural democracy interact with Future Paisley. In my time in Paisley, RHSCP and its community-centred health activities become more involved in Future Paisley. This involvement is layered and connected with Engage Renfrewshire's engagement with the local third sector and involvement with Future Paisley at both strategic and delivery level. This layering creates multiple possibilities for third sector organisations to interact with Future Paisley, either directly or indirectly. Interactions that are created by this layering are enhanced by the strong partnership between RHSCP and Engage Renfrewshire.

The following of the research trail of how cultural activity emerges in Paisley and the current and possible future interactions with Future Paisley has led me to observe constellations of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing activity in Paisley, in their dynamic and holistic form. Insights into my research proposal and research puzzle emerge from bringing these observations together with my proposal for the fifth wave of public health, my counter-conceptualisation work and my investigation

of my research puzzle, the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley. In order to centre processes of becoming human in my insights I now need to fold in experiential knowledge of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing as everyday practices.

7. Loneliness as a public health issue

7.1. Introduction

In this chapter, I follow up my argument for the importance of including experiential knowledge in research and policy as part of the wider argument that my proposal for the fifth wave of public health is characterised by diverse ways of knowing. I use loneliness as a public health issue as a site of investigation for exploring the experience of loneliness and how this experience encounters the research puzzle of the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley.

I start with the heart of my proposal for the fifth wave of public health by elaborating on what ‘becoming human’ means to my research and my investigation into loneliness as a public health issue.

I argue that understanding what a place-based policy can do to achieve its health and wellbeing objectives requires conceptually exploring the nature of the problem. The previous chapters of this thesis have highlighted how policy and the experience of health and wellbeing might be misaligned. I have proposed the fifth wave of public health as relational health to attune policy to the experience of health and wellbeing.

In this chapter I explore this alignment by following the research trail of seeking out experiences of loneliness and how loneliness is discussed and treated as a policy challenge in Paisley, in academic literature, and through my brought selves. I use my conceptual exploration of loneliness to ‘know through’ health and wellbeing as emerging from everyday life. ‘Knowing through’ loneliness helps assess how the experience of loneliness and everyday life aligns with conceptualisations of loneliness in policy and practice. The AHRC Cultural Value report (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016) states that we should start with people’s own experiences when considering how projects and policies perform. Following this research trail leads to viewing how the entanglement of culture and loneliness as policy can provide insight into my research aim of shifting thinking about health and wellbeing.

This chapter starts the research trail by evolving my conceptual view of loneliness developed in Chapters 4 and 5. This view provides the argument of why observing loneliness as a public health issue is relevant to answering the research question and understanding the fifth wave of public health.

I trace the policy presence of loneliness in Paisley since the UKCoC21 bid through participant observation and documents. The chapter then explores how loneliness is used as a rationale for the

role of culture and arts in health and wellbeing through the idea of social prescribing. This activity has become a key component of the field of arts and health. This chapter assesses my observations of the development of social prescribing through my argument for a focus on relational health and loneliness as everyday experience. This takes me to explore the alignment between loneliness as conceptualised by policy, practices to tackle loneliness, and loneliness as experienced. I use my suggestions for gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts to investigate whether these concepts can contribute to the process of alignment and centre a concern with processes of becoming human.

7.2. Resonance and research trails

Section 3.9.3 describes the process of resonance out of which research trails are formed. My theoretical work became interested in ‘senses’ of feelings’ (Section 4.3.6). Loneliness emerged as the ‘sense of’ feeling that would be the site for my research to explore health and wellbeing. This emergence was due to resonance (Table 7.1) and emerged in the summer of 2020 when I brought my focus on loneliness to a CAHSC meeting and there was interest in my research direction.

Table 7.1: Resonance dimensions for loneliness as a public health issue

Theory	Convivial spaces, loneliness as a cluster of emotions, non-human ontologies, categories of loneliness
Empirical	Critical approaches to social prescribing, experiences of loneliness, the art of becoming human (Ravetz and Gregory, 2018)
Paisley context	Development of social prescribing, Renfrewshire Connected Champions Project, RHSCP strategic priorities, co-production in Paisley, creating places of belonging through Paisley Museum and Recovery Hub, Future Paisley Step Change 2 development
Brought selves	Volunteering to create spaces that people feel like they belong, personal moments of creating conviviality with strangers
Situationally created self	Critical friend regarding concepts of loneliness, providing information on the latest research and projects relating to social prescribing
Policy	Future Paisley - Step Change 2, national loneliness strategy
Emergence of research trail	Summer 2020

Selected key sites of knowledge growing on the path of the research trail is given in Table 7.2. These sites are presented by type and in chronological order of when I became aware of them.

Table 7.2: Growing knowledge for loneliness as a public health issue

<p>Key knowledge growing sites in Paisley</p>	<p>Future Paisley Step Change 2 and subsequent development (Spring 2019 – Spring 2021)</p> <p>Interest in social prescribing observed in meetings in CAHSC meetings (Spring 2019)</p> <p>Interactions with HSCP (Spring 2019 to Spring 2022- including research encounters through CAHSC, SPG Connectedness Network and other meetings, emails and documents)</p> <p>Internal document provided through CAHSC Membership in August 2019 Case Study: Renfrewshire Model: a community and cultural response to Covid 19</p> <p>CAHSC meetings (Summer 2020)</p> <p>Paisley Museum (Summer 2020 -Autumn 2022 – meetings with strategic staff members, meeting with workstreams, literature and webinars signposted by Museum, discussion, observation and documents of Listening Project, discussion with staff in a working with the community role, Paisley Museum website and social media accounts)</p> <p>SPG Connectedness Network – attendance at group meetings and discussions with project officers (Autumn 2020 to Spring 2022)</p> <p>Social prescribing co-ordinator role (Future Paisley Strategic Outcomes workshop Spring 2021 SPG Connected Network meetings Spring and Summer 2021, discussion in October 2021, Internal document provided in October 2021 through CAHSC membership Proposal for Future Paisley Activity Plan Funding 2022-24)</p> <p>Scottish Government Community Mental Health and Wellbeing fund (Autumn 2021 – Autumn 2022: Scottish Government website, Engage Renfrewshire website, SPG Connectedness Network meetings in 2021-2022)</p>
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Context in Scotland and elsewhere	Scottish Government Connected Strategy (Scottish Government, 2018a)
Everyday sites	<p>Personal everyday experiences of conviviality and connection</p> <p>Volunteer role gathering exhibition participants experiences of what the exhibition means to them</p> <p>Volunteer role curating exhibition with love and care and immersing in people’s representations of the everyday and what they connect to</p>
Perspectives	<p>Andersson’s trivialism (Ratner, 2015)</p> <p>Existential feelings (Section 4.3.6)</p> <p>Social, emotional and existential loneliness (Section 4.5.2)</p> <p>Tensions between experiential knowledge of loneliness and academic literature and policy knowings of loneliness (Section 4.5.3 and 4.5.4)</p>

7.3. Loneliness as a challenge of living

‘It is hard being a human,’ says a character in Roy Andersson’s film (2001), *Songs from a Second Floor*. A sentence that chimes with Illich’s (2003) warnings of society’s attempts to take away pain from the experience of living. A warning that could apply to considering loneliness as a public health issue. While Chapter 4 shows no conceptual consensus regarding the pain of loneliness, there is agreement that it hurts. I think with Andersson’s films during my conceptual explorations to build a proposition and conceptual toolkit for the fifth wave of public health. Andersson’s focus on what he calls trivial moments (Lindqvist, 2010; Ratner, 2015), I suggest, can show the beauty in the everyday, and reveal how our environment, society, social constructs, and histories are folded into the day-to-day to form our individual and collective existence. These moments I suggest in Chapter 5, show how global forces weave into the narratives and relationships that co-constitute our lives. A view of life the fourth wave of public health is not equipped to illuminate (Williams, 2003). Andersson’s characters are lonely: socially, emotionally, and existentially, usually trapped in a tableau of mundanity. Sometimes with others, in a visual depiction of the loneliness of being in a crowd. His films resonate with my ideas about the fifth wave of public health; loneliness is a condition of living found in the humdrum and in intensities. Mitigating loneliness is not solely a matter of identification and solution (Chapter 4). These are the solutions of individualistic thinking that have a lineage from

the health behaviours school of thought where aspects of ourselves, such as our size or thoughts, are an aberration from the norm. I suggest that loneliness is more than a matter of improving people's social participation (Chapter 4 and 5). My proposed gateway concept (Section 4.4.3), enabling place, seeks to increase the possibilities of material, social and affective encounters that provide opportunities for connections and accumulate to an experience of everyday life that is relationally richer. *Being a human person*, the title of a documentary about Roy Andersson (*Being a Human Person*, 2020), I take being as a verb, as an action, so I think with the term of 'becoming human' as introduced in Chapter 4.

My proposition for the fifth wave of public health is that it should be concerned with how we can be in the world together. This concern brings into focus when you feel out of togetherness with the world, when the relationship is strained and remote, yet still defined by the other, as you are estranged from something. Loneliness, though it can be felt as an intensely personal experience (Chapter 4.5), has its effect at the population level, not just statistically, but how we are collectively together, both constituted by and being constituents of other feelings such as sense of stigma, purpose and belonging. Therefore, while this research trail is focused on loneliness, it also acknowledges the inseparableness of loneliness from other existential feelings.

7.4. Loneliness as a policy challenge

Loneliness and social isolation have evolved into a policy concern for Future Paisley. In April 2021, a workshop was held to review Step Change 2, 'Lifting Paisley's communities out of poverty' and the associated strategic outcomes. A new Step Change was proposed in 2021 'Raise prosperity and increase wellbeing in our communities' with an attached outcome of 'Enhanced mental health and reduced social isolation in our communities.'. Based on my conceptual work (Chapter 4.5), I raised the question of whether loneliness should be included with social isolation because addressing social isolation does not always translate into addressing loneliness (Burholt, Nash and Phillips, 2013). In addition, I raise concerns that focusing on loneliness obscures the conceptual differences between types of loneliness (Dahlberg and McKee, 2014), leaving undisturbed the greater focus on social loneliness than emotional loneliness (Mansfield *et al.*, 2019). The outcome now has loneliness instead of social isolation.

Social prescribing has been defined as a development of national importance in arts and health development (Clift, Phillips and Pritchard, 2021). In Paisley, developing a social prescribing project has been a key interest of CAHSC since the group's inception (Chapter 6). The concern of duplicating existing social prescribing activity has resulted in the social prescribing of culture taking a while to emerge. A Social and Cultural Prescribing Co-ordinator was appointed in 2021.

My involvement with the RHSCP subgroup Loneliness and Social Isolation, discussed in Chapter 6, led me to find, through documents, emails, and conversations with members, that there is a history of community-centred and peer approaches to tackling loneliness in Paisley. RAMH, a charity that promotes recovery from mental ill health, led the Renfrewshire Connected Champions Project in 2020. The project used a peer-led approach to support others to overcome the barriers to social connectedness. The champions' main role was to increase community awareness of loneliness and social isolation issues by increasing knowledge and information about local community groups, activities, and services within Renfrewshire. I find in documents a history of research undertaken in October 2017 and March 2018 by ACUMEN and RAMH on social connectedness within Renfrewshire. The highest loneliness scores came from those who identified mental health problems as barriers to social connectedness. The research identified the importance of providing information on local services, including formal and informal peer support, to build people's confidence in accessing services. The research noted that one of the key aspirations for individuals was to form more meaningful relationships. I find in RHSCP's previous strategic plan for 2019-2020 that priorities are co-created with staff, service users, and partners, including tackling isolation and further embedding their social prescribing model (Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Partnership, no date).

I observed in documents that RHSCP had identified loneliness and social isolation as priority issues. This focus is informed by results from Renfrewshire's Health and Wellbeing Survey 2017/18, which showed that 1 in 14 (7%) residents felt isolated from family and friends, rising to 15% in the most deprived areas. A Short Life Working Group was set up in May 2019, with members from the public sector and third, and a joint report between RHSCP and RAMH was created in October 2019, representing the thoughts of its members. Perlman and Peplau's (1981) description was used in the report to define loneliness. The report considered that the group's vision should be of connectedness rather than loneliness due to the negative connotations of loneliness. The group views loneliness as an issue that crosses all society as the contributing factors, and the implications of loneliness are beyond healthcare. Therefore, the group go on to say that addressing loneliness requires the co-ordinated efforts of all of society to work together. I find the group's opinions show a societal conceptualisation of loneliness beyond the standard individual-centric view of loneliness. For example, in social prescribing research and programmes, there is a stronger focus on individuals and less on the capacity of groups and the voluntary and the third sector to welcome new participants and create a sense of belonging.

A year later, the RHSCP strategic priority Loneliness and Social Isolation subgroup, as introduced in Chapter 6, is formed and names itself the SPG Connectedness Network. The growing presence of culture and arts activity in Paisley can be seen through the changing membership of the groups. The

Working Group had no cultural workers or representatives from cultural organisations. The current subgroup has had representation from Paisley Museum and OneRen. I was invited to join by a member of RHSCP.

ROAR: Connections For Life, the lead third sector organisation for the SPG Connectedness Network has received funding from the first fund of Scottish Government's Communities Mental Health and Wellbeing fund introduced in Chapter 6. This entanglement demonstrates a process of how a concern with loneliness and social isolation emerges out of community-centred health and national policy concerns with loneliness and how this concern entangles with culture and the arts.

The links to culture have been strengthened by the appointment of the Social and Cultural Prescribing Co-ordinator for culture in mid-2021 by OneRen. This post creates a link to Future Paisley with activities addressing loneliness in Paisley. OneRen's current business strategy puts health and wellbeing at its core compared to its previous business plan. Under the strategic objective of a healthier community, social prescribing is one of the actions (Renfrewshire Leisure, 2021). Linkages to culture and the arts, have also happened organically. The first project officer for the group has moved on, and the post of project officer is shared between two people with a professional background in the cultural sector. These roles are newly appointed as of the end of 2021.

Knowledge grown about loneliness as a policy interest in Paisley has led to the insight that this interest has arisen out of a community-centred health context, made its way into the strategic concerns of organisations and networks in Paisley and now is a key health and wellbeing priority for Future Paisley as part of one of the three outcomes attached to Step Change 2. Following the path of loneliness as a policy challenge grows knowledge about how the agenda of cultural organisations has become entwined with loneliness as a public health issue at an organisational level, partnership level, and policy level.

7.5. Loneliness and the everyday

Academic research that has suggested social prescribing as a policy recommendation (Hammoud *et al.*, 2021; Mughal *et al.*, 2021) does not always draw on the everyday nature of loneliness and does not acknowledge the complexity of loneliness. Social prescribing focuses on linking individuals to community assets and takes less account of everyday culture, such as being free to potter and to hang out, which may lead to a narrow view of how activities become meaningful. Social prescribing may have a limited view of what entities we can connect with. COVID-19 has shown how these resources intermingle: I have found through my activities during the lockdown period of COVID-19,

that activities such as virtual races, plant swap groups to litter picking have the potential to combine various practices relating to a sense of place and draw in nonhuman and social connections.

Andersson uses trivialism to articulate why his films focus on mundane moments such as putting on clothes and eating as a way to answer existential moments, we are all in this world together, and trivial moments create a focus on our common existence (Hanke, 2019). Blokland and Jackson (2022) suggest that spaces that facilitate 'trivial' activities matter to people as 'they nurture unplanned, unorganised and spontaneous forms of casual exchanges, and have the potential to foster belonging and recognition.' In Andersson's films and Jackson's research, the trivial matters as the trivial is a place where practices of belonging form. In particular, those who describe themselves with no other person to talk to are more likely to talk to familiar others at bars, cafes and sports grounds than those who describe themselves as having somebody (Blokland and Jackson, 2022). The importance of Blokland and Jackson's descriptions resonates with my experience of how the trivial alleviates social isolation and loneliness, and draws me closer to the world. I am the third in the queue when my local café opens after the first lockdown. The relief and delight of its reopening, by the two people ahead of me matched my own as we enacted Jackson's convivial scenes, and atmospheres of sociality were being remade. The term 'places to be' is a phrase I encounter. One site of encounter is a report by Voluntary Health Scotland that presents the findings of a qualitative study to investigate loneliness and social isolation experienced by under-represented demographics in Scotland. The report illuminates experiences of loneliness and social isolation. People spoke about 'places to be' as somewhere social contact could be made and community developed and could range from their homes, the local park, and shops they enjoy visiting (Zubairi, 2018).

7.6. Loneliness and the conceptual toolkit

I suggest in Chapter 4 that loneliness as a public health issue is a useful site of investigation to explore the importance of concepts to policy and the tensions that arise when some concepts crowd out others. I argue that the underlying influence of looking at the social dimension in policy from the social determinants of health, social capital, to social infrastructure leads to an unbalance between material, social and affective resources, and a narrow view of loneliness. The conceptual tangle with social isolation emphasises social loneliness over emotional loneliness and existential loneliness. In Paisley, I observe social prescribing is one of a range of connected activities addressing loneliness, thus mitigating the potential narrowness of a social prescribing approach. I find that OneRen's Social and Cultural Prescribing Co-ordinator for culture has the freedom to scope out their own approach to social prescribing. They start their job by meeting with a range of people who might be relevant to their role to understand what is happening already in terms of social isolation, loneliness and culture

and people's view of their role. I hear in conversations about how roles related to Future Paisley's cultural programme are about layering activities, of activities adding to what is already in existence and drawing in knowledge and relationships. Social prescribing is an additional thread to be woven into the asset-based workings of Paisley.

A critical approach to loneliness does not mean minimising the importance of social relationships. Duff's (2012) research into resources for recovering from mental illness found that the most important resources are social in character. The importance of social resources is shown at a general population level. In 2020, I had conversations with staff from the Neebors project (Figure 7.1), an outreach art project of the Scottish National Gallery that engaged with North Ayrshire Health and Social Care Partnership. Thousands of people took part, and I could take a Neebor home with me. My conversations with project staff indicated that many Neebors were like mine, that one of the main wants was friendship.

Figure 7.1: Lan Pham (2020) Photograph of Neebors exhibit and an individual Neebor

I suggest in Chapter 4 that taking a critical approach to loneliness means taking a conceptual view of health and wellbeing that gives space to the importance of nonhuman connections in order to account for the range of people’s experiences in what makes them well. A report (Mughal *et al.*, 2021) into the community response to COVID-19 reports responses to a survey question, ‘what did you do in your free time during COVID-19 restrictions?’ The most popular answer was ‘Other’ (26%), which includes singing, DIY, films, games/gaming, mindfulness, dog walking and pets, visiting nature, studying, and quizzes. One in ten reported gardening, which includes houseplants. These responses I find resonates with Oman’s (2020) analysis of free text boxes in response to what matters to people in life and make visible the ‘ordinary’ cultural practices that are side-lined as evidence for what people value as important to their wellbeing.

These responses also resonate with my practice of facilitating the entanglement of culture, the arts and mental health. Annually I take on the task of being part of the curating group of the exhibition I volunteer with. A role that requires a deep immersion in the submissions. A practice of care and a belief in reciprocal love means a relationship is formed with each piece. Every year there is a strong

nonhuman theme. The role of nature in people's wellbeing varies from the reflectiveness that pausing and paying attention to nature can provide, to activist statements about climate change, and individual connections to the more-than human. Pets and flowers are often subjects. A common theme is how being in nature helps with wellbeing, sometimes just immersing in a natural environment, sometimes through activities from wild swimming to walking. The exhibition provides diverse perspectives on the human experience. Without a nonhuman perspective, the exhibition would be much smaller in scale and encompass less of the experience of becoming human.

I bring my nonhuman perspective to the SPG Connectedness Network meeting when they reveal their new logo of interlinked hands. The project is to be called Well Connected, and I ask if humans are the only thing people connect to? My fifth wave of public health lens takes the view that the process of becoming human and centring experience is not the same as centring humans which reinforces human exceptionalism. My critical approach to loneliness contributes to a commitment to cultural democracy as it aligns with the focus on what matters to people and what they find meaningful. I subsequently find out that the Well Connected logo now includes icons that relate to nature, animals, digital and place.

I am attentive to the nonhuman dimension, as using my conceptual approach, I could consider myself as a more-than-human collective of plants and dogs. Being a collective means my relating to others, and my sense of being in the world is altered. As strangers share stories with me due to the dog: on buses, in streets, in pubs, of the often-repeated phrase, dogs are better than humans, they are kinder, straightforward in their relating and make people feel seen. I live my concepts in my everyday life. Drawing on my conceptual approach Luca, my dog, could be a mobile affective resource, circulating affect between us and passersbys, building to an atmosphere of sociality and safety, where personal thoughts can potentially be shared. He is also a material resource of warmth and weight, encouraging tactile moments that facilitate wellbeing. Sometimes not much is said beyond a thank you for being the highlight of their day. For myself and passerbys, wellbeing occurs through a collapsing of boundaries between ourselves and Luca, and moments of intimacy occur, which are part of what Mason (2017) terms as affinities, where we inhabit Luca's orientation to the world and feel part of something bigger. Mitigating loneliness needs an attunement to everyday life to sense affinities and moments of material, social, and affective encounters, which build how people live and become well together and therefore view culture in its nonhuman dimensions.

The feeling of something bigger through engaging with plants and animals was felt by participants in a research project 'Wonderland; the art of becoming human' (Ravetz and Gregory, 2018). In the Wonderland project, recoverists is a term seeking to humanise the experience of those with

substance abuse. Recoverists sometimes feel they are treated as subhuman. The process of becoming human can be for some, an expression of ‘the political and affective need to be treated as valuable, equal and without stigma’ and ‘becoming more connected with transformative versions of being human, more ecologically and sociologically just, and more vibrant and feeling’ (Ravetz and Gregory, 2018, p. 367). I find this quote aligns with my proposals for thinking about health and wellbeing, such as my concept of existential feelings, my suggestion of making the affective dimension more visible, of connection to the nonhuman as well as the human. This quote shows how open and connective conceptual approaches to health and wellbeing reveal the interconnectivity of a range of fifth wave of public health issues such as depression and environmental issues. This approach is not about identifying and treating causes of health and wellbeing, but about making visible processes of transformation in order to consider how these processes may be facilitated.

These entanglements between culture, place, social, and nonhuman are seen in Paisley, where my observations suggest that having a gardening project is part of an aspiring social hub. Paisley Museum is considering a garden, both for health and wellbeing and for public programming purposes. I observe that creating an accessible space to the community, could be a way for the museum to become part of people’s lives. I hear in meetings of ideas of how to use this space such as being a meeting place for groups to gather to start their activity, such as walking and jogging groups. For the Recovery Hub, I’m told in a conversation that space for gardening, like fitness and creative groups, are part of the menu of proposed activities that people want. I hear in meetings from people who are potential users of the Recovery Hub, that they want something to do, to occupy themselves, and that the activity itself is less important. I also hear in a meeting that within Paisley’s litter-picking group, members are now thinking beyond the initial activity and wanting their own community garden. I observe on social media that the STAR Project, through work tackling food insecurity, setting up a community pantry and a community garden is considered a natural step. I find that, like culture-based activities, garden-based activities emerge from the community in various ways. Culture and nature may be a false dichotomy (Haraway, 2003). Both could be thought of as activities that could conceptually be subsumed into leisure.

One way I suggest to the new SPG Connectedness Network project workers to better understand how loneliness is experienced is when they undertake research to understand loneliness better, they ask what the opposite of loneliness is, a question that has no consensus on the answer. Social prescribing comes from seeing loneliness as an indicator of something lacking in people. I suggest a survey question ‘what does loneliness indicate about society?’ Loneliness could indicate something is amiss in the way we relate to each other and the world. This awryness could be a lack of shared

understanding, collective belonging, empathy and listening. When I reread my notes on my conversations in 209 with the STAR Project, I find that although loneliness is not mentioned, their work is strongly relational and address these ways of relating to each other. When they talk about how they relate to people, they talk about listening and attuning to small moments in order to meet people where they are in terms of how they are in the world, to move with them, at their pace, rather than at them, with suggestions they may not be ready for. I see this through the lens of the practice of how to be well together.

My research focus on loneliness and everyday experiences grows knowledge regarding relational health's conceptual contribution to the description of individual and collective wellbeing. Relational health can provide a way of articulating how collective wellbeing is more than the sum of individual wellbeing by querying what we mean by living well together and who is included in this togetherness. Participatory practices such as co-production and peer work could contribute to the process of articulating collective wellbeing. These practices create shared meanings out of personal experiences. I encounter many of these practices in Paisley, from the emphasis on peer work and lived experience of the Drug and Alcohol task force, to nationally recognised co-production work at the Museum, to Renfrewshire's Early Action System Change collaborative project where young people co-design resources to tackle wellbeing and inequality.

I suggest in Chapter 3, and in this chapter, there should be more focus on 'what matters' in policy and evaluation processes. And the focus should be widened beyond 'how did change occur' to questions such as those posed by Roy Andersson's adverts for the Swedish Social Democratic Party (Bateman, 2015): 'Why should we care about each other?'¹⁶ 'Can we care for each other?'¹⁷ A limitation of my research is its minimal engagement with care, which is evaluated as a slippery term, that is ambivalent, contextual and relational and 'a valuable and necessary part of living with and alongside others' (Martin, Myers and Viseu, 2015, p. 628). A policy concerned with collective wellbeing and how we live well together is inherently engaged with care. I find that thinking with the gateway concepts of relational health leads me to Mol's (2008) argument to deal with disease by a 'logic of care' that is immersed in everyday life and hard to measure. Logic of care provides a challenge to individualism as it is contrasted with the individualism of logic of choice. This idea of how to approach health is less frequently encountered in arts and health literature compared to the search for efficacy and mechanisms. Logic of care has made its way to Paisley through the theory of

¹⁶ <https://www.filmarkivet.se/movies/varfor-ska-vi-bry-oss-om-varandra/>

¹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E93RP96Eall>

Museums as a Space of Care (Morse, 2020) discussed in the next chapter. I find that this framework could be a way of dealing with health that brings together relational health, place-based policies, cultural democracy, and community-centred health. My research also encounters care such as Future Paisley's actions in using culture to deliver The Promise¹⁸, which is made to care experienced infants, children, young people, adults, and their families: that every child grows up loved, safe, and respected, able to realise their full potential. I observe that care connects with Paisley's stories of itself. Local communities that have participated in a listening exercise by Paisley Museum to find out what they want from the Museum, talk about how they want to showcase Paisley's unique 'caring town' side through people's stories. I suggest that as care can be an affective state, a conceptual viewpoint that acknowledges affects is therefore needed. This acknowledgement is required to take us beyond causal stories. Without acknowledgement of affective knowledge, the illusions of rationality provided by reductionist frameworks and mind body dualities keep their dominant hold (Martin, Myers and Viseu, 2015), providing a resistance to a shift in thinking of health and society.

7.7. Conclusion

In this chapter I grow knowledge regarding my ontological and epistemological roots of the fifth wave of public health, the focus on the relational and the everyday and a commitment to diversity in ways of knowing, by exploring what different ways knowing could do to the policy process. I undertake this exploration by following the experience of loneliness and how this experience encounters the research object of the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley. Through this exploration, I live my gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts and examine if there is any resonance between my proposal for the fifth wave of public health and the knowledge grown from investigating loneliness as an experience and a policy challenge. Through following this research trail, I have observed and grown knowledge about the entanglement of policies designed to use culture and the arts for social purposes with loneliness as a policy concern. This entanglement provides knowledge into how policies might shift ideas of health and wellbeing.

My process of placing processes of becoming human at the heart of my proposal for the fifth wave of public health has led to my argument that 'what works and why,' requires 'what matters' and feelings. 'What matters' requires an approach to sit with people and be where they are. That enacts Roy Andersson's repeated use of a line from the Peruvian poet César Vallejo poem in his film *Songs from a second floor*, 'beloved be those who sit down'. The use of the line is a declaration of radical

¹⁸ <https://thepromise.scot/>

love and connection. This small yet often repeated moment in everyday life is enacted by most of us. A reminder of what we have in common. An enactment of trivialism, without which the drive for incorporating lived experience into research and policy, meets Dewsbury et al.'s (2002) vampirism draining life itself. Fourth wave thinking is too blunt an approach to 'what matters'. The dominance of the fourth wave crowds out more nuanced approaches that can immerse in the everyday, where the methods themselves are about becoming human rather than erasing human and humanness (Keyes, 2019; D'Ignazio and Klein, 2020).

Growing this knowledge develops the insight that are challenges to shifting idea of health and wellbeing through using place-based policies designed to use culture. Following loneliness as a public health issue shows the gap between the experience of loneliness and research and policy. A gap that has been identified as problematic in cultural policy and practice in the UK. Loneliness shows the limits of reductionist approach to a complex feelings and situations, where feelings and situation co-constitute each other. Pulling apart loneliness from other existential feelings to cast it as a factor in a model can be helpful to further understanding for whom, and in what circumstances loneliness is an issue. And helpful for identifying potential health inequalities due to loneliness. However, the neatening of loneliness required by these reductionist techniques, narrowly conceives loneliness as a deficit of human connections, in contrast to the messiness, complexity and non-humanness of the experience of loneliness and the practice of connection. Through this tension I demonstrate that policy considerations of loneliness in Scotland lack nuance of how connections are formed, to what are people connected to, and quality of connections, particularly existential feelings. The lack of nuance in the consideration of loneliness is compounded by the conceptual blurring with social isolation and the deployment of social prescribing being the go-to answer. Loneliness is affective and embodied. Loneliness can be a stigma and historically and culturally contingent. Loneliness is many things but without a conceptual space for affect and emotions, we will have an incomplete understanding of it, and incompletely assemble resources to live with it as a condition of becoming human. Living with loneliness requires affective resources, as well as social and material resources. Places that provide the warmth of mattering and the gift of reciprocity. I propose that my conceptual toolkit can help create alignment between policy and experience by providing a language for a more complete understanding of loneliness. Through this use of my conceptual toolkit, I continue my work of the counter-conceptualisation of health and wellbeing. I therefore demonstrate how to translate the ontological and epistemological roots of my proposal into ideas that we can think with to view and make visible the health and wellbeing processes we encounter in our daily lives and facilitate as part of our practice of health and wellbeing.

I grow insights relating to how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society chapter through growing knowledge of how integral everyday culture is to people's health and wellbeing. Therefore, I continue the growth of knowledge in Chapter 6 to argue that ideas of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing need to take care to not crowd out everyday culture and also support the emergence of everyday culture. I suggest that these ideas need to situate loneliness as a societal issue rather than current thinking of loneliness as an individual deficit of the social. I develop the insight that loneliness is a co-ordinating force for bringing informal healthcare stakeholders together as I observe many organisations and networks concerned with tackling loneliness including community-centred health and cultural activity.

In this chapter, I develop insights into how might a place-based policy, designed to use culture and the arts for social ends, grow a health and wellbeing dimension that I take forward into Chapter 9. Investigating loneliness as a public health challenge grows knowledge regarding how the fields of arts and health and cultural regeneration entangle and constitute formal place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for health and wellbeing purposes and informal policy such as community-centred health policy and practice. Loneliness as a public health and societal issue has informed the growth of a health and wellbeing dimension to Future Paisley. How loneliness is conceptualised will influence whether this health and wellbeing dimension can contribute to a shift in thinking about health and society, whether we can make visible and valued relational health, becoming human and considering how to be well together.

My research trail of growing knowledge from experiential observations had led to my insights of the constellations of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing activity in Paisley encompass a range of ways of knowing. These insights are part of my attunement to the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health. The next research task is to find ways of assisting people to attune to these characteristics in order to consider how health and wellbeing might be facilitated by organisations and programmes in Paisley and whether this facilitation can contribute to relational health.

8. Thinking with the conceptual toolkit

8.1. Introduction

Place is the setting for everyday life and is constituted from relationships. The dynamics of people and their places constitute the emergence of health and wellbeing. This chapter follows the research trail of using the conceptual toolkit developed in Chapter 4 to view and articulate health and wellbeing processes in a way that aligns with the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health. This trail will consider the resonance of my proposed gateway and sensitizing concepts with people, activities and organisations in Paisley. I seek out how ideas and practices of place entangle with health and wellbeing practices and place-based policies using culture for health and well-being ends.

My conceptual toolkit uses the term 'enabling place' as a gateway concept to the idea of relational health. Enabling place will guide my examination of how health and wellbeing could be facilitated by place-based policies using culture. This chapter uses enabling places to 'know through' rather than to 'know in' or 'know with'; therefore, it is not in the scope of my research to assess enabling place as a concept. The concept provides a gateway to thinking about material, social and affective resources and encounters. Through these encounters, atmospheres are formed. Atmosphere is a sensitizing concept in the toolkit and is used to attune to everyday encounters.

I start this chapter by reintroducing the term enabling places. My encounters in Paisley with the three types of resources that form an enabling place, material, social and affective, are analysed through my observations and drawing on policy documents. The concept of atmospheres is brought into this chapter to attune to the everyday encounters between processes of place and processes of health. The concept of atmospheres is used to evaluate how these resources create encounters that generate health. Paisley Museum is used to explore how an enabling place emerges. The chapter goes on to consider how place-based policy may facilitate enabling places. The conclusion summarises how following the concept of place through the lens of enabling places has contributed to exploring the potential of place-based policies utilising culture for health and wellbeing outcomes to shift ideas of health and wellbeing.

8.2. Resonance and research trails

Section 3.9.3 describes the process of resonance out of which research trails are formed. This research trail emerged from the research trail that forms Chapter 4 in Summer 2021. My multiple encounters with Paisley Museum in different settings means the Museum was a useful site to think with my conceptual toolkit when this trail emerged in Summer 2021 (Table 8.1).

Table 8.1: Resonance dimensions for thinking with the conceptual toolkit

Theory	Enabling places and atmospheres, counter-conceptualisation of health and wellbeing
Empirical	Community-based arts and health practice, The Participatory Museum and The Art of Relevance (Nina Simon)
Paisley context	Paisley Museum
Brought selves	Volunteer experience of creating atmospheres, evaluation professional
Situationally created self	Critical friend regarding concepts of health and wellbeing
Policy	Future Paisley - Step change 2 delivery and evaluation
Emergence of research trail	Summer of 2021

Selected key sites of knowledge growing on the path of the research trail is given in Table 8.2. These sites are presented by type and in chronological order of when I became aware of them.

Table 8.2: Growing knowledge for thinking with the conceptual toolkit

Key knowledge growing sites in Paisley	<p>STAR Project (Spring 2019 to October 2022, meetings and interview with key members of staff, research encounters where staff are present such as Future Paisley Strategic Outcomes workshops and UKRI funded place-based partnership project, meetings where people mention Star Project, Star Project social media)</p> <p>Renfrewshire Arts Team (Spring 2019 – Spring 2022 – meetings and workshops including CAHSC, Open Mind and Future Paisley, Future Paisley field trip meetings with individual senior staff, meetings with part of the team and the whole team, project meetings such as RenTV)</p> <p>Art Boss project (October 2019, emails to develop the brief for the project, articles about the awards Art Boss has won, presentation by Art Boss project at CCSE Annual Conference in Summer 2021, discussion with Renfrewshire Arts Team Autumn 2021, discussion of Art Boss project in a</p>
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	<p>range of meetings such as Future Paisley evaluation workshop: Step Change 2 in December 2021)</p> <p>Paisley Museum (Summer 2020 - Autumn 2022 – meetings with strategic staff members, meeting with workstreams, literature and webinars signposted by Museum, discussion, observation and documents of Listening Project, discussion with staff in a working with the community role, Paisley Museum website and social media accounts)</p> <p>Recovery Taskforce and Recovery Hub (Autumn 2020 – Summer 2021, meetings with Recovery Taskforce and Recovery Hub Focus Group)</p>
Context in Scotland and elsewhere	<p>20 minute neighbourhood (Scottish Government, 2020b)</p> <p>Place Principle (Scottish Government, 2019)</p>
Everyday day sites	<p>Personal experiences of being a volunteer and facilitating atmospheres of belonging, safety and sociality</p> <p>Personal experiences of asking people what does the exhibition mean to you</p> <p>Training courses for evaluation of arts and health projects</p> <p>Evaluator of arts and health projects – a situationally created self in Paisley and a brought in self from volunteering outside Paisley</p>
Perspectives	<p>The Participatory Museum and The Art of Relevance (Simon, 2010, 2016)</p> <p>‘Lantern Road’ and ‘Empirical Highway’ (White, 2014)</p>

8.3. Thinking with a gateway concept - enabling places

Making relational health processes visible requires attunement to the small moments of everyday life and how they accumulate. Enabling places conceptually offers this attunement by focusing on social, material, and affective encounters. By being attentive to these not necessarily conscious moments ‘beings constitute each other and themselves. Beings do not pre-exist their relating.’ (Haraway, 2003, p. 6). Enabling place is a gateway concept, a way to view health and place through the lens of the everyday and consider how health facilitating places emerge and how culture and the

arts contribute to this emergence. This section demonstrates the contribution of thinking with the lens of enabling place.

8.3.1. Affective resources and affective infrastructure

Enabling places is a helpful lens as the concept draws attention to affective resources, which are discussed less than social and physical resources in discussions relating to policy. Future Paisley's cultural regeneration programme I see in documents and presentations is articulated as physical and environmental, social, and economic. The social dimension focuses on thriving communities, that have community cohesion, creativity, and opportunities for children and young people. Affective resources are not explicitly mentioned. Enabling places by including affective resources highlights the practice of facilitating health and wellbeing outside of formal health services, as shown by the work of community artists. Enabling places also highlights a place's health and wellbeing capabilities through concepts such as atmospheres. I argue affective and emotional encounters are part of the process of wellbeing, particularly for the existential feelings that contribute to relational health. Therefore, I suggest emotional and affective infrastructure should be explicitly acknowledged alongside social and physical infrastructure. The subsuming of feelings into concepts related to the social, such as social infrastructure or social capital (Ahn and Davis, 2020), loses the focus on how feelings are formed and facilitated. Thinking through loneliness in the previous chapter shows that subsuming affective and emotional encounters into social encounters may lead to a focus on the quantity of social encounters rather than the quality. I suggest adding the concept of enabling places to the landscape of community health and cultural democracy can create a focus on the places people and communities create, to facilitate their wellbeing, and therefore could be an asset-based approach.

The previous chapter talked about the experience of loneliness. In this chapter I explore language that could help make conceptual room for the multiple dimensions of loneliness, and how the complexity of the experience of loneliness intertwines with existential feelings. Language that makes this conceptual room would better make visible the richness and diversity of the experience of loneliness and making connections. The previous chapter argued for the need for concepts that provide room for considering affective resources, in order to widen the focus of loneliness as a public health issue beyond social connections. The following quote shows that nuanced understandings of social connections are needed to illuminate its material and affective dimensions:

'For Robert, Melissa, Chan, Mark, Gregory and Al, among other participants, social connection was explicitly linked to an array of material and affective factors and processes. Examples include the feelings of belonging or 'fitting in' that Robert and Melissa associated

with social interactions in a cafe and a hair salon, respectively; or the feelings of acceptance and understanding that Mark, Grant and Al described. Social connections were thus described as material to the extent that they are mediated or transformed in place; and affective inasmuch as they modulate the various feeling states associated with sociality.'

(Duff, 2012, p. 1391)

Future Paisley seeks to build material and social resources and infrastructure. There are several capital projects that will contribute to Paisley's cultural infrastructure. Paisley Museum is a key project and is set to open in 2023. PACE Theatre Company has been developing a new theatre for children, young people, and families that will be a cultural and community hub that will open in 2023. Also opening in 2023 is the Paisley Learning and Cultural Hub, a community and educational facility which includes a library. Paisley Town Hall will be an entertainment venue opening at the end of 2022. Future Paisley seeks to increase material resources through economic regeneration. I observe conversations about the development of social resources. In a meeting members of the Renfrewshire Arts Team talk about how developing social resources is a key component of their practice when engaging with local artists and communities. They tell me trust builds by proving themselves, and overturning doubt and negativity. Trust must be demonstrated by the team and show that they trust the ideas communities bring up.

8.3.2. Enabling places and atmospheres

Enabling places create atmospheres. To 'know in' the sensitizing concept of atmospheres, I attune to atmospheres in my volunteering. I reflect on the atmospheres of belonging and sociality I have facilitated in the events and meetups I have organised and participated in. Attuning to atmospheres enables me to view how through peer work, spaces, like the exhibition I volunteer for, that are created by those with lived experiences are sensitive to issues of atmospheres of safety. These atmospheres are health and wellbeing generating as exhibitors tell of how they feel able to be vulnerable, express themselves more authentically, allowing themselves to be seen in a different way and feel validated. These factors create places that are conducive for reciprocal connections to form. These atmospheres of safety are intertwined with atmospheres of belonging. These atmospheres create a space where people can be visible and feel seen. A process I also observe in the Recovery Hub, where tasks from deciding the name, to the logo, go through an interactive decision process with the Peer Recovery Focus group.

‘It’s amazing, this place is a complete blank canvas and it’s all about what the service users want to see. Being in recovery, we know that you can feel invisible, but CIRCLE aims to reiterate that our service users are here and they’re contributing to society again.’

(Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Partnership, 2021a)

Following the research trail of loneliness in the last chapter has grown my attentiveness to atmospheres of sociality. In a SPG Connectedness Network meeting, people talk about atmospheres that through my conceptual approach could be considered atmospheres of sociality such as one that has grown around a community hub or the ones that they would like to create, such as chatty tables, where people can sit if they want to talk to other people.

8.3.3. Affective infrastructure and atmospheres

My attunement to affective resources means I view places as relational achievements. Reading my notes, I apply this lens to the STAR Project. A community organisation that is involved in Future Paisley as part of Future Paisley Partnership Board and organisations set up as part of Future Paisley’s delivery structure when I started the PhD in 2019. I could view the foundation of the service, the core of the space, through my sensitizing concept of atmosphere, in this case, atmospheres of safety. I visited the STAR Project at the start of my PhD. Staff told me how the energy of where people drop-in and sit is paid attention to by staff and volunteers. The lack of demands on people creates safety; people can sit there for months and drink cups of tea without feeling that they must engage. The atmosphere builds affective resources such as trust and provides agency, as engagement with activities is their decision.

Atmospheres of sociality emerge in conversations I have about other projects in Paisley. I observe in presentations and discussions that a project that gave young people the chance to learn about planning and producing creative projects and events, and that what participants wanted most was social engagement. Creative activities just happened to be the vehicle. I observed that feedback had been given that the creative outputs of this project had a level of excellence. The quality of cultural output was emergent, rather than planned or targeted. This observation of emergent creative excellence aligns with observations from my own cultural democracy practice.

While writing this up, atmospheres of safety was highlighted by others in a meeting I attend as a volunteer as important, particularly for those who do not feel they have a voice in mainstream spaces, which in this instance are those with intersectional identities encompassing gender, race, and disability. Atmospheres of safety I have found in my practice as a volunteer in this project is important to health-facilitating encounters. Atmospheres emerge from practice and continuous

tending. An atmosphere of safety initiates and reinforces atmospheres of belonging, sociality, and convivial spaces and constitutes affective infrastructure.

8.4. Paisley Museum and enabling places

I hear from an interviewee that OneRen's work with people is just as much an infrastructure as the physical infrastructure of leisure centres. The organisation's value is in the relational of its role as a partner to community, people, and other organisations. Paisley Museum is a key part of this relational work. The role of museums as a public health asset is a well-explored topic in academic literature (Froggett, Farrier and Poursanidou, 2011; Camic and Chatterjee, 2013; Desmarais, Bedford and Chatterjee, 2018). The consideration of the role of museums in health and wellbeing ranges from the delivery of specific health and wellbeing projects to roles such as leading the cultural sector's involvement in public health, and broader issues such as the museum's civic role in creating a better society (O'Neill and Hooper, 2019). Contributing to this literature requires an engagement beyond the scope of my research. Paisley Museum is encountered in this research, as the Museum is described as a flagship development, a key part of Paisley's regeneration in terms of the capital investment and the economic dimension of the project (Renfrewshire Leisure, 2018). Therefore, an exploration of Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension naturally has repeated encounters with Paisley Museum. I present these encounters in this section. A discussion of Paisley Museum in this section is presented as an illustration of the ongoing activity and work in Paisley to develop the health and wellbeing dimension of cultural organisations. The sections show how 'knowing through' enabling places, attunes me to the health and wellbeing dimension of Paisley Museum.

8.4.1. Concepts of health and wellbeing

My participation in meetings with Paisley Museum was facilitated by a senior manager who was also a member of CAHSC. I was invited to participate in the public programming and the volunteering and skill workstreams. The public programming workstream was in the midst of delivering a variety of programmes. Health and wellbeing were to be part of the criteria for selecting which activities to develop.

I find through formal and informal research encounters that health and wellbeing is a concern for Paisley Museum. These research encounters include Paisley Museum staff in non-museum meetings, conversations with Paisley Museum staff online and through emails, an interview of a member of staff, reports, and participant observation in meetings for the workstreams I was invited to join. This concern is interwoven with Paisley Museum's aim of being a place that belongs to people and has meaning for people. The Museum has a variety of ways to engage with the community from various

projects to inform what the Museum could be to the community, a dedicated co-production officer to volunteering opportunities. The manager I was liaising with was keen to develop an organisational approach to health and wellbeing. I asked questions to understand what health and well-being meant to the Museum and what definitions of health and wellbeing were in use. This questioning found that Museum staff were wrestling with concepts of health and wellbeing. In response, I created and shared an overview of key health and wellbeing concepts and research on how cultural spaces could mitigate loneliness. There was an intention to set up a short-term working group to examine how the Museum would articulate ambitions around health and wellbeing for the public programming workstream, and potentially across the Museum and OneRen as a whole. It was anticipated that I would be part of the working group. The senior manager who facilitated my participation in Museum activities facilitated this work and the workstreams. When they left, these activities did not continue.

One conceptual conversational starter I shared came from a report that reviewed academic and grey literature to answer how spaces and places can enhance wellbeing or reduce loneliness through sport, physical activity, and participatory arts (Mansfield *et al.*, 2020). I found an overlap between my conceptual toolkit and the summary diagram of this report¹⁹. The diagram had an affective dimension, such as safety and belonging, a social dimension, and processes of relationality. This diagram resonated with the senior manager. They used it in a conversation with their manager about the Museum as a place of health and wellbeing, as their manager was keen to ensure that the Museum's health and wellbeing dimension was being developed. The diagram helped articulate processes being developed by Museum activities, which the Museum had not articulated in health and wellbeing terms such as processes of belonging.

The conversation initiated by the diagram shows the usefulness of reductionist techniques to distil complexity into a quickly communicated form. It also shows the limitations of reductionist techniques, as how these processes come about is not conveyed by the diagram.

8.4.2. Practice – a museum that belongs to people

Through meetings and informal conversations, I found awareness amongst staff of the research and practice on the impact and value of museums to health and wellbeing. For example, I was told that the Paisley Museum staff participated in a 'bootcamp' delivered by Of/By/For All, a non-profit organisation helping cultural institutions matter more to people and together create a movement to

¹⁹ <https://whatworkswellbeing.org/resources/place-space-wellbeing-loneliness-art-sport-culture/>

make more inclusive community organisations. This movement stems from Nina Simon's work that originated when she was a museum director to make the museum meaningful to the community it was situated in (Simon, 2010, 2016). I find resonance in Simon's work with Braden's (1978) arguments for how to make culture meaningful to people. In particular, the situation of the community not knowing Simon's museum existed when she first took on the director role resonates with Braden's warning of 'polite apathy' by the local community that occurs if the means of expression of the local community is not understood. Subsequently, Paisley Museum has been putting into practice the Of/By/For All approach. This approach suggests that for a museum to be 'of' the community, then board/staff/partners should be representative of that community, and programmes should be co-created by the community. These suggestions would make the institution a welcoming space for all members of the community.

8.4.3. Thinking with sensitizing concept - atmospheres

In August 2020, informed by the Of/By/For All approach, Paisley Museum carried out 67 conversations with services, organisations, and groups across Renfrewshire to ask about their opportunities and priorities and what the Museum could do for them (GEM, 2021). These were thematically analysed, and six key themes were constructed. I observe through meetings, an interview, and discussions that the most prominent theme was community health and wellbeing. I identify atmospheres as part of this theme as safe and welcoming spaces are, particularly for specific groups such as autism or dementia. Social resources came into the discussion as part of the key theme of tackling social isolation. Suggestions include the Museum being a drop-in centre and a meeting place for all. I identify affective resources in a discussion about the theme of confidence such as a sense of belonging and a feeling of ownership of the Museum.

Through social media, participant observations and conversations, I become aware of the range of co-production activities undertaken by the Museum. Co-production as a cornerstone of the Museum's approach its creation (Paisley Museum, 2022). The listening exercise is intended to result in co-production, as the themes identified are fed back to participants to find out which resonated most and to give an opportunity for organisations to declare an interest in co-producing programs. The public programming and volunteer programming workstreams are another strand of the Museum's community work.

The concern that the Museum should feel like it was owned and belonged to the community was repeatedly expressed. An interviewee discussed how they were seeking out communities that engaged less with the Museum and felt the Museum was not for them. I attended a webinar where Paisley Museum presented a project with care experienced people. When asked how they felt about

the Museum at the start of the project, responses included outdated and unwelcoming. The project made the Museum feel accessible to care experienced people. When they were asked what they would like the new Museum to be, replies included a sense of community, where many people are represented and would feel like it was theirs.

8.4.4. Encountering concepts – Museum as Space of Social Care

My conversations with Paisley Museum pointed me to the opening launch of Dr. Nuala Morse's book, *The museum as a space of social care*. Subsequently, I observe on social media, Dr. Morse has been in conversation with Paisley Museum and staff felt her ideas resonated with what they are doing (Strachan, 2021). Her research (Morse, 2020) builds on the work of museums as places of health and wellbeing by considering health and wellbeing through the notion of care and community engagement practice as care practice. She terms this practice 'the museumness of care,' a practice with distinct relational, affective, and material dimensions that has resonance with enabling places. Her concepts have theoretical commonalities and concerns with my theoretical and conceptual underpinnings. As mentioned in the previous chapter, the idea of the museum as a space of social care brings together many of the ideas I have been using to develop my proposal for the fifth wave of public health. The interest in the idea of museum as a space of social care in Paisley indicates that there is potential for my ideas for the fifth wave of public health to resonate.

8.5. Nurturing enabling places

This chapter has shown how enabling places provide a language for how health and wellbeing emerge through the relational achievement of place (Ivanova, 2022). This language provides a way of pulling together and articulating the affective work of cultural organisations and cultural workers. I suggest that a concept of place that is explicit about affective resources and encounters could assist place-based policy to make visible the health creating processes emerging out of everyday life. Such a concept of place could also provide a lens for the practice of those who facilitate health and wellbeing outside the formal healthcare system.

In conversations with staff of the Recovery Hub and Paisley Museum, I hear a commonality in a desire to make spaces that mean something to people. In particular, places that people would feel they belonged to and belonged to them. In my conversations, I suggest evaluations of projects and programmes should look for value beyond a before and after snapshot. Meaningful places weave their way into your life. How they affect you is not just about what happens in the space, or the activities facilitated there. Places that feel good evolve out of processes of meaning-making (Ivanova, 2022). After the first lockdown in November 2020, the exhibition I volunteer for asked

audience and participant members, 'what does the exhibition mean to you?' I detect a theme that the exhibition was an anchor in people's lives in these responses and also in conversations with exhibitors. The exhibition gave something that could not exactly be expressed as a purpose or a meaning, this something encompassed these elements and more. For some, there was the accumulation of small things, of vague affects, a tangibility to time, a sense that there was something out there, beyond a life shrunk and scrapped bare by COVID-19 lockdown measure. These small moments do not amass to a change in health and wellbeing that can be identified or even consciously realised. Instead, they repeatedly nudge themselves into your existential feelings, into your identity and the scope of what you consider community. Slowly the texture of life alters. The exhibition alters people's affective background and sense of being in the world. For some, being part of the exhibition is a practice of relating and becoming human. I find transformation and prevention happen in this background, as hindsight reveals that my feelings of being in the world have changed, and I am not the same person I used to be. The relatings that constitute me have changed due to the exhibition. These moments gathering into nudges and transformations align with my argument that the accretion of small moments is how transformation happens. I suggest these small moments is where the claims for the benefits of culture and arts should be situated if a case is to be made for the contribution to the prevention agenda. In the mundane, not measurements and mechanisms. Mundanity offers possibilities of experience, from the transformative to the ephemeral that do not settle into feelings or memories to be recalled in surveys. Cultural democracy validates fleeting feelings as there is no expectation or dictation of what you are meant to feel, unlike fine art. The concept of fine art implies intense concentration and reverence to be an appropriate response to experiencing art (Crehan, 2011). However, the evidence-based agenda and evaluation techniques would consider a project or programme a failure if people are not nudged beyond the project baseline, such as a measurable level of wellbeing.

8.6. Small moments and evaluation

Gathering small moments is where creative research approaches could play a role in complementing the orthodoxy of theory of change diagrams. Ravetz and Gregory 's (2018) account of artistic research in an arts and health setting illustrate their attentiveness to atmospheres and affect. Attending to small moments I suggest, could lead research and evaluation down White's (2014) 'Lantern Road' of reflective practice and relational working and away from the 'Empirical Highway' of calls for evidence and knowledge framed by the medical model of health. Attention to these moments, could help course correct from the lack of focus on the strengths of community-based arts in health, such as their spatial dimension (Raw, 2014; White, 2014). Enabling places could serve as a conceptual tool to assist with this course correction.

Future Paisley, for a policy that uses culture for myriad ends, I find little discussion of the use of culture and the arts in evaluation. Given the cultural workers and creatives funded by Future Paisley, I have not found this creative resource channelled into evaluation. I was interested when I talked to a member of the Renfrewshire Arts Team about how they could evaluate their project, that one of the projects was an artist in-residence at a leisure centre. I suggest could the artist not contribute to the evaluation? And why not just them? Why not harness the creative thinking of all the artists that are being commissioned? They could be given the space to engage, challenge, and inform the ethos and purpose of evaluation. I put forward that their creativity and knowledge could be used to inform the evaluation agenda as well as create evidence. If Future Paisley seeks to be radical, could this be a starting point? Place-based policy designed to use culture for health and wellbeing purposes by its position outside both the cultural sector and the healthcare sector has the potential for critically engaging with healthcare standards of rigour and evidence. This type of policy could break the one-way relationship between culture and other sectors, such as through policy attachment (Gray, 2017) or by conforming to the standards of what government policy and scientific research deem trustworthy (Ravetz and Gregory, 2018).

During my participation in a training course for the evaluation of arts and health projects, I find a tension between the desire of trainers and practitioners to be pragmatic and provide evidence in the language of the dominant paradigm to obtain funding and the desire to talk about their practice in their terms. A tension that aligns with White's (2014) two paths of 'empirical highway' and the 'lantern road'. Utilising the concept of enabling places provides a way of navigating this tension. To counter this tension, I suggest it is pragmatic to value the work that is currently being done and the resources that are being built up, rather than losing them due to lack of visibility, care, and attention. To make fully visible the work and resources of tending to the potential of places to facilitate health and wellbeing would require starting from the dimensions of material, social, and affective. To do so there needs to be radicalness in evaluation to bring these assets into view of policy makers. I therefore suggest that being pragmatic is to accept the complexity and the unknowingness of the world and recede the desire to understand change. As argued by Ravetz and Gregory (2018), artistic research with a narrative reasoning that includes gaps and pauses would be a more pragmatic approach than the futility of wrestling neatness from the world.

My suggestions have implications on what evaluation is for. Usually, evaluation processes seek to provide evidence and data to show what works. I suggest this should not be the only role of evaluation. The process should also be about articulating what works through gathering tacit knowledge. An interviewee tells me they know what works in the moment. And as the previous chapters have suggested, evaluation should be concerned with what matters. Community energy

and radicalness are the qualities I find people in Paisley declares that Paisley has, so I propose these qualities should be the guiding principle for evaluation. The work of RAMH and their Loneliness champions and speaking to RHSCP show that in Paisley, spaces have been created for community voices to share their knowledge to health and wellbeing policy makers. The themes that Doherty and De St Croix (2019) have from their research into evaluating and valuing youth work, could be a guiding principle: what is the everyday and what is the remarkable? Paisley's radical past is often brought up in conversations. This past involved a social movement. I suggest another useful question could be what movements can be created amongst the public, communities, and practice? These questions have the potential to generate health and build relational health capacity and would contribute to arts and health research (Daykin, 2019b). They would also be more reflective of what I observe Paisley's policymakers are interested in, for example, the desire to be a place of excellence for socially engaged practice is a phrase I have heard repeatedly. Therefore, how these questions are incorporated in the development of evaluation plans will indicate Paisley's approach to health and wellbeing, of what good practice is identified, and for what ends. This chapter argues enabling places is a way of identifying good practice that would contribute to health and wellbeing, including the fifth wave of public health.

8.7. Affective infrastructure and inclusiveness

I observe new policy developments in Paisley that I argue highlight the importance of considering affective resources alongside social and material resources. I find coming up in conversations the idea of 20 minute neighbourhood (Scottish Government, 2020b). The idea has resonance with Paisley's three dimensions of physical, social, and economic regeneration. It is a component and outcome-based description of a neighbourhood. Through the lens of enabling places, I suggest this idea lacks the affective infrastructure to cohere these components. The idea is missing the emotional needs that another national idea, the Place Principle (Scottish Government, 2019), contains, such as a sense of control and belonging. Affective and emotional infrastructure is particularly important when considering the inclusiveness of a place. Inclusiveness is more than a sense of belonging but also a place to feel like a visible part of society, as shown by the research on convivial spaces for those who do not feel part of mainstream society (Bredewold *et al.*, 2020). As shown in the previous chapter convivial spaces are important for causal encounters that mitigate loneliness. I find the importance of convivial spaces in people's opinions on how Scottish Government's Communities Mental Health and Wellbeing Fund should be spent. The organisation that facilitates my Edinburgh exhibition is a collective advocacy charity. They asked their mental health collective advocacy group attendees what the best use of the funding would be. One need was identified as:

‘Places to be – no cost, no pressure social spaces where people can hang out with friends, make new friends, get out of the house. People don’t have money to go to cafes, drop-ins require referrals and forms and have criteria, and often insist on activities.’

(CAPS Independent Advocacy, 2021)

Ideas of place are important as they create a shared understanding of what a place should be, so without explicitly mentioning affective infrastructure, this dimension will remain subsumed into other concepts such as social infrastructure. Lacking language to talk about the affective dimension also puts less focus on the practices identified in this research of facilitating affective encounters and infrastructure and less focus on the everyday experience of being in a place. The pairing of Future Paisley’s desire to be a place of excellence for socially engaged practice with explicit acknowledgement of affective resources would contribute to developing Future Paisley’s approach to leverage culture for health and wellbeing outcomes and contribute to national ideas of place.

8.8. Conclusion

In this chapter I explore the translation of the ontological and epistemological roots of my proposal for the fifth wave of public health, the focus on the relational and the everyday and a commitment to diversity in ways of knowing, into ideas we can think with. I offer enabling places as a gateway concept to think relationally, make visible the affective dimension of health and wellbeing and articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health. My argument is not that enabling places is a necessary concept for the fifth wave of public health. As I show in Chapter 7 and in this chapter, there are other concepts that may be more suited to the local context. I offer enabling places as a demonstration of the contribution of my work to counter-conceptualise health and wellbeing. This work makes visible the processes of relational health and the work of facilitating relational health. I suggest concepts need to make room and make explicit the affective dimension, as well as the social and material. I argue that without these concepts, processes that inform policy, such as evaluation, will lack the potential to shift ideas of health and society to relational health. And new policy ideas relating to place may lack inclusiveness.

The knowledge I have grown from ‘knowing in’ and ‘knowing about’ my proposed gateway and sensitizing concepts contribute to my growing insights regarding culture, health, and wellbeing as everyday, emergent, and asset-based grass root approaches to health and wellbeing. In particular, the gateway concept of enabling place, through an emphasis on affective resources and encounters, alongside material and social has a resonance with people, activities, and organisations in Paisley. Thinking with enabling places has attuned my research to everyday encounters that accumulate into

meaningfulness. I think through the knowledge grown from academic literature, that focusing on the everyday, atmospheres become more tangible and can help highlight who belongs to a place and who does not and link this knowledge to existential feelings. I grow the insight that enabling places is where our existential feelings shift as we are drawn into these places and enact practices such as belonging and community that help us in becoming human and be well together. Enabling places if taken up in policy processes, could help shift ideas of health and wellbeing by making tangible these harder to articulate moments. I show in this chapter how concepts that allow for an affective dimension are important to policy processes as these concepts provide a language that widens what is thought of as health and wellbeing resources and practices. Using this language can help people think themselves as health and wellbeing workers, even though that is not their written role. It can give value to practices that people already have and already know are valuable such as facilitating atmospheres of belonging.

The use of concepts that align with the fifth wave of public health can bring into policy and practice the ontological and epistemological roots of my proposal for the fifth wave of public. Concepts that resonate can draw into discussions of health and wellbeing those activities, organisations and people who are outside the formal health and wellbeing sector. One activity that could be drawn in is the process of evaluation. I grow knowledge to think about how evaluation could mobilise culture and arts-related activity to contribute to thinking about relational health. I find in my experience; evaluation can distance or bring practitioners closer to policy. I find evaluation is a site of tension, as these processes are usually structured by orthodox thinking which may not align with the knowledge of practitioners or experiential knowledge. Evaluation processes help form the territory for what knowledge is valued, therefore my work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing is needed ensure this territory is amenable to relational health.

My research has made more visible some of the health and wellbeing processes we encounter, and the work required to facilitate relational health. Making visible some of these processes shows how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised for relational health. This knowledge grows my insights of the constellations of culture, the arts, health and wellbeing activity in Paisley which prepares a canvas for me to layer knowledge gained during the next research trail I explore. I now go on to investigate the case for culture in Paisley, the conditions for a health and wellbeing dimension of place-based policy to develop in Paisley and the possible future entanglements between health and wellbeing and Future Paisley. I gain insights into whether these entanglements can contribute to the mobilisation by a place-based policy, of culture and arts-related activity to create a fifth wave of public health.

9. Growing a health and wellbeing dimension to Future Paisley

9.1. Introduction

Eight years have passed since the publication in 2014 of *The Untold Story*. Health and wellbeing have moved from being a passing mention in this report to being part of one of the five Step Changes in the Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme in 2021. During this time, two broader movements have been growing. Scotland has a policy movement toward greater localism and community empowerment in public services (Elliott, Fejszes and Tàrrega, 2018; Markantoni *et al.*, 2018) and a growing arts and health field in the UK (APPGAHW, 2017). Paisley is part of a Scottish landscape with a polyphony of place-based policies designed to use culture and the arts for social purposes. Culture is woven into a myriad of schemes from a billion-pound regeneration project²⁰, a town-based cultural activism project²¹ to the introduction of a national cultural policy²² bringing diverse projects at different scales together, to share ideas and practice.

This chapter follows the research trail of how a health and wellbeing dimension of a culture informed place-based policy comes together. From this facet of how health and wellbeing emerges in place-based policies designed to use culture and the arts for social purposes I will grow knowledge of what possibilities for the fifth wave of public health may appear. Applying the commitment of assemblage thinking to anti-reductionism, uncertainty, and fluid forms to viewing policy, invites analysis of how the elements of an assemblage might or might not be made to cohere how policy-making emerges from the moving configuration of these elements and asks what is made probable by this assemblage (Li, 2007; Savage, 2019). The chapter continues the use in Chapter 6's of Tsing's (2017) language of assemblages as open-ended gatherings that may become happenings.

This chapter explores the case for culture and the arts to be part of place-based policy and how this case shapes the approach to seeking changes in health and wellbeing. The recent rise in the policy interest of the arts and health field and the rise of wellbeing as a policy goal provides a range of warrants for the case for culture in the design of place-based policy that aims to improve health and wellbeing.

This chapter starts by drawing together the academic discussion on the use of culture in policy for social ends, with my observations on the stated intent of using culture in policy by the Future Paisley

²⁰ <https://www.dundewaterfront.com/about/>

²¹ <https://www.deveron-projects.com/about/artocracy/>

²² <https://www.creativescotland.com/what-we-do/latest-news/archive/2021/02/culture-collective-recipients>

Partnership Board. This chapter then follows the research trail’s interest in what culture is used for in the design and practice of place-based policy by examining the strategic use of culture in Paisley. The chapter also follows how such a policy emerges by examining what elements are drawn in and constitute policy. From this, knowledge will be grown to understand the processes of gathering entities into the practice of cultural regeneration policy for health and wellbeing purposes. The chapter goes on to explore what conditions shape the gathering process. The characteristics of the research object are analysed to identify the factors that facilitate the gathering process. This analysis leads to an appraisal of the policy’s features that emerge from the ongoing practice of policy. The chapter then assesses the possibilities for culture, arts, health, and wellbeing that such a policy could create. This chapter’s final section considers if policies that use culture and the arts for social purposes may contribute to a shift in ideas about the nature of health and society.

9.2. Resonance and research trails

Section 3.9.3 describes the process of resonance out of which research trails are formed. My research focus moved from projects to policy in Spring 2021. This growing focus on policy also emerged in other research trails such as the work of counter-conceptualisation in Chapter 4, knowledge grown in Chapter 5 and 6 of what type of culture, arts, health and wellbeing activities constituted Future Paisley, knowledge grown in Chapter 7 of the importance of how loneliness is conceptualised in policy and how the knowledge grown in Chapter 8 regarding the conceptual toolkit could be drawn into Future Paisley and its evaluation process. This emerging interest in policy as the research puzzle resonated across a range of dimensions (Table 9.1)

Table 9.1: Resonance dimensions for growing a health and wellbeing dimension for Future Paisley

Theory	Instrumental use of culture in policy, implicit cultural policy, policy mobility, policy assemblage
Empirical	Practices of assembling policy (Li, 2007), relationship between cultural policy and wellbeing measures (Oman, 2015, 2021)
Paisley context	Untold Story, Future Paisley evaluation, development of a health and wellbeing dimension to Future Paisley
Brought selves	Economic development professional assessing the economic impact of cultural projects and tourism for agencies such as regional development agencies and developing economic development strategies

Situationally created self	Facilitator of evaluation processes, critical friend to practitioners regarding evaluation and concepts of loneliness, health and wellbeing, knowledge of activities in Paisley related to culture, health and wellbeing, member of CAHSC
Policy	A Culture Strategy for Scotland (Scottish Government, 2020a)
Emergence of research trail	Spring 2021

Selected key sites of knowledge growing on the path of the research trail is given in Table 7.2. These sites are presented by type and in chronological order of when I became aware of them.

Table 9.2: Growing knowledge for growing a health and wellbeing dimension for Future Paisley

Key knowledge growing sites in Paisley	<p>Paisley the Untold Story: Paisley Town Centre Asset Strategy and Action Plan (Renfrewshire Council, 2014)</p> <p>The Journey Continues (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b)</p> <p>UK City of Culture the Bidding Legacy (Crearie, 2018)</p> <p>Future Paisley - Step change 2 development (Spring 2019 – Spring 2021)</p> <p>CAHSC development (Spring 2019 – Spring 2021)</p> <p>Social media to understand connections between projects (Spring 2020- Autumn 2022)</p> <p>Future Paisley – interviews with staff in strategic leadership roles (Spring 2021)</p> <p>Renfrewshire Leisure strategies (Accessed Spring 2021) and interview with staff with strategic leadership role</p> <p>Committee documents from Renfrewshire Council Leadership Board and Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Integration Joint Board (started accessing Spring 2021 and continued till Autumn 2022)</p>
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Context in Scotland and elsewhere	<p>Cultural regeneration projects in Scotland (Spring 2019 – Autumn 2022 – continuous engagement for example social media of key individuals and organisations such as Creative Scotland and SURF)</p> <p>Scottish Government Wellbeing Economy Agenda (Spring 2019 – Autumn 2022 – continuous engagement due to professional interest as an economic impact professional)</p> <p>Examples of culture, arts, health and wellbeing from other areas (Spring 2019 – Autumn 2022 – continuous engagement for example social media of key individuals, networks and organisations in the arts and health sector, subscribing to relevant newsletters)</p> <p>Consultation responses to Scottish Government Draft Culture strategy (Accessed Summer 2020)</p>
Everyday sites	<p>Ongoing professional engagement with my practice as an evaluator and economic and social impact assessment expert such Wellbeing Economy Book Club and volunteering as an impact expert</p>
Perspectives	<p>Gatherings and happenings (Tsing, 2017)</p> <p>Boundary spanners (Daykin, 2019b)</p> <p>‘Lantern Road’ and ‘Empirical Highway’ (White, 2014)</p>

9.3. The use of culture and the arts in policy

What policy is and who is involved is a complex question (Bell and Oakley, 2015). Future Paisley has many components, due to the involvement of organisations across sectors and society through Future Paisley Partnership Board, the Future Paisley delivery structure and an emphasis on community voice and participation (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018a). Bell and Oakley (2015) define policy as ideas that have some kind of form and are assumed to have some kind of effects. This chapter seeks to understand this form and what effects relating to health and wellbeing emerge. Policy in this chapter covers those who develop policy, who as part of their role work on programmes that formally constitute the Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme and those that contribute to Future Paisley informally as their role aligns and contributes to policy objectives. This contribution may not be immediately visible as the contribution may be in terms of creating the structures and systems that formal policy initiatives could embed into or link with.

The case for culture in the design of policy that seeks social change is inherently instrumental (Hadley and Gray, 2017) as culture is utilised for a purpose. The instrumental use of culture in policy has been a decades-long debate and an iteration of the centuries-old history of culture being used for societal ends (Belfiore and Bennett, 2008). This debate influences the discussion of the value of culture. An instrumental value of culture derives from how well culture achieves societal ends, for whom, and whose cultural value is utilised (Belfiore, 2012, 2018). The instrumentalisation of culture is a key concept in the field of cultural studies (Bell and Oakley, 2015). Bell and Oakley (2015) identify four categories of cultural policy research: a discourse, a text, a process, and a practice. My observations of where health and wellbeing encounter culture and arts, draws on all four categories. For my research to analyse how approaches to improving health and wellbeing may be shaped by a policy designed to utilise culture, requires my research to explore the purposes of utilising culture in Paisley, by those who constitute the Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme.

My research requires a way to view how policy is constituted from the text, ideas, processes, and practices I encounter. Again, I find assemblage thinking is a useful guide to consider the diffuseness of place-based policy that is designed to use culture for health and wellbeing ends. I observe in Chapter 6 how culture emerges in Paisley from outside the cultural sector and as an emergent activity. I observe in Chapter 7 how loneliness as a Future Paisley policy concern comes from activity both within and out with Paisley, and how this activity brings in involvement of culture and the arts for health and wellbeing improvement. In Chapter 8, I examine how ideas can make some health and wellbeing facilitating processes and practices more visible and be gathered into policy. The gathering of these activities in policy aligns with Ahearne's (2009) categorisation of implicit cultural policy, which refers to policies that are not explicitly labelled cultural. Ahearne defines two types of implicit cultural policies. The first are policies that explicitly pursue culture for its own ends but are not labelled as a cultural policy. The second type is where culture is an emergent activity. The previous chapters have grown knowledge about how the explicit cultural policy of Future Paisley interweaves with implicit cultural policies which emerge through local, regional and national organisations, and programmes, sometimes in combination. Policies co-constitute each other through relationships. These can be formal such as through strategic and delivery structures set up by policy, or informal such as through partnership working and co-production.

9.4. Gathering elements for a place-based policy using culture and the arts for health and wellbeing

9.4.1. Gatherings

The economic dimension of cultural regeneration policy could be defined as having a global form that is generally known and considered valid in different places (Prince, 2010). Assemblage thinking considers policy assemblages as gathering things from elsewhere and in place (McCann, 2011). For the economic dimensions there are things to gather from elsewhere and in place. Therefore, if required, cultural regeneration policies can quickly assemble a vision, action plan, and evaluation process for the economic dimension. The economic dimension has a known form. This is shown in the wording of the Future Paisley Step Change that is related to the economic dimension. The original wording of 'grow significant new dimensions to Paisley's economy by growing the cultural, tourism, creative, and digital sectors' evolves to its current phrasing of 'develop a sustainable and resilient creative economy in Renfrewshire.' The Step Change is still recognisably concerned with sector development, despite the changes in the definition of the sector and a different emphasis on the qualities of the development.

The gathering of a place-based policy using culture and the arts for health and wellbeing requires more gathering of entities than leveraging for economic aims. The guidance for bidders to UKCoC21 demands a demonstrable economic impact (Department for Culture, Media and Sport, 2016). Paisley's cultural regeneration process has always had an economic dimension, from the description in *The Untold Story* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014) of a heritage-driven economic regeneration to the Step Changes in the UKCoC21 legacy report (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b) and in the current iteration of Future Paisley. I have developed many logic chains for an economic dimension of a policy, organisation or project. These logic chains are linear in causality and are designed to be measurable. The aim is to develop and grow the economy, usually defined through the headline measures of an increase in additional jobs and income in an area. In my experience, common methods used by policymakers to achieve economic aims through the use of culture include increasing visitor spend in an area through increasing visitor numbers and developing the creative sector through skills and inward investment programmes. In Scotland, the economic dimension of local authority level policies is usually tasked to a public sector economic development team.

9.4.2. Gathering from elsewhere

There is a lack of things to gather from elsewhere in the context of health and wellbeing compared to economic development. There are no established definitions and actions for the health and

wellbeing dimension. Paisley has had to evolve its own approach. The lack of things from elsewhere increases the difficulty of quickly designing cultural regeneration policy's health and wellbeing dimension. *The Untold Story* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014) has one mention of health. This mention is not related to Paisley's regeneration activities, and no mentions of wellbeing. Headline measurements for the health and wellbeing of an area, such as mortality rates or levels of health inequalities, do not have straightforward causal links to culture and the arts, which are usually measured as the participation of people in culture or the activities of the cultural sector. For example, the indicators for the Scottish Government's National Performance Framework (Scottish Government, 2018b). Commonly used measures of wellbeing have only recently emerged relative to the history of economic impact measures. The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing scale is one measure that I observe in meetings as a well-known scale. The scale was developed in 2007 (Warwick Medical School, 2020) and is part of Coventry 2021's monitoring and evaluation framework (University of Warwick and Coventry University, 2022). However, attributing population-level changes in wellbeing to specific projects faces challenges of identifying causality, measurement and conceptual issues (Atkinson, 2020). The array of conceptual and empirical choices to define health and wellbeing compared to defining the economy, compounds these measurement and conceptual issues. The lack of a standard cultural regeneration model for health and wellbeing, such as delivery structure and activities, contributes to the difficulties of quickly designing a dimension.

9.4.3. Gathering in place

To grow knowledge of how Future Paisley has evolved and add to my knowledge of what has gathered in place, I investigate Renfrewshire Leadership Board online meeting documents. The Leadership Board is delegated to provide strategic leadership for the Council and ensure consistency across the Council's policy objectives. Future Paisley is part of the Leadership Board's remit. (Renfrewshire Council, 2022). I find a report written by the Chief Executive and Strategic Director for Paisley 2021 with input from UKCoC21 bid partners gathered in two workshops. This report from February 2018 puts forwards proposals to build on the legacy of UKCoC21 bid (Crearie, 2018). I find reference to how the bid process 'uncovered' cultural practices in health programmes. The report describes a Council commitment to working with health to promote arts in health along with health and social prescribing to reduce loneliness, social isolation, and depression. This commitment appears in the next report I find, which is *The Journey Continues* (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b). The report is an action plan to secure and maximise the legacy of Paisley's bid for UKCoC21. In this report, activities relating to health and social care are attached to the Step Change, 'lifting communities out of poverty'. Activities on digital inclusion, volunteering, and education are also

attached to this Step Change. The Step Change also includes outcomes on drug and recovery, education, poverty mitigation, and digital inclusion.

At the start of my research as illustrated in Chapter 1, public sector health services and organisations were gathered into Paisley's explicit cultural regeneration practice through CAHSC, the leadership body for the Step Change, 'lifting communities out of poverty', which is referred to in conversation as Step Change 2. Other issues out with health, such as digital inclusion, do not have a strategic body involved with Step Change 2, therefore CAHSC evolved into assuming delivery for the overall step change. CAHSC had representatives from both the NHSGCC, who also chaired and also from RHSPC. A different composition and lead for CAHSC could have led to a different focus. The first meeting I attended in April 2019 was the second for CAHSC. I attended three CAHSC meetings in 2019, which focused on how projects were developing. Related to these meetings were discussions I participated in regarding how to evaluate projects attached to the Step Change to assess CAHSC's contribution to Future Paisley. I observed that non-health organisations were unsure how to embed health and wellbeing into activities, as there is a lack of strategic guidance on what is meant by health and wellbeing. Organisations did not feel aligned to Future Paisley as they did not feel that their activities contributed to lifting communities out of poverty. Organisations also had difficulty reconciling how their work contributed to poverty reduction and health and wellbeing. There was a disconnect between the stated purpose of Step Change 2 and the capacity of organisations to deliver on the Step Change.

9.4.4. Reassembling

I observed discussions about the role of CAHSC. The initial meetings I was involved in spent time discussing projects and participants talked about what contribution CAHSC could make beyond being the sum of the projects in its remit. CAHSC's structure was reorganised in 2020 with a reduction in organisations. I observed that a greater connection with the social determinants of health was created through membership of CAHSC such as third sector representation through Engage Renfrewshire and representation from the Council's poverty and inequalities team. To bring in practitioner knowledge, one of CAHSC's roles was to set up a Renfrewshire culture, arts and health network, which would gather those whose practice involved both culture and the arts and health and wellbeing. This network would have provided a way to gather into Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension practitioners. This restructuring also set up the CAHSC Research and Evaluation Working Group to evaluate programs and projects in line with Future Paisley's strategic objectives.

A workshop in January 2020 was set up to align Future Paisley's Step Changes with the evaluation process. I observed acknowledgement amongst Future Paisley stakeholders of the disconnection

between the wording of Step Change 2 and the organisations involved in undertaking programmes as part of this Step Change. Actions to develop Step Change 2 and create alignment between strategy and delivery were delayed by COVID-19. This delay in developing Step Change 2 and the impact of COVID-19 meant there was also a delay in the development of an action plan by CAHSC. Workshops were undertaken in 2021 with the organisations who would deliver Step Change 2 in 2021 and a new Step Change was agreed in mid-2021. This agreement led to an explicit health and wellbeing dimension to Future Paisley with Step Change 2 changing to 'raise prosperity and increase wellbeing in our communities.' Prosperity is defined as a balance of more equitable economic sufficiency, health and wellbeing. The three outcomes attached to Step Change 2 are; enhanced mental health and reduced loneliness in our communities, children and young people thrive through everyday access to arts and culture, and marginalised groups build confidence and transferable work skills through cultural participation.

I draw on Li's (2007) viewpoint of focusing on the practices of assembling policy to view how Future Paisley grows a health and wellbeing dimension. These practices are the process of hard work pulling together something that coheres into policy. Li identifies a practice of reassembling which is the adding of new entities to the assemblages, repurposing existing ones and shifting the meaning of key terms. This section has shown the reassembling process that Future Paisley underwent to repurpose and add entities to grow a health and wellbeing dimension.

9.4.5. Developing alignments with policy

The capacity for Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension to develop happenings, is bolstered the increased focus on health and wellbeing by non-health organisations, as shown by the example of Paisley Museum's health and wellbeing activities in Chapters 6, 7 and 8. These activities have a community-centred focus, bringing a community-centred health approach to the role. I note that for OneRen, the overall organisation strategy for Paisley Museum, the previous organisational strategy for 2018-2022 health is mentioned as an impact through 'residents who live healthily for longer.' The vision changes in the next Business Strategy for 2021-2026 (Renfrewshire Leisure, 2021) from one of 'enriching people's lives through increased participation in culture, leisure, and sport' to a new vision of 'everyone locally living lives that are healthy, happy, and fulfilled' with a mission to 'improve our community's health and wellbeing.' The language in the organisational strategy has moved from customers to community with a current mission statement that declares; 'we are passionate about the part we play in improving life-long physical and mental health in every one of our communities.' This language aligns with the language of Step Change 2. This document also articulates that being in

active partnership with others, such as RHSCP, will be a core part of the approach to delivering health and wellbeing.

What is gathered into Future Paisley, is a continuing process as cultural regeneration's health and wellbeing dimension is one element in the interactions between the health and social care sector and the culture and the arts sector. At the end of 2021, CAHSC is again restructured with a new oversight group to provide direction to CAHSC that includes the Chief Executive of OneRen, Renfrewshire cultural regeneration team members and members of RHSCP. The process to develop Future Paisley leaves the scope of Step Change 2 wider than the activities of CAHSC. At the same time the activities of CAHSC are considered to be wider than Future Paisley. As alongside Future Paisley Step Change 2, the oversight group will be informed by OneRen's and RHSCP strategic plans. What will be gathered will depend on the new post of the CAHSC co-ordinator. The two-year job was advertised in April 2022. This role creates for CAHSC the resource of a dedicated staff member to drive forward the agenda of embedding culture and the arts in health and social care sector. The role will also be responsible for designing a cultural strategy for health and social care sector and developing partnerships and networks. This role and three other connected roles form the new delivery activity of Step Change 2. These other roles are: the Social and Cultural Prescribing Co-ordinator, a Cultural Champions Network Co-ordinator that focuses on creative learning, and an Arts and Cultural Engagement Support Worker that focuses on The Promise, a commitment by the Scottish Government to the care experienced community. The coherence of the cultural regeneration's health and wellbeing dimension will be shaped by how these four roles connect and the relational labour undertaken both within the roles and between the roles. Possibilities for the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley may range from cohering a life course approach as the children and young people dimension of Step Change 2 segues into the adult dimension, or there could be fragmentation of activities across the life course into the agendas of the organisers employing these roles. The sustainability of what will be gathered beyond the posts, will shape the future evolution of cultural regeneration's health and wellbeing dimension.

Li (2007) identifies a practice of assemblage of forging alignments which is 'the work of linking together the objectives of the various parties to an assemblage, both those who aspire to govern conduct and those whose conduct is to be conducted.' (Li, 2007, p. 265). This section has shown the ongoing work of developing and aligning governance structures, such as between the Future Paisley's Step Changes, CAHSC, and Renfrewshire's culture and health organisations. CAHSC has until 2022 relied on the capacity of members who have other roles. The lack of dedicated resources within CAHSC has hampered the relational work needed to forge alignments. With the four new

roles and the articulation of a new set of Step Changes, the resources dedicated to forging alignments has significantly increased.

9.5. Conditions and processes for gathering

9.5.1. Place and connections

Interviewees mentioned that the size of Renfrewshire is ideal for making Future Paisley cohere. Paisley is large enough to make a bid for UKCoC21 status and small enough that people know each other. I observe multiple links and relationships that draw organisations together and shape the intertwining of culture, arts, health and social care. Some connections are less visible such as Board Membership or attendance at events. Others are more discernible such as projects. An example has been shown in Chapter 6 regarding the Scottish Government's Communities Mental Health & Wellbeing Fund. Another example I observe from conversations and social media is Paisley Museum has co-production projects with Kairos Women+, a community-led space that aims to be a second home for women and non-binary people. The charity shared a space with STAR Project while their new space was being made ready. Kairos Women+ is part of the Ethnic Communities Cultural Steering Group. This alliance includes Engage Renfrewshire and OneRen and organises events for Black History Month, with funding support from Future Paisley and Engage Renfrewshire. This example is a slice of the connectivity between these groups and the multiplicity of linkages. I could reconfigure these groups into a different arrangement by selecting a different set of connections. Interviewees talk about knowing who to go to when they want something due to the conversations, trust, and working together that has happened in the last few years. Therefore, the gatherings of cultural regeneration policy also gather constellations of relationships.

9.5.2. People

I raise a concern in one interview that these connections of trust can be exclusionary. In my experience there is a danger that reliance on those you know and trust, means the same groups get funded, growing their capacity and leading to imbalances of power and influences between groups. I ask how this can be mitigated and how other groups can grow into the next STAR Project. The reply is that the layering of opportunity and networks in Renfrewshire gives multiple points for involvement. They talk about how in their role to develop third sector capacity in Renfrewshire they reach out to charities and groups and go to places and meetings where organisations may be and take note of who is there. As mentioned in Chapter 6, I hear in a meeting that a charity formed during COVID-19 described its growth and the support received from other charities and

organisations. The charity speaks enthusiastically about the experience of being at the end of this practice of reaching out and their involvement in networks.

The work to gather elements into the practice of a policy that seeks to create more interaction between culture, the arts, and health and wellbeing, requires people who can cross boundaries between sectors. Daykin (2019a) terms these individuals who build bridges between different groups and domains, as boundary workers. A related term Daykin uses is boundary spanners for those who work across these areas. Boundary working is one way to examine the work of community-centred health approaches. One of these individuals describes themselves as a wearer of many hats. They work across strategy and delivery, across different strategies, facilitate networks, draw people in and work across sectors. The new CAHSC co-ordinator role could be thought of as a boundary worker, along with the three other new posts created in this period. The collective purpose of these four roles is given in meetings I attended as the builders of the cultural ecology in health and social care. These workers could be thought of as cultural workers who seek various ways to configure new relationships between art, culture, and society (Bennett, 2017).

As I follow the research trail of boundary workers and practices of assemblages, I start to see how cultural workers could be viewed as boundary workers who use culture to make things happen by gathering relationships. In a workshop with Renfrewshire Arts Team, the way some people talk about their roles fits with my emerging view. Unlike Bennett's (2017) view of culture workers as configuring new relationships, based on my observations, I view configuring relationships as ongoing work such as existing relationships configuring, deepening, opening up to others, and transporting existing relationships into new partnerships. The community response to lockdowns during COVID-19 shows that community-centred approaches to health and wellbeing can be nimble due to quickly identifying those in need and having the bureaucratic freedom to respond. I observe on social media and in newsletters, that foodbanks were delivering art packs and art organisations were delivering food packs. Closeness to the community mattered more than the organisation type and activity. This response shows fluidity in thinking of who are cultural workers and who are public health workers and resonates with a comment from an interviewee that culture should be a fluid living organism.

I suggest that expanding the idea of who is considered a public health worker is an important role of any proposal for the fifth wave of public health. I observe opportunities for how this can occur in Paisley. In a conversation I have with Paisley Museum, I hear a suggestion that all staff should be trained to be more inclusive such as training in mental health, neurodiversity and antiracism. I mention how this training could contribute to public-facing staff being considered health and wellbeing staff. As with this training, these staff are more skilled in creating atmospheres of

belonging and affective resources that can facilitate health-creating encounters. I observe another instance of what could be considered a boundary worker facilitating health and wellbeing emerging from OneRen's greater organisational focus on health and wellbeing. The new business plan identifying a priority as having staff who are community builders.

9.5.3. Events

Events such as the UK City of Culture competition catalyse partnerships (Culture, Place and Policy Institute, University of Hull, 2018; Munro, 2020). Paisley demonstrates that this catalytic effect occurs for applicants to the UKCoC21 bidding process and provides a route to gather and embed organisations into the practice of policy. Paisley's partnership approach to cultural regeneration at a local authority level is unique in Scotland. Eight out of Scotland's 32 local authority councils submitted a public opinion on the draft Scottish Culture Strategy consultation that opened in 2018. Renfrewshire Council was the only local authority governance to provide opinion through a partnership. The UKCoC21 bid was found to have:

'Strengthened existing partnerships and brought new partners and offers of funding to the table. For organisations involved in established partnerships, such as community planning, the focussed process of bidding, its immovable deadlines and the understanding of mutual benefits, brought a fresh imperative to the benefits of working collaboratively.'

(Crearie, 2018, p. 4)

9.5.4. Time

Time is a condition for the alignment of cultural activities with non-cultural activities. Renfrewshire Arts Team talked about how doing good work meant fully being able to do things together with everybody. This relational work required time to build trust, understand what they could contribute and be invited to conversations. This trust is now happening after a couple of years. I have also heard in conversations how this trust and understanding extends to working with the community. Through this trust process, other areas are more open to ideas about working with the community and know that the Team is a resource if they wish to engage with communities. The approach of the Team to work across cross-sectors and with communities and groups could be viewed through the idea of boundary spanners. Daykin (2019a) identified time and perseverance as a requirement of this type of work and that there is a need to be seen as legitimate by other workers. I was told by an interviewee how at the beginning of the bid process the relevance of culture, to issues from potholes to poverty, was greeted with scepticism. Legitimacy was built from repeated conversations. Over time, this built trust and a closer alignment between culture and the needs of the community.

Time is needed for Future Paisley's intention of embedding culture and arts in other sectors. Time is needed to align these other sectors with cultural activities. The activities to align non-cultural sectors through the new co-ordinator roles for Step Change 2 are being implemented for only a year or two. The new areas of work as part of Step Change 2 I hear referred to as system change and sustainable change. Coherence is sought between connecting projects. The terms used are pathways and pipelines. This coherence will enable services and projects to leverage cultural participation as a step towards one of Future Paisley's Step Changes. However, the short period of time for these new roles means the conditions for embedding are not favourable. This short period results in a disconnect with my observations that those involved with Future Paisley understand that building relationships and an environment of working together, where constant conversations with communities and other sectors are part of good practice.

9.5.5. Listening as a gathering process

Paisley has a variety of ways of gathering, from participatory practices such as co-production and co-creation activities with the Museum and SMHAFF, to more formal networks such as the SPG Connectedness Network and CAHSC. These ways of gathering weave organisations into an array of relationships with each other. What is woven together, their interests, and their capabilities will affect the whole. Labour is required to layer activity from Future Paisley and its connectivity to other strategies, to the activities of its constituent parts such as CAHSC, to the activities of the organisations that constitute all these parts. How to undertake the work of connecting all the parts and programmes is a recurrent theme I observe in meetings to create a system of services so that people who encounter one programme can move smoothly onto another programme.

My observations find listening can be thought of as a gathering process to create relationships between culture and people. Interviewees mentioned that they had encountered people in their work who said culture was not for them and they did not do anything creative. Listening to these opinions and feelings I observe is a starting point to engagement, a process of starting where people are, rather than what you bring. I view this work is the labour of shaping existential feelings. Paisley Museum is engaging with mitigating this belief through its listening exercises and its co-production projects such as the example in Chapter 7 where Paisley Museum's practice of listening creates engagement and discussion that turn an atmosphere of fear into an atmosphere of potential belonging. One member of the Renfrewshire Arts Team commented that they never had a job that required so much listening. Interviewees enthusiastically talked about the many conversations they had in their roles in Paisley and how this was a core part of the strength of Paisley's bid. Engage Renfrewshire led engagement with the public about the UKCoC21 bid and 36,000 people joined in

the conversation (Crearie, 2018), corresponding to approximately half of the population of Paisley, and a fifth of the population of Renfrewshire.

I become part of the practice of listening in Paisley. New appointees to roles relating to loneliness, the Loneliness and Isolation Project Workers and Social and Cultural Prescribing Co-ordinator, ask for or are directed to conversations with me when they start their roles. This is part of many conversations they have with various organisations to get to know people and organisations, build connections, and understand existing activity and interests so that their programme of work can be tailored to build on what is already happening. Conversations with me, involved sharing my learnings about concepts of loneliness and social isolation and my knowledge of how to carry out evaluations. Listening, I was told in an interview, is an essential process for service development. Services must be meaningful to be trusted. Listening to those affected by the service is argued as key to understanding if a service works or fails. The skill of listening is a relational process as it requires reciprocity and may create affective encounters as people feel seen.

9.5.6. Ideas

What coheres depends on what health and wellbeing ideas are articulated and circulated. I have observed characteristics of the fourth wave of public health, such as social determinants of health and health inequalities. The stalling progress in reducing health inequality in Scotland suggests that there is still work to be done to fully deliver the fourth wave of public health. Future Paisley's emphasis on social regeneration as well as economic and physical regeneration builds a fourth wave approach to public health. There is no mention of affective resources or infrastructure which resonates with my growing awareness examined in Chapter 8, of the lack of explicit policy focus on the affective dimension of place and health and wellbeing. I have found in conversations a lack of familiarity of the term affective. I suggest this shows the disconnect between language and activities as this research has identified a range of activities and practices that are concerned with facilitating affective resources such as sense of belonging, sense of mattering and place attachment. Shifting ideas of health and society needs to bring the idea of affect into greater usage. I put forward my gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts as language that could make affect more visible to policy makers and practitioners and bring the idea of affect into policy.

I observe that the five ways of wellbeing are used to report the wellbeing impact of activities in Paisley. The New Economics Foundation (Ng *et al.*, 2015) was tasked by the government to develop evidenced actions to develop personal wellbeing and came up with five ways of wellbeing. These are: connect, be active, take notice, keep learning, and give. The five ways of wellbeing approach is used across a range of settings in the UK from health to education and is used globally (Ng *et al.*,

2015). My brought self has found the approach useful in my professional career as it avoids conceptual difficulties of wellbeing. Amongst people in Paisley, there is an awareness and usage of the five ways of wellbeing. I have found the way of 'take notice' a useful starting point for bringing up my ideas about the importance of small moments in discussions about my research. Two of these ways, 'connect' and 'give' I use as an opening to talk about relational activities. This opening offers me a starting point to undertake the work of counter-conceptualising of health and wellbeing in discussions with people in Paisley.

9.5.7. Learning from emergencies

I observe in meetings and in documents that a learning from lockdown in Renfrewshire was that a responsive and connected third sector could preventatively keep people connected and active. I find the effects of the strong links between the third sector, Renfrewshire Council, RHSCP and the TSI, Engage Renfrewshire, in my observations of Paisley through social media, meetings after the first lockdown and drawing on reports of learnings from the period. I observed these links could swiftly harness people's desire to volunteer, which is a health and wellbeing activity in itself. The learning highlighted the importance of local knowledge. The existing strong links between organisations on the RHSPC strategic board were strengthened through this period. For example, setting up the seven Neighbourhood Hubs in March 2020 by a partnership between Renfrewshire Council, RHSCP, and Engage Renfrewshire. A report by Carnegie UK (Coutts *et al.*, 2020) examines how community hubs were part of the emergency response to COVID-19. The report finds that the Neighbourhood Hubs in Renfrewshire had strong connections to the local communities, which minimised duplication of activities. The Hubs could respond to what was already existing and concentrate activities in areas lacking a strong community group. The sense of emergency reduced bureaucratic hurdles. The Hubs had the ethos of seeing people as a whole, being kind, and community empowerment. The ethos directed an approach where people were given a choice of support. The Hubs provided support that went beyond what is traditionally considered basic needs such as food and medicine and providing toys and dog walking. Needs which align with Oman's (2015) analysis of what matters to people discussed in Chapter 5 and the discussion of trivial and mundane moments and loneliness in Chapter 8. This lesson has been learnt before. Crummy (1992) describes the community partnership response to the severe winter of 1981/1982 in similar terms. Red tape was slashed as the Craigmillar Festival Society worked with statutory bodies to form a co-ordinated team based at the community centre that harnessed a whole range of workers, including volunteers, churches, health visitors, the police, council workers, and the Department of Social Security. Crummy (1992, p. 104) finishes her story with a quote that could apply to many of the community responses to COVID-19:

‘People are capable of taking the initiative and responding quickly and effectively to need, given that there is trust and an efficient local co-ordinating structure functioning in the heart of the community.’

The Scottish Government has drawn on these lessons. In Chapter 6 the Scottish Government’s Communities Mental Health and Wellbeing Fund was introduced. Grassroots community groups and third sector organisations are requested to apply with proposals to deliver activities and programmes to reconnect and revitalise communities in order to take a preventative approach to mental health. In Renfrewshire, the fund will contribute to the capacity of Engage Renfrewshire to work with the community and further the relationship working with the RHSCP. As evaluated in Chapter 6, the fund will increase local capacity for cultural production as some of these proposals involve cultural activities. Renfrewshire and Craigmillar’s responses to emergencies align with research into how small-scale and co-designed spaces can help tackle society’s challenges, and how the pandemic made grassroots community solutions more visible, due to the speed of problem solving and organising to help mitigate the economic and social impact of the pandemic (Lange, 2022). COVID-19 has strengthened relationships between RHSCP SPG members and helped strengthen the recognition of the importance of working together and that organisations need each other (Renfrewshire Health and Social Care Partnership, 2021b). A shift in thinking about health and society is needed so the same lessons do not need to be repeatedly learnt, and to ensure these assets and relationships exist and are nurtured to respond to the next emergency or crisis.

9.5.8. The intent for culture

Future Paisley’s intentions in using culture in its place-based policy are stated in response to the draft Culture Strategy for Scotland²³. In Paisley, culture is being used to steer collective action for the purpose of a regeneration of Paisley that includes physical, social, and economic regeneration. I observe culture is a coordinating force in Paisley to gather different sectors together, and culture is used as a mobilising agent to engage people in a conversation about the future of Paisley²⁴. This statement is an instrumental use of culture beyond the rhetoric of narrow economic instrumentalism (Belfiore, 2012).

²³ https://consult.gov.scot/culture-tourism-and-major-events/culture-strategy/consultation/published_select_respondent

²⁴ <https://www.renfrewshire.gov.uk/article/12243/Future-Paisley-exhibition-showing-how-town-being-transformed-now-open>

Hadley and Gray (2017) identify a type of instrumentalism, hyperinstrumentalism, where the value of culture is only in its ability to meet non-cultural goals. In discussions in Paisley about the use of culture in health and wellbeing, I observe a concern with supporting people and communities to do meaningful things. There is less concern with mass participation and professional production of culture, although this is one of the outcomes of Step Change 3, which states that 'innovation in Paisley's flagship venues leads to wider engagement by local and national audiences.' I observe in workshops to develop Step Change 2 that culture is considered to have value because it has the potential to be meaningful to people and to be used to think about how to make services meaningful. The nature of the connection varies depending on the stakeholder's perspective, such as education or volunteering. These meetings about cultural participation are service-focused and about engaging with activities that will increase learning, skills development, and economic activity. I observe in discussions that support for culture is about people's relationship to culture rather than about participation. Support for culture is about feeling that culture is for you; however, you may define it, even if you do not participate. I find this stance stated publicly by Paisley Partnership Board's (2018a) response to the draft Culture Strategy for Scotland:

'We'll know the strategy's working when we stop having to point out what constitutes a cultural activity and when our more disadvantaged community members 'feel/believe' that they have equality of access, that culture does indeed belong to everyone. We will also stop differentiating between different 'levels' of cultural activity, i.e., grassroots/community and formal.'

I observe participation is an emergent effect rather than a goal. I observe that there is a view that participation is best achieved obliquely (Kay, 2004) rather than as an outcome. I hear participation possibly increasing through people enthused by their encounter with a cultural activity or place and will return with family and friends.

The use of culture in Paisley is more nuanced than the arguments of instrumentalisation of policy allows. Using culture for non-cultural purposes is inherent in an asset-based approach such as Future Paisley. However, culture's value is not only about reaching those other goals. I observe across my research encounters in Paisley, in conversations, interviews, discussions and reports culture is considered part of everyday life. This view of culture emerges in the composition of the strategic leadership for Future Paisley. For example, the involvement of the leisure trust in strategic leadership broadens culture to encompass leisure. Not all leisure trusts in Scotland also encompass cultural and heritage venues and this is a relatively recent development in Renfrewshire with Renfrewshire Council's cultural assets being transferred to OneRen in 2015 (Renfrewshire Leisure,

2015). I see a document in a meeting in the summer of 2020 after the first phase of lockdown, which illustrates the community and cultural response to COVID-19 in Renfrewshire, the examples range from quizzes to litter picking. Organisations range from housing association, community centres, and project delivering sports activities to Renfrewshire Council teams.

In Chapters 5, 6, 7 and 8 culture through a lens of the everyday is threaded through people's lives, environment, history, and context. It is one of the possible threads that weave through the life-course and the different areas of an individual's life. An asset-based approach pulls the asset that threads through the most areas such as health, employment, and education. Assets are formed by local context, geographies, histories, and needs. In Paisley, these assets are culture. The report *Untold Story's* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014) account of Paisley's heritage and its history examines these assets. Hadley and Gray (2017) are concerned that these non-cultural arguments for policy weaken the case for cultural policy. For if culture and arts are not shown to make a demonstrable difference to health and wellbeing, then funding will be given for something that can achieve these outcomes better. In a complex context such as health and wellbeing, where attribution is hard to do and changes take a long time to be visible, how to achieve outcomes will be uncertain. I find Hadley and Gray's point partly acute for the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley, particular in terms of preventative health and wellbeing. The focus on demonstrable difference can have a warping effect by shifting focus onto proximal factors on health and wellbeing and away from social and political determinants such as the example of 'lifestyle drift' that I examine in Chapter 2. My proposal for relational health, also has issues of demonstrating difference, due to culture and the arts, particularly activities that emerge through community-centred health, are not often a proximal factor on health and wellbeing.

9.6. Happenings

In Paisley a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social purposes was evolved from an asset-based strategy (Renfrewshire Council, 2014), through the catalytic effects of UKCoC21 bid (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b) and came into an explicit expression in the latest iteration of Future Paisley's Step Change 2. A health and wellbeing dimension to this strategy has grown through these iterations into explicit acknowledgement in Step Change 2 and resourced with four co-ordinators who I have viewed as boundary workers. Understanding what a policy can do, the agentic power off the disparate elements gathered, is an examination of what possibilities for culture, arts, health, and wellbeing such a policy could create. These possibilities shape whether an approach of culture and wellbeing together can emerge and whether policy can shift ideas of health and society.

9.6.1. Gathered a sense of doing things together

The development of Paisley's UKCoC21 bid to the development and evolution of Future Paisley has created a sense of doing things together amongst some people and organisations. Renfrewshire Arts Team have expressed that what has emerged from the time spent relation building and trust that has developed is a sense that they are doing things together with other sectors and the community. An interviewee mentioned that doing things together was an outcome of the bid. In Chapter 6, I observe third-sector organisations and housing associations contribute to cultural activity and are embedded in projects and programmes. In conversations and interviews, community-based, co-production, and co-designed work is considered regular practice. One interviewee feels there is no longer a sense of 'going to talk' to the community groups as there are constant conversations with community groups. Partnership is expressed to me as a practice, as connections need to be maintained, and an openness to new connections needs to be kept up such as trying to attend as many meetings and invitations as feasibly possible.

Co-production and co-creation are practices that I encounter in Paisley in both the culture and the arts sector and the health and social care sector in chapters 6, 7 and 8. These complex and contentious practices offer promises of flattening hierarchies and broadening the range of knowledge gathered into policy and service design such as lived experience. However, they also face challenges of being co-opted into existing systems (Raffay *et al.*, 2022; Rowley *et al.*, 2022). It is beyond the scope of my research to explore the conceptual and implementation challenges of these practices. These practices exist at the project level in Paisley. I observe the keenness to use these approaches in a Future Paisley evaluation workshop.

I presented my emerging argument to the Future Paisley Partnership Board in the summer of 2021. The golden thread, or more appropriately to Paisley, the Sma' Shot²⁵ of the argument, is the call for focusing on small moments. I title the presentation *Small is beautiful: a study of health as if people mattered*. A deliberate riff on Schumacher's (1993) radical economic book as I am presenting to strategic partners of a policy usually dominated by the economic dimension. In addition, I observed that Paisley frequently expresses its desire to live up to its radical past. For example in a report that sets out ideas to maintain the legacy of UKCoC21, part of the vision includes the phrase 'to reignite our radical and entrepreneurial spirit' (Crearie, 2018). I talked about taking the idea of small moments as a way of being attentive to moments of transformation and how this attunement can

²⁵ The cotton thread which binds all the colour weft threads into the warps of a Paisley shawl.

contribute to building the system change that Future Paisley is seeking. I illustrate how scaling up can be undertaken not just by making existing programmes bigger but could also be built from the multiplicity and accumulation of small moments and the implications for evaluation of focusing on small moments. My argument aligns with the lessons learned from emergencies, in Renfrewshire, Craigmillar, and more broadly as discussed in Section 9.5.7. I bring my argument of focusing on the everyday to attune to the nuance of activities. I find the idea of small moments and the everydayness of culture as having a transformational and sustainable effect on people's lives has resonance with the audience. Thinking small is a way of resisting abstraction. It is not a dismissal of the global. It is about focusing on how do we live together, be well together, and make our way through life together? The theme small is beautiful resonated with Future Paisley Partnership Board.

Focusing on the everyday and small moments counters the tendency that Oakley (2015) identifies in urban regeneration to focus on newness and spectacle and an unclear fit with everyday culture and aligns. During the period of this research, there are many new activities in Paisley, from a new book festival to hosting the first date for a UK tour of a year-long national event celebrating the UK's creativity²⁶. I observed this tension in discussions and interviews. Everyday culture is valued, but not brought to the fore, as capturing these moments and its effect on everyday life is challenging as the orthodox evaluation tools are not equipped for this task.

Using knowledge grown in Chapter 6, I suggested a focus on community-centred health and informal health lens could assist in navigating this tension. This focus grounds urban regeneration in activities that inherently matter to people. Everyday culture by its continual nature, rather than the splash of the spectacle, has the potential to weave its way into existential feelings that are the affective backgrounds of our lives and shape our being in the world. This sustained influence highlights Crossick and Kaszynska's (2016) point that small cultural assets may have more sustained positive effects than relatively larger assets.

9.6.2. What is valued?

I observed in conversations involving people outside the cultural sector in Paisley that there is a commitment and a belief in culture as a way to improve how services are delivered and as a way for achieving social outcomes. I suggested in Chapter 6 community-centred health can help with coherence by linking with and gathering in the culture and health-related activities outside culture and healthcare sector. The research trails have found these activities emerging in informal

²⁶ <https://www.millmagazine.co.uk/about-us-comes-to-paisley/>

healthcare activities, in practices where the two are entwined and in community groups and organisations with neither the word culture and health in the name or website description. These activities could be made more visible to strategic stakeholders through engagement with the language of Future Paisley, by using the term prosperity which is used in Step Change 2. The use of the term prosperity in Step Change 2 along with wellbeing, provides an opportunity to put relational thinking into policy and strengthen the explicitness of the health and wellbeing dimension. I suggested that definitions for prosperity could assist this shift in thinking of health and society, for example, by describing prosperity as residing in relationships. Assemblages of health would develop this idea further by describing prosperity as being rich in social, material, and affective resources. Prosperity would be gained through healthy ecosystems and its constituent parts due to a non-human approach. This articulation of prosperity would bring together culture and nature, and therefore projects that involve both activities could be more holistically articulated. Altogether this would give an idea of connective health and wellbeing, bringing to the fore ideas existing across different fields, giving room for voices less heard, strongly linked to place and theoretically informed. This description would be the shift in thinking about health and society the fifth wave of public health requires and provides the radical language that Future Paisley aspires to. The process of developing the strategic prosperity into one fitting the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health could be considered as one of Li's (2007) practices of assemblage, specifically reassemblage.

Future development of creative health and cultural policy could learn from Paisley as cultural policy is usually talked about in the macro (Gibson, 2019). The locally focused approach of my research highlights leadership and partnership working particular to the local health and community context. This is relevant to the future of the arts and health sector in Scotland. A Creative Scotland mapping report of arts and health (Rocket Science, 2021, p. 26) notes the need for a strong TSI to develop the sector without elaborating what that means. The report notes a strong TSI is:

'A useful network to share services and enhance / promote participation...Organisations noted that it is a challenge to build partnerships between arts organisations and health care providers. There is currently limited engagement with Health and Social Care Partnerships, though there are likely to be regional variations in this.'

Through my research trails I have had a variety of research encounters with Engage Renfrewshire in a range of contexts and grown a knowledge of what TSIs could do. I have examined the features of a mature TSI and the possibilities it creates, which goes beyond sharing services and promoting participation and forms a core part of building partnerships with health providers, particularly HSCPs.

9.6.3. Evolution of the use of culture in policies

In UKCoC21 legacy report (Paisley Partnership Board, 2018b) I found that the field of arts and health was gathered in through social prescribing and I observe the influence of the APPGAHW report (2017) due to its front cover appearing in the report. The evolution of activities where culture emerges from means, Paisley has evolved dimensions of culture, arts, health, and wellbeing outside the usual typology of arts and health as evaluated in Chapters 5 and 6.

Cultural regeneration policy is an ongoing process that is developing analogue structures to other policies and strategies in other geographical places that are bringing culture, arts, health, and wellbeing together such as Coventry, the winner of the UKCoC21 competition, Wales²⁷; Greater Manchester, and the Australian state of Victoria²⁸. The use of culture in policy in these areas goes beyond the economic dimension. Analogue activities include co-creation with communities and co-ordinator roles to embed culture and arts in healthcare and social prescribing. I find culture has been used for wellbeing through community approaches as a way to work with communities that may be marginalised. In my conversations with people in Paisley, I shared documents, reports, and blog posts from other areas. I highlight in these conversations Paisley's ambition to be the leading place for creative health activity even though it has a significantly smaller population these other areas, even when considering Renfrewshire as a whole. I find Greater Manchester's ambitions in Social Glue (Parkinson, 2021) resonate with Paisley's ambitions, yet Renfrewshire has approximately 6% of the population of Greater Manchester. This has resource implications for what type of evaluation and evidence can be delivered, such as dedicated data collectors, evaluation and coordinating roles such as Coventry has for its UK City of culture programme. Future Paisley seeks to embed evaluation in all activities to complement its high-level evaluation, however I find a lack of capacity to undertake this work.

9.6.4. Reassembling initiatives

From my observations in Paisley, local authority place-based policy can play a coordinating role between local and national initiatives. New developments emerging from national health and cultural policy can be woven into new initiatives at the local level. I suggest that policy informed by community-centred health and a cultural democracy approach has the potential to gather into policy informal culture and informal health activity. At a local level an asset-based approach could be

²⁷ <https://www.nhsconfed.org/publications/advancing-arts-health-and-wellbeing>

²⁸ <https://www.vichealth.vic.gov.au/our-work/arts-and-social-connection>

cohered as this is the level at which TSI, HSCP and leisure trusts operate, and knowledge of local health, wellbeing and cultural assets, and networks can be found and formed. The ‘taking of elsewhere’ that constitutes policy takes in developments from the field of arts and health, but this could also take in the tensions. The Creative Scotland mapping report (2021) has a narrow approach to arts and health. The cultural regeneration approach in Paisley gives room for a wider approach to culture for example non-artist led cultural activities, can be emphasised, supported, and connected to not just arts and health, but to community health.

Future Paisley brings a variety of approaches to public health. There is the community-centred health approach of RHSCP strengthened by the strong link to an active TSI, Engage Renfrewshire as examined in Chapter 6 and in this chapter. The presence of Paisley Museum brings in health and wellbeing ideas from this field as analysed in Chapter 5, particularly from the literature regarding care as described in Chapter 7 if the idea of museums as places of social care is embraced or as an example of an enabling place as shown in Chapter 8. There is strength in peer and lived experience processes through the Renfrewshire Community Planning Partnership’s Alcohol and Drugs Commission, one of the first of its kind in Scotland and a strategically engaged Leisure Trust which earlier in this chapter has declared its passion for improving health and wellbeing in communities. Therefore, a cultural regeneration policy can bring in and weave the multiplicity of wider approaches to public health.

9.6.5. Reassembling and the wellbeing agenda

This research argues that an explicit focus on health and wellbeing by place-based policies leveraging culture opens policy up to a range of perspectives compared to the dominant economic arguments. However economic arguments are also moving towards incorporating wellbeing. The Scottish Government is enthusiastic about the wellbeing economy²⁹.

The wellbeing economy agenda argues for a broader approach to the economy beyond GDP. Widening the economy to encompass a greater range of factors echoes the path of widening health to encompass a more diverse range of factors. I have argued that a social model of health provides a contribution to thinking about health beyond the biomedical model, however without explicitly resisting individualism and reductionism, is not equipped to tackle fifth wave of public health challenges. This argument can be extended to argue that a wellbeing economy needs my proposed version of the fifth wave of public health, one that is characterised by relational health. A wellbeing

²⁹ <https://www.gov.scot/groups/wellbeing-economy-governments-wego/>

economy may still remain within a dominant framework of focusing on the individual and the human rather than encompassing the collective and nonhuman (Atkinson, 2020). The struggle to conceptualise and operationalise collective wellbeing as something more than the sum of individual wellbeing contributes to the difficulty of moving away from individualism. Wellbeing policy and practice has had limited engagement with theories of relationality, assemblage and post-human (Atkinson, 2020). Engagement with these theories would give stakeholders in Future Paisley the radical thinking they aspire to.

A wellbeing economy approach to policy, despite its best intentions for more participatory practices (Wellbeing Economy Alliance, 2021), could lapse into reductionist tendencies by replacing one measurement, GDP, with a group of measurements. The tensions I have highlighted in this thesis created by reductionist and causal narrative approaches to evidence, will not be resolved. Such as the example in Chapter 2 of how the measurement of salutogenesis crowds out the spirit of the idea (Kickbusch, 1996). I offer a proposal for the fifth wave of public health that is characterised by relational health that serves as a necessary critical approach to wellbeing measures. My thesis has highlighted the uneasy relationship between cultural policy and wellbeing measures (Campbell, Cox and O'Brien, 2017; Oman, 2021) and critiques from health and cultural geography research with the concept and measurement of health and wellbeing (Atkinson, 2020). If the wellbeing economy is to be implemented in policy, engagement with critical approaches to wellbeing is necessary to ensure the intentions of participatory practices are realised.

9.6.6. Reassembling health and wellbeing

An asset-based approach to policy starts with the problem. In Paisley this is deindustrialisation. The solution is heritage assets. Overtime these heritage assets grew into cultural assets as the idea of cultural regeneration was assembled from parts elsewhere (Renfrewshire Council, 2014). Examining cultural regeneration policy through health and wellbeing, results in a process of reassembling cultural regeneration to fit this domain. Where ideas from elsewhere such as social prescribing and from the field of arts in health are drawn into Paisley's policy assemblage. The conceptual view of culture as everyday draws community centred health into the assemblage. These are ideas that I have evaluated as being driven by leadership from health and community organisations. A policy assemblage with a health and wellbeing focus centres these organisations, who could possibly be more marginal in a wellbeing economy focused policy assemblage.

A place-based policy designed to improve health and wellbeing requires more reassembling than looking at economic regeneration which has many established typologies. Paisley has taken on the typologies of events and landmark capital projects. Economic value in the practice of economic

regeneration is relatively uncontested in Scotland, usually one of jobs and GDP or Gross Value Added. The narrowness has led to the move to consider economic value as insufficient and the use of wellbeing as the value of the economy. What model of cultural regeneration emerges in a wellbeing economy has been little explored. Paisley aims for more than a change of economic systems. One way of looking at health could be to see how events and visits to cultural venues also generate social and cultural values along with economic value. This approach uses methods such as social return on investment or surveys of wellbeing impact from attending events. Future Paisley has multiple approaches. Future Paisley, by having health organisations integral to the partnership, and the delivery results in the health and wellbeing dimension assembled through the doings of partners. By having health and wellbeing as a Step Change, regardless of the clarity of definition, means that practitioners who combined both culture and health and wellbeing in their practice could be drawn into a larger collective whole and contribute a systemwide landscape of connected encounters between culture, health, and wellbeing

9.6.7. Evaluation as the forging of alignments

I have found from being invited to discussions about evaluation, that this process contributes to what is valued and guiding what coheres. Evaluation could be considered as one of Li's (2007) practices of assembling policy, that of 'forging alignment'. The approach to evaluation, such as whose knowledge it considers will influence the future possibilities for the use of culture in the design of policy in Paisley. There are three evaluation processes. Evaluation of Future Paisley overall undertaken in partnership with CCSE. It is used to identify impact, question Future Paisley's influence and hypothesis to change, and assess if further investment by Council to extend Future Paisley beyond 2024 is justified. There are PhD projects of which this research is one. The third level is project and programme level evaluation. In conversations, I note a demand that change must be demonstrated across the physical, social, and economic domains, including health and wellbeing due to Future Paisley.

As my evaluation practice develops due to undertaking training and an expanding conceptual toolkit, my situated self moves on from its logic chain-based approach. As the ethos of action research is to be useful and logic chains are what CAHSC would like to develop for its projects. I offer my expertise at the beginning of my time with CAHSC with a couple of projects. We work through their logic chains, to have a framework to think through what they want to achieve, how they can go about it and how they can show it. This shapes what their project evaluation processes seek to find out. This logic chain evaluation approach could be considered as another of Li's (2007) practices of assembling policy, that of 'rendering technical' which is the process of reducing the messiness of policies to a

diagram that shows linear narratives where interventions are applied to a problem to produce results. This practice underplays the openness and diffuseness of policy which has been highlighted in this chapter, such as emergent cultural activities and by the describing of the entities gathered into the Future Paisley cultural programme through relationship working.

My later conversations take a more critical approach to evaluation. I attune more to the tensions between what people do, what they think is valuable and transformative in their work. I seek out the moonbeams (Tanner, 2020) and the everyday (Artlink, 2005; Doherty and De St Croix, 2019). My brought self has had many conversations that have started with 'this is what I need to do and show, how do I do this?'. Turning this around to ask, 'tell me what you do and the change you think it makes?' opens the conversation. I received passionate answers, tales of little moments that people felt were transformative but would never have mentioned if we started with the first question. As people feel this is not what evaluation processes look for or is too intangible to measure. I reassured people that this knowledge is valid and that we should think through how we can make it tangible. Evaluations could crowd out the space for reflection and learning (Jancovich and Stevenson, 2021). Instead of asking how data can be captured and build evidence bases, I promote my emerging belief that evaluation can be a relational process and a practice of mutual caring and recognition, thus further health and wellbeing. Policies that are designed to use culture and the arts for social ends such as Future Paisley, with its assets of artists, creatives, and socially engaged practices, should be the ideal policy context for bringing this agenda forward. Using their creativity to make tangible the intangible and develop and embed creative research and evaluation approaches. Evaluation processes could produce cultural outputs as well as health and wellbeing.

The process of evaluation by CAHSC was put on hold due to COVID-19. A CAHSC Research and Evaluation was formed in January 2020 as part of the restructuring of CAHSC, and I was invited to be a member and develop my action research proposal with the group who would become a community of enquiry, and this would have also fed into the work of Renfrewshire Arts Team. Evaluation of CAHSC is now proposed to be managed by the new CAHSC co-ordinator through the hiring of an external consultant.

I was invited by those delivering the evaluation of Future Paisley to attend an evaluation workshop for those involved in Step Change 2. This had the aim to try to understand what kind of impacts project leaders think their projects and activities might have or have already had. This workshop highlighted a theme regarding excellence in practice. This is also an interest of Future Paisley Project Board. A possible future would be knowing how a policy foregrounding excellence in practice is experienced through co-produced evaluations.

Raw (2014) identifies a key characteristic of community-based, participatory arts practice as intuition. This is defined as working responsively, drawing on feelings, which may emerge out of atmospheres. Several boundary spanners mention intuition as part of practice. For one person, it negates the question of what works, as what works is something that is felt in the moment and responded to immediately. Intuition creates a further tension between evaluation and arts practice. My brought self has found that evaluation can align practitioners with policy or distance them, again highlighting Li's (2007) forging of alignment as a practice of policy assemblage. I notice this in my conversations, sometimes I find the way people talk about evaluation in their role, that it has transactional nature, a task to be done to appease the funders. A task left to professional evaluators so they can get on with their work. When I discussed evaluations in terms of what evaluations can do for you, your project, and how you would like to communicate to Future Paisley and other funders, a much more engaged discussion occurs. The conversations that emerge are not about advocacy. Conversations are about the conceptual nature of culture and the arts and its social purposes. Affect comes into the conversations as there is talk about how to capture the change in atmosphere due to a showing, the change in conversations as excitement and interest rise and there is a sense of engagement and the sense of charge. Therefore, a radical means of systems change would be instead of asking what we can do for evaluation, we ask what evaluation can do for us. In one of my meetings where I was invited to discuss the evaluation of a project, I suggested creating a manifesto for evaluation for making explicit the tension between what they feel they have to provide and what others find valuable and what they find valuable. I referred to Illich's Tools for Conviviality (Illich, 1973) to introduce the phrase convivial evaluation in conversations.

Wellbeing measures are rising in popularity (Hey, Musella and Hvide, 2022). However, I suggest that a commitment to cultural democracy and to centre people's experience requires a critical approach to utilising wellbeing measures. My commitment to cultural democracy prompts reflection on an exhibit I encountered in my volunteering. The piece critiqued wellbeing scales as another manifestation of uncaring practices that the exhibitor is subjected to by public services. I have seen the use of wellbeing scales in other settings intruding on atmospheres of belonging and safety. I have also seen scales used without negative effects in places where there are atmospheres of belong and safety as relationships have been built between those administering the scale and those surveyed. Attuning to the atmospheres in a space is needed to judge if the use of scales is appropriate. In an context where more evaluation is being demanded of culture and arts activity to justify their use for health and wellbeing (Rocket Science, 2021) and more toolkits and guidance are

being created³⁰, without anchoring what is meant by health and wellbeing in the relational, in the idea of becoming human, the pursuit of knowing what works crowds out knowing 'what matters' and erodes the spirit of cultural democracy. I consider administering wellbeing scales as a social justice issue, which aligns with the multiplicity of tensions Oman (2021) considers between wellbeing data and social justice.

9.7. Conclusion

In this chapter, I have followed the research trail of how a health and wellbeing dimension of a culture informed place-based policy comes together by growing understandings of the research puzzle, the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley. I have grown insights of what possibilities for health and wellbeing this dimension might create and whether these possibilities might contribute to my proposal for a fifth wave of public health.

I have found that Paisley has gathered many elements into a place-based policy designed to use culture for health and wellbeing. Some of these elements are created by other strategic gatherings local and national, creating more connections and layers for Future Paisley to weave into. An explicit strategic intent for health and wellbeing has emerged that aligns with organisations that are delivering Step Change 2. Resources are in place to make things happen. Other strategic forces align. Emerging from the gathering is a sense of doing things together. The period of my research has covered an in-between stage of Future Paisley, from its first written form and initial delivery structure to its latest intent and delivery structure. A period both disrupted and informed by COVID-19. Paisley is a place ripe with potential happenings, with roles being put in place to deliver the new iteration of Future Paisley and significant capital projects opening up in 2023. I gain insights into how gatherings have created possibilities that include the potential to facilitate relational health and deliver the radicalness Future Paisley aspires to. I gain insight into elements that could help realise these possibilities, including what ideas of health and wellbeing are brought into Future Paisley and what evaluation processes are developed. The realisation of these possibilities depends on what ideas of health and wellbeing are brought into Future Paisley and what evaluation processes are followed. I develop the insight that by continuing with the exploration into thinking about culture and wellbeing together could help us think about culture, the arts, health and wellbeing holistically as a greater whole. This counter-conceptualisation work would be an active process of resistance to the dominant paradigm of individualism and reductionism.

³⁰ <https://www.culturalvalue.org.uk/our-work/evaluation/evaluation-principles/>

The insights gained about my research puzzle and my research proposal are taken into the next chapter to examine the nature of my research contribution.

10. Conclusion

‘Before rejoining the kids in the body of the hall, Barry sighs: ‘In an ideal world we would get funded for building trusting relationships with young people.’ Maybe one day he will. It’s a task which, I can assure you, is not as easy – or simple – as it sounds.’

(McGarvey, 2017, p. 83)

10.1. Introduction

I start the chapter by outlining how the thesis makes a research contribution through four propositions of ‘adding to the model’. I then elaborate how on how the research contribution has emerged, summarising how the research evolved changed. The four propositions of ‘adding to the model’ provide the framework for the following sections, which demonstrate how I have grown insights in service of the aim of understanding the research puzzle, the health and wellbeing dimension of Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme and developing my proposal for the fifth wave of public health. The chapter closes with a discussion of the strengths and limitations of the research and offers suggestions for further research.

10.2. Research contribution

Take a model (Chapter 2), any model (Chapter 4) or framework. The Scottish National Performance is a popular framework in the context of my research, especially with the rise of the wellbeing agenda (Chapter 9). What is our relationship to models and frameworks in our everyday practice of evaluation (Chapters 4, 5 and 9), in designing policies (Chapters 5 and 9), when we view the changes our work and our practice makes (Chapter 6, 7 and 8)? Before I started this research (Chapters 3) I would have listened to you and encouraged you to develop a narrative and ways to evidence this narrative. I would help you shape and fit these narratives and evidence into these models and frameworks. People’s experiences would be cut up and simplified to better fit these models and frameworks (Chapter 5, 7 and 9).

The final purpose of this research was not the purpose I started with originally: my intention was to draw another model, to investigate the lines between boxes, examining the path from culture and the arts to health and wellbeing (Chapter 1). Within that scenario, my contribution would have been to refine and extend current models of health and wellbeing. These models could be used to frame how culture and the arts lead to health and wellbeing by my contribution of adding something new, something conceptually rooted that hadn’t been drawn before.

As well as my shifting research and methodological focus, my relationship to models and frameworks of health and wellbeing changed throughout the research process. These changes emerged from my research inquiries. Through developing the literature review, I found that line drawing and model making was proliferating in the area of culture, the arts, health and wellbeing (Chapter 5). I encountered new models and frameworks, such as Fancourt et al.'s (2021) multi-level theoretical framework of mechanisms of how leisure affects health. I began to wonder what another model would contribute. Part of my research practice has been a growing awareness of ontological and epistemological issues, and an increasingly critical relationship with orthodox health and wellbeing approaches as I developed my models and framework. This changing awareness also brought a growing realisation during my literature review and during my conversations with people in Paisley about their practice, that I also have a practice of infusing meaningfulness into my facilitation of community activities. This involved creating atmospheres that contributed to health and wellbeing. During my desk based theoretical analysis of culture and the arts for social purposes (Chapter 5) my practice-led knowledge started to resonate more with community arts than the models and frameworks of public health. COVID-19 altered my proposed research activities in Paisley and my everyday life and left me alone to experience my concepts (Chapter 3 and 7).

As my new relationship to models and frameworks emerges, my thesis becomes increasingly aligned with the work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing. I find myself agreeing with Atkinson's (2020) argument for the necessity of this work. My purpose becomes to add to 'the model'. But not by developing a new model or by amending a current model. My thesis contributes the following propositions for 'the model':

- 'The model' for the fifth wave of public health requires ontological and epistemological roots to anchor the shift in thinking about health and wellbeing, so that the paradigm change I propose does not drift back to the current paradigm (Chapter 3). I argue for a focus on the relational and the everyday and a commitment to diversity in ways of knowing.
- The relationship between the parts in 'the model' should resist the dominant paradigm of individualism and reductionism and find alternatives to breaking health and wellbeing into parts. I use assemblage thinking to think about parts holistically as a greater whole for example by considering the three dimensions of loneliness as one (Chapter 4).
- My approach to thinking about health and wellbeing is also concerned with how to translate the roots and relationships into ideas we can think with and lead us to ideas relating to relational health. This translation provides a lens that we can use to view and make visible the health and wellbeing processes we encounter and facilitate. I offer the idea of gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts (Chapter 4).

- My purpose through these research tasks of ‘adding to the model’ is to centre ‘becoming human’ at the heart of a new paradigm in health and wellbeing (Chapter 4).

These four propositions provide insights to the questions that I use to meet my research aim to investigate how place-based policies designed to utilise culture and the arts for social ends might shift thinking on health and wellbeing by observing developments in policy and activity in Paisley:

- (1) What might the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health be?
- (2) What concepts could help articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health?
- (3) How might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and wellbeing?
- (4) How might a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends grow a health and wellbeing dimension?

The following sections in this chapter will present my research contributions through these four propositions of ‘adding to the model’.

10.3. Summarising the change in research contribution over time

I started this research in 2019, supported by external partners from NHSGGC and Renfrewshire Council (Chapter 1) and entered the strategic context of a newly formed cultural regeneration programme approach in Paisley, where stakeholders were interested in health and wellbeing (Chapters 1 and 9). My initial aim was to contribute to knowledge of how culture and the arts influence health and wellbeing. At this time, Paisley was alive with the buzz of the UKCoC21 bid two years earlier.

The APPHGAW report, published in 2017, influenced stakeholder interest in how health and wellbeing could emerge from involvement in culture and the arts (Chapter 9). The initial expectation for my research was that we would focus on two or three examples of the intersection of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing in order to investigate activities that were contributing to Step Change 2, ‘lifting communities out of poverty’. I subsequently learned that this Step Change had not settled into its final form. In Chapter 2, the rapid development of the arts and health evidence base and the development of a Culture Strategy for Scotland by the Scottish Government is presented to show the dynamic nature of my research’s strategic and research context. The dynamic nature of the academic and policy context means answers change to the questions that guide my collaborative action-informed approach developed in Chapter 3 such as ‘what knowledge would be useful to you?’ and ‘what challenges do you have that I could help with?’ I anticipated that the type of knowledge

that would be useful to partners would be to examine the pathways and mechanisms between participating in culture and the arts and health and wellbeing. Through this knowledge, I anticipated that I would make a theoretical contribution as the link between culture and the arts and health and wellbeing has been less examined through a theoretical lens (Chapter 5). I also anticipated a policy contribution by adding to the evidence base for Future Paisley's evaluation (Chapter 1).

In addition to keeping pace with the changing policy context in Paisley, I faced two challenges in scoping out my potential contribution. There was a policy issue as health and wellbeing were not issues that were explicitly defined in Future Paisley's Step Change 2 (Chapters 1 and 9). This lack of definition created tensions in members of CAHSC with responsibility for projects to contribute to Step Change 2. The members were left unsure what they were addressing when they were addressing health and wellbeing. I had an aim to contribute knowledge to address these issues, but I faced the conceptual issue examined in Chapter 5, where there is a lack of conceptual interrogation of health and wellbeing concepts and frameworks in the two academic terrains of the use of culture and the arts for social purposes, arts and health and cultural regeneration. I found health models are taken off the shelf and are chosen to provide a rationale for non-clinical interventions. Health and wellbeing approaches are used as framing devices to build the case for culture and the arts for social purposes. Chapter 5 suggests this is due to the prevalence of advocacy tendencies for the benefits of culture and the arts. A question I keep returning to when I converse with academic literature and with people, organisations, and networks in Paisley, as shown in Chapter 8, is 'what are we contributing to when we say we are contributing to health and wellbeing?', particularly 'what health and wellbeing work is being facilitated?'

The lockdown measures that arrived with the COVID-19 pandemic, as illustrated in Chapter 3, paused my proposed action research plan. The pause gave me room to deepen the critical engagement in the thesis with definitions of health and wellbeing by investigating a wider range of academic fields relating to non-clinical interventions into health and wellbeing improvement.

Lockdown measures changed the nature of the knowledge I could grow as I was observing Paisley from a distance rather than being immersed in the activities in the town. These measures grew the experiential knowledge in the thesis of the concepts of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing. As my world shrank spatially, socially, and affectively, the conceptual explorations of loneliness and isolation took up most of my diminished world and became entangled with the increasing encounters with these concepts in my everyday life. As I became more estranged from the world, I became more aware of what was anchoring me to existence. One anchor was my volunteering with the Edinburgh exhibition. The words to articulate what participating in a cultural activity means to

me and those who converse with me through their exhibits did not find resonance with the academic literature of culture and arts for social purposes or health literature. Our experiences are too diverse, too informed by our own relationships to culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing, and too ingrained in our identity. I felt it would be a betrayal to the voices in the exhibition to flatten their experiences into statements such as 'improvement of confidence' or 'cheerfulness'. There has been nowhere else where I can be receptive to such a range of voices and experience so much of humanity. How can I conceptually talk about culture, arts, health, and wellbeing in this research and keep true to this collective voice? In this period, I become aware that I have a practice of infusing activity with meaning and creating transformation. Through my practice, people have done things and taken on identities that they had never considered or were aware of when we first met. I questioned how can baselines for improvement be measured? A question that arises in Chapters 6 and 9. The language of models, mechanisms and factors sits uncomfortably with my experiential knowledge. I have shown in Chapters 2 to 5 how I interrogated this tension through my work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing.

By 9 August 2021, the legal requirement for physical distancing and limits on gatherings was removed in Scotland, my research encounters in Paisley tapered away (Table 3.1) and I focused on developing insights from my knowledge. By this point my critical relationship to models had solidified into an embracing of Atkinson's (2020) provocation that work was needed to counter-conceptualise health and wellbeing. I used this work as a way of responding to Hanlon et al.'s (2011) idea of a paradigm shift in how we think about health and society. My thesis settled on my research focus of investigating my research puzzle, the health and wellbeing dimension of the Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme, and developing a proposal to shift how we think about health and wellbeing.

10.4. Roots and anchoring

My first research question (RQ1) was, 'what might the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health be?'.

In Chapter 2, I analysed how the fifth wave of public health in policy and academic literature draws on Davies et al.'s (2014) proposal for a fifth wave of public health which focuses on cultural health rather than Hanlon et al.'s (2012) proposal. I argued that the proposal for a focus on cultural health is too narrow to create a paradigm shift and does not address the range of public health issues that Hanlon et al. (2011) identify as requiring a paradigm shift. I argued that these issues are still relevant and remain under-addressed by public health. I suggest that the characteristics for fifth wave of public health should be an acknowledgement of embracing multitudes of knowledge and

complexity, a concern with connections, and a focus on the everyday. Characteristics of a fifth wave should include a direct engagement with what it means to be human and be well together, and view practices and experiences of everyday life as generating the foundational processes of health and wellbeing. I undertook this engagement in Chapters 4, 5 and 7 by my use of loneliness as a public health issue.

My proposal for the fifth wave of public health is concerned with providing a suggestion for the ontological and epistemological roots of any proposal for the fifth wave of public health. I suggested a focus on the relational and the everyday and a commitment to diversity in ways of knowing. I argued in Chapters 2 and 4 that these roots need to be made explicit as any proposal needs to be anchored with explicit ontological and epistemological approaches or risk being subsumed into the dominant paradigm. Chapter 4 highlighted this danger, such as how scales and measurements can blunt the radicalness of ideas. An issue that Chapter 5 showed is also present in the literature of culture and arts for social purposes. I identified in Chapter 9 how the wellbeing economy agenda could be susceptible to this danger.

My proposal has implications for how I conceptually view culture and my third research question (RQ3) 'how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society?'. I argued that for culture to be mobilised to creating a fifth wave of public health, culture should be viewed as emerging from everyday processes of meaning making. I drew on community arts literature to show how these processes may be facilitated and how health and wellbeing emerges. In Chapter 9 my presentation of this literature shows that lessons learnt in COVID-19 are already known.

10.5. Relationships and entanglements

I continued exploring my first research question (RQ1), 'what might the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health be?' by focusing on what characteristics I need to think with in order to align myself with my proposed ontological and epistemological roots, the focus on the relational and the everyday and a commitment to diversity in ways of knowing. My proposal for these characteristics resulted in my second research question (RQ2) 'what concepts could help articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health?'.

I use assemblage thinking to guide my relational thinking, as developed in Chapter 4. My thinking includes a non-human ontology to expand meaningful relationships beyond the social dimension and closer to people's experiences of what matters to them as examined in Chapters 5. In Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 9, I demonstrated how assemblage thinking has been deployed to view my conceptual and

empirical interests through a relational lens. My inclusive view of connections contributed to my proposal for the fifth wave of public health. Through my view of culture as everyday I provide conceptual space for activities such as gardening, swimming, and dog walking. Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 7 has shown that people find these activities meaningful and contribute to health and wellbeing. Therefore, I addressed my third research question (RQ3) 'how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society?' by answering that these activities need to be viewed as everyday processes that are meaningful to people, as when these activities become recognised as health and wellbeing facilitating activities, the view of how we think about health shifts focus to meaningfulness, the everyday and what we connect to.

To help people think about categories and dimensions together, rather than separate and linked, I developed gateway concepts and engage with the ontological and epistemological roots for the focus on relational health. I develop my first gateway concept by drawing on the field of psychology. Ratcliff's (2005) idea of existential feelings aligns with the ideas of affect and emotion I encounter in literature relating to assemblage thinking. I introduced this term in Chapter 4 and show how I repurposed the term for my conceptual needs. Existential feelings provide a way to talk about the feeling of 'being in the world' that I argued encompass feelings that can be expressed as 'sense of' such as loneliness, belonging and stigma. I draw on academic health literature to demonstrate that these feelings are factors in health and wellbeing. Existential feelings are a gateway concept for my research and are used in Chapter 7 to think about the three dimensions of loneliness together, and in Chapter 8 and 9 to think about the work of facilitating health and wellbeing.

My proposal to focus on relational health has led to different questions about health. Rather than the epidemiological question about causes of health or disease, my proposal has taken the causes as given. Health, wellbeing, and disease can emerge from the state of our connections. I focus on the relational work to facilitate health-creating connections. I have done this from my position outside public health and I have drawn on a variety of fields of cultural activity that contribute to health and wellbeing. I have situated this knowledge in the wider context of activities that contribute to health and wellbeing. I have brought to academic literatures of public health and culture and the arts for social purposes, a concern with the work of facilitating health and wellbeing. This work is often place-based such as the practice of community arts and the practice of facilitating health and wellbeing creating places. I have suggested that a focus on this work would help mitigate the dominance of the focus on describing health and wellbeing by identifying factors and pathways.

Hanlon et al.'s (2012) fifth wave of public health proposal starts from the perspective of considering the role of public health practitioners. I started with those who facilitate health and wellbeing

through culture both directly in Chapter 5 through looking at the work of community artists and museum staff in Chapter 8, and indirectly in chapter 6 through emergent culture. The application of this lens contributed to the literature on culture and arts for social purposes as it provides an analytical frame to bring together three fields of the social purpose of arts and culture, cultural regeneration, arts and health, and community arts. Into this synthesis, I added a view of culture and the arts as emergent, a typology of culture and the arts less present in the literature of arts and health. In particular, in Chapter 6, I viewed the intersection between community-centred health and cultural democracy as a site for emergent culture, health, and wellbeing processes to arise.

Through thinking relationally, I drew in critical approaches to the dominant paradigm wherever I encountered them and grow knowledge for my work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing.

10.6. Attuning and articulating

As I developed the roots of the proposal for the fifth wave of public health, I attuned to viewing the world in its holistic form. The purpose of my research evolved to consider how do I talk about my proposal for the fifth wave of public health with other people. This purpose encompassed a range of queries such as ‘how do I help make the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health resonate with people, with their experience of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing, and with their practices of meaning making?’ ‘How can this resonating help people view their work as part of the wider work of public health?’ ‘How can I help people think in a way that enriches the evaluations and impact narratives that people have to produce?’ People often know what works in their practice of meaning-making (Chapter 8), and the idea of transformation emerging from the accumulation of everyday moments also resonates (Chapter 9). What can I contribute to assist the linking of this knowledge to the fifth wave of public health and help facilitate a shift in how we think of health and wellbeing? These queries coalesce into further developing an answer to my research question (RQ2), ‘what concepts could help articulate the work required to deliver the fifth wave of public health?’.

In Chapter 3 I termed these concepts as ‘sensitizing concepts’ to help people attune to the characteristics of the fifth wave of public health. My proposal suggests that one characteristic is attention to everyday moments. Therefore, I sought sensitizing concepts through which people can attune to everyday health-facilitating moments. This attunement provides insight into how lives are transformed as I demonstrate in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5, which created a nuanced understanding of loneliness as a way of being in the world in Chapter 7. For these concepts to resonate they needed to align with how people and organisations work. This alignment contributes to the mobilisation of culture and arts and therefore contributes to answering my third research question

(RQ3) 'how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society?'

In Chapter 8 I demonstrated how my contribution of the sensitizing concept of 'atmospheres', particularly 'atmospheres of belonging' resonates with the aim of projects I encounter in Paisley. I show how the concept of enabling places aligns with how Paisley Museum describes itself and what others want from the Museum in Chapter 8. Providing the sensitizing concept of 'atmospheres' gives people a framework to draw in the everyday moments they observe, that contribute to health and wellbeing. In Chapter 8 I suggested attending to small moments, could lead research and evaluation down White's (2014) 'lantern road' of reflective practice and relational working and away from the 'empirical highway' of calls for evidence and knowledge framed by the medical model of health. Attention to these moments, I argued in Chapters 5 and 9 could help address the lack of focus on the strengths of community-based arts in health, such as their spatial dimension.

White's (2014) 'empirical highway' has changed since 2014. Evidence calls are evidenced by models drawing on social models of health as given in Chapter 5. The wellbeing economy agenda (Chapter 9) may further embed this direction. However, as I noted in Chapter 9, this does not change the underlying approach of building evidence. For example, the evidence for cultural participation projects, mentioned in Chapter 5, includes the wider language of wellbeing such as social cohesion. However Jancovich and Stevenson (2021) note that these create narratives of deficit within individuals. Narratives that in Chapter 7 I suggest are reinforced by the dominance of the social dimension of loneliness in policy and academic research. The outcome of this failure of resistance against individualism means that it is harder to shift the focus of health and wellbeing to structural issues and a concern with what society can collectively do. In Chapter 8 I showed how using my gateway and sensitizing concepts creates a concern with how we can be well together rather than fixing individuals. With these concepts, the focus now shifts to asking, 'what can we make together' and 'how can we create material, social and affective encounters that bring us closer to the world and help us become more human'. These questions contribute to how culture and arts-related activity are mobilised in a way that allows a shift in thinking about health and wellbeing and therefore these questions contribute to answering my third research question. My contributions support White's argument for the 'lantern road' of supporting relationship-based working as a means for realising his vision of community arts in health.

A focus on the social processes that White (2009) calls for as well as psychological processes, is occurring. However, through building knowledge with my gateway concept of enabling places in Chapter 5 and Chapter 8, I argued to fully understand the spaces of transformation identified by

White (2009), and the work undertaken by artists to create these spaces, the affective dimension needs to be made visible. My proposal is well situated conceptually and empirically to be in dialogue with White's proposal for arts in health to be re-configured as 'arts for emotional spaces'. I demonstrate that my proposal for a focus on relational health aligns with research in other fields and sectors that contribute to health and wellbeing in non-clinical ways from youth work to leisure (Chapters 5 and 8). My thesis, by providing a proposal that aligns across sectors contributes to addressing White's concern that health and wellbeing effects are looked at in isolation.

10.7. Becoming human and loneliness

The heart of my proposal is an explicit recognition and engagement with 'becoming human' as a dynamic everyday process of being in the world. I do not mean this philosophically, as this question has occupied philosophers for centuries. My thesis explores how to attend to this process when considering how might place-based policies designed to use culture for health and wellbeing ends, create a fifth wave of public health. The complexity of this process and the fields in which it is examined is beyond the scope of my thesis. However, it cannot be ignored as it underpins the work of health and wellbeing as illustrated by my explorations into loneliness as a public health challenge in Chapter 7 and the work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing. Ignoring this task would be to take intellectual shortcuts identified by Belfiore (2009) as an issue with research in cultural policy. I approach my research with the intellectual humility and the questioning of culture and society Belfiore (2009) suggests is needed to avoid adding more advocacy-flavoured research to the evidence base. This humility is part of my methodological approach of bricolage (Kincheloe, 2005).

My use of loneliness as a public health issue as a site of investigation showed how the dominant paradigm transforms the complexity of loneliness into a troubling feeling that needs to be fixed. Loneliness becomes a public health problem due to correlations with health and wellbeing. While this view is helpful for demonstrating the effects of subjective feelings, it reinforces the idea of health as something that resides in the individual and therefore loneliness as an aberration from the norm. Chapter 2 demonstrated how thinking of health issues in terms of deviating from the norm pushes people away from becoming human. Thinking about health and wellbeing in terms of becoming human, situates loneliness as a quality of life and situates the 'cure' as strengthening the collective by paying attention to the everyday nature of connectedness. Through my gateway concept of existential feelings, I contribute a lens to attend to emotional and existential loneliness as well as social loneliness. In particular, I contribute a proposal to acknowledge these dimensions while at the same time viewing them as intertwined with each other and with other existential feelings.

My argument of more expansive conceptualisation of loneliness has policy implementations. Policy approaches to loneliness examined in Chapters 4, 5 and 7 focuses mainly on social loneliness. A focus on social prescribing may exacerbate this tendency. My argument for a greater focus on emotional and existential loneliness means I suggest that policy approaches to loneliness also expand the sense of connectivity, so feelings of lacking are less likely to arise. For example, in Chapter 7, I suggested that more consideration is given to the idea of reframing loneliness as solitude by considering non-human connection.

My research has another characteristic that aligns with a type of research that Belfiore (2009, p. 354) terms as 'explorative research' and refers to a type of research that is separate from advocacy. This type of research aims to 'describe, explore and illuminate complex issues around the role and condition of culture, cultural production, consumption and administration in contemporary society'. My research has explored the role and condition of culture in health and wellbeing in order to gain insight into the role of culture in place-based policy that is designed to use culture for health and wellbeing purposes. I have explored cultural production by observing where cultural processes arise with health and wellbeing. In doing so I have contributed research that resists tidy answers by making explicit my engagement with the complexity of 'becoming human'. In this way, I have avoided another issue highlighted by Belfiore (2021, p. 8) where the role of culture is looked at in terms of a methodological problem, a 'case for the arts'. Where the solution is by a quest 'for the ultimate impact evaluation toolkit, applicable to all art forms, all audiences and in all geographical and social contexts.' My research instead explored the complex role of culture as an ontological and epistemological problem. Therefore, my research approach aligns with Belfiore's argument to consider research as an interplay of ideas with policy rather than in terms of providing evidence into policy.

Looking back on my methodological approach, I find I have engaged with Belfiore's (2021) questioning of the nature of evidence and consideration of evidence in terms of an argument and an act of persuasion. I suggest to people in Paisley that they might consider a manifesto for evaluation as a way of expanding their engagement with Future Paisley's evaluation process. Through this and together with my other research activities in Paisley, I align myself with Belfiore's (2021) view of a researcher as a policy actor with a voice and a perspective. The reflexive nature of my research and the way in which I engage with people in my research through highlighting the 'selves' presented in Chapter 3 contribute to addressing the concerns highlighted by Belfiore regarding claims to objectivity and neutrality.

10.8. Gatherings and happenings in Paisley

So far, this chapter has set out my contributions to exploring what is meant by health and wellbeing and what is meant by culture when seen through the lens of my proposal for a paradigm change. These contributions equip me to bring these insights to my research puzzle, Future Paisley's health and wellbeing dimension. Therefore, the next step in describing my contribution is to consider the nature of a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends in order to understand what such a policy can do in terms of health and wellbeing and the possibilities to create a fifth wave of public health. The next step leads to my next two research questions (RQ3) 'how might culture and arts-related activity be mobilised to contribute to the shift in thinking about health and society?' and (RQ4) 'how might a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends grow a health and wellbeing dimension?'

My research started with a place-based policy using culture for health and wellbeing purposes as illustrated in Chapter 1. After my exploration of the fifth wave of public health and the social purpose of culture and the arts, I now bring these insights into examining what I have learnt about place-based policy using culture for health and wellbeing purposes. I argued in Chapter 3 that a policy which seeks to contribute to health and wellbeing, should contribute to the fifth wave of public health to complement the approaches of the other waves of public health, and that the work of the fifth wave of public health needs to include the work of paradigm change. In Chapter 9 I argued policies that are interested in improving health and wellbeing should have an explicit approach to health and wellbeing. I do not mean a definition of health and wellbeing, as a definition may constrict the evolution of people and organisations taking their approaches to health and wellbeing (Chapter 2). I suggested an approach of characteristics to be valued, so these values do not get lost and subsumed by the current waves (Chapter 2)

I suggest in Chapter 9, that if the explicit approach to health and wellbeing was framed in terms of paradigm change, then Future Paisley could meet the radical aspirations it seeks for itself. Future Paisley could situate itself as being ahead of the national wellbeing agenda through setting a more radical tone. This agenda would bolster what is already going on in Future Paisley in terms of an interest in system change and excellence in socially engaged practice, by giving these interests a theoretical and conceptual platform. By reaffirming and embedding core values of becoming human in the face of systems that seek to corrode them, a radical health and wellbeing dimension to place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends could be grown.

I contributed knowledge of two different uses of culture and the arts for social purposes coming together through place-based policy, cultural regeneration and arts and health. As this coming

together has only started emerging, particularly due to the relative newness of the arts and health field as examined in Chapter 4, my account provided a contribution of an analysis of an early example of the two purposes coming together. I have situated my account in the history of culture and the arts for social purposes by drawing on accounts of community arts to grow knowledge of the work of facilitating health and wellbeing. Knowledge from community arts, shows that 'what works', such as the lessons from COVID-19 regarding how the community response, has already been known, and therefore I reiterate throughout the thesis the need for a greater focus on 'what matters' rather than 'what works'. This focus would help develop an alignment between the fifth wave of public health and a health and wellbeing dimension of place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends.

This thesis an account of a health and wellbeing dimension being assembled by a place-based policy designed to use culture and the arts for social ends. Looking back, my thesis covers a particular phase in the development of such a policy. This interim phase covers when a policy intent has been made, an interest in health and wellbeing and the arts and health field, but what this intent means in terms of goals, action and what this intent means to other organisations is not yet settled. Following a policy in live time in this unsettled interim phase, gives a contribution of how a place-based policy that uses culture and the arts, forms a health and wellbeing dimension. In Chapters 6 to 9 I analyse what has been gathered into this Future Paisley from within Paisley and elsewhere. Through my bricolage and facet approach, I observe constellations of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing activity in Paisley in their dynamic and holistic form. Future Paisley is both a constituent of these constellations and is co-constituted from these constellations. I suggest that place-based policy at a local authority level can contribute to using culture to create my proposal for a fifth wave of public health by being outside both the cultural sector and the public sector. Being outside the cultural sector provides an opportunity to view culture as everyday and emerging (Chapter 5) and makes more visible the cultural activity that emerges from outside the cultural sector in what people and communities find meaningful (Chapters 6 and 7).

10.9. Strength and limitations

My thesis has provided a structure that is ontologically and epistemologically committed to the characteristics of my proposal for a fifth wave of public health. The purposeful juxtaposition of these chapters layers the knowledge I have grown to provide the thesis with both a depth of attunement to the small moments that accumulate to the transformation of lives and a view of the whole research puzzle in its dynamic and holistic form. The co-development of insights into the research puzzle and the proposal for paradigm change, provides both novel knowledge and also a guidance

for actions to undertake the counter-conceptualisation of health and wellbeing and create a fifth wave of public health.

My thesis has offered a unique glimpse into the formation of the health and wellbeing dimension of place-based policy that is designed to use culture and the arts for social purposes. I have followed Future Paisley in live time in an evolutionary phase between the first written iteration of the policy and the finalisation of the wordings in the policy. A phase made turbulent by COVID-19. My research took place between the initiation of capital projects in Paisley, such as Paisley Museum and the capital projects opening to the public. This phase finishes when the 'co-ordinating' roles have been designed but before all the appointments have been made. Gatherings and happenings into policy are continuous processes. My thesis has made visible much of the gathering. In this period Future Paisley was moving forward from the UKCoC21 bid and different configurations of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing are being tried. At the same time as the growth in activities 'happening within', there was growth in the potential for 'things elsewhere' to be drawn in, particularly due to the development of Culture Strategy for Scotland. The happenings occur outside the scope of my thesis. Chapter 2 shows the stalling progress in Scotland over the past decade on the Christie Commission recommendations and on health and wellbeing challenges. Therefore, for change to occur and to be observed requires a time-frame beyond this thesis.

The proposal in my thesis for the fifth wave of public health has left room for people and organisations to bring their knowledge gained from experience, practice and academic fields and develop proposals situated in their own contexts and assets. By not approaching the invitation to develop the fifth wave of public health in terms of developing a model or framework, there is ample room for different knowledge and perspectives to be brought in and to grow with my proposals. I suggest investigating and developing this knowledge should researched, such as the example given in Chapter 8 of Museums as Spaces of Social Care and the wider literature related to the concept of care. I argue this contribution would contribute to realisation of the Future Paisley cultural programme's desire to be radical.

My thesis has engaged in the necessary work of counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing. My gateway and sensitizing concepts have made more visible dimensions that have received less focus in literature and policy such as the emotional and existential dimensions of loneliness and explicitly considering affective infrastructure. For example, in one presentation of my proposal for the fifth wave of public health, I was asked by a local councillor about existential loneliness. I argue the practice of policy making should continue the work of counter-conceptualisation of health and wellbeing. I suggest that work is undertaken to investigate how to engage with these concepts, for

example understanding the barriers to adopting these ideas and how people feel these ideas relate to their work.

10.10. Further research

I have made a range of contributions to undertake the work counter-conceptualising health and wellbeing and create fifth wave of public health. The holistic insights I have gained into the dynamic conditions and processes of culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing mean I have created a multitude of avenues for further research. My holistic approach of seeing the research object as a whole and my following of the evolution of my research puzzle in live time means there are many points where a more stationary viewpoint of the research puzzle could be adopted to fill out my research.

Further research is needed to address the limitations in communicating and disseminating my proposal for a fifth wave of public health and develop the capacity of the proposal to be part of the process of argumentation and persuasion between policy and researcher (Belfiore, 2021).

The nature of my thesis means I have made a number of suggestions to continue my research contributions to the work of creating paradigm change. For example, gateway concepts and sensitizing concepts should be examined further. I have given examples of places that could be seen as enabling places in Chapter 8. I have suggested that ‘atmospheres of belonging’ is a sensitizing concept that would be of interest to people and organisations in Paisley. As these places are new or in a new form due to a capital project, Paisley provides an opportunity to undertake ethnographic and practice-based approaches (Sumartojo and Pink, 2018) into how these atmospheres are facilitated and the role of culture and the arts in this facilitation. These opportunities would be in a position to chart the development of atmospheres and how they co-constitute people’s dynamic processes of health and wellbeing. This knowledge would contribute to research on health-creating places, particularly the fields of human geography and anthropology which Sumartojo and Pink (2018, p. 128) draw on for their approach to thinking with atmospheres which they use to ‘move towards more ethical and just ways of relating to each other – is where atmosphere’s radical potential lies’. Therefore, further research that uses this approach towards atmospheres would contribute to Future Paisley’s desire for radicalness.

Sumartojo and Pink’s (2018) approach is concerned with how people understand their own experiences in their own terms. Therefore, adopting this approach would contribute to and further the co-production work undertaken in Paisley. If this approach also takes up Mason’s (2017) invitation to think with affinities to understand the role of sensations in relationships, a sociological contribution would be made through applying a topic that has lacked attention in sociology to a new

area, health-creating places. Mason (2017) draws on her own facet approach (Mason, 2011) to explore affinities. Carrying on this methodological approach to studying affinities, would create a methodological contribution by applying this approach beyond its roots in sociology.

I have argued that there needs to be a greater focus on the underexplored dimension of emergent culture, the arts, health, and wellbeing. There is currently a second round of Scottish Government Community Mental Health and Wellbeing fund in development³¹ that could provide an avenue for further research. The focus of this fund on loneliness and social isolation would provide an opportunity to develop my ideas in Chapter 7 such as contributing to policy knowledge regarding loneliness as a public health issue, theoretical knowledge of loneliness by engaging with critical health and wellbeing ideas, conceptual knowledge through developing my proposals for the ideas of affective infrastructure and existential feelings, and the experiential experience of loneliness through engaging with thinking about atmospheres and affinities. This further research could draw on the emergent interest in health from cultural activities in Paisley as I have observed an interest in health and wellbeing by Renfrewshire's Ethnic Communities Cultural Steering Group. Through the Scottish Community Wellbeing Fund comparative research could be undertaken to investigate the culture, arts, health, and wellbeing assemblages in other local authorities. This research route would also enable further examination of the role of HSCP and TSI as facilitators of the conditions for the emergence of culture. Knowledge from this research would complement and expand the discussion in Scotland related to the field of arts and health discussed in Chapter 9. This knowledge would also complement and contribute to research and evaluation being undertaken in Scotland across the range of place-based policies using culture and the arts for social ends in Scotland.

³¹ <https://engagerenfrewshire.org/engage-support/community-mental-health-wellbeing-fund.html>

Appendix 1: Research Encounters

Year	Day & Month	Name of organisation, event, people, project, network	Type	Purpose	Who invited me/how did I hear about this	Knowledge grown into chapters	Check ins
2019	21st March	Centre for Culture, Sport and Events: Launch	Event	Observe culture, the arts, health and wellbeing activities in Paisley	Membership of CCSE	9	
2019	2nd April	Culture, Arts and Social Care Network	Meeting	Observe culture, the arts, health and wellbeing activities in Paisley, build relationships	PhD brief to contribute to the evaluation of Future Paisley Step Change 2 includes the activities of CAHSC	6, 9	
2019	9th April	STAR Project - strategic leadership role	Discussion	Learn about art and creativity in a community organisation that is strategically involved in the development of Paisley's cultural regeneration approach, build relationships	External supervisor provided introduction	4, 5, 6, 9	
2019	12th April	Renfrewshire Arts Team - meeting with the team lead	Discussion	Learn about the Team's planned activities, build relationships	Membership of CAHSC	6, 9	
2019	13th April	Renfrewshire SMAF - planning meeting with organisations involved (RHSCP and community organisations)	Meeting	Observe community organisations involved in culture, the arts, health and wellbeing in Renfrewshire, build relationships	Through CAHSC	6, 9	
2019	24th April	CCSE Steering Group	Meeting	Presenting my research, learning about CCSE and Paisley	PhD is part of CCSE's activities	6, 9	Check-in with cultural regeneration and arts and health activities

2019	3 days in April to June	NHS Health Improvement	Course	Understanding how to embed knowledge about health inequalities into my research practice, learning from practitioners about how their practice contributes to mitigating health inequalities	External supervisor helped arrange	4	
2019	2.5 days 30th April to 2nd May	SGSSS and UWS	Course	Learn about participatory methodology and Paisley as a place	Scottish Graduate School of Social Science (SGSSS)	5, 6, 9	
2019	28th May	Culture, Arts and Social Care Network	Meeting	Observe culture, the arts, health and wellbeing activities in Paisley, build relationships	Membership of CAHSC	6, 9	
2019	12th June	Arts & Health sector in Scotland - practitioner meeting	Discussion	Learn about the Arts & Health sector in Scotland	External supervisor introduction	5, 9	
2019	13th June	Health Inequalities Symposium with SGSSS and University of Edinburgh	Conference/Symposium	Learn about health inequalities	SGSSS	4	
2019	14th June	FESTSPACE	Conference/Symposium	Learn about Hull's experience as City of Culture	CCSE	5	
2019	25th June	SGSSS	Workshop	Learn methodologies that could inform development of approach to evaluation	SGSSS	5, 9	
2019	2 days 11th and 12th July	Participatory Action Research	Course	Learn more about methodologies that could inform a co-production research approach	Through Supervisor	9	
2019	18th July	"Get Creative! Research with Pictures & Stories" SAGE Publishing	Course	Learn more about methods that could inform a co-production research approach	Online	6	
2019	23rd July	Culture, Arts and Social Care Network	Meeting	Observe culture, the arts, health and wellbeing in Paisley, build relationships	Membership of CAHSC	6, 9	

2019	23rd July	Culture, Arts and Social Care Network - Future Paisley Evaluation	Meeting	Observe and explore how CAHSC can connect with the CCSE evaluation of Future Paisley	Arranged by CAHSC and includes members of CAHSC from Renfrewshire Arts Team, NHS GCC, Renfrewshire Council and OneRen	6, 9	
2019	23rd July	STAR Project - project leadership role	Discussion	Learn about evaluation activities relating to culture, the arts, health and wellbeing activities in Paisley, build relationships	Follow up meeting	4, 5, 6, 9	
2019	31st July	Board member Arts Culture Health and Wellbeing Scotland	Discussion	Learn about Arts & Health activity in Scotland	External supervisor introduction	5, 9	
2019	15th August	QMU - Situating the local in cultural policy	Event	Learn about local approaches to cultural policy	Online	5, 9	
2019	21st August	NHSGGC Health Improvement - invitation to meeting of department	Meeting/Presentation	Presenting my research and checking in with practitioners if my conceptual direction resonates	External supervisor	5	Check-in with resonance of theories and concepts of health with strategic leaders in public health
2019	24th August	Create Paisley and Renfrewshire Council	Meeting	Meeting with Create Paisley in order to advise on the evaluation of a mental health conference project (subsequently named Open Mind Summit), build relationships	Membership of CAHSC	6	
2019	18th September	CCSE Steering group	Meeting/Presentation	Presentation of research	Membership of CCSE	5, 9	Check-in with cultural regeneration and arts and health activities

2019	24th September	Future Paisley - over 20 stakeholders	Field Trip	Learning from other cultural regeneration projects, learn about the stakeholders involved in Future Paisley, build relationships	Wide range of stakeholders in Future Paisley including PhD research	4, 5, 6, 9	Check-in with cultural regeneration and arts and health activities
2019	15th November	Meeting with Open Mind Summit planners	Meeting	Contribute to the development of Open Mind Summit's evaluation and theory of change approach, build relationships	Membership of CAHSC	6, 9	
2019	21st November	Public Engagement in Mental Health Research	Workshop	Explore how to incorporate mental health service users into research. Explore what participatory research means.	Online	4	
2019	25th November	Arts and Health researchers in Scotland	Meeting	Observing culture, arts, health and wellbeing activities in Scotland to provide national context to activities in Paisley	External supervisor	5, 6, 9,	
2020	8th January	Culture Arts and Social Care Research and Evaluation Group Working Group - subset of Culture Arts and Social Care members	Meeting	Inaugural meeting of Working Group. Presenting on my emerging ideas about researching the evaluation of culture, arts, health and wellbeing in Paisley. Scoping out interest in the applicability and usefulness of my ideas to projects in Paisley. Assessing the capacity and potential of an action research related to evaluating culture, arts, health and wellbeing in Paisley.	Membership of CAHSC Research and Evaluation Group	4, 5, 6, 9	Check-in with evaluation, cultural regeneration policy and health and wellbeing concepts
2020	23rd January	RHSCP & Create Paisley staff members	Meeting	Check-in on the resonance of my ideas with practitioners in Paisley. Scoping out interest in the applicability and usefulness of my ideas to projects in Paisley and assess the possibility for an action research project. Developing knowledge about local culture, arts, health and	Through CAHSC	4, 5, 6,	Check-in with practitioners regarding evaluation and concepts of health and wellbeing

				wellbeing activity and developing relationships to inform the development for an action research project.			
2020	23rd January	Future Paisley Partnership Board – over 20 attendees of strategic leaders from partner organisations and members of CCSE	Workshop/Presentation	Workshop to check that the Step Changes still fit. Observing what meanings Future Paisley stakeholders have of health and wellbeing.	Through CCSE	4, 5, 9,	
2020	24th January	Renfrewshire Arts Team - meeting with the team lead	Meeting	Check-in on the resonance of my ideas with practitioners in Paisley. Scoping out interest in the applicability and usefulness of my ideas to projects in Paisley and assess the possibility for an action research project. Developing knowledge about local culture, arts, health and wellbeing activity and developing relationships to inform the development for an action research project.	Through CAHSC	5, 6	Check-in with practitioners regarding evaluation and concepts of health and wellbeing
2020	24th January	Launch of 'A Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030'	Event	Renfrewshire Council, the Scottish Government and Scotland's Towns Partnership are revealing 'A Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030'. This exhibition and report use the town as a case study to examine issues affecting town centres across the country and potential solutions. Observe the development of regeneration activities in Paisley.	Invitation forwarded by supervisor	9	
2020	21st February	Improving Community Wellbeing Through Culture Workshop	Workshop	Part of UKRI funded place-based partnership project, led by CCSE, STAR Project and Renfrewshire Council Cultural Regeneration Team and STAR Project and	Through CAHSC	4, 5, 6,	

				attended by about 50 local community members alongside representatives from a range of local and national organisations to discuss what culture means to them. Observe community perspective on what culture means to them.			
2020	21st May	Webinar: Evaluating Arts, Loneliness & Isolation held by Arts & Health South West	Webinar	Observing how arts and health interlinks with the topic of loneliness and learning current practice on evaluation processes in this context	Learning about best practice	5, 9	
2020	15th June	Renfrewshire Arts Team - meeting with team members	Meeting	How to evaluate RenTV	Invitation in response to my email asking what help I can be to CAHSC partners	5, 9	
2020	17th June	CAHSC (renamed from Culture, Arts and Social Care Network)	Meeting	Restarting after lockdown, this is the group's second meeting since its inception, a general catchup on what people and organisations have been up to and how community activity and cultural activity have emerged together during lockdown	Membership of CAHSC	6, 9	
2020	14th July	Paisley Museum staff member with strategic and leadership responsibilities	Meeting	UWS research update from CCSE's PhD students	Request by Paisley Museum to hear about our research	4, 5, 8, 9	Check-in with practitioners of concepts of health and wellbeing and ideas of culture and the arts for social purposes
2020	22nd July	NHS Arts Practitioners	Discussion	Talk about my research to scope out areas of mutual interest with two NHS Arts Practitioners	External supervisor invite	4, 5	Check-in with practitioners about concepts of health and wellbeing and ideas of

							culture and the arts for social purposes
2020	12th August	Renfrewshire Arts Team - meeting with team members	Meeting	How to evaluate Ren TV	Ongoing conversation	4, 5	
2020	19th August	CAHSC	Meeting	Updates and considering actions and outcomes	Membership of CAHSC	5, 6, 7, 8,9	Check-in with practitioners about concepts of health and wellbeing and ideas of culture and the arts for social purposes
2020	24th August	Recovery Hub project leads	Discussion	Talk about my research to scope out areas of mutual interest	External supervisor	4,5,6,8	Check-in with practitioners about concepts of health and wellbeing and ideas of culture and the arts for social purposes
2020	11th September	Oor Mad Project - three project members with lived experience and the project facilitator	Group interview	Contribution to delivery of SGSSS Co-production research training, listening about how they work in a participatory way	Personal connection	7	
2020	w/c 14th September	Delivering SGSSS co-production research training	Delivering training	Contribution to delivery of SGSSS training and includes listening to STAR project talk about co-production with academia	Supervisor	6, 9	
2020	16th September	Open Mind Summit organisers	Meeting	How to evaluate the Summit	Direct invitation	9	

2020	23rd September	CCSE Board Meeting	Meeting	Presenting research update	Membership of CCSE	9	Check-in with cultural regeneration and arts and health activities
2020	23rd September	Paisley Museum staff member with strategic and leadership responsibilities and staff member with managerial responsibility	Discussion	Talk about my research to scope out areas of mutual interest	Direct invitation	4, 5, 8, 9	Check-in with practitioners of concepts of health and wellbeing and ideas of culture and the arts for social purposes
2020	30th September	SPG Loneliness and Social Isolation Sub Group (subsequently SPG Connectedness Network)	Meeting	Initial meeting of subgroup	Invitation by RHSCP who chair the group	7	
2020	5th October	Paisley Museum - Volunteer Workstream	Meeting	Joining the workstream to observe what health and wellbeing means to Museum staff, build relationships	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2020	9th October	Open Mind Summit	Conference/Symposium	Facilitated a roundtable to discuss the definition of loneliness	Through CAHSC	7	Check-in with concepts of loneliness
2020	19th October	Open Mind Summit organisers	Meeting	Catching up on evaluation	Through CAHSC	5, 9	
2020	22nd October	Paisley Museums - Public Programming Workstream	Meeting	Joining the workstream to observe what health and wellbeing means to Museum staff, build relationships	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2020	26th October	Recovery Taskforce	Meeting	Talk about my research to scope out areas of mutual interest - build relationships	Through NHS Arts Practitioner	4,5,6,8	Check-in with practitioners of concepts of health and wellbeing and ideas of culture and

							the arts for social purposes
2020	28th October	CAHSC	Meeting	Developing an action plan	Membership of CAHSC	5, 6, 7, 8,9	
2020	November - 3 workshops	Creative and Credible - An Introduction to Arts Health and Wellbeing Evaluation	CPD	Improve knowledge of evaluation relating to Arts & Health field	Researching evaluation in the arts and health sector	5, 9	Check-in with current evaluation practice in Arts and Health
2020	23rd November	Recovery Taskforce	Meeting	Talk about my research to scope out areas of mutual interest - build relationships	Through NHS Arts Practitioner	4,5,6,8	Check-in concepts of health and wellbeing, place and ideas of culture and the arts for social purposes
2020	24th November	Beyond Measure? panel discussion 'What is it about art & culture that can make a difference to our health?' - Cultural Institute and partners Centre for Cultural Value, and Leeds Arts Health and Wellbeing Network	CPD	Improve knowledge of evaluation relating to Arts & Health	Through subscribing to newsletter	4, 5, 6, 9	Check-in with Arts and Health sector development and practice development
2020	7th December	Paisley Museums - Volunteer Workstream	Meeting	Getting to know the Museum in preparation for project to define health and wellbeing for the Museum	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2021	15th January	SGSSS 'PHOTO and OBJECT Elicitation Methods'	Course	Training on creative methods	SGSSS	7, 9	
2021	20th January	Third Sector Research Forum and Policy Scotland - Innovating in the	Webinar	Improving knowledge of evaluation with community organisations	Professional knowledge	9	

		third sector – online research and services in 2020					
2021	25th January	Paisley Museums - Volunteer Workstream	Meeting	Getting to know the museum in preparation for project to define health and wellbeing for the Museum	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2021	26th January	Ethnography - UWS Doctoral College	Course	Training on methods	Online	4	
2021	2nd February	Paisley Museums - Public Programming Workstream	Meeting	Getting to know the museum in preparation for project to define health and wellbeing for the Museum	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2021	8th February	Paisley Museums - Volunteer Workstream	Meeting	Getting to know the museum in preparation for project to define health and wellbeing for the Museum	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2021	17th February	Scotland's Third Sector Research Forum conference 2021 - Researching Well - Good practice and ethics in third sector research	Meeting	Learning from researchers in the third sector, including peer and creative research approaches	Professional knowledge		
2021	18th February	Scottish MedSoc Webinar: Perspectives on Loneliness and Social Isolation	Webinar	Academic research into social prescribing and how to live together	Online	7	
2021	24th February	CAHSC	Meeting	Update on Future Paisley and includes presentation by CCSE on UKRI Improving Community Wellbeing Through Culture Project	Membership of CAHSC	5, 6, 7, 8,9	
2021	2nd March	Paisley Museums - Public Programming Workstream	Meeting	Getting to know the museum in preparation for project to define health and wellbeing for the Museum	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	

2021	8th March	Paisley Museums - Volunteer Workstream	Meeting	Getting to know the museum in preparation for project to define health and wellbeing for the Museum	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2021	23rd March	Recovery Hub project leads	Meeting	Talk about my research to scope out areas of mutual interest and build relationships	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4,5,6,8	
2021	25th March	External Supervisor - Renfrewshire Council	Meeting	Talk about my research and Future Paisley activity	External Supervisor	5, 9	Check-in with cultural regeneration activities in Paisley
2021	30th March	Paisley Museums - Public Programming Workstream	Meeting	Getting to know the Museum in preparation for project to define health and wellbeing for the Museum	Invitation by Museum	4, 5, 6, 8	
2021	31st March	CCSE Steering Group	Meeting	Future Paisley update	Membership of CCSE	5, 6, 9,	
2021	9th April	Future Paisley preplanning for Strategic Outcomes Workshop - 15 in attendance from mostly RC across a range of services from Children's services to Digital and Library services, other organisations include Police Scotland, Engage Renfrewshire, RHSCP, Star Project, Create Paisley and NHS GG&C, roles of attendees include Heads of Services, Head of Teams, strategic leaders involved in Future Paisley and CAHSC members	Meeting	Workshop to agree Step Change 2 wording and refreshed strategic outcomes - invitation to contribute to workshop as a member of CAHSC	Through CAHSC	6, 7, 9,	
2021	13th April	Future Paisley Strategic Outcomes Workshop - 23 people from organisations and representing roles	Meeting	Workshop to develop an activity plan for Step Change 2 with resource requirements - invitation to contribute to workshop as a member of CAHSC	Through CAHSC	6, 7, 9,	

		as listed in the preplanning meeting on the 9 th of April 2021					
2021	14th April	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	
2021	23rd April	Paisley Museum - working with the community role	Discussion/inter view	Learn about Paisley Museum listening project	Through informal conversations in previous research encounters	4, 5, 6, 7, 8	Check-in concepts of health and wellbeing, place and ideas of culture and the arts for social purposes
2021	27th April	STAR Project - Future Paisley strategic leadership role	Discussion/inter view	Learn about community engagement activities that occurred during UKCoC21 Bid	Open invitation by interviewee to help with research	9	
2021	27th April	Reimagining Museums as Caring Places	Webinar	Learn about Museum's work with communities and how Museum views itself in relation to care	Informed by Paisley Museum interviewee	4, 5, 6, 8	
2021	28th April	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	
2021	29th April	SPG Connectedness Network (previously SPG Loneliness and Social Isolation Sub Group)	Meeting	The network is for sharing knowledge and developing community-based activities to tackle loneliness. It also provides an opportunity to observe activities relating to tackling loneliness in Paisley by community groups	Membership of SPG Connectedness Network		
2021	5th May	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	

2021	5th May	Engage Renfrewshire - Future Paisley strategic leadership role	Discussion/interview	For context on community engagement activities that occurred during UKCoC21 Bid	Open invitation by interviewee to help with research		
2021	10th May	Renfrewshire Council - Future Paisley strategic leadership role	Discussion/interview	Strategic context of Future Paisley	External supervisor		
2021	19th May	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	
2021	24th May	Renfrewshire Leisure - Future Paisley strategic leadership role	Discussion/interview	Strategic context of Future Paisley	External supervisor		
2021	26th May	Bromley by Bow - Measuring what matters to communities	Webinar	Learning about community-based research	External Supervisor		
2021	3rd June	Creating Wellbeing': University Museums in Scotland (UMIS) conference 2021	Conference/Summit/Symposium	Learn about Museums and wellbeing	Online	4,5,8	
2021	9th June	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	
2021	9th June	CCSE Annual Conference	Conference/Summit/Symposium	Organisation and hosting presentations from NHS Arts and Renfrewshire Arts Team - listening to others talk	Membership of CCSE	6	
2021	16th June	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	
2021	17th June	Future Paisley Partnership Board	Meeting/Presentation	Presenting research update	PhD is part of this group's activities	6, 7, 9,	Check-in with concepts of loneliness

2021	23rd June	SPG Connectedness Network - project officer	Discussion/inter view	The network is for sharing knowledge and developing community-based activities to tackle loneliness	Through membership of Network	6, 7	Check-in with concepts of loneliness
2021	23rd June	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	
2021	30th June	Recovery Hub Focus Group	Meeting	Listen to lived experience, observe peer work and embedding lived experience in service delivery	Invitation by Recovery Taskforce	4, 5, 8,	
2021	9th September	SPG Connectedness Network	Meeting	The network is for sharing knowledge and developing community-based activities to tackle loneliness	Membership of SPG Connectedness Network	6, 7	
2021	21st September	Great Place GM Online Conference: Culture Health and Wellbeing	Conference/Su mmit/Symposiu m	Manchester Institute for Arts, Health & Social Change		5, 9	Check-in with culture and wellbeing sector development, policy development and practice development
2021	7th October	Social Prescribing co-ordinator	Meeting	To share ideas and knowledge about loneliness and social prescribing	Met online at the SPG Connectedness Network	5	Check-in with concepts of loneliness
2021	17th November	Renfrewshire Arts Team (Eight members in the team)	Group discussion	How does the work of public sector art producers in Paisley connect with health and wellbeing and Future Paisley and how they engage with communities	Through CAHSC	6, 9	Check-in with ideas of evaluation, health and wellbeing concepts and engagement with communities
2021	25th November	CCSE Steering Group	Meeting	Future Paisley update	Membership of CCSE	9	Check-in with cultural regeneration and arts and health activities

2021	2nd December	SPG Connectedness Network	Meeting	The network is for sharing knowledge and developing community-based activities to tackle loneliness	Membership of SPG Connectedness Network	6, 7	Check-in with concepts of loneliness
2021	7th December	Future Paisley evaluation workshop: Step Change 2	Workshop	Hear how Future Paisley projects and activities consider their contribution to the five step changes	Membership of CAHSC	7, 9	
2021	20th December	SPG Connectedness Network - project officer	Discussion	Share knowledge and ideas	Membership of SPG Connectedness Network	6, 7	
2022	9th March	CCSE Steering Group Meeting VIII	Meeting	Future Paisley update	Membership of CCSE	9	
2022	22nd March	Place Partnership Evaluation meeting with members of Renfrewshire Arts Team	Meeting	Share knowledge and ideas regarding evaluation of culture and place related projects	Relationship building with Renfrewshire Arts Team	9	
2022	24th March	SPG Connectedness Network	Meeting	The network is for sharing knowledge and developing community-based activities to tackle loneliness	Membership of SPG Connectedness Network	6, 7	Check-in with concepts of loneliness
2019	21st March	Centre for Culture, Sport and Events: Launch	Event	Observe culture, the arts, health and wellbeing activities in Paisley	Membership of CCSE	9	
2019	2nd April	Culture, Arts and Social Care Network	Meeting	Observe culture, the arts, health and wellbeing activities in Paisley, build relationships	PhD brief to contribute to the evaluation of Future Paisley Step Change 2 includes the activities of CAHSC	6, 9	

Appendix 2: Group invitations

Groups - invited membership	Date of involvement	Organisations invited to be members of the group	Total number of members	Average attendance
Culture, Arts and Social Care Network	February 2019 to January 2020	NHS GG&C Health Improvement, RHSCP, RC Cultural Regeneration Team, RC Cultural Service in Schools, RC Heritage, RC Cultural Service, Renfrewshire Leisure, RAMH. Members roles include Head of Service, Head of Teams, Managers. UWS researchers are also members	Fluctuating membership of around 20 depending on interests	10
CAHSC	June 2020 to February 2021	NHS GG&C Health Improvement, RHSCP, RC Cultural Regeneration Team, RC Cultural Service in Schools, RC Heritage, RC Cultural Service, Renfrewshire Leisure, Engage Renfrewshire and Strategic Partnerships and Inequalities. Members roles include Head of Service, Head of Teams	14 at the start, 2 more added	14 including invited speakers
Paisley Museums - Public Programming Workstream	October 2020 to March 2021	Range of staff members from curators, officers and co-ordinators	Approximately 8	6
Paisley Museums - Volunteer Workstream	October 2020 to March 2021	Range of staff members from curators, officers and co-ordinators	Approximately 11	8
Recovery Hub Focus Group	April 2021 to June 2021	Peer workers	8	4

Appendix 3: Growing knowledge

CCSE Website Article: Finding a conceptual coat that for arts, culture, health and wellbeing (November 2020)

The search for concepts I feel comfortable with to describe arts, culture, health and wellbeing has been a long one. Theories and concepts have been described as a lens to see the world or a framework to scaffold the thesis. For me it has felt more like trying on many conceptual coats. It is not just finding one that can help me get the job done. Though it is helping. There are projects and services where I know there is a health and wellbeing impact but previously I didn't have the lens to discern the mechanisms that created health and wellbeing. It's also finding that melds with the values I have and how I see the world, that I can be comfortable in and is how I want to encounter the world. The current coat is a bit new, it's a little stiff, not yet snug. I'm not quite used to it and its possibilities. But after time and some reflective journeys, I hope I can break it in make it my own.

One form of reflective journey is through my volunteer experiences. I'm re-reading my submission on what the exhibition I volunteer for means to me as part of our annual exercise (<https://www.outofsightoutofmind.scot/what-does-it-mean-to-you>) I'm frustrated as I've written so many words, too many and they don't get to the heart of what it means to me to be part of the exhibition. Hoping the next sentence, might be the one to get close. I'm using language that turns up in commonly used scales of wellbeing. Feeling useful, interested in other people and so on. The words say something about the wellbeing impact, but the language flattens my experience, lessening the uniqueness, I could say the same for having my dogs in my life or my other volunteering. The language doesn't convey the texture of the experience, how it shifts in response to my personal context and to what shape the exhibition is currently in.

I realise I am in the territory of the concepts in my PhD, in the affective realm. Affects can be feelings or emotions or even harder to describe – affects can be vague, can precede conscious thought, can be intensities, energies, flashes, sensations (Stewart, 2007, Andrews, Chen and Myers, 2014). These arise through the many encounters with the diversity of relationships that emerge from the exhibition, from the zoom meetings and being in the exhibition space to seeing the posters around the city and the exhibits. The sensations of joy, excitement and emotional warmth that animate these relationships, giving my connection with the exhibition a potency can be described as affinities (Mason, 2017). All these moments, encounters, affects, affinities, tangle into shifting configurations of feeling and meaning regarding the exhibition. I am in fact giving an account of atmosphere, which

by their constant movements are elusive and ephemeral (Sumartojo and Pink, 2018). This will explain why I found the annual exercise difficult!

This way of thinking, helps me think through what the exhibition is and why it is so meaningful to me, leading me to think of the exhibition as an assemblage. As it is more than its component parts of people, exhibits, organisations, events, buildings, walls. It is a constellation of the relationships between these components, giving room to the non human as well as the human, to the material, social and affective resources (Duff, 2012). It seems obvious to say the exhibits have their own presence, they create connections, feelings, meanings, dialogues, conversations. However, an evaluative process which centers the human, would count exhibits as outputs, without generative power. This focus on the relational, highlights one of the key ways the exhibition becomes rich in meaning. From the values that inform our interactions with others and objects, the care that is taken with each exhibitor throughout the year from initial inquiry to pick up of exhibit, to the way decisions are made in planning meetings. This contributes to the emergence of atmospheres, which enable people to enter other worlds (Duff, 2016). Academic research where health is seen as an assemblage finds a range of atmospheres that help in the process of becoming well. Some of these resonate with my experience and with the conversations I've had with others who have encountered the exhibition. It is a non-physical place that is 'rich in the atmospherics of sociality...animated by forces of connection, interaction, expression, solicitation and concern in a kind of gathering of social affects (Duff, 2016, p.67). It can create atmospheres of safety and belonging. This has been a theme in both the exhibits and in the replies to this exercise. An atmosphere of safety, makes it easier for people to take off the masks they present to the rest of the world and relate to the exhibition in a way that is more themselves, whether it is the exhibits they create or who they are with other people. This sharing of themselves and their experience can create feelings such as mattering, being seen, can then be used to construct atmospheres of belonging, which in turn create wellbeing.

Seeing the exhibition as a constellation rich in relationships gives a way of describing why the accounts of what the exhibition means to people is so diverse and why some are deeply personal. People relate to different parts of the constellation and reassemble the relationships that they connect to into their own constellations of health and wellbeing. Some meanings are fleeting, where it is another exhibition and have a temporary effect on health and wellbeing. Some meanings become part of identities, built up from multiple encounters over time, becoming a steady source of health creation. In this way it can be seen how the exhibition becomes a health resource or asset. History can be accounted for when talking about the process of health and wellbeing. Futures can also be accounted for in this way of thinking. The exhibition is place of potential encounters which could create health and wellbeing, where people have the potential to become someone or

something else. I have become less lonely, less isolated, less of a shadow and a PhD candidate due to the exhibition.

The exhibition is a collective, through community and voice, individuals and exhibits. Using constellation thinking - atmospheres, and affects, which is like putting on my conceptual coat, a fuller account of the collective can be given – its different meanings, how it is formed and what a collective does. This highlights what constellation thinking can do, that it shifts the focus of health and wellbeing from the individual, who is usually seen as being in deficit in terms of health and wellbeing qualities (Atkinson, 2013). This shift provides more space for the encounters and relationship with the social, affective, spatial, material resources and environments that affect health and wellbeing (Atkinson, 2013, Duff, 2014). Viewing things with this conceptual coat conceives of health positively and situates health and wellbeing creation within the experience of everyday life. The need to shift focus to everyday experience, to relational and collective changes, is highlighted in the Arts and Humanities Research Council Cultural Value project report, as being needed when the value of arts and culture to individuals and society is discussed and researched (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016). Particularly as ‘methodologies for evaluation that are limited to the individual can in many cases, as we have seen, be no more than partial’ (2016, p.153). The report finds that one of the most significant ways in which arts and cultural activity and engagement bring value is through creating the conditions of change. The report identifies a range of spillover effects that my reflections here have also identified. With this conceptual coat, I am starting to find my approach to understanding how these effects occur and aim to use these new insights to inform evaluations that focus on the relational and collective as well as the individual. The next few months of fieldwork will be a test of how much I can make this coat my own.

Screenshot of note from Lan Pham's Note Manager

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying an Evernote note. The browser's address bar shows the URL: `evernote.com/client/web?_sourcePage=ehA2ja72TqviMUD9T65RG_YVRLZ-1eYQ3IqfqrU0lymRL_1nukN4gH1t86pc15P8...lp=YYQ7Kouj5Q3yWPvuidLz-TPR6B3Px8&hops=158...`. The browser tabs include 'New Tab', 'MethodSpace - Co...', 'Rhetorical Function...', 'De-stuffing your wo...', 'How to write a stati...', 'Data Humanities m...', '2021 Group', 'Sarah Waters on Tw...', and 'Christopher Clee, B...'. The Evernote interface shows the user 'Lan Pham' and the note title '(Thematic Reflective Journal)'. The note is dated 'Last edited on 29 Jan 2021'. The note content is as follows:

20210128 Meetings with OOSOOM and ETL

Had a really positive meeting with OOSOOM [redacted] loved my blog post - I was really nervous to show it to them as they are practising artists - [redacted] is a socially engaged artist and they have engaged with deeply in their roles of organising it and being exhibition assistant. And they are very engaged with theories of what art does, what art is, as well as mental health. They have also struggled with trying to describe what OOSOOM means to them due to the ephemeral and vagueness of it - on some level we can describe what it means to us - but that warmth and feeling, that having a presence in our lives, the themes we get from people's meanings - tying it all together is really hard, and having the framework of the constellations really helped - they were thinking of even using it for a subheading. It's interesting that we don't talk about the exhibits that much even though the core of what we do is this exhibition. Partly because we don't want to single one work out, or if somebody interprets the work in a different way from the artist - it might create awkwardness - but it shows the strength of OOSOOM that we can talk so much of it, without talking about its core function. One thing we struggle with is how OOSOOM speaks truth to power, of trying to push back on what can be, on what is seen as, on the medical model - lots of interesting discussion about the role of arts in society.

With ETL talking about objects got [redacted] excited. He'd love to explore that more, the fact that an imperfectly made object by you is worth more than a perfectly made object by a stranger - showing the important of the relationship with the object - if the object disappeared - you'd still have that feeling there. Showing the importance of the material world. [redacted] has previously said those that have most transformed are those that encounter ETL in different ways.

At the bottom of the note, there is a 'Need a little help?' link and an 'Add tag' button. The status 'All changes saved' is visible in the bottom right corner.

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